

**ILLUMINATED BUDDHIST MANUSCRIPTS FROM EASTERN
INDIA (10TH-12TH CENTURIES A.D.): ICONOGRAPHIC
DEVELOPMENT, AESTHETICS, AND MADHYAMAKA
THOUGHT IN THE LATE PĀLA PERIOD**

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This is to certify that the thesis titled, "*Illuminated Buddhist Manuscripts from eastern India (10th-12th centuries A.D.): Iconographic development, aesthetics and Madhyamaka thought in the late Pāla period*", submitted by Mr. Archishman Sarker in partial fulfillment of the requirements for award of degree of Ph.D. of Jawaharlal Nehru University, New Delhi, has not been previously submitted in part or in full for any other degree of this university or any other university/institution.

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To:

My late mother Malati Dey, and my father Balaram Sarker,

Lt. Brindaban Sarkar (ca. 1871-1929), mathematician,

And the taxpayers of India for funding my education.

In loving memory of Malati Dey (1955-2017)

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List of abbreviations

AsP : *Aṣṭasāhasrikāprajñāpāramitāsūtra*

PvP : *Pañcaviṃśatisāhasrikāprajñāpāramitāsūtra*

PrK : *Pañcarakṣā*

DnS : *Dhāraṇīsāṅgraha*

KvS : *Kāraṇḍavyūhasūtra*

V&A : The Victoria and Albert Museum

AIIS: American Institute of Indian Studies

ASI : Archaeological Survey of India

CUL: Cambridge University Library

LACMA : Los Angeles County Museum of Art

NGMPP : Nepal-German Manuscript Preservation Project

WHC : World Heritage Convention

Note:

- a) All names of places/ persons which are still in modern use like Patan, Bodh Gaya, Lumbini, Kushinagar, Vaishali, Sarnath, Rajgir, Nalanda, Rahul Sankrityayan etc. have been written without IAST diacritical marks, while names of historical places like Vikramaśilā, Sāṅkāśyā, Gandhāra, Puṇḍravardhana, Nāgārjunikoṇḍā, Oḍḍiyāna, Kučā etc. have been written following the IAST conventions for diacritical marks.
- b) In iconographic descriptions of images, when ‘left’, ‘right’ or ‘on the left’, ‘on the right’ are mentioned, it always implies the viewer’s left and right respectively, if otherwise it’s not mentioned explicitly.
- c) For the names of deities, IAST diacritical marks have been followed throughout, including those deities whose worship is prevalent today: including ‘Śiva’, and not ‘Shiva’, ‘Śākyamuni’ and not ‘Shakyamuni’ etc.
- d) The names of books, *sūtras*, and texts in all languages have been italicised throughout, and Sanskrit words in general have been italicised throughout, with the exception of some proper nouns. For Prajñāpāramitā, as a philosophical term or concept, has been italicised; as the title or name of a text or text corpus, has

been italicised; as a deity or personified goddess, has not been italicised. Words in languages other than English and Sanskrit, like in Pāli, Tibetan, French or German, have been italicised.

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Introduction

This thesis is primarily concerned with illuminated palm-leaf Buddhist manuscripts produced between the tenth and twelfth centuries CE in eastern India, which leads to an exploration of the veneration of Prajñāpāramitā in the Pāla-period and elsewhere, explored in the second chapter. The third chapter proposes a set of theoretical frameworks for understanding how illuminated manuscripts functioned as ritual objects, how they shaped and were shaped by the devotional experience of the practitioners who produced, venerated, and interacted with them, or in other words, in the context of the constitution of religious subjectivity¹. The last chapter, offers a perspective on aspects of Buddhist sacred geography focussing on the eastern Indian subcontinent, and Nepal, where these manuscripts were produced and preserved respectively. These highly sought after manuscripts, were produced extensively in the monastic strongholds like Nalanda and Vikramaśilā, and centres of regional production throughout eastern India, where they were patronised widely. These were equally popular among pilgrims, and played an important part in the transmission of Buddhist thought and philosophy, and in the sophisticated evolution of the artistic and aesthetic exchanges between northern India and the Himalayan regions, Tibet and beyond. Around forty-eight of these manuscripts are known to exist today, of which twenty-seven have their colophons intact. Many of these manuscripts exist as scattered folios in different collections across the globe. These illuminated² manuscripts include important Mahāyāna *sūtras* like the *Aṣṭasāhasrikāprajñāpāramitāsūtra*

¹ By 'religious subjectivity,' I mean the forms of selfhood, devotional orientation, and soteriological aspiration that Buddhist ritual practice: including the commissioning, copying, venerating, and ritual activation of manuscripts- both presupposes and produces in its practitioners. I approach this not through direct access to interior states, which is unavailable to the art historian, but through the material and iconographic evidence of how manuscripts were designed to be used: their illustration programmes, and the ritual contexts for the Buddhist book cult, all of which carry assumptions about the subject who encounters them and the transformations that encounter was intended to effect.

² I use the term "illuminated" throughout this dissertation, and not 'illustrated' or 'painted' to designate these manuscripts, following a scholarly tradition that reserves 'illuminated' for manuscripts in which images and decorative elements are integral to the devotional and ritual programme of the text rather than merely supplementary to it. In the Pāla-period manuscripts under study, the paintings, decorative bands, and string-hole embellishments constitute a unified visual-textual object whose aesthetic and soteriological qualities are fundamentally inseparable: a relationship that 'illuminated,' with its global medieval connotations of sacred luminosity and the interpretation of word and image, captures more precisely than 'illustrated,' which can imply a secondary pictorial function.

(henceforth *AsP*), *Pañcaviṃśatisāhasrikāprajñāpāramitāsūtra* (henceforth *PvP*), and the *Prajñāpāramitāstotra*, belonging to the *Prajñāpāramitā* body of texts, which mainly expound Madhyamaka philosophy and metaphysics. The illuminated manuscripts also include the *Pañcarakṣā* (henceforth *PrK*) and the *Dhāraṇīsaṅgraha* (henceforth *DnS*), which are collections of charms with descriptions of divine forms, the *Kāraṇḍavyūhasūtra* (henceforth *KvS*): another important Mahāyāna *sūtra* which extols the virtues and powers of Avalokiteśvara, and the *Guhyasamājatantra*, which like the *Kālacakratantra* belong to a different category of tantric esoteric Vajrayānist Buddhist texts.

These manuscripts are made of palm-leaves with the paintings and the text executed in natural pigments. The folios of the manuscripts would generally be held together by a cord (*sūtra* or *nāḍī*) through pre-bored holes, and sometimes a pair of wooden covers (*paṭa* or *paṭlī*) were added to provide a layer of protection. Some of the manuscripts have these surviving wooden covers, which were often added at a later date, and mostly in Nepal, which are often illustrated, and intricately decorated. The type of palm leaves used in the production of these manuscripts is the talipot palm (*Corypha umbraculifera*), different from Palmyra palm (*Borassus flabellifer*): the latter becoming popular for manuscript production in South Asia from the sixteenth century CE onwards³. Whether the palm leaves used in the production of these manuscripts were indigenously produced or imported from southern India, or elsewhere, is debatable. Although southern India is generally considered the ‘home of the talipot,’ the earliest dateable palm-leaf manuscript from the region is a Jain manuscript from the twelfth century CE; and it was the Palmyra palm, introduced from East Africa, which became the main medium of manuscript production in southern India from the sixteenth century CE onwards⁴. As suggested by the production of several palm leaf manuscripts in eastern India and Nepal during this period, the talipot palm was either abundant in eastern India during the medieval period, or traded from elsewhere:

There must have been in ancient India a flourishing trade in the leaves, either in their raw or finished states, from south to north ... The eastern manuscripts on the other hand tend

³ Jeremiah P. Losty, *The Art of the Book in India* (London: British Library, 1982), 6.

⁴ Losty, 6.

to be much more even, suggesting availability of a good supply, and they may have been in much more intensive cultivation in Bengal than now. All the same, the great scriptoria of Bihar and Nepal would have had to have obtained their supplies from a source at some considerable distance.⁵

The fact that palm leaves were extensively used for the production of manuscripts in northern India during this period is further attested by the Spitzer manuscripts, one of the oldest surviving Sanskrit Buddhist manuscripts, containing Buddhist as well as Brahmanical texts⁶.

Alongside the depiction of different Buddhas and Vajrayānist deities, the manuscripts are often illustrated with the eight major events from the life of the Buddha (birth, enlightenment or *nirvāṇa*, descent from the Trāyastriṃśa heaven at Sāṅkāśyā, offering of honey by a monkey at Vaishali, confounding of heretics at Shravasti, the first sermon at Sarnath, taming of the mad elephant Nāḷāgiri, and death or *mahāparinirvāṇa*). Palm-leaf is very fragile, so many of them are now in a brittle state. However, in comparison with later palm-leaf manuscripts, those produced during the Pāla-period are often better preserved. This is primarily because they were made of the best quality of palm-leaves obtained from a particular variety of palm.

A number of these manuscripts belong to the *Prajñāpāramitā* body of texts. The *AsP* is amongst the earliest scriptures in the Mahāyāna tradition of thought. This is a foundational *sūtra* of the Mahāyānist Buddhist body of literature and it assumed its now known structure by developing gradually between the first century BCE and the first century CE. The main philosophical treatise of the *sūtra* was developed by the first century CE, and it received its most sophisticated and well-known treatment in Nāgārjuna's treatises. The *AsP sūtra* forms the basis of the Madhyamaka school of thought and practice, and belongs to an early stage of the *Prajñāpāramitā* or 'Perfection of Wisdom' body of literature. The *AsP* is not the only known variant of the *Prajñāpāramitā* body of literature,

⁵ Losty, 6.

⁶ See: Eli Franco, ed., *The Spitzer Manuscript: The Oldest Philosophical Manuscript in Sanskrit*, 2 vols., Philosophisch-Historische Klasse Denkschriften 323, Beiträge zur Kultur- und Geistesgeschichte Asiens 43 (Vienna: Verlag der Österreichischen Akademie der Wissenschaften, 2004).

with the existence of several more elaborative or voluminous versions. Between the 2nd and the 4th CE, this literature sometimes assumed a more lengthy form, like the *Śatasāhasrikāprajñāpāramitā*.

Prajñā is translated as:

... “wisdom,” but having connotations perhaps closer to “gnosis,” “awareness,” and in some contexts “cognition”; the term has the general sense of accurate and precise understanding, but is used most often to refer to an understanding of reality that transcends ordinary comprehension. It is one of the most important terms in Buddhist thought, occurring in a variety of contexts.⁷

Prajñāpāramitā, on the other hand, distinct from *prajñā*: “... refers to a level of understanding beyond that of ordinary wisdom, especially referring to the wisdom associated with, or required to achieve, buddhahood.⁸” *Prajñāpāramitā* also refers to “... a genre of texts in which that wisdom is set forth⁹”. The *Prajñāpāramitāsūtra* is considered the ‘mother¹⁰’ of all Buddhas, and the “name of a goddess ... who is the embodiment of the perfection of wisdom¹¹”: since it is from this understanding of wisdom that the possibility of enlightenment arises. The ‘perfection of wisdom’ is also sometimes defined as the knowledge of emptiness (*śūnyatā*):

In addition to numerous descriptions of, and paeans to, emptiness, the perfection of wisdom sūtras also extol the practice of the bodhisattva path as the superior form of Buddhist practice. Although emptiness is said to be the chief topic of the sūtras, their “hidden meaning” is said to be the detailed structure of the bodhisattva path.¹²

I.1 Genealogy of Manuscript Studies

⁷ Robert E. Buswell, Jr. and Donald S. Lopez, Jr., *The Princeton dictionary of Buddhism*. (Princeton, New Jersey: Princeton University Press, 2014), 655.

⁸ Buswell, Jr. and Lopez Jr., 656.

⁹ Buswell, Jr. and Lopez Jr., 655.

¹⁰ *Prajñā* as distinct from *jñāna*, while the later derives from the objective world, the former is the more intuitive qualitative aspect of episteme.

¹¹ Buswell, Jr. and Lopez Jr., 657.

¹² Buswell, Jr. and Lopez Jr., 656.

None of these illuminated manuscripts were discovered in either Bengal or Bihar, but in Nepal and Tibet in the nineteenth and early twentieth centuries. The integration of Sanskrit Buddhist manuscripts into modern scholarly studies took off with British colonialism in the nineteenth century, introducing both unprecedented access and significant disruptions in the history of the physical existence of these manuscripts. Prior to the colonial discovery of the Sanskrit Buddhist manuscripts in Nepal, European scholars lacked evidential grounding to trace the origins and diffusion of Buddhism, often leading to speculative and politically charged efforts to construct linear histories of religious practices. The evolution of manuscript cultures in Nepal itself has been shaped by centuries of assimilation, transformation, and appropriation, facilitated by the region's distinctive geographical position as a pivotal nexus in trans-Himalayan¹³ trade, pilgrimage, and cultural exchange. Nepal, well-known today for its unparalleled contributions to Buddhist Sanskrit manuscript studies, Nepal has served as a crucial repository for an extensive corpus of Buddhist, Brahmanical, and Jain manuscripts. These manuscripts, which were widely collected and disseminated across European institutions during the nineteenth and early twentieth centuries, as will be discussed here subsequently, provided the foundation for critical editions of numerous Buddhist Sanskrit treatises, and profoundly influenced the trajectory of modern scholarship on Buddhism. This intellectual legacy was enabled by Nepal's historical emergence as a hub for manuscript preservation, translation, production, as well as, circulation. By the twelfth century CE, the trade, commerce, and pilgrimage networks connecting the medieval cities of Kathmandu, Lalitpur, and Bhaktapur with northern India and Tibet had already established the Kathmandu valley as a central conduit for the transmission of material and intellectual cultures from northern India, to across the Himalayan regions. The study of manuscript traditions in Nepal should therefore be situated within the region's broader historical role as a mediator of trans-Himalayan exchanges, and not isolated from the historical layers, continuities, and discontinuities, which are often overlooked by linear and allochronic historiographical models.

¹³ I use the term "trans-Himalaya" in this dissertation to denote 'cross-Himalaya' or 'through the Himalayas', and not the geographical region of Transhimalaya/ Trans-Himalaya.

In the latter half of the nineteenth century, as the British colonial rule in India focussed on gaining access to Tibet, due to diverse geo-political reasons, including what came to be known as the ‘Great Game’ between the imperial powers— numerous land routes to Tibet, mostly through the dense forests of the Terai leading through Nepal, were often explored through covert operations. The closure of the Chumbi valley route, central to trade between Tibet and British Bengal, following the Gurkha conquest of Kathmandu, redirected focus to alternative routes. In 1848, Joseph Dalton Hooker attempted to access Tibet via Nepal, but it was Sarat Chandra Das, the British Indian agent, who first successfully transported manuscripts from Tibet to British India. Initially planning to travel through Walung, Das altered his route to the neighbouring Yangma valley to avoid scrutiny, returning with manuscripts, from Tibet as well as Nepal, including the *Avadāna Kalpalatā*. Although his expedition focussed on Tibet, he was able to gather and bring to Calcutta a significant number of manuscripts that unveiled an extensive repository of Indian Buddhist texts. However what revolutionised the modern study of Sanskrit Buddhist manuscripts, were the discoveries¹⁴ of Brian Houghton Hodgson (1801-1894), British Resident in Kathmandu. In our discussion on the genealogy of these manuscripts, considering the important position he occupies in the history of modern scholarly studies of the manuscripts, I shall briefly reflect on Hodgson and his contributions.

Born in 1801 in Prestbury, Cheshire, to a “well-connected, but impoverished family,”¹⁵ he joined the Bengal Civil Service in 1818, after doing parts of his schooling at Haileybury, an institution then well-known for preparing civil servants for the British empire, where a place for him was obtained by James Pattison, then director of the East India Company¹⁶. Following his training at the Fort William College in Calcutta, where he showed an aptitude in the study of Indian and oriental languages, he received his first posting as the Assistant to the Commissioner of Kumaon, and in 1820, he exchanged this position for that of Assistant to the Resident of Kathmandu. He returned to the

¹⁴ There were two main components to the initial manuscript discoveries of Hodgson: the Sanskrit Buddhist manuscripts as discussed here, and a collection of xylographs comprising two complete sets of the *Kangyur* (Also referred to as the *Kanjur*) and the *Bstan-’gyur* (or the *Tengyur*, or *Tanjur*), which were first published by M. Csoma de Körös.

¹⁵ D.M. Waterhouse, “Brian Hodgson - a biographical sketch” in Waterhouse, D.M. (ed.). *The Origins of Himalayan Studies: Brian Houghton Hodgson in Nepal and Darjeeling, 1820–1858*. (London: Routledge, 2004), 1.

¹⁶ Waterhouse, 1-3.

latter position in 1825, until himself being appointed as the Resident, a position he held between 1833 and 1843, before retiring from the civil service. In 1848 he returned to Darjeeling as a private resident and stayed for nine years. Hodgson significantly took advantage of his position in Kathmandu to further his own scholarly and professional interests: “The ordinary round of duties devolving on an Assistant in an Indian embassy is limited enough; but an officer in a foreign court has many opportunities of collecting and digesting valuable information, and Mr. Hodgson utilised them to the utmost”¹⁷. Hodgson became well-known as a man of letters with significant contributions to, among other things ranging from: the importance of the vernacular in the colonial Indian education system, to polity and administration, many different branches of the ‘Natural Sciences’ whose works have laid the foundations of modern scholarly studies on Nepal and several regions on India, for numerous disciplines like zoology, botany, anthropology, ornithology, ethnology, history, archaeology etc. Due to the versatility of his scholarly engagements and the foundational role it played in modern scholarly studies of this region, he is also often considered as being the first pioneer in Himalayan studies. Hodgson amassed a significant amount of Buddhist manuscripts in his lifetime, which were sent off to various collections like: the Asiatic Society of Bengal, Royal Asiatic Society, India Office Library, Bodleian Library, the Société Asiatique and Eugéné Burnouf in France: the latter two being later incorporated into the collections of the Bibliothèque nationale de France. Overall, these included: “... the most important *sūtras* and *tantras* of Sanskrit Buddhism, works that in India, and in translations into Chinese and Tibetan, were among the most important in the history of Buddhism.¹⁸” These discoveries fundamentally transformed European studies of Buddhist religion, culture, and philosophy, as aptly noted by Rajendralal Mitra, in his catalogue of the ninety-four manuscripts at the Asiatic Society of Bengal: “The existence of these was before his time perfectly unknown, and his discovery has entirely revolutionized the history of Buddhism as it was known to Europeans in

¹⁷ R. Mitra, *The Sanskrit Buddhist Literature of Nepal*. (Calcutta: The Asiatic Society of Bengal, 1882), iv-v.

¹⁸ Donald S. Lopez Jr., “The Ambivalent Exegete: Hodgson’s contributions to the study of Buddhism” in Waterhouse, D.M. (ed.). *The Origins of Himalayan Studies: Brian Houghton Hodgson in Nepal and Darjeeling, 1820–1858*. (London: Routledge, 2004), 55.

the early part of this century”¹⁹, and led Max Müller to write: “the real beginning of an historical and critical study of the doctrine of Buddha dates from the year 1824. In that year Mr Hodgson announced the fact that the original documents of the Buddhist canon had been preserved in Sanskrit in the monasteries of Nepal.”²⁰ From the manuscripts sent to Paris at the end of 1837, Burnouf would publish *Introduction a l'histoire du Bouddhisme Indien* in 1844. In terms of Hodgson’s legacy as one of the first Europeans with access to these texts, it is summed up appropriately by Lopez Jr.:

It was Hodgson's fate to live a long life, a life that saw sweeping changes in the production of knowledge. Over the course of the nineteenth century, authority would shift away from the amateur scholar and towards the professional scholar, away from the collector and towards the academic specialist, away from the traveller and towards the professor. If the European study of Buddhism is an academic discipline (which remains a question), and if that discipline has a founder, it is Eugene Burnouf and not Brian Hodgson. But Burnouf was only able to make such remarkable strides in his understanding of Buddhism because he had before him in Paris the texts that Hodgson had dispatched from Kathmandu.²¹

The sudden accessibility of Indian manuscripts in Nepal also affirmed for the colonialists: the centuries-old epistemological networks of the Himalayan regions and the Indian subcontinent, to which many of their interventions would subsequently prove to be disruptive. Although at Cambridge, the study of South Asian Buddhist manuscripts was already well-developed by the beginning of the nineteenth century, especially through the efforts of Edward Byles Cowell (1826-1903), Professor of Sanskrit, and noted Sanskritist Cecil Bendall’s (1856-1906) predecessor at Cambridge, it was mainly due to the contributions of Daniel Wright (1833-1902), Surgeon-Major in the Indian Medical Service in 1866–76, and Surgeon to the British Residency, Kathmandu in 1873–76, that a large collection of Indian manuscripts from Nepal arrived at Cambridge, and is presently housed at the Cambridge

¹⁹ Mitra, xxiv.

²⁰ Max Müller, *Chips from a German Workshop, Volume 1: Essays on the Science of Religion*, reprint, (Chico, California: Scholars Press, 1985), 187.

²¹ Lopez Jr., 67.

University Library (henceforth CUL): “During this period, with the help of the Residency Pandit, Guṇānanda, he collected approximately 450 manuscripts, more than a half of which are Buddhist manuscripts”²². As Camillo Formigatti has traced in detail, the Wright and Bendall collections at Cambridge played a pivotal role in integrating Sanskrit Buddhist manuscripts into modern scholarship. It was Wright, who is credited with procuring the first original palm-leaf manuscripts for universities in Britain, the ones addressed in this dissertation as the Cambridge University Library manuscripts. The earlier manuscripts sent by Hodgson were copies on paper made for him by Nepalese scribes²³. The Daniel Wright collections and the collections of Cecil Bendall proved to be instrumental in integrating Sanskrit Buddhist manuscripts into modern disciplinary studies: “Like the Hodgson collection in Paris used by Burnouf, the Wright and Bendall collections of Sanskrit manuscripts played a pivotal role in the spread of knowledge about Buddhism in the West.”²⁴ During this period, there were different publications on Sanskrit Buddhist manuscripts, including those by colonial administrators, bibliographers and Indologists like: Henry Bradshaw (1831-1886), T. H. Ralph Griffith (1826-1906), and Cecil Bendall (1856-1906), who famously wrote in his professorship application to Cambridge: “Buddhist Sanskrit literature has been my special study, and for it materials exist nowhere in Europe comparable to those of Cambridge”²⁵, and by “... 19th and 20th century, the UL collections of Sanskrit manuscripts were known and tapped into mostly by scholars of Buddhism precisely thanks to Bendall’s catalogue.”²⁶

I.2 Methodology and Description of Chapters

²² Camillo A. Formigatti, “Sanskrit Manuscripts in the Cambridge University Library: Three Centuries of History and Preservation” in Vincenzo Vergiani, Daniele Cuneo and Camillo Alessio Formigatti (eds.). *Indic Manuscript Cultures through the Ages: Material, Textual, and Historical Investigations*. (Berlin: De Gruyter, 2017), 5. My account of the genealogy of Sanskrit Buddhist manuscripts studies in European institutions in this section draws substantially on Formigatti’s recent and authoritative reconstruction of three centuries of history and preservation at the Cambridge University Library, to which I direct the reader for a fuller treatment of the subject.

²³ Formigatti, 13.

²⁴ Formigatti, 12.

²⁵ Cecil Bendall, *Application and Testimonials for the Professorship of Sanskrit*. (Cambridge: 1903), 8.

²⁶ Formigatti, 15.

The methodologies across the four chapters in this dissertation build progressively. In the course of analysis, several new terms are introduced where existing vocabulary proves inadequate; in each case, the rationale for the new term is provided at the point of its introduction.

Chapter 1 examines illuminated Buddhist manuscripts and stone sculptures from the Pāla period through what I term *polycentric semiosis*: an approach that treats these objects not as products of a single dominant centre but as evidence of multiple, locally active production sites, each having its own iconographic and stylistic characteristics within a broader shared tradition. Existing classifications based on criteria such as colophons, iconographic programmes, script styles, regnal chronologies, and patronage networks provide an essential foundation; however, they sometimes obscure the degree to which individual manuscripts and sculptures bear the marks of specific regional workshops and monastic contexts rather than conforming to a uniform ‘Pāla style’. While these classifications serve as this study’s bedrock, they are also sometimes critiqued for their limitations in capturing the place-specific articulations that render Pāla imagery heterogeneous. Drawing principally on Claudine Bautze-Picron's foundational investigations into the art and iconography of medieval southeastern Bengal, particularly her analysis of an illuminated *PvP* manuscript housed at

the Baroda State Museum and Picture Gallery²⁷, this chapter proposes a new classification and

Fig. 1. Map illustrating Magadha, Varendra/ Puṇḍravardhana and Samataṭa.

nomenclature of Pāla objects: the *Magadha-Varendra-constellation*, *Varendra-confluens*, and *Samataṭa-littoral*.

The term *Magadha-Varendra-constellation* describes Magadha and Varendra as interconnected but co-equal centres of artistic and monastic activity, rather than treating either as a dominant core from which the other derives. Such framing avoids both the conventional privileging of Magadha (as the seat of Nalanda and Vikramaśīla) and the anachronistic Bihar-Bengal boundary imposed by modern colonial administrative boundaries. Within this constellation, the term *Varendra-confluens* refers specifically to the northern Bengal region centred on sites such as Mahasthangarh, Paharpur, and Bangarh, which functioned as a major zone of monastic and artistic production at par with Magadha. The suffix ‘confluens’ reflects the fact that this region’s cultural significance derived partly from its position at the intersection of overland routes to the Kāmārūpa region (Assam) and

²⁷ Claudine Bautze-Picron, “Images of Devotion and Power in South and Southeast Bengal,” in *Esoteric Buddhism in Mediaeval Maritime Asia: Networks of Masters, Texts, Icons*, ed. Andrea Acri (Singapore: ISEAS Press, 2016), 163–91; Claudine Bautze-Picron, “Buddhist Painting During the Reign of Harivarmadeva (End of the 11th C.) in Southeast Bangladesh,” *Journal of Bengal Art* 4 (1999): 159–97; Bautze-Picron, “The ‘Vredenburg Manuscript’ and Its Book-Covers”.

riverine networks linking it to the Bay of Bengal's maritime trade. The *Samataṭa-littoral*, designates the region east of the Meghna river, including the historical territories of Vaṅga, Samataṭa, and Harikela in present-day Bangladesh and parts of Tripura. Although conventionally treated as peripheral to the Pāla heartland, this region produced distinctive manuscripts and sculptures that warrant treatment as a third major zone of production, extending the geographical scope of Bautze-Picron's foundational work on southeastern Bengal.

This regional nomenclature is intended not to replace existing classifications, but to supplement them by foregrounding place-specific differences that broader categories may tend to flatten. In art-historical terms, this approach challenges the long-standing tendency to treat Magadha as the normative centre of Pāla artistic production and to measure all other regions against it. *Varendra-confluens* and *Samataṭa-littoral* thus both operate as synthesisers and co-relators of heterogeneous semiotic vectors, in complex negotiation with Magadha's canonical hegemony. By semiotic vectors, I mean the specific carriers of meaning operational in Pāla period cultural production, including: iconographic programmes, script styles, patronage inscriptions, material choices, pilgrimage routes, and the movement of artisans and monks between monastic centres- each of which signifies and transmits localised religious and political meaning across regions.

Rather than treating manuscripts and artefacts as products of a few dominant centres like Nalanda and Vikramaśīla, this chapter approaches them as evidence of a decentralised production landscape in which so-called peripheral sites had their own iconographic and stylistic innovations: thereby also marking a departure from colonial heartland-periphery binaries and diffusionist models that had, to an extent, ossified medieval South Asian studies in the previous century. Taken together, my approach treats Pāla cultural production not as a hierarchy centred on Magadha, but as a network of multiple, locally active centres. Each region, monastery, or workshop participates in making meaning and knowledge, within a wider field of shared symbols and ways of knowing.

Chapter 2 traces the transformation of Prajñāpāramitā from an abstract philosophical concept: the 'perfection of wisdom' as articulated in second-century CE Mahāyāna texts, into a fully

deified devotional figure in the Pāla period and beyond. This transformation is examined as an extended historical process shaped by trans-regional circulation of Mahāyāna Buddhism across South, Central and Southeast Asia. This development had two dimensions: on one hand, a decisive shift from textual abstraction to iconographic embodiment, visible in the emergence of Prajñāpāramitā as a depicted and worshipped deity; on the other, a gradual, centuries-long process of textual proliferation, doctrinal elaboration, and ritual adaptations the Prajñāpāramitā tradition spread across multiple regions and Buddhist communities. This *longue durée* perspective frames Prajñāpāramitā's rise as a narrative event: shaped over centuries by monastic networks, patronage structures, and the convergence of diverse temporal frameworks, that culminated in the distinctive iconographic elaborations of the Pāla period.

The chapter commences with a tracing of Prajñāpāramitā's textual, ideological, and visual transmissions across South and Central Asia, spotlighting Gilgit manuscripts, Kashmiri Mahāyāna hubs facilitating Central Asian conduits like Khotan, and interactions with Brahmanical *mātrkā* and goddess traditions in eastern India. It then analyses her Pāla-period proliferation, iconographic innovations, and briefly extends to Newari ritual evolutions in the Kathmandu Valley. Through this reconstruction, Prajñāpāramitā's development emerges as a series of distinct but interconnected phases: from early Mahāyāna textual formulations, through interactions with Brahmanical goddess and *mātrkā* traditions, to the elaborate Vajrayāna iconographies of the Pāla period. Prajñāpāramitā's development as a deity did not unfold as a smooth, continuous process but through a series of distinct intensifications: textual, iconographic, and ritual, distributed unevenly across time and geography, each building on but also departing from what came before. This approach also illuminates how the cult of Prajñāpāramitā was inseparable from the broader structures of Buddhist monastic life: its soteriological goals, ritual practices, and community organisation, and how the material production of manuscripts and images both reflected and shaped the devotional experience of the communities that produced them.

Chapter 3 examines how Pāla-period illuminated manuscripts functioned not merely as aesthetic objects or textual containers but as ritually activated artefacts whose sacred status was grounded in the Madhyamaka teaching of *śūnyatā*²⁸ (emptiness) and *pratītyasamutpāda*²⁹ (dependent co-arising), as understood within the late Pāla Vajrayāna context. The chapter is organised around three dimensions of the manuscript's significance. Section 3.2 establishes the manuscript's doctrinal status as a *dharmā*-relic. Section 3.3 introduces Bourdieu's concept of *habitus* to analyse the embodied, socially structured practices through which manuscripts were produced, activated, and transmitted within Pāla period monastic communities: from the technical labour of scribes and painters working within the iconographic conventions of the *Sādhanamālā*, through the ritual practices of recitation, *darśana*, and veneration that sustained the manuscript's sacred presence, to the trans-Himalayan networks of exchange through which manuscripts and their accompanying ritual practices circulated between eastern India and Nepal. Section 3.4 extends the analysis to the *bodhi* tree and the *stūpa*, which share with the manuscripts the characteristic that their sacred status arises dependently from the convergence of material form, doctrinal narrative, and ritual practice. The chapter's central argument is that *pratītyasamutpāda* is not only the doctrinal content of these manuscripts but the condition of their existence as the kind of objects they are: their sacred reality arising through the interdependence of their material, textual, iconographic, and ritual dimensions.

Chapter 4 adopts a reflexive, first-person methodology, examining how historiographical and anthropological frameworks have tended to relegate Buddhist heritage in South Asia to a distant past rather than recognising its continuing presence and contemporary significance. It mainly scrutinises infrastructural politics governing custodianship, management, and accessibility of Buddhist sites in twenty-first-century eastern India, the Pāla heartland, once teeming with institutions like Bodh Gaya and Nalanda, extending to northern Bengal's Bangarh (a key Puṇḍravardhana centre rivalling Mahasthangarh), Nepal's manuscript cultures (observed via 2023 fieldwork), and Ladakh's intermediary role in Buddhist transmission (from 2022 fieldwork), highlighting emic knowledge

²⁸ Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 871-872.

²⁹ Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 669-670.

limits, military infrastructures, and fragile ecologies. The first-person perspective, used deliberately and reflexively, corresponds with, and complements Johannes Fabian's critique of temporal distancing³⁰, integrating the author's positionality as a northern Bengal native and Partition-descendant attuned to borderland legacies of economic precarity, cultural dislocation, and neglect. Informed by Arindam Dutta's *developmental time* and cultural production³¹, Akhil Gupta's postcolonial bureaucracy³², Sara Ahmed's affective economies³³, and Arjun Appadurai's *production of locality*³⁴, this attempt at emic-etic integration draws on eight years of fieldwork in museums, sites, and collections since 2017 which led to interrogating resource inequities undermining heritage stewardship. The chapter concludes with tentative solutions for bridging these disjunctures, advocating for some equitable, temporally integrated, and sensitive approaches.

The concept of time and temporality emerges as a structuring motif across Chapters 2, 3, and 4 of this dissertation. In Chapter 2, temporality is interrogated through the *evental continuum* of Prajñāpāramit'ās iconographic evolution, where the amalgamation of cyclical cosmological time and linear historical consciousness, manifested in the *longue durée* of textual, ritual, and visual disseminations across South, Central, and Southeast Asia, positions her ascendancy as a narrative event. Chapter 3 extends this temporal inquiry by examining how the ritual use of manuscripts dissolved fixed temporal boundaries: the practitioner's engagement with the text enacted a coming together of the past (the Buddha's teachings), present (the ritual moment), and future (the soteriological goal) into a single devotional experience. In Chapter 4, temporality is examined through

³⁰ Johannes Fabian, *Time and the other : how anthropology makes its object*, reprint, (New York: Columbia University Press, 2014).

³¹ Arindam Dutta, "Incompletion: on more than a certain tendency in postwar architecture and planning," in *Architecture in Development: Systems and the Emergence of the Global South*, ed. Aggregate Architectural History Collaborative (Oxon and New York: Routledge, 2022), 25-46; Arindam Dutta, "Designing the Present; The Cole Circle and the Architecture of (an) Imperial Bureaucracy, 1851- 1901" (PhD thesis, Princeton University, 2001); Arindam Dutta, *The Bureaucracy of Beauty: Design in the Age of its Global Reproducibility*, (New York: Routledge, 2007).

³² Akhil Gupta, *Red Tape: Bureaucracy, Structural Violence and Poverty in India*, (Durham and London: Duke University Press, 2012).

³³ Sara Ahmed, *The Cultural Politics of Emotion*, reprint, (Edinburgh: Edinburgh University Press, 2014); Sara Ahmed, "Affective Economies," *Social Text* 79 22, no. 2 (2004): 117-139.

³⁴ Arjun Appadurai, "The Production of Locality" in Appadurai, A. *Modernity at Large: Cultural Dimensions of Globalization*. (Minneapolis: University of Minnesota Press, 1996), 178-199.

the lens of what Fabian calls ‘allochronism’: the tendency of scholarly and administrative frameworks to place Buddhist heritage in a sealed-off past, while my own positionality as a native of northern Bengal, a region shaped by Partition and its ongoing dislocations, provides a ground-level perspective on the asynchronous temporalities that characterise postcolonial heritage management.

Chapter 1: *Polycentric semiosis*: Regional production and iconographic variation in Pāla-period illuminated Buddhist manuscripts and stone sculptures

This chapter examines illuminated Buddhist manuscripts and stone sculptures from the Pāla period through what I term *polycentric semiosis*: an approach that foregrounds localised iconographic features as evidence of regionally distinct production contexts. Existing classifications³⁵, which organise these artefacts by subject matter, colophon, iconographic programme, script style, regnal chronology, geographic origin, and patronage, provide the essential foundation for this study. However, they do not always capture the degree to which individual manuscripts and sculptures bear the marks of specific regional workshops, monastic settings, and local artistic traditions rather than conforming to a single uniform “Pāla style.” Primarily building upon Claudine Bautze-Picron’s study of the art and iconography of medieval³⁶ southeastern Bengal³⁷, especially of an illuminated *PvP* manuscript at the Baroda State Museum and Picture Gallery,

³⁵ Frederick M. Asher, *The Art of Eastern India, 300–800* (Minneapolis: University of Minnesota Press, 1980), 69-101; Susan L. Huntington and John C. Huntington, *Leaves from the Bodhi Tree: The Art of Pāla India (8th–12th Centuries) and Its International Legacy* (Dayton: Dayton Art Institute, 1990), 73-194; Susan L. Huntington, *The Art of Ancient India: Buddhist, Hindu, Jain* (New York: Weatherhill, 1985), 387-414; J. P. Losty, “Bengal, Bihar, Nepal? Problems of Provenance in 12th Century Illuminated Buddhist Manuscripts, Part 1,” *Oriental Art* 35, no. 2 (1989): 86–96; J. P. Losty, “Bengal, Bihar, Nepal? Problems of Provenance in 12th Century Illuminated Manuscripts, Part 2,” *Oriental Art* 35, no. 3 (1989): 140–49; Claudine Bautze-Picron, “The ‘Vredenburg Manuscript’ and Its Book-Covers,” in *The Diverse World of Indian Painting, Vichitra-Visva: Essays in Honour of Dr. Vishwa Chander Ohri*, ed. Usha Bhatia, Amar Nath Khanna, and Vijay Sharma (New Delhi: Aryan Books International, 2009), 7-10; Eun-su Lee, “On Defining Buddhist Art in Bengal: The Dhaka Region” (PhD diss., University of Texas at Austin, 2009), esp. 54-60; Jinah Kim, *Receptacle of the Sacred: Illustrated Manuscripts and the Buddhist Book-Cult in South Asia* (Berkeley: University of California Press, 2013), 216-218; Jinah Kim, “Brahmanical-Buddhist Sculptures: Looking for ‘Bengal’ness,” in *A History of Bangladesh: Early Bengal in a Regional Perspective*, ed. A.M. Choudhari and Ranabir Chakravarti (Dhaka: Asiatic Society, 2018); Phyllis Granoff, “Reading Medieval Buddhist Manuscripts: Thoughts on Text and Image,” *Hualin International Journal of Buddhist Studies* 1, no. 2 (2018): 14-57.

³⁶ I use the term “medieval” in this chapter, and in this dissertation, mainly to denote the period between the ninth and thirteenth centuries CE.

³⁷ Claudine Bautze-Picron, “Images of Devotion and Power in South and Southeast Bengal,” in *Esoteric Buddhism in Mediaeval Maritime Asia: Networks of Masters, Texts, Icons*, ed. Andrea Acri (Singapore: ISEAS Press, 2016), 163–91; Claudine Bautze-Picron, “Buddhist Painting During the Reign of Harivarmadeva (End of the 11th C.) in Southeast Bangladesh,” *Journal of Bengal Art* 4 (1999): 159–97; Bautze-Picron, “The ‘Vredenburg Manuscript’ and Its Book-Covers”.

Baroda³⁸, *qua* a provocateur, I propose a regional nomenclature: *Magadha-Varendra-constellation*, *Varendra-confluens* and *Samatāṭa-littoral*: that foregrounds the geographical distribution of production centres rather than subsuming all Pāla-period art under a single category. The first term positions Magadha and Varendra as interconnected points within a broader cultural cosmos, emphasising their co-centrality without implying a singular core. The second term, a subset of the first, refers to the co-existence and co-emergence of northern Bengal's role as a co-central locus to Magadha³⁹, synthesising monastic, artistic, and intellectual traditions centred at Mahasthangarh, Paharpur and Bangarh, but culturally extending beyond geographic Varendra, with active links to the *Kāmārūpa-interstice*⁴⁰ and the maritime networks of Bay of Bengal through the inter-linked river-systems of north Bengal. The third term⁴¹, I advance to designate the assemblage of the entire trans-Meghna region (present Dhaka Division, Khulna Division, Barisal Division, Chittagong Division and parts of Sylhet Division in Bangladesh, and parts of Tripura in northeastern India: which constituted historic Vaṅga, Samatāṭa and Harikela), as a 'peripheral' locus within the Pāla empire's *polycentric semiotic* landscape. This nomenclature, necessitated by the taxonomic paradigm to be elaborated in this chapter, attempts to look critically at, especially, the Magadha-centric and Varendra-centric monads, and the Bihar-Bengal binary, the latter essentially a modern construct. While Bautze-Picron's iconographic and stylistic study situated the Baroda manuscript in the artistic milieu of southeastern Bengal⁴² (present Bangladesh), to draw stylistic comparisons with other known and related illuminated manuscripts, I use the term *Samatāṭa-littoral* to imply the region beyond southeastern Bengal, incorporating the entire trans-Meghna region, within which regional variations are accounted for. Similarly, *Magadha-Varendra-constellation* would not imply heartland Magadha

³⁸ B. Bhattacharyya, "Twenty Two Buddhist Miniatures from Bengal (11th Century A.D.)," *Bulletin of the Baroda Museum and Picture Gallery* 1, pt. 1 (1944): 17–36; Sarasi Kumar Saraswati, *Pāl Yuger Chitrakalā* (Calcutta: Ananda Publishers, 1978), 45-46, no. 15; Claudine Bautze-Picron, "Buddhist Painting during the Reign of Harivarmadeva (End of the 11th C.) in Southeast Bangladesh," *Journal of Bengal Art* 4 (1999): 159–197, pls. 13.4-6, 13.9-11, 13.14, 13.16-18, 13.20-26, 13.28-30.

³⁹ Connected to Varendra through historic Aṅga.

⁴⁰ I also use the term *Kāmārūpa-interstice*, to theorise the larger Kāmārūpa region in northeastern India as a region mediating trans-Himalayan cultural entanglements with the Pāla imperium.

⁴¹ Although "littoral" may *ipso facto* underemphasise Samatāṭa's inland sites and internal cohesion, this nomenclature is adopted based on relative accuracy to other alternatives.

⁴² Bengal refers to in this study both West Bengal and Bangladesh.

and Varendra, but it takes into account the assemblage of several smaller sites and regional ateliers existing within the extensive cultural boundary(s) of either Magadha or Varendra. This nomenclature supplements existing classifications by drawing attention to how the physical forms and iconographic features of manuscripts and sculptures were shaped by, and in turn shaped, the specific monastic and regional contexts in which they were produced.

Art historical scholarship on the Pāla period has long privileged Magadha as the normative centre, treating regions like Samatāṭa as marginal derivatives. This chapter treats the *Samatāṭa-littoral* as a test-case for the *polycentric* model: its maritime connections to Southeast Asia, its distinctive tantric practices, and its iconographic innovations demonstrate that ‘peripheral’ regions were not passive recipients of metropolitan styles but active producers of their own artistic traditions. This chapter’s principal argument is that Pāla manuscripts and stone sculptures are better understood as products of a distributed network of regional workshops than as emanations from a few dominant centres like Nalanda, Vikramaśīla, or Somapura. Manuscripts and sculptures from Samatāṭa, Varendra, and smaller sites across the constellation exhibit iconographic and stylistic features that cannot be adequately explained by a diffusionist model radiating outward from Magadha. This approach also departs from the heartland-periphery binary inherited from colonial-era scholarship, which has continued to shape assumptions about centre and margin in the study of Pāla art.

This theoretical lens is reliant on Jinah Kim’s extensive and foundational study of Pāla-period Buddhist manuscripts in the context of the Buddhist book-cult, and the ritual and material agency of these manuscripts⁴³, Claudine Bautze-Picron’s numerous studies which highlighted the regional specificity of south and southeastern Bengal, its position as an intermediary between India and Myanmar, as well as the region’s international status in the context of the maritime networks of

⁴³ Jinah Kim, *Receptacle of the Sacred: Illustrated Manuscripts and the Buddhist Book-Cult in South Asia* (Berkeley: University of California Press, 2013); Jinah Kim, “A Book of Buddhist Goddesses: Illustrated Manuscripts of the Pañcarakṣā Sūtra and Their Ritual Use,” *Artibus Asiae* 74, no. 2 (2014): 259-262; Jinah Kim, “Emergence of a Buddhist Warrior Goddess and the Historical Development of Tantrism: The Case of Marīcī,” *Journal of the Indian Society of Oriental Art* 28 (2013): 49-76.

the Bay of Bengal in the medieval period⁴⁴, and localised re-articulation of standardised motifs across Magadha and Varendra, to reflect the heterogeneous aesthetic landscape within Magadha itself, demonstrated for example through stone images from the same period in Kukrihar, northern Bihar⁴⁵. This framework is complemented and supported by Janice Leoshko's critique of heartland-centric taxonomies perpetuated during the colonial period⁴⁶, the works of Daud Ali, who posited that 'peripheral' polities often cultivated distinct aesthetic regimes through patronage, which *diffracted* courtly hierarchies⁴⁷; the recent works of Olli-Pekka Antero Littunen who highlighted the connections between Magadha and Nepal in the context of manuscript cultures⁴⁸; of Giovanni Verardi, who argued that the emergence of localised tantric imagery in central and southeastern Bengal reflect a radical antinomian response to Brahmanical hegemony, suggesting that such imagery was not merely a stylistic, but a material diffraction of Buddhist resistance, challenging the agrarian *varṇa* based Brahmanical order⁴⁹; of Christian K. Wedemeyer, who radically suggested that tantric imagery often functioned not as marginal or primitive, but as a highly managed ritual praxis within a sacerdotal elite, deeply embedded in the institutional framework of South Asian Buddhism⁵⁰; of Gregory Schopen, who emphasised the materiality of Buddhist practice, particularly the integration of tantric

⁴⁴ Claudine Bautze-Picron, *The Jewelled Buddha from India to Burma: New Considerations* (New Delhi: Sanctum Books, 2010), 47–50; Claudine Bautze-Picron, "The Emaciated Buddha in Southeast Bangladesh and Pagan (Myanmar)," in *Archaeopress, Publishers of British Archaeological Reports* (Oxford: Archaeopress, 2008), 77-96. Claudine Bautze-Picron, "The Buddha and His Emaciated Demons," *Berliner Indologische Studien* 19 (2010): 87-122; Claudine Bautze-Picron, "Buddhist Painting During the Reign of Harivarmadeva (End of the 11th C.) in Southeast Bangladesh," *Journal of Bengal Art* 4 (1999): 159-97; Claudine Bautze-Picron, "Lakhi Sarai, an Indian Site of Late Buddhist Iconography and Its Position within the Asian Buddhist World," *Silk Road Art and Archaeology* 2 (1991/92): 239-84; Claudine Bautze-Picron, *Iconographic Development in Pāla-Sena Sculptures and Religious Transformation in Bihar and Bengal (cir. AD 800–AD 1200)* (PhD diss., Jawaharlal Nehru University, New Delhi, 1980). Etc.

⁴⁵ Claudine Bautze-Picron, *The Forgotten Place : Stone Images from Kurkihar, Bihar* (New Delhi: Archaeological Survey of India, 2015).

⁴⁶ Janice Leoshko, *Sacred Traces: British Explorations of Buddhism in South Asia* (Aldershot: Ashgate, 2003), 1-135, esp. 96-122.

⁴⁷ Daud Ali, *Courtly Culture and Political Life in Early Medieval India* (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2004), 13-17, 19, 172.

⁴⁸ Olli-Pekka Antero Littunen, "The Social Life of a Manuscript," *Textual Cultures* 17, no. 2, Special Issue: Material Texts: Religion, Mobility, and Responsibility (Fall 2024): 106-136..

⁴⁹ Giovanni Verardi, *Hardships and Downfall of Buddhism in India* (Singapore and Delhi: Institute of Southeast Asian Studies and Manohar Publishers, 2011).

⁵⁰ Christian K. Wedemeyer, *Making Sense of Tantric Buddhism: History, Semiology, and Transgression in the Indian Traditions* (New York: Columbia University Press, 2014), 170-206, esp. 171-175 "The Social Location of Esoteric Buddhism as an interpretative problem" and "Contriving Marginality"."

rituals into mainstream monastic life⁵¹; of Ronald Inden, who framed ‘polities’ as distinct from ‘society’, as a *co-constituent* of imperial formations with caste being an important determinant, which developed its own meaning, implications, practices and heterogeneity in eastern India in the medieval period⁵²; and of Ryoosuke Furui, whose extensive work has demonstrated the Pāla empire’s decentralised socio-political structure in the context of contradictions in the power relations with regional kingships and subordinate rulers and other social groups, and the social aeration caused by the Brahmanical system in the later Pāla-period⁵³. Further through the lens of Sheldon Pollock⁵⁴, cultural production in the *Samataṭa-littoral* can be situated within the Sanskrit cosmopolis, mediating cosmopolitan as well as vernacular semiotics; and employing Tansen Sen’s perspective, as a pivotal ‘peripheral’ locus in the Bay of Bengal’s maritime networks, facilitating trans-regional dissemination

⁵¹ Gregory Schopen, *Bones, Stones, and Buddhist Monks: Collected Papers on the Archaeology, Epigraphy, and Texts of Monastic Buddhism in India* (Honolulu: University of Hawaii Press, 1997), 23-55, 238-257.

⁵² Ronald Inden, *Imagining India* (Oxford: Blackwell, 1990), 5, 23, 25, 27-31, 217-222, 230-231, 268, esp. 227, 229; Cf. Ronald B. Inden, *Marriage and Rank in Bengali Culture: A History of Caste and Clan in Middle-Period Bengal* (Berkeley: University of California Press, 2023; originally published 1976), 1-48.

⁵³ Ryoosuke Furui, *Land and Society in Early South Asia: Eastern India 400-1250 AD* (London: Routledge, 2019), 130-249; Ryoosuke Furui, “Rangpur Copper Plate Inscription of Mahīpāla I, Year 5,” *Journal of Ancient Indian History* 27 (2011): 232-45; Ryoosuke Furui, “Changing Patterns of Agrarian Development in Early Medieval North Bengal: A Delineation from the Inscriptions,” in *The Archaeology of Early Medieval and Medieval South Asia: Contesting Narratives from the Eastern Ganga-Brahmaputra Basin*, ed. Swadhin Sen, Supriya Varma, and Bhairabi Prasad Sahu (London and New York: Routledge, 2023), 139–53; Ryoosuke Furui, “Subordinate Rulers under the Pālas: Their Diverse Origins and Shifting Power Relation with the King,” *The Indian Economic and Social History Review* 54, no. 3 (2017): 339–59; Ryoosuke Furui, “Brāhmaṇas in Early Medieval Bengal: Data of Inscriptional References,” in *Zen-kindai Minami-Ajia Shakai Ni Okeru Matomari To Tsunagari (Clustering and Connections in Pre-Modern South Asian Society)*, ed. Nobuhiro Ota (Tokyo: Research Institute for Languages and Cultures of Asia and Africa, Tokyo University of Foreign Studies, 2017), 1–36; Ryoosuke Furui, “Agrarian Society and Social Groups in Early Medieval Bengal from a Study of Inscriptions,” in *Inscriptions and Agrarian Issues in Indian History: Essays in Memory of D. C. Sircar*, ed. B. D. Chattopadhyaya, Suchandra Ghosh, and Bishnupriya Basak (Kolkata: The Asiatic Society, 2017), 168–88; Ryoosuke Furui and Arlo Griffiths, “A New Copperplate Inscription: Grant of the Village Kumudavillikā during the Reign of Śaśāṅka, Year 8,” *Pratna Samiksha: A Journal of Archaeology*, new ser., 11 (2020 [published 2021]): 99–113; Ryoosuke Furui, “Merchant Groups in Early Medieval Bengal: With Special Reference to the Rajbhita Stone Inscription of the Time of Mahīpāla I, Year 33,” *Bulletin of the School of Oriental and African Studies* 76, no. 3 (2013): 411–32; Ryoosuke Furui, “Buddhist Vihāras in Early Medieval Bengal: Organizational Development and Historical Context,” *Buddhism, Law & Society* 7 (2021–2022 [published 2023]): 1–45 etc. Also see: B. N. Prasad’s study of votive inscriptions on the sculptures of early medieval Samataṭa-Harikela (Birendra Nath Prasad, “Votive Inscriptions on the Sculptures of Early Medieval Samataṭa-Harikela, Bengal: Explorations in Socio-Religious History,” *Religions of South Asia* 4, no. 1 (2011): 27-43.)

⁵⁴ Sheldon Pollock, *The Language of the Gods in the World of Men: Sanskrit, Culture, and Power in Premodern India* (Berkeley: University of California Press, 2006), 237-258 “Power and Culture in a Cosmos”, esp. 244 [Also Cf. “Kāmarupa” in *Rāmacaritam*, for an idea of kingship, and physical/ mythical geography in the Pāla-period (Majumdar, Basak, and Banerji, *Rāmacaritam*, III, 47; IV,5); Daud Ali, *Courtly Culture and Political Life in Early Medieval India*, 15-16, 71, 172, 265; Also see: Sudipta Kaviraj, “The Two Histories of Literary Culture in Bengal,” in *Literary Cultures in History: Reconstructions from South Asia*, ed. Sheldon Pollock (Berkeley: University of California Press, 2003), 504-505, and Probal Dasgupta, “Bangla,” in *The Indo-Aryan Languages*, ed. George Cardona and Dhanesh Jain (London: Routledge, 2003), 354; Jesse Knuston, *Into the Twilight of Sanskrit Court Poetry: The Sena Salon of Bengal and Beyond* (Berkeley: University of California Press, 2014), 9-15.

of Buddhist texts and iconography⁵⁵, which is further corroborated by the works of Andrea Acri⁵⁶ and Himanshu Prabha Ray⁵⁷. Rob Linrothe's works help us understand the social underpinnings of the development of tantric Buddhism, and the iconography of *mahāsiddhas*⁵⁸. The works of Sarasi Kumar Saraswati⁵⁹, Pratapaditya Pal's meticulous cataloguing of Pāla manuscript iconography⁶⁰, studies of Jeremiah P. Losty⁶¹ and Eva Allinger⁶², and those by Asher, Huntington, Huntington and Huntington, Bautze-Picron, and Kim, as outlined previously, provide a foundation for the iconography study in this chapter. Nalini Kanta Bhattasali's catalogue⁶³, an *opus primum* in ancient and medieval Bengal's iconographic studies, the works of Enamul Haque⁶⁴ and others⁶⁵, document several sculptural

⁵⁵ Tansen Sen, *Buddhism, Diplomacy, and Trade: The Realignment of India-China Relations, 600-1400* (Honolulu: University of Hawaii Press, 2003), esp. 285; Cf. "Kenneth R. Hall, "Coinage, Trade and Economy in Early South India and Its Southeast Asian Neighbours," *The Indian Economic and Social History Review* 36.4 (1999): 431–459. See also Tilman Frasch, "The Buddhist Network in the Bay of Bengal: Relations between Bodhgaya, Burma and Sri Lanka, c. 300–1300," in *From the Mediterranean to the China Sea*, ed. Claude Guillot, Denys Lombard and Roderich Ptak (Wiesbaden: Harrassowitz Verlag, 1998): 69–92."

⁵⁶ Andrea Acri, ed., *Esoteric Buddhism in Mediaeval Maritime Asia: Networks of Masters, Texts, Icons* (Singapore: ISEAS-Yusof Ishak Institute, 2016), esp. 7-13 and 19-22.

⁵⁷ Himanshu Prabha Ray, "Buddhist Monuments Across the Bay of Bengal: Cultural Routes and Maritime Networks," *TRaNS: Trans-Regional and -National Studies of Southeast Asia* 7, no. 2 (2019): 159-180, esp. 162-163; Himanshu Prabha Ray, *The Winds of Change: Buddhism and the Maritime Links of Early South Asia* (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 1994); Himanshu Prabha Ray, *Coastal Shrines and Transnational Maritime Networks Across India and Southeast Asia* (London & New York: Taylor & Francis, 2020), Chapter 7 "The Buddhist Cosmopolis Re-Examined"; H. P. Ray, "The Archaeology of Bengal: Trading Networks, Cultural Identities," *Journal of the Economic and Social History of the Orient* 49, no. 1 (2006): 68–95.

⁵⁸ Rob Linrothe, *Holy Madness: Portraits of Tantric Siddhas* (New York: Rubin Museum of Art, 2006), 14-47, 125-142; Rob Linrothe, *Ruthless Compassion: Wrathful Deities in Early Indo-Tibetan Esoteric Buddhist Art* (Boston: Shambhala, 1999).

⁵⁹ S.K. Saraswati, "Eastern Indian Manuscript Painting," in *Chhavi Golden Jubilee Volume 1920–1970* (Varanasi: Bharat Kala Bhavan, 1971); S. K. Saraswati, *Tantrayāna Art: An Album* (Calcutta: The Asiatic Society, 1977); S.K. Saraswati, *Pālajuger Chitrakalā* (Calcutta: Ananda Publishers, 1978).

⁶⁰ Pratapaditya Pal and Julia Meech-Pekarik, *Buddhist Book Illuminations* (New York: Ravi Kumar, 1988); Pratapaditya Pal, *Indian Painting: A Catalogue of the Los Angeles County Museum of Art Collection* Vol. 1 (Los Angeles: LACMA, 1993).

⁶¹ Jeremiah P. Losty, *The Art of the Book in India* (London: British Library, 1982) etc.

⁶² Eva Allinger, "Mahāmāyūrī and Jāṅgulī as Attendants of Prajñāpāramitā: Investigation of an Unusual Iconographic Feature Based on Bihari Aṣṭasāhasrikā Prajñāpāramitā Manuscripts from the 11th Century," in *Prajñādhāra: Essays on Asian Art, History, Epigraphy and Culture, in Honour of Gouriswar Bhattacharya*, ed. Gerd J. R. Mevissen and Arundhati Banerji (New Delhi: Kaveri, 2009); va Allinger and Gudrun Melzer, "A Pañcarakṣā Manuscript from Year 39 of the Reign of Ramapala," *Artibus Asiae* 70, no. 2 (2010) etc.

⁶³ Nalini Kanta Bhattasali, *Iconography of Buddhist and Brahmanical Sculptures in the Dacca Museum* (Dacca: Dacca Museum, 1929).

⁶⁴ Enamul Haque, *A descriptive catalogue of the Buddhist and Hindu sculptures in the Bangladesh National Museum* (Dhaka: Bangladesh National Museum, 2018).

⁶⁵ Sarasi Kumar Saraswati, *Early Sculpture of Bengal* (Calcutta: Sambodhi Publications, 1962); Marie-Françoise Bousac and Vincent Lefèvre, *Chefs-d'œuvre du delta du Gange: Collections des musées du Bangladesh* (Paris: Réunion des Musées Nationaux; Musée national des arts asiatiques Guimet, 2007); Claudine Bautze-Picron, "The Art of Eastern India in the Collection of the Museum für Indische Kunst," *Indo-Asiatische Zeitschrift* 2 (1998): 4–19; P. K. Bhattacharyya, *Akshaya Kumar Maitreya Museum Catalogue, Part I (Sculptures, Terra Cotta Objects, Paintings, Folk Arts, Coins, etc.)* (Raja Rammohanpur, Darjeeling: University of North Bengal, 1981), 9; P. K. Bhattacharyya, *Iconography of Sculptures* (Darjeeling: Akshaya Kumar Maitreya Museum, University of North Bengal, 1983) etc.

parallels. Archaeological evidence provides further scaffolding to this framework, especially the excavations at the Lalmai-Mainamati region⁶⁶ in southeastern Bangladesh, and the newly-discovered site of a *vihāra* at Bikrampur⁶⁷ in south-central Bangladesh etc.

1.1 Chronology and timeframe

This chapter and this thesis adopt the chronology of the Pāla kings as suggested by D.C. Sircar, with slight modifications based mainly on the works of Jinah Kim on Pāla-period manuscripts, and of Shin'ichirō Hori. Some alternative chronologies are those suggested by: R.C. Majumdar (1971)⁶⁸, B.P. Sinha (1977)⁶⁹, D.K. Ganguly (1994)⁷⁰, and S.C. Mukherji⁷¹. The works of Royosuke Furui have shed new light in understanding Pāla genealogy, epigraphy and society⁷². Shin'ichirō Hori

⁶⁶ F. A. Khan, *Mainamati: A Preliminary Report on the Recent Archaeological Excavations in East Pakistan* (Karachi: Department of Archaeology, Ministry of Education and Information, Government of Pakistan, 1963); Ahmad Hasan Dani, "Mainamati Plates of the Chandras," in *Pakistan Archaeology*, no. 3 (1966): 22-55; Chaudhury Rehmatullah, "Brief Note on Some Problems in Treating Bronze Objects from Mainamati (East Pakistan)," in *Pakistan Archaeology*, no. 3 (1966): 91-98; Md. Shafiqul Alam, *Excavations at Ananda Vihara, Mainamati, Comilla 1979-82, B.A. Series 17* (Dhaka: Department of Archaeology, Ministry of Cultural Affairs, Government of the People's Republic of Bangladesh, 1999); Md. Shafiqul Alam, "Buddhist Establishments at Rupban Mura, Mainamati, Bangladesh," *East and West* 42, no. 2/4 (1992): 281-300; Abu Imam, *Excavations at Mainamati: An Exploratory Study* (Dhaka: International Centre for Study of Bengal Art, 2000); Gouriswar Bhattacharya, "Mainamati: City on the Red Hills," in *Bengal: Sites and Sights*, ed. Pratapaditya Pal and Enamul Haque (2003), 74-75; Bijoy Krishna Banik, *Mainamati: Sanskrit Inscriptural and Archaeological Study* (New Delhi: Sandeep Prakashan, 2022) etc. Cf. Jae-Eun Shin, "Claiming Sovereignty on the Edge of the Imperial Kingdom: The Pālas of Kāmarūpa and the Candras of Vaṅga," in *Self-Representation and Presentation of Others in Indic Epigraphical Writing*, ed. Dániel Balogh and Annette Schmiedchen, *Asien und Afrikastudien der Humboldt-Universität zu Berlin* 63 (Wiesbaden: Harrassowitz Verlag, 2024), 71-92; Also Cf. Maliha Rahman, "An Archaeological Museum Complex: Framing the Buddhist Remains of Mainamati," INSPIRELI Awards, accessed August 5, 2025, <https://www.inspireli.com/en/awards/detail/7991>.

⁶⁷ The discovery of the Buddhist *vihāra* was announced on 23 March 2013, following four years of excavation jointly conducted by the Agrasar Bikrampur Foundation and the Department of Archaeology, Jahangirnagar University, with funding from Bangladesh's Ministry of Cultural Affairs, and collaboration with the Hunan Provincial Institute of Cultural Relics and Archaeology, People's Republic of China. Till March 2013, around hundred artefacts have been found; Mahisun Binte Wahab Rashti, *A Report on the Archaeological Survey and Excavation in Bikrampur Region*, field report submitted to the Department of Archaeology, Jahangirnagar University, Savar, Dhaka, June 6, 2023; "The Daily Star," "Digging Out the Past," *The Daily Star*, August 11, 2013, <https://www.thedailystar.net/news/digging-out-the-past>.

⁶⁸ R.C. Majumdar, *History of Ancient Bengal* (Calcutta: G. Bharadwaj, 1971), 161-162.

⁶⁹ Bindeshwari Prasad Sinha, *Dynastic History of Magadha, Cir. 450-1200 A.D.* (New Delhi: Abhinav Publications, 1977), 253.

⁷⁰ Dilip Kumar Ganguly, *Ancient India, History and Archaeology* (New Delhi: Abhinav, 1994), 33-41.

⁷¹ S.C. Mukherji, "The Royal Charters of King Madanapāla and the Chronology of the Pāla Kings of Bengal and Bihar," *Journal of Bengal Art* 4 (1999): 61-65.

⁷² Ryosuke Furui, "A New Copper Plate Inscription of Gopala II," *South Asian Studies* 24, no. 1 (2008): 67-75; "Re-reading Two Copper Plate Inscriptions of Gopāla II, Year 4," in *Prajñādhāra: Essays on Asian Art History, Epigraphy and Buddhist Studies in Honour of Gouriswar Bhattacharya*, ed. Gerd J. R. Mevissen and Arundhati Banerji (New Delhi: Kaveri Books, 2009), 319-30; "The Pāla Copperplate Inscriptions and Their Engravers," in *Aspects of the Literary Sources in South Asian*

refined the chronology of the Pāla dynasty by establishing the accession and regnal period of king Rāmapāla, which is now considered to be between 1078 CE and 1131 CE⁷³.

1.2 Overview of manuscript production under different Pāla rulers

The historical trajectory of the Pāla empire, spanning from its establishment in the eight century CE under Gopāla I to its dissolution in the thirteenth century CE, as documented in different inscripational sources, reveals the different crests and troughs in political power, that shaped its geopolitical significance over time⁷⁴. These fluctuations were influenced by monarchical succession, administrative capacity, and broader subcontinental developments, resulting in the periodic relocation of the Pāla heartland across Varendra and other settlements in eastern India. By the reign of Mahipāla I, the Pālas had institutionalised Buddhism as a cornerstone of royal patronage, as evidenced by inscriptions, colophons, and copper-plate grants, which served as expressions of both political legitimacy and cultural authority. The Bangarh copper-plate inscription of Mahipāla I mentions how

Historical Studies, ed. Kan Ishikawa, Tokyo Bunko Research Library 25 (Tokyo: The Tōyō Bunko, 2013), 85–114; “Rajibpur Copper Plate Inscriptions of Gopāla IV and Madanapāla,” *Pratna Samiksha: A Journal of Archaeology*, new series, 6 (November 2015): 39–61; *Land and Society in Early South Asia: Eastern India 400–1250 AD* (London: Routledge, 2018).

⁷³ Shin’ichirō Hori, “On the Exact Date of the *Pañcarakṣā* Manuscript Copied in the Regnal Year 39 of Rāmapāla,” *Bulletin of the International Institute for Buddhist Studies* 2 (2019): 49–55.

⁷⁴ Akshaya Kumar Maitreya ed., *Gauḍalekhamālā* Vol. 1 (Rajshahi: Varendra Research Society, 1912), 9-28, 33-44, 55-69, 70-85, 86-126, 147-158.

he brought back the lost glory of the Pāla empire, alluding to how the Pāla imperial power was shaken earlier by the Kambojas, and how the fortunes of the dynasty were restored by Mahipāla I⁷⁵.

Fig. 1. Graphic illustration of manuscript production during different Pāla rulers.

It can probably be held that during and after the reign of Mahipāla I, the Pāla empire enjoyed a brief sustained period of prosperity: which makes it obvious that the production of manuscripts, and cultural production in general, witnessed a spurt during this period, demonstrated by the number of surviving manuscripts from that period, despite the fact that he had to deal with Rājendra's Cōḷa's invasion in 1021-1024 CE⁷⁶. The first known Pāla-period illuminated manuscript was produced in the tenth century CE during the rule of Mahipāla I, who was possibly the eleventh Pāla ruler. If manuscripts were also produced during the rule of the earlier Pālas, they unfortunately do not survive. The twelfth century text *Rāmacaritaṃ*, which is dated to the reign of Rāmapāla, and

⁷⁵ Akshaya Kumar Maitreya ed., *Gauḍalekhamālā*, 91-100.

⁷⁶ Kim, *Receptacle of the Sacred*, 223.

serves as both a historical account and a poetic eulogy of his rule, particularly focus on his efforts to restore Pāla power after the rebellion in Varendra⁷⁷. It vividly describes Varendra’s cultural and economic significance, noting its flora, fauna, and institutions like the Jagaddala Mahāvihāra, which supported manuscript production⁷⁸.

Fig. 2. Pie-chart illustration of manuscript production under different Pāla rulers.

Due to the political stability achieved during his rule, Rāmapāla’s reign has been argued to be a peak period of cultural output. The number of illuminated manuscripts dated to Rāmapāla’s regnal years is also the highest. Moving eastwards, the Pāla capital was shifted to Rāmāvātī in Varendra during this period⁷⁹. This resurgence, although not similar in scale, corresponds with a significant increase in the production of illuminated manuscripts during the rule of some later Pālas,

⁷⁷ R. C. Majumdar, Radhagovinda Basak, and Nanigopal Banerji, eds., *Rāmacaritam by Sandhyākara Nandi* (Rajshahi: Varendra Research Museum, 1939).

⁷⁸ Majumdar, Basak, and Banerji, *Rāmacaritam*, I, 39; III, 7, 29; IV, 2.

⁷⁹ Kim, *Receptacle of the Sacred*, 225.

with notable clusters datable to the reigns of Gopāla III and Govindapāla. Exceptions indicate sustained manuscript production beyond these primary periods. During the reign of the later Pālas, following the short-lived rule of Kumārapāla, starting with Gopāla III and continuing till the end of the Pāla dynasty, manuscript production remained popular, as discerned from the number of known surviving manuscripts. Beyond the scope of this dissertation, illuminated manuscripts continued to be produced in eastern India till at least the fifteenth century CE. After the fifteenth century, illustrated palm-leaf manuscript production might be safely assumed to have come to a temporary end in eastern India.

1.3 A post-taxonomic iconographic and stylistic framework

In her study of the Baroda *PvP* manuscript, Bautze-Picron situated it within the context of manuscript traditions active in southeastern Bengal in the late eleventh century CE, under the reign of Harivarman. She identified the Rajshahi manuscript⁸⁰, preserved at the Varendra Research Museum, and dated to the nineteenth regnal year of Harivarman, as its closest counterpart, emphasising shared features like a trefoil-arched framing, linear draughtsmanship, and the frequent depictions of *caityas* and *stūpas* within vertically tiered compositions. The *KvS* manuscript in the British Library (Or.13940⁸¹) was also judged to be stylistically proximate, particularly in its depiction of architectural elements like deities enshrined within rock-like formations. Bautze-Picron also drew parallels with an Asia Society New York manuscript⁸² (inv. 1987.1), which has two distinct stylistic parts: Part A and Part B, and in which there are two dedications in the colophon: the first mentions its dedication in the fifteenth regnal year of Vighrahapāla III, and a re-dedication in the eighth regnal

⁸⁰ Bhattacharya, "Twenty Two Buddhist Miniatures from Bengal", 17–36; Sachindra Nath Siddhanta, *A Descriptive Catalogue of Sanskrit Manuscripts in the Varendra Research Museum Library*, vol. 1 (Rajshahi: Varendra Research Museum, University of Rajshahi, 1979), 383-384, cat. 689; S.K. Saraswati, *Pāl Yuger Chitrakalā*, 46, no. 16; Bautze-Picron, "Buddhist Painting": 160, 162, 178, 188, 192-193.

⁸¹ Kim, Receptacle of the Sacred, 114, 127-129; Bautze-Picron, "Buddhist Painting": 162; Losty, *Art of the Book in India*, 34, no. 10; Jeremiah P. Losty, "An Early Indian Manuscript of the Kāraṇḍavyūhasūtra," in *Nalinikānta Śatavārṣikī, Śrī N.K. Bhattasali Centenary Volume (1888–1988)*, Studies in Art and Archaeology of Bihar-Bengal, eds. Debala Mitra and Gouriswar Bhattacharya (Delhi: Indian Books Centre, 1989), 1–21; Bautze-Picron, "Buddhist Painting": 162.

⁸² The Asia Society, New York, Mr. and Mrs. John D. Rockefeller 3rd Collection, inv. 1987.1. Part 1 ("part B"): Vighrahapāla III's regnal year 15; and part 2 ("part A"): Gopāla IV's regnal year 8; Huntington and Huntington, 185-189, cat. 58.

year of Gopāla IV. Bautze-Picron stylistically re-interpreted Part B of this manuscript, which was earlier suggested to be part of the later re-dedication, suggesting that there are stylistic resemblances between Part A (and not part B) of the manuscript and other illuminations produced during Gopāla IV's reign. Further resonances were observed in the Cambridge Add. 1643 manuscript⁸³ (which can plausibly be a copy of a manuscript originally produced in the *Samataṭa-littoral* due to its stylistic resemblances with the Baroda manuscript), whose depictions of *caityas* and mountainous terrain parallels the Baroda manuscript. Bautze-Picron also noted the continuities between the illuminations in the Baroda manuscript and the Bodleian *AsP* manuscript (Sansk a.7.) ascribed to Rāmapāla. In another study of images from medieval south and southeastern Bengal, Bautze-Picron critiqued the term 'esoteric Buddhism,' highlighting that the practitioners themselves referred to their path as *pravaramahāyāna* (excellent Mahāyāna), and the supposed esotericism lies not in inaccessible content but in its multi-layered reception where some meaning were exoteric and immediate, while others remained symbolic or subtle, readable only to initiated audiences. Her study also demonstrated how Bengal, particularly the Dhaka-Comilla-Chittagong corridor, acted as a religious and cultural conduit linking the subcontinent with Southeast Asia, with the circulation of bronzes (copper-alloys), manuscripts, and architectural styles attesting to Bengal's internationalism, based on which, the iconography in south and southeast Bengal developed distinctive characteristics. Bautze-Picron observed on the role of south and southeastern Bengal as a cultural transitory zone between India and Myanmar⁸⁴, and further examined the relationship between Buddhist institutions and political

⁸³ This manuscript is unique in the way it illustrates different pilgrimage sites in the medieval Buddhist world along with captions identifying the particular site. For a recent detailed study of this manuscript in the context of "transregional and intraregional activities of people and ideas moving across Monsoon Asia" and how "the sites remembered in the manuscript open a possibility to connect the dots of human movement beyond the known networks and routes of "world systems,"" see: Jinah Kim, "An Ambitious Itinerary: Journey Across the Medieval Buddhist World in a Book, CUL Add.1643 (1015 CE)," *Religions* 16, no. 7 (2025): 900, <https://doi.org/10.3390/rel16070900>; Another recent study on this manuscript by Phyllis Granoff highlighted through a comparative study of the text in this manuscript vis-à-vis various examples of depictions of sacred sites, including an Avalokiteśvara image from Alchi, Ladakh in which "The lower garment or *dhotī* is lavishly decorated with small delicate scenes of temples and worshippers.", that the illustrations in the Add. 1643 manuscript may "well reflect a popular practice of depicting the world, experienced and imagined".(Phyllis Granoff, "Reading Medieval Buddhist Manuscripts": 18-26)

⁸⁴ T. N. Ramachandran, "Mainamati and Lalmai Finds and the Kingdom of Pattikerā," *The Journal of the Greater India Society* 12, no. 1 (1945): 99–101; Gordon Luce, *Old Burma, Early Pagan*, 3 vols. (New York: Artibus Asiae/Institute of Fine Arts, New York University/J. J. Augustin Publisher, 1969–70); Casey Singer, "Painting in Central Tibet, c. 950–1400," *Artibus Asiae* 54, no. 1/2 (1994): 87–136; Bautze-Picron, "Buddhist Painting": 189.

authority: for example, though the Pālas and the Candras proclaimed themselves as *paramasaugata* (excellent devotees of the Buddha), their royal charters reveal a sophisticated negotiation between Buddhist and Brahmanical affiliations, and even as political patronage declined after the eleventh century CE, Buddhist manuscript production and iconographic innovation persisted, particularly under the Varmans and local lay donors. Bautze-Picron had already outlined a brief body of scholarship that suggested the stylistic variations in discussion, which I will be engaging with throughout this chapter⁸⁵. Based on the above laid out framework, I propose a *post-taxonomic* paradigm organised primarily into two stylistic categories⁸⁶: *Magadha-Varendra-constellation* and *Samataṭa-littoral*.

1.3.a *Magadha-Varendra-constellation*

A. Los Angeles County Museum of Art *AsP* (M .86.185 a-d.)

The four illuminated folios⁸⁷ of the *AsP* held at the Los Angeles County Museum of Art (henceforth LACMA) are a significant example of early Pāla-period manuscript production, dated to approximately 1004 CE, during the twenty-seventh regnal year of Mahipāla I⁸⁸. As per the colophon, it was commissioned by Tejokā, a female householder and wife of an official (*kāyastha*)⁸⁹. There are a total of nine illustrated panels⁹⁰ (Plate 1) across all the four folios. Not all the illustrations in this manuscript are in an optimum state of preservation. Red and yellow coloured borders which once adorned each painted panel, have been mostly lost in the panels on the edges. The two central panels (Plate 2) depict the deity Prajñāpāramitā and the *bodhisattva* Mañjuśrī, the side panels (Plates 3 & 4)

⁸⁵ Bautze-Picron, “Buddhist Painting”: 184, 189.

⁸⁶ With cognisance of the regional stylistic variations within each category. While I will be drawing comparisons with iconographic prescriptions in the *Sādhnamālā* in this iconographic study, I will not be engaging in comparisons with the *Sādhnamālā* exhaustively for each deity/ iconographic type, as it is a subject that has already covered in much detail in the works of Bautze-Picron and Kim.

⁸⁷ Pal and Meech-Pekarik, *Buddhist Book Illuminations*, 58-61, figs. 10, 11, Pl. 4; Pratapaditya Pal, *Indian Painting: A Catalogue of the Los Angeles County Museum of Art Collection*, cat. no. 1 (Los Angeles: Los Angeles County Museum of Art, 1993), 50–53; Kim, *Receptacle of the Sacred*, 80, 228.

⁸⁸ Kim, *Receptacle of the Sacred*, 216.

⁸⁹ Kim, *Receptacle of the Sacred*, 225-228.

⁹⁰ Pal, *Indian Painting*, cat. no. 1, 50–51.

Los Angeles County Museum of Art (M .86. 185 a-d.)		
Birth of Buddha	Prajñāpāramitā	Enlightenment at Bodh Gaya
First Sermon at Sarnath	Mañjuśrī	First Sermon at Sarnath
Taming of the elephant Nālāgiri	No illumination	Descent from the Trāyastriṃśa heaven
Damaged	No illumination	Mahāparinirvāṇa

depict additional scenes from the life of the Buddha. The illustration in the first folio depicts the Buddha's birth, with Māya, the Buddha's mother, shown standing and holding a *śāla* tree branch, with her sister beside her, and the infant Śākyamuni emerging from her side. A male deity, possibly awaiting to pay homage, and four *kalaśas* below, symbolise the infant's first ablution. The second folio depicts two Buddhas in a preaching gesture (*dharmacakrapravartanamudrā*), representing the first sermon at Sarnath, and the miracle at Shravasti respectively. The third folio illustrates two well-known episodes from the Buddha's life: the taming of the mad elephant Nālāgiri, and his descent from Trāyastriṃśa heaven. In the Nālāgiri scene, the elephant is symbolically represented by four roaring lions with fire emanating from their mouths. The descent from Trāyastriṃśa heaven depicts Brahmā, with three heads instead of the customary four, holding a fly whisk, and Indra with a parasol, alongside a kneeling figure, possibly the nun Utpalavarṇā. There is a depiction of a monk watching this scene. The fourth folio depicts the death of the Buddha or his *mahāparinirvāṇa*, with the Buddha lying on a couch like structure under the shade of *śāla* trees. There is a small *stūpa* depicted in the sky: symbolising both the *mahāparinirvāṇa* of the Buddha and the presence of Dharma. A pair of

celestial hands plays the drum, while another pair holds some sacred symbols: perhaps implying the eventful nature of this scene. Stylistically, this manuscript appears close to mural painting traditions, like those at Ajanta. The decorative bands are populated with serpent deities and the script itself has resemblance to an inscription on a sculptural pedestal from Sarnath dated to Mahipāla I's reign, and the celestial figures on the decorative bands echo carvings on Nalanda doorframes from his eleventh regnal year⁹¹. I concur with Pal that it was likely produced in or near Nalanda or Vikramaśilā⁹², within the *Magadha-Varendra-constellation*. An incomplete inscription mentions the dates NS 194 (1074 CE) and NS 355 (1235 CE), and the name of Abhayamalla (a Malla king of Kathmandu, 1216-1255 CE)⁹³.

B. The LACMA *DnS* (M.72.1.20 a-b)

The two surviving folios (Plates 5a and 6a) of this *DnS* manuscript⁹⁴ (M.72.1.20 a,b), from the Nasli and Alice Heeramanek Collection, is preserved at the LACMA. It is dated to

⁹¹ Pal and Meech-Pekarik, *Buddhist Book Illuminations*, 60; Pal, *Indian Painting*, cat. no. 1, 53.

⁹² Pal and Meech-Pekarik, *Buddhist Book Illuminations*, 61; Pal, *Indian Painting*, cat. no. 1, 53.

⁹³ Kim, *Receptacle of the Sacred*, 299-300.

⁹⁴ Kim, *Receptacle of the Sacred*, 51, 56, 77-86, 213-215, 264; Eva Allinger, "Mahāmāyūrī and Jāngulī as Attendants of Prajñāpāramitā: Investigation of an Unusual Iconographic Feature Based on Bihari Aṣṭasāhasrikā Prajñāpāramitā Manuscripts from the 11th Century," in *Prajñādhāra: Essays on Asian Art, History, Epigraphy and Culture, in Honour of Gouriswar Bhattacharya*, ed. Gerd J. R. Mevissen and Arundhati Banerji (New Delhi: Kaveri, 2009); Pal, *Indian Painting*, cat. no. 1, 56-57; Nasli Heeramanek, *The Arts of India and Nepal: The Nasli and Alice Heeramanek Collection*, exhibition catalogue (Boston: Museum of Fine Arts, 1966), 105, no. III; S.K. Saraswati, *Pālajuger Chitrakalā* (Calcutta: Ananda Publishers, 1978), 40-42.

approximately 1041 CE during the fourteenth regnal year of the Pāla king Nayāpāla⁹⁵. The text of the

first folio contains homages to the deity Prajñāpāramitā. While the reverse of the second folio, contains very detailed colophon information. It states clearly that this manuscript is a collection of *dhāraṇīs*, or sacred phrases in Buddhism, which are considered to be potent and powerful. Both the folios have three panels of illustrations, with a total of six illuminations. All the illuminations are exquisitely detailed and the manuscript is distinguished by its exquisite craftsmanship: characteristic of manuscripts produced under Nayāpāla's reign. Donated by a Nepalese devotee named Rāmājīva, and inscribed by the scribe Svameśvara, this manuscript reflects the medieval interconnected networks of pilgrimage and material culture between Nepal and the Buddhist heartland Nalanda⁹⁶. This is however the only known example of a Nepalese Buddhist patronising an illuminated manuscript on visiting Nalanda⁹⁷. The string holes are decorated by bands of *stūpa* motifs, and on the second folio, by two lotus motifs within roundels. The central panel of the first folio (Plate 5, a-d)

⁹⁵ Kim, *Receptacle of the Sacred*, 216.

⁹⁶ Kim, *Receptacle of the Sacred*, 48, 51, 52, 213, 214, 219, 226, 244, 254, 344.

⁹⁷ Pal, *Indian Painting*, cat. no. 1, 57

depicts the deity Prajñāpāramitā⁹⁸, with two *utpalas* (lotus flowers) on either side, each supporting a book representing the *Prajñāpāramitāsūtra*. The left panel portrays the Buddha's nativity, similar to those encountered in the previous manuscript, with the infant Śākyamuni emerging from his mother Māyā's side as she holds a *śāla* tree branch, accompanied by *kalaśas*. The right panel illustrates the Buddha's enlightenment at Bodh Gaya, with Māra and his demons attacking, and Bhūdevī as witness. The second folio's (Plate 6, a-d) central panel features the *bodhisattva* Mañjuśrī⁹⁹, painted in a yellow-ocher complexion and seated in the *mahārājājalāsana*, accompanied by worshippers. Two *utpalas* flank the central figure, though it is unclear if they support books, as in the first folio. The left panel depicts the offering of honey by a monkey in a narrative sequence showing the monkey's transformation into a *bodhisattva*. The right panel portrays Śākyamuni's *mahāparinirvāṇa*, overlooked by three monks. The rendering of the Buddha's robes in these folios differ slightly from earlier Pāla manuscripts. Pal noted that there are two distinct types of style to be noticed in the folios: the first, the composition and figuration, which is very suave and reflect artistic sophistication, while the second, like the striations of the Buddha's robes, were perhaps rendered later¹⁰⁰.

C. Kaiser Library Kathmandu *AsP* (Kaiser Library Acc. No. 9.102, National Archives Kathmandu Acc. No. 18, Digital Acc. No. KLD0062)

This *AsP* manuscript¹⁰¹ held at the Kaiser Library, Kathmandu has eight unfinished illuminated panels (Plate 7)¹⁰², allowing a chance to see the process of manuscript illumination. The original colophon does not survive, and there is a later colophon attached at the end of the manuscript, made with yellow Nepalese paper. The absence of a colophon prevents precise dating, but judging from the shape of the folios, which are shorter in width, and the volume and structure of the

⁹⁸ Bhattacharyya, *Sādhnamālā*, vol. 1, 319, 321; Bhattacharyya, *The Indian Buddhist Iconography*, 197.

⁹⁹ Bhattacharyya, *Sādhnamālā*, vol. 1, 49; Benoytosh Bhattacharyya, 48; Bhattacharyya, *The Indian Buddhist Iconography*, 94-95.

¹⁰⁰ Pal, *Indian Painting*, cat. no. 1, 57

¹⁰¹ Kim, *Receptacle of the Sacred*, 257-259

¹⁰² Kim, *Receptacle of the Sacred*, 257.

manuscript, Kim assigned a late twelfth century date¹⁰³, based on comparisons with a *PrK* manuscript produced during the sixteenth regnal year of Govindapāla (ca. 1177 CE). Kim further suggested that the manuscript was produced somewhere between Varendra and Magadha, and remained there for a period of time, before being *transmitted* to Nepal¹⁰⁴. The manuscript was completed as the texts were finished, but the illuminating process stopped at an early stage. Kim also importantly noted, that although the paintings were incomplete, the eyes of every deity in all the illustrations, have been rendered, perhaps implying that due to financial strains, the scribe might have lost access to a painter to collaborate with, and possibly painted the eyes themselves in order to make the manuscript ready for ritual consecration¹⁰⁵. In some of the illustrations, the background colours have been applied (29v-30r), while in some other folios the outline of the figure, throne, cushion, and nimbus are visible (2r), and the detailed delineation of the figures visible in some others (43v-44r)¹⁰⁶. The illuminated folios in this manuscript are also placed “unusually”, as instead of being distributed evenly, they are “... stacked at the beginning (folio 1v-2r), the beginning of chapter 1 (folio 29v-30r), the beginning of chapter 2 (folio 43v-44r), and the beginning of chapter 11 (folio 219v-220r)”, which may imply that the manuscript was earlier intended as a fancier commission, a plan which was later abandoned¹⁰⁷. Although the illuminations are incomplete, the compact lines of the figures, and the elaborate throne outlines, would perhaps allow us to ascribe this manuscript to the *Magadha-Varendra-constellation*.

D. Victoria & Albert Museum *AsP* / Vredenburg Manuscript (IS.5-1958-IS.10-1958)

This *AsP* manuscript held at the Victoria & Albert Museum in London (henceforth V&A), also known as Vredenburg Manuscript¹⁰⁸, after Eric Vredenburg, who acquired the six illuminated

¹⁰³ Kim, *Receptacle of the Sacred*, 257.

¹⁰⁴ Kim, *Receptacle of the Sacred*, 257.

¹⁰⁵ Kim, *Receptacle of the Sacred*, 258-259.

¹⁰⁶ Kim, *Receptacle of the Sacred*, 257-258.

¹⁰⁷ Kim, *Receptacle of the Sacred*, 259.

¹⁰⁸ E. Vredenburg, “The Continuity of Pictorial Tradition in the Art of India,” *Rupam*, no. 1 (Calcutta, 1920), figs. 3, 4, and 8; Saraswati, *Tantrayāna Art*, ill. 155 & 202; Losty, *Art of the Book in India*, 32, cat. 6; Zwalf, *Buddhism: Art and Faith*, 116, cat. 157; Pal and Meech-Pekarik, *Buddhist Book Illuminations*, fig. 19 & pl. 9; Bautze-Picron, “The ‘Vredenburg Manuscript’ and Its Book Covers,” in *The Diverse World of Indian Painting*, ed. Usha Bhatia et al. (New Delhi: Aryan Books, 2009); Bautze-Picron, “Buddhist Painting,” 194; Kim, *Receptacle of the Sacred*, 150-154.

folios in the 1920s. Originally, the manuscript came with wooden covers, which Bautze-Picron documented in a recent study: where she traced the writings of Sentaro Sawamura (1884-1930), a Japanese art historian and poet, who wrote about these covers in 1926¹⁰⁹, hypothesising that Sawamura possibly acquired this manuscript from Abanindranath Tagore¹¹⁰; however, the present location of these covers remain unknown¹¹¹. This *AsP* manuscript is a well-preserved exemplar of manuscript production in the *Magadha-Varendra-constellation* in the late-Pāla-period. As per the colophon, it was produced during the thirty-sixth regnal year of Rāmapāla, dateable to approximately 1115 CE¹¹². Donated by Udaya Siṃha, identified in the colophon as a *vāsāgārika-rāṇaka* (minister of internal affairs), a high-ranking lay official, the manuscript's copious illustrations reflect the significant patronage that enabled its elaborate artistic programme¹¹³. The six illuminated folios, each feature three illustrated panels bordered by thick red decorative bands at the folio's extremities. The iconographic programme focusses on Avalokiteśvara, alongside other *bodhisattvas* and Vajrayāna deities. The central panel of folio 2r (Plate 8, a-d) depicts the *bodhisattva* Avalokiteśvara in the *dharmacakrapravartamudrā*, seated in his mythical abode, Mount Potalaka¹¹⁴, flanked by Hayagrīva (in Sanskrit, "Horse-Necked One"¹¹⁵) on his left and Bhrikutī (in Sanskrit, "She Who Frowns"¹¹⁶) on his right. The left panel portrays the future *bodhisattva* Maitreya¹¹⁷ (in Sanskrit, "The Benevolent One"¹¹⁸) also in the *dharmacakrapravartamudrā*, with an attendant, while the right panel features Avalokiteśvara as Lokanātha¹¹⁹, identifiable by his *jatādhara* (matted hair) and attended by

¹⁰⁹ Sentaro Sawamura, "Miniatures of a Recently Discovered Buddhistic Sanskrit Manuscript," *Ostasiatische Zeitschrift*, Neue Folge 3. Jahrg., Der ganzen Reihe 13. Jahrg., no. 3/4 (1926): 119–23.

¹¹⁰ Bautze-Picron, "The 'Vredenburg Manuscript' and Its Book Covers", 1-2.

¹¹¹ Kim, *Receptacle of the Sacred*, 318, Ch. 5, Note 2.

¹¹² Following 1079 CE as the ascension date as suggested by Shin'ichiro Hori. Kim dated it to 1113 CE (Kim, *Receptacle of the Sacred*, 150, 217.)

¹¹³ Kim, *Receptacle of the Sacred*, 150.

¹¹⁴ Mentioned in the final chapter of the *Buddhāvataṃsakanāmamahāvaiṇyaśūtra* (Tibetan *Kanjur*: Tohoku 44 *Sangs rgyas phal po che zhes bya ba shin tu rgyas pa chen po'i mdo* in the *Derge Kanjur*; Taisho 278, 279, 283 In Chinese *Tripitaka*; part of *Daśabhūmika Sūtra* In P.L. Vaidya's *Mahāyānasūtrasaṃgraha* Buddhist Sanskrit Texts 17, Darbhanga: Mithila Institute, 1960), often identified with Pothigai Hills in Tamil Nadu.

¹¹⁵ Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 347.

¹¹⁶ Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 116.

¹¹⁷ Benoytosh Bhattacharyya, ed., *Sādhnamālā*, vol. 1 (Baroda: Oriental Institute, 1925), 49; Bhattacharyya, *Nispannayogāvalī*, 50, 66; Bhattacharyya, *The Indian Buddhist Iconography*, 93-94.

¹¹⁸ Buswell, Jr. and Lopez, Jr., 517-518.

¹¹⁹ Bhattacharyya, *Sādhnamālā*, vol. 1, 49-50; Bhattacharyya, *The Indian Buddhist Iconography*, 130-132.

Hayagrīva (*Sādhana* Nos. 259, 260¹²⁰). Each figure is set against a deep red nimbus with a *bodhi* tree outline, and the central panel's background includes plantain grove-like trees. There is an absence of elaborate foliated arches or ornate thrones. The central illumination of folio 178v¹²¹ (Plate 9, a-d) again depicts Avalokiteśvara Lokanātha, similarly flanked by Hayagrīva and Bṛkūti (*Sādhana* nos. 169, 170¹²²) (In Sanskrit, “She who Frowns¹²³”), with a similar Mount Potalaka-inspired background featuring plantain-like foliage. Due to its depiction of the eight *bodhisattvas*: Vajrapāṇi (in Sanskrit, “Holder of the Vajra¹²⁴”) (folio 1v, left), Mañjuśrī Vadirāt¹²⁵ (folio 1v, right), Maitreya (folio 2r, left), and Lokanātha (folio 2r, right), and Sarvanivarṇaviṣkambhin (In Sanskrit, “Blocking all Hindrances”) ¹²⁶ (folio 89v, left), Samantabhadra ¹²⁷ (folio 89v, right), Kṣiṭigarbha (In Sanskrit, lit. “Earth Store”) ¹²⁸ (folio 90v, left), and Ākāśagarbha (In Sanskrit, “Storehouse/Womb of Space”) ¹²⁹ (folio 90v, right), signifying the *bodhisattvas* of the Akṣobhya *maṇḍala* as stated in the *Niṣpannayogāvalī*, Kim suggested that the manuscript possibly features a *maṇḍala* of eight *bodhisattvas* surrounding Vajrasattva in the central illumination of folio 89v¹³⁰, and that in this manuscript, Vajrasattva takes over the position of Akṣobhya, substituting Akṣobhya's eight *bodhisattvas* as his own¹³¹. The left panel depicts the goddess Tārā, elegantly reclining on an

¹²⁰ Benoytosh Bhattacharyya, ed., *Sādhanamālā*, vol. 2 (Baroda: Oriental Institute, 1928), 508-509; Bhattacharyya, *The Indian Buddhist Iconography*, 146, 165.

¹²¹ The V&A online catalogue, has listed as folio 178(?) the folio which has a Buddha image in the central illustrated panel, who is depicted with two *bodhisattvas*, situated inside a trefoil arch. The illustrations on the two extremities of the folio depict the *bodhisattva* Avalokiteśvara, with Hayagrīva and Bhrikutī in the first, and depicted taming a demon, while flanked by Hayagrīva and Bhrikutī in the second. Kim listed the folio with the central illustration of Avalokiteśvara as folio 178v.

¹²² Bhattacharyya, *Sādhanamālā*, vol. 1, 341-342; Bhattacharyya, *The Indian Buddhist Iconography*, 152-153.

¹²³ Buswell, Jr. and Lopez, Jr., 116.

¹²⁴ Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 955; Bhattacharyya, *Sādhanamālā*, vol.1 , 49; Bhattacharyya, *The Indian Buddhist Iconography*, 53, 98-99.

¹²⁵ Bhattacharyya, *Sādhanamālā*, vol. 1, 98; Bhattacharyya, *The Indian Buddhist Iconography*, 122-123.

¹²⁶ Buswell, Jr. and Lopez, Jr., 780. Bhattacharyya, *Sādhanamālā*, vol. 1, 50; Benoytosh Bhattacharyya, ed., *Niṣpannayogāvalī of Mahāpaṇḍita Abhayākaragupta* (Baroda: Oriental Institute, 1949), 50, 59; Bhattacharyya, *The Indian Buddhist Iconography*, 92-93.

¹²⁷ Buswell, Jr. and Lopez, Jr., 745; Bhattacharyya, *Sādhanamālā*, vol. 1, 49; Bhattacharyya, *Niṣpannayogāvalī*, 58, 67, 85; Bhattacharyya, *The Indian Buddhist Iconography*, 83-84.

¹²⁸ Buswell, Jr. and Lopez, Jr., 448; Bhattacharyya, *Sādhanamālā*, vol. 1, 49; Bhattacharyya, *Niṣpannayogāvalī*, 58; Bhattacharyya, *The Indian Buddhist Iconography*, 85.

¹²⁹ Buswell, Jr. and Lopez, Jr., 26; Bhattacharyya, *Sādhanamālā*, vol. 1, 49; Bhattacharyya, *Niṣpannayogāvalī*, 58; Bhattacharyya, *The Indian Buddhist Iconography*, 85-86.

¹³⁰ Kim, *Receptacle of the Sacred*, 151.

¹³¹ Kim, *Receptacle of the Sacred*, 153.

Victoria & Albert Museum/ Vredenburg Manuscript (IS.5-1958-IS.10-1958)

2r	Maitreya	Avalokiteśvara	Avalokiteśvara as Lokanātha
178v	Tārā	Avalokiteśvara as Lokanātha	Ucchuṣmajambhala
179r	Oḍḍiyāna Mārīcī	Vasudhārā	Parṇasaḅarī

elaborately designed seat under a tree in the *dharmacakrapravartamudrā*, accompanied by two attendants, a depiction Kim connected to Tārā's growing prominence in Pāla iconography¹³². The right panel features Ucchuṣmajambhala¹³³ (*Sādhana* Nos. 291-295¹³⁴) in the *pratyālīdhāsana*, coloured deep blue, with a ferocious expression, holding a *kapāla* (skull cup)¹³⁵ in his right hand and a jewel emitting mongoose in his left, conforming to iconographic prescriptions in the *Sādhanamālā*. The central panel of folio 179r depicts Vasudhārā (*Sādhana* Nos. 213-216¹³⁶), identifiable by her six arms, holding a pot of wealth in her lower left hand and displaying *varadamudrā* in her lower right, seated gracefully in the *lalitāsana*. The left panel portrays Oḍḍiyāna Mārīcī¹³⁷, characterised by a fierce expression, three eyes, protruding tongue, and fangs, standing in the *ālīdha* pose, coloured in

¹³² Kim, *Receptacle of the Sacred*, 157, 264.

¹³³ Another term for Ucchuṣma: one of the various emanations of Akṣobhya, who is also often depicted with an image of Akṣobhya in his crown.

¹³⁴ Bhattacharyya, *Sādhanamālā*, vol. 2, 569-576; Bhattacharyya, *The Indian Buddhist Iconography*, 239, 179.

¹³⁵ The *kapāla*, basically a bowl made from a human skull, also often symbolises *prajñā* itself— and is a recurring attribute in the pantheon of Vajrayānist deities.

¹³⁶ Bhattacharyya, *Sādhanamālā*, vol. 2, 421-423; Bhattacharyya, *The Indian Buddhist Iconography*, 202-203, 244-245.

¹³⁷ Bhattacharyya, *The Indian Buddhist Iconography*, 214.

yellow, holding a sword in her upper right hand, a bow and arrow in her upper-left, and the *khaṭvāṅga* (in Sanskrit, “The foot of a bedstead¹³⁸”) - *kapāla* (in Sanskrit, “Skull¹³⁹”) in the lower left hand, though only eight of her prescribed twelve arms are visible, as per the *Sādhnamālā*¹⁴⁰. The right panel depicts Parnaśabarī (*Sādhana* Nos. 148-149¹⁴¹), a deep-blue, multi-armed goddess in a fiery nimbus, holding a bow and displaying the *tarjanīmudrā*, with her right foot on a corpse, the latter signifying disease. Stylistically, this manuscript is similar to those produced at Nalanda and Vikramaśilā. Kim noted the palaeographic and stylistic similarities between this manuscript and the *AsP* manuscript at the Bodleian (Sansk a.7.): the letters in the script reflect to have been rendered by a steady hand with a prominent hook at the bottom of each stroke, and in the painting, the figuration and modelling being smooth and proportionate, suggesting its production in or near Nalanda¹⁴², with which I concur. Kim also noted that the colour palette of this manuscript is less vibrant compared to the Bodleian *AsP*, dominated by vermillion and light yellow¹⁴³. Eva Allinger mentioned this manuscript in her comparison with other extant contemporaneous examples, like the *AsP* manuscript at the Tibet Museum in Lhasa from Rāmapāla’s thirty-seventh regnal year¹⁴⁴, or a reassembled *PrK* manuscript in the Benkaim collection¹⁴⁵, from Rāmapāla’s thirty-ninth regnal year, noting the stylistic differences between them; while the Lhasa *AsP* has a colophon which mention that it was written in Nalanda, for the other two manuscripts, there is no such record¹⁴⁶.

¹³⁸ Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 433.

¹³⁹ Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 417-418.

¹⁴⁰ Bhattacharyya, *Indian Buddhist Iconography*, 186–188.

¹⁴¹ Bhattacharyya, *Sādhnamālā*, vol. 1, 306-308; Bhattacharyya, *The Indian Buddhist Iconography*, 196-197, 232-234.

¹⁴² Kim, *Receptacle of the Sacred*, 150.

¹⁴³ Kim, *Receptacle of the Sacred*, 150.

¹⁴⁴ Partially published in *Precious Deposits: Historical Relics of Tibet, China*, vol.1, Prehistoric Age and the Tubo Period (Beijing: Morning Glory, 2000), 118–12; and Jinah Kim, “Unorthodox Practice: Rethinking the Cult of Illustrated Books in South Asia” (Ph.D. diss., University of California, 2006), 94–97; Kim, *Receptacle of the Sacred*, 116-123.

¹⁴⁵ Presently on permanent loan to the Cleveland Museum. Shirley M. Black, “An Early Nepalese Palm-Leaf Manuscript,” *Oriental Art* 13, 2(1967): 107–12; and “Correspondence,” *Oriental Art* 14, 2(1968): 124; Sam Fogg, *Indian Paintings and Manuscripts*, Catalogue 21 (London, 1999), 6–7; Sam Fogg, *Tibetan Manuscripts*, Catalogue 22(London, 2001), 22, 23; and Sam Fogg, *Dreams, Devotion, Romance*, Catalogue 31 (London, 2006), 42; Eva Allinger and Gudrun Melzer, “A Pañcarakṣā Manuscript from Year 39 of the Reign of Ramapala,” *Artibus Asiae* 70, no. 2 (2010): 387; Phyllis Granoff, “Reading Medieval Buddhist Manuscripts”: 51-56, esp. 56.

¹⁴⁶ Allinger and Melzer, 406.

E. Bodleian *AsP* (Sansk a.7.)

Bodleian Library (Sansk a.7.)			
92v	Maitreya	Vajrasattva	Vajrapāṇi
187v	Monkey's offering of honey	First Sermon at Sarnath	Mahāparinirvāṇa
188r	Taming of the elephant Nālagiri	Ānanda with two monks	Descent from the Trāyastriṃśa heaven

One of the most well-known and well-preserved illuminated *AsP* manuscripts¹⁴⁷, dating from 1094 CE, corresponding with the fifteenth regnal year of Rāmapāla, is held at the Bodleian¹⁴⁸ at Oxford. It was bought by the university from the collections of A. F. Rudolf Hoernle, the Indian-born German Indologist. Comprising six illuminated folios organised in three pairs, this manuscript is distinguished by its sophisticated aesthetics represented by very elegant physiognomic features “... with controlled clean lines and painted sheer green over yellow with delicate shading almost like chiaroscuro modelling.” The colour palette is “... rich in saturated vermillion orange, golden yellow,

¹⁴⁷ Saraswati, *Tantrayāna Art*, ill. 143 & 201; Zwalf, *Buddhism: Art and Faith*, 116, cat. 156; Losty, *Art of the Book in India*, 31–32, cat. 5; Losty, “The ‘Vredenburg Manuscript’ in the Victoria and Albert Museum,” in *Makaranda: Essays in Honour of Dr. James C. Harle*, ed. Claudine Bautze-Picron (Delhi: Indian Books Centre, 1990), fig. 12; Bautze-Picron, “Buddhist Painting,” 194; Kim, *Receptacle of the Sacred*, 140–148.

¹⁴⁸ Jeremiah P. Losty, *The Art of the Book in India* (London: British Library, 1982), 32.

and dark blue, with white and black as accent colours”, as also noted by Kim¹⁴⁹. Each illuminated folio features three illustrated panels and four ornamental bands, with decorative bead motifs on both sides. The colophon mentions that the manuscript was copied in Nalanda, and identifies the scribe Ahanakuṇḍa whose script stands out in design and ornamentation, and notes a dedication to a lay female donor, though the name “Rājyapāla” in the colophon is likely a later addition¹⁵⁰. On folio 92v (Plate 10 a-b), there is an exquisite depiction of Vajrasattva, and the *bodhisattva* Vajrapāṇi (Plate 10b) in the centre and right panels respectively, and Maitreya in the left panel¹⁵¹. Painted in green over a yellow base, Vajrapāṇi is portrayed with a serene expression, with slightly upturned lips and curly hair. This central image is flanked on both sides by various scenes of the life of the Buddha. Folio 187v (Plate 10c) depicts the Buddha preaching. Folio 188r (Plate 10d) portrays a monk, painted in a green hue. The monk figure, which is present in more than one illustration in this manuscript, may possibly be a representation of Ānanda, the Buddha’s disciple, who played an important role in preserving and transmitting the Buddha’s teachings: implying the spiritual and intellectual genealogy, in which the monastic community of twelfth century Nalanda is connected to the first disciples of the Buddha, and delivering “... the simple yet crucial narrative of the last chapter of the book, the transmission of the *Prajñāpāramitā* from the Buddha to Ānanda”¹⁵². The placement of the illustrated folios in this manuscript, according to Kim: “show how the makers utilise the three-dimensional space in a book to create an interactive *maṇḍala*”¹⁵³. Stylistically, the manuscript represents one of the finest examples of artistic sophistication during the rule of Rāmapāla in the *Magadha-Varendra-constellation*. Losty noted that this manuscript is stylistically dissimilar to other known manuscripts produced in Nalanda, referring to the Asiatic Society Kolkata *AsP* (Acc. No. G.4713)¹⁵⁴ from Mahīpāla I’s sixth regnal year (ca. 983 CE), and a Royal Asiatic Society *AsP* (Acc. No. Hodgson Ms.

¹⁴⁹ Kim, *Receptacle of the Sacred*, 141.

¹⁵⁰ Kim, *Receptacle of the Sacred*, 140-141; Losty, *The Art of the Book*, 32.

¹⁵¹ Identified by Kim based on the *Niṣpannayogāvalī* (Kim, *Receptacle of the Sacred*, 142.)

¹⁵² Kim, *Receptacle of the Sacred*, 142-143, 146.

¹⁵³ Kim, *Receptacle of the Sacred*, 133.

¹⁵⁴ Kim, *Receptacle of the Sacred*, 223-224, 226, 255-256.

I)¹⁵⁵, dated to Govindapāla's fourth regnal year (ca. 1165 CE), and the absence of throne-backs and cushions in the standing Buddha images in this manuscript¹⁵⁶.

F. Museum of Fine Arts Boston *AsP* (Acc. 20.589)

The *AsP* manuscript¹⁵⁷ (Plate 11 a-d) held at the Museum of Fine Arts, Boston, is a notable example of later Pāla-period production, dated to the fourth regnal year of Gopāla III, approximately 1132/1136 CE¹⁵⁸. There is a set of wooden covers that comes with this manuscript which are painted on both sides, and has been dated to be contemporaneous to the folios. Although badly damaged, and cleaned by the museum to remove traces of worship, the outsides depict vegetal patterns and floral motifs, while the insides feature an elaborate iconographic scheme with a prominent depiction of the Buddha's enlightenment, attended by Maitreya on the right and Avalokiteśvara on the left¹⁵⁹. Remarking on the book covers, Kim observed that in the grand representation of the Buddha's enlightenment in the centre of the interior of one cover, "[...] The shrine structure and the attending images of Maitreya and Avalokiteśvara on either side make a clear reference to the Mahābodhi temple at Bodhgayā ...".¹⁶⁰

As mentioned in the colophon, it was commissioned by Śāntiśrīkamalapāṇisimha, son of Śāntiśrīvajrapāṇisimha¹⁶¹, who as noted by Kim, is identified by the donor title: *dānapati-sāndhi*, and his name itself constructed like the name of a *bodhisattva*¹⁶². This manuscript prominently features Vājayāna deities. There are three illuminated panels per folio, framed by two decorative bands with

¹⁵⁵ Kim, *Receptacle of the Sacred*, 168, 174-176, 199, 202, 237, 265, 333.

¹⁵⁶ Losty, *The Art of the Book*, 32.

¹⁵⁷ Harriet Otis Croft Fund. Provenance on Met website: "Before 1917, probably purchased in India by Ananda K. Coomaraswamy (b. 1887 - d. 1947), Boston; 1920, sold by Ananda Coomaraswamy to the MFA. (Accession Date: April 1, 1920)". <https://collections.mfa.org/objects/149606/>; Kim, *Receptacle of the Sacred*, 150-167, 178, 183, 201-208, 241-243.

¹⁵⁸ *Receptacle of the Sacred*, 216.

¹⁵⁹ Kim, *Receptacle of the Sacred*, 167.

¹⁶⁰ Kim, *Receptacle of the Sacred*, 167.

¹⁶¹ Museum of Fine Arts, Boston. *Inscriptions: The colophon identifies the donor as śāntiśrīkamalapāṇisimha, son of śāntiśrīvajrapāṇisimha*. Accessed August 2, 2025. <https://collections.mfa.org/objects/149606/>; Kim, *Receptacle of the Sacred*, 157.

¹⁶² Kim, *Receptacle of the Sacred*, 241.

red borders and additional bands at the extremities. Folio 205v prominently features the *bodhisattva* Sadāprarudita's (in Sanskrit, "Ever Weeping"¹⁶³) self-mutilation, an act of extreme devotion to the *bodhisattva* Dharmodgata (in Sanskrit, "Elevated Dharma" or "Dharma Arising"¹⁶⁴), depicted across multiple folios. Sadāprarudita is shown standing, bleeding as he cuts his hands with a sword, observed by a Brahman and a female figure in an inquisitive gesture, possibly reflecting a sense of awe (Plate 11 b-d). This imagery may correspond with tantric emphasis on blood and self-sacrifice, as noted by Kim, who connected such scenes to the iconography of tantric goddesses like Vajravārāhī¹⁶⁵ and Chinnamuṇḍā¹⁶⁶. Kim also suggested that Sadāprarudita and the merchant's daughter, depicted in related narratives, could serve as models for lay Buddhist couples, emphasising devotion over conjugal relationships¹⁶⁷. However given the colophon's identification of the donor Śāntiśrīkamalapāṇisimha, son of Śāntiśrīvajrapāṇisimha, it is perhaps also plausible that the manuscript was commissioned to honour the donor's father, with Sadāprarudita's devotion serving as a metaphor for filial piety and spiritual dedication. I suggest this as Sadāprarudita's absolute self-subordination, willingness to sacrifice bodily integrity, and endurance of suffering: demonstrate spiritual dedication in the affective vocabulary of South Asian filial devotion, as the same emotional register that structures parent-child and teacher-student relationships as models of selfless service in Brahmanical and broader South Asian ethical traditions. As Reiko Ohnuma has shown in her study of body-gift narratives in Indian Buddhist literature, such stories of self-sacrifice draw consciously on familial devotional models to construct a Buddhist soteriology of selfless giving that transforms rather than rejects those models¹⁶⁸. In the manuscript context, this connection is reinforced by the figure of Prajñāpāramitā herself as the mother of all Buddhas: with the manuscript thus demonstrating

¹⁶³ Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 728.

¹⁶⁴ Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 254.

¹⁶⁵ Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 957; Bhattacharyya, *The Indian Buddhist Iconography*, 208.

¹⁶⁶ Kim, *Receptacle of the Sacred*, 164.

¹⁶⁷ Kim, *Receptacle of the Sacred*, 126, 164.

¹⁶⁸ Reiko Ohnuma, *Head, Eyes, Flesh, and Blood: Giving Away the Body in Indian Buddhist Literature* (New York: Columbia University Press, 2007).

both the object of devotion, Prajñāpāramitā, and the model of devotion which is Sadāprarudita's filial-style service.

With the first few folios offering profuse depictions of Tārā: Durgottāriṇī Tārā¹⁶⁹, (folio 1v, left panel), Khadiravaṇī Tārā (*Sādhana* No. 89¹⁷⁰) (named after the location she inhabits: a forest (*vaṇ*) of *khadira*¹⁷¹ (*Senegalia catechu*¹⁷²) (folio 1v, right panel), and Vajra Tārā¹⁷³ (folio 2r, right panel)., Kim noted that this manuscript symbolises a culmination of the ascendancy of Tārā in social, religious and cultural contexts, to the extent that the iconography of goddess Prajñāpāramitā started to closely resemble that of Tārā, with the latter's attendants: Jaṅgulī¹⁷⁴ and Mahāmāyūrī (associated with the Mahāsrī Tārā form¹⁷⁵), also transposed into the iconography of Prajñāpāramitā: which can be seen in a mid-twelfth-century CE painting of Prajñāpāramitā on folio 1v of an *AsP* manuscript at the Asia Society, New York (Acc. No. 1982.001.), which was produced in Nalanda¹⁷⁶. Kim further noted that this manuscript, along with the V&A *AsP* (Acc. No. IS.4.1958-10.1958) marks the 'esotericisation' of iconographic programmes¹⁷⁷, especially because of the placement of an image of the Buddha's enlightenment and Vajrasattva-Maṅjuvajra (*Sādhana* No. 83¹⁷⁸) at the centre of the book which "transforms the Buddha's enlightenment from a historical event to the transcendental goal of a spiritual quest of medieval Indian Esoteric Buddhist practitioners¹⁷⁹", and other significant and

¹⁶⁹ Bhattacharyya, *The Indian Buddhist Iconography*, 307.

¹⁷⁰ Bhattacharyya, *Sādhanamālā*, vol.1, 176.

¹⁷¹ A trope that finds visual representation in sculptures, and also very exquisitely depicted, in some late eleventh century dispersed folios of the *AsP* at the Metropolitan Museum of Art: Acc. No. 2001.445i.

¹⁷² While the exact geographical location of Khadiravaṇī is hard to determine, but it can be a toponym. However, I suggest, based on the geography of southeastern Bengal, where *Senegalia catechu* is a common naturally occurring tree, that Khadiravaṇī Tārā might have been a deity specifically worshipped in the *Samatāṭa-littoral*. Bangladesh is one of the world's largest producers of edible catechu: an extract of the *Senegalia catechu*, which is used as a food additive, astringent, tannin, and dye.

¹⁷³ Bhattacharyya, *Sādhanamālā*, vol. 1, 179; Bhattacharyya, *Nispannayogāvalī*, 38; Bhattacharyya, *The Indian Buddhist Iconography*, 240-243.

¹⁷⁴ Bhattacharyya, *Sādhanamālā*, vol. 1, 248, 253; Bhattacharyya, *The Indian Buddhist Iconography*, 191-193.

¹⁷⁵ Bhattacharyya, *Sādhanamālā*, vol. 1, 244-245; Bhattacharyya, *The Indian Buddhist Iconography*, 227-229.

¹⁷⁶ Kim, *Receptacle of the Sacred*, 158, 183.

¹⁷⁷ Kim, *Receptacle of the Sacred*, 150.

¹⁷⁸ Bhattacharyya, *Sādhanamālā*, vol. 1, 161, 163; Bhattacharyya, *The Indian Buddhist Iconography*, 117-119; Bhattacharyya, *Nispannayogāvalī*, 2, 48.

¹⁷⁹ Kim, *Receptacle of the Sacred*, 161.

Museum of Fine Arts Boston (Acc. 20.589)			
94v	KṛṣṇaYamāri	Enlightenment at Bodh Gaya	Vighnāntaka
204v	Sadāprarudita's self-mutilation	Merchant's daughter goes to her parents with Sadāprarudita	Merchant's daughter talks to her father
2r	Eight-armed Tārā or Mārīci	White Tārā	Vajra-Tārā

“high-ranking” esoteric deities like Hevajra¹⁸⁰ (centre of folio 94v) and Sambara¹⁸¹ (centre of folio 95r)¹⁸². Kim argued that the manuscript has been :

... structured as if bringing together the Mahāyāna imagery and the Esoteric Buddhist imagery with the highly esoteric deities (Hevajra, Mañjuvajra, and Sambara) and protector deities (KṛṣṇaYamāri and Vighnāntaka) in the centre and with the Sadāprarudita narrative recast in Esoteric Buddhist context¹⁸³.

Stylistically, Allinger drew similarities between the illuminations in this manuscript and those in the *KvS* manuscript at the British Library (Or.13940) and the Benkaim *PrK* manuscript¹⁸⁴.

¹⁸⁰ Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 348-349; Bhattacharyya, *Nispannayogāvalī*, 14-15; Bhattacharyya, *The Indian Buddhist Iconography*, 157-159.

¹⁸¹ Bhattacharyya, *Sādhnamālā*, vol. 2, 504; Bhattacharyya, *Nispannayogāvalī*, 26; Bhattacharyya, *The Indian Buddhist Iconography*, 160-162.

¹⁸² Kim, *Receptacle of the Sacred*, 159.

¹⁸³ Kim, *Receptacle of the Sacred*, 243.

¹⁸⁴ Allinger and Melzer, 407.

Although there is no colophon information about the location of production, stylistically, in the Boston manuscript, Kim observed the architectural frame surrounding the deities, and suggested that it was produced somewhere in Varendra. Kim also noted that this manuscript uses the full royal epithet of Gopāla, like a *PrK* manuscript at the Rietberg Museum, Zurich (Acc. No. RVI 960a¹⁸⁵) which uses the full epithet of Madanapāla: which was produced somewhere closer to Nalanda than the Boston manuscript, suggesting that both were produced somewhere east of Nalanda¹⁸⁶. I concur with Kim that this manuscript was produced somewhere east of Magadha, but I also propose that this manuscript is representative of a stylistic evolution characteristic of twelfth century manuscripts produced in the *Magadha-Varendra-constellation*, which shows distinctive stylistic appropriation and assimilation from the *Samataṭa-littoral*, indicating multidirectional stylistic and semiotic exchanges, *co-constructing* the visual landscape of both regions.

G. National Archives Kathmandu *AsP* (Acc. No. 4.20; NGMPP Reel No. B23/11)

This *AsP* manuscript¹⁸⁷ held at the National Archives, Kathmandu is an example of later Pāla-period manuscript production, dated to approximately 1160 CE¹⁸⁸ during the reign of Madanapāla. As per the colophon, it was dedicated by a *śausādhu*¹⁸⁹ named Yamāricanda (probably alluding Yamāri, a popular wrathful deity in the esoteric Buddhist pantheon¹⁹⁰), and was prepared by a scribe (*saulekhaka*) named Mahīpati, who was a resident of Santovanagara¹⁹¹. The manuscript features seven illuminated folios (Plates 12a–c and 13a), and two intricately designed book covers

¹⁸⁵ Kim, *Receptacle of the Sacred*, 148, 331, 333.

¹⁸⁶ Kim, *Receptacle of the Sacred*, 331.

¹⁸⁷ Kim, *Receptacle of the Sacred*, 217, 263, 331.

¹⁸⁸ Kim, *Receptacle of the Sacred*, 217.

¹⁸⁹ Cf. the discussion on the “*sādhu*”-related epithets in manuscript colophons in Kim, *Receptacle of the Sacred*, 241–242; and by Allinger and Melzer. Allinger and Melzer’s comments are apposite here: “The word *sādhu* (“good”) can be a part of the name; however, there are at least two instances where it is not clear whether the word is part of the name or a title. In one colophon, mention is made of a *Sādhu*-Gañjaka who is on his pilgrimage to Bodh Gaya and who is the son of the goldsmith *Sādhu*-Sevadhara. The second example is the above-mentioned *Sādhu*-Riyoka. Finally, a much later manuscript was donated by *sādhu*-Śrī-Mūrtidhara, son of *sādhu*-Śrī-Paradhara. Here, as well as in our colophon, *sādhu* unambiguously represents a kind of title. The title *sādhu* along with the female form *sādhunīs* also known from eastern Indian inscriptions and has been translated as “merchant” by Gouriswar Bhattacharya.” (Allinger and Melzer, 411)

¹⁹⁰ Kim, *Receptacle of the Sacred*, 241.

¹⁹¹ Kim, *Receptacle of the Sacred*, 263.

National Archives Kathmandu (Acc. No. 4.20; NGMPP Reel No. B23/11)

No illumination	Vajrayāna deity	No illumination
No illumination	Vajrayāna deity	No illumination
No illumination	Vajrayāna deity, perhaps Prajñāpāramitā	No illumination

(Plate 13b). Accessed via microfilm, which limits analysis of its colour palette, the manuscript's iconographic programme emphasises Vajrayāna deities, *bodhisattvas*, and scenes from the Buddha's life, set within a less refined but ornate compositional framework. Each of the seven folios features a central panel with a single illustration like the Buddha in the *bhūmisparśamudrā*, and Vajrayāna deities flanked by two thin, minimally decorative bands, with undecorated string-holes. The damaged condition of the manuscript restricts detailed study of these decorations. The front cover contains eight illustrations, and the back cover has seven, with the central panels depicting two seated Buddhas in the *dharmacakrapravartamūdrā* and the *bhūmisparśamudrā* respectively, accompanied by attendants. These are flanked by scenes from Śākyamuni's life, including his birth, where Māyā is shown holding a *śāla* tree branch, identifiable by the preserved outline.

The exact location of Santovanagara is uncertain from the colophon. Kim noted that stylistically, and based on the proto-Bengali script, the manuscripts reflect a Varendra origin¹⁹².

¹⁹² Kim, *Receptacle of the Sacred*, 263.

National Archives Kathmandu (Acc. No. 4.20; NGMPP Reel No. B23/11)

No illumination	Enlightenment at Bodh Gaya	No illumination
No illumination	Vajrayāna deity	No illumination
No illumination	Vajrayāna deity	No illumination
No illumination	Vajrayāna deity	No illumination

Although the manuscript is badly damaged and it is difficult to arrive at stylistic judgements based on the microfilm photographs, I concur with Kim, and suggest that even if not produced in the Varendra heartland, this manuscript might be a provincial production somewhere within the ambit of the *Varendra-confluens*.

H. LACMA *AsP* (M.72.I.23)

This single illuminated folio (Plate 14) of an *AsP* manuscript held at the LACMA¹⁹³ (Heeramanek collection), likely dating to ca. 1140 CE, was acquired by Giuseppe Tucci from Tibet. The absence of a colophon and the unknown whereabouts of the remaining folios preclude precise details about its scribe, donor, or production context¹⁹⁴. The folio features three illustrated panels depicting scenes from Śākyamuni's life: the descent from Trāyastriṃśa heaven, the miracle at

¹⁹³ Giuseppe Tucci, *Tibetan Painted Scrolls*, 3 vols. (Rome: Istituto Poligrafico e Zecca dello Stato, 1949): pl. A; Heeramanek, 106, 107, no. 115; Huntington and Huntington, 190-191, no. 59; Huntington, *The Art of Ancient India*, 406-407, pls. 28, 29; Pal and Meech-Pekarik, 57, fig. 20; Pal, *Indian Painting*, 64.

¹⁹⁴ Pal, *Indian Painting*, 64.

Shravasti, and the Buddha's birth. The margins and string holes are framed by decorative bands, with the string-hole boundaries adorned with a seated male celestial figure atop a flower. The obverse's decorative bands are filled with intricate motifs, while the reverse's bands lack such ornamentation. The colour palette emphasises yellows, greens and blues, and the garments of the figures are often depicted semi-transparent. The central panel (Plate 14b) portrays the miracle at Śravastī, where Śākyamuni multiplies himself, flanked by two emanations, seated in the *dharmacakrapravartanamudrā* within a heavily decorated shrine¹⁹⁵. The left panel (Plate 14c) depicts the Śākyamuni's descent from Trāyastriṃśa heaven, accompanied by Brahmā, Viṣṇu, and Maheśvara (Śiva)¹⁹⁶. Brahmā is positioned to the Buddha's right, while Viṣṇu, and Maheśvara flank his left, each enclosed within a halo. The striations on the Buddha's robe, featuring a rectangular patchwork pattern, signifies poverty, reflecting the monastic practice of sewing discarded rags into garments, resembling the rice fields of Magadha¹⁹⁷. The right panel (Plate 14d) depicts the Buddha's birth, with Māyā standing in contrapposto, holding a *śāla* tree branch during childbirth, accompanied by her sister. Māyā is coloured yellow, her sister green, and both are framed within the *śāla* tree's spatial delimitation. Indra and an unidentified blue female deity stand beside them, with the infant Śākyamuni emerging from Māyā's right thigh, and reappearing as a young boy before Indra. It has been suggested that stylistically this folio can be attributed to Bengal, without mentioning the exact stylistic markers¹⁹⁸. Pal differed with this suggestion and posited that this folio was produced somewhere in Bihar, due to its stylistic proximities with the Boston manuscript and an *AsP* manuscript at the British Library (Acc. No. Or.6902¹⁹⁹), which was produced in the monastic-university establishment of Vikramaśilā, east of Bhagalpur, in Bihar²⁰⁰. Due to the ornamental but contained depiction of the shrines, thinner delineation of figures, the nature of depiction of the Buddha's crown, and especially the compositional structure of a Māyā giving birth to the Buddha

¹⁹⁵ Pal, *Indian Painting*, 64

¹⁹⁶ Pal, *Indian Painting*, 64.

¹⁹⁷ Pal, *Indian Painting*, 64.

¹⁹⁸ Huntington, *The Art of Ancient India*, 406-407.

¹⁹⁹ Losty, *The Art of the Book in India*, 32, no. 7; Kim, *Receptacle of the Sacred*, 114, 127-132.

²⁰⁰ Pal, *Indian Painting*, 66.

standing in a contrapposto, in the illumination on the right side, behind whom the gardens of Lumbini are depicted: which formally resonates with sculptural depictions²⁰¹ of the standing images of Buddha and Māyā, where the *śāla* tree is often depicted in an elliptical formal rendering, I concur with Pal that this manuscript was produced in the *Magadha-Varendra-constellation*, perhaps near a monastic-university establishment in the region.

1.3.b *Samataṭa-littoral*

I. Cambridge University Library *AsP* (MS Add.1464)

The CUL *AsP*²⁰² is one of the finest and well-preserved examples of an illuminated Pāla-period manuscript. It has a wooden front cover, possibly a later addition. The manuscript is dated to the fifth regnal year of Mahīpāla. It is debatable whether it was produced during the rule of Mahīpāla I or Mahīpāla II, as it is not mentioned in the colophon. Mahīpāla I ruled between 977 CE and 1027 CE. Mahīpāla II ruled for a very short period of one or two years between 1070-1071 CE. The manuscript was commissioned by a lay woman named Lāḍokā, as noted in its colophon. The illustrated folios follow a three-panel layout with a very thin decorative bands on both edges. The string holes are left undecorated. The iconographic programme is relatively simple: primarily depicting the Buddha in the central panel, flanked by *bodhisattvas* or scenes from Śākyamuni's life. The central panel on folio 2r (Plate 15) represents the enlightenment of the Buddha at Bodh Gaya, depicted in the *bhūmisparśamudrā*, flanked by devotees on both sides, symbolising his triumph over Māra. The Buddha, robed in crimson red, is seated inside a shrine, with celestial figures with bows

²⁰¹ Cf. Ashmolean Acc. No. EA OS.56, Metropolitan Acc. No. 2007.305. (Discussed later in this chapter in the section on stone images).

²⁰² Cecil Bendall, *Catalogue of the Buddhist Sanskrit Manuscripts in the University Library, Cambridge. With Introductory Notices and Illustrations of the Palæography and Chronology of Nepal and Bengal* (Cambridge: University Press, 1883); Alfred Foucher, *Étude sur l'iconographie bouddhique de l'Inde d'après les documents nouveaux* (Paris: Ernest Leroux, 1900), 31, pl. X.1, 3–5; S. K. Saraswati, *Tantrayāna Art: An Album* (Calcutta: The Asiatic Society, 1977), manuscript III, col. pl. 261–263; S. K. Saraswati, *Pāla-Yuger Citrakalā* (Calcutta: Ananda Publishers, 1978), 56, 59, 62; Pal and Meech-Pekarik, *Buddhist Book Illuminations*, 58, 61–64, figs. 13 & 15, pl. 7; D. C. Sircar, “Mahīpāla of a Manuscript in the Cambridge University Library,” *Journal of the American Oriental Society* 102, no. 1 (January–March 1982): 125–27. Losty, *Art of the Book in India*, 30, cat. 2; Zwalf, *Buddhism: Art and Faith*, 116, cat. 155; Bautze-Picron, “Buddhist Painting,” 193; Kim, *Receptacle of the Sacred*, 216, 224, 297.

and arrows depicted at the top. The left panel portrays the *bodhisattva* Avalokiteśvara²⁰³, rendered in white per traditional iconographic conventions, while the right panel depicts Maitreya, coloured yellow and seated within a red nimbus, framed by a shrine. Folio 127v (Plate 16) features the Buddha in the *dharmacakrapravartanamudrā* in the central panel, symbolising the first sermon at Sarnath. The right panel illustrates the Buddha’s birth, with the infant Buddha curiously depicted as a young boy standing beside his mother, Māyā, who leans on her sister under a śāla tree. An attendant offers gifts, in contrast to depictions in later manuscripts where deities like Indra and Brahmā appear. The left panel narrates the offering of honey by a monkey, depicted in four temporal stages: climbing a tree, gathering honey, offering it to the Buddha, and finally ascending to heaven in the form of a *bodhisattva*. The colour palette: dominated by blue, yellow and crimson red, remains consistent. In this folio, there are no elaborate shrines depicted. Folio 128r (Plate 17) depicts the Buddha’s

Cambridge University Library (Add.1464)			
2r	Avalokiteśvara	Enlightenment at Bodh Gaya	Maitreya
127v	Offering of honey by monkey	First Sermon at Sarnath	Buddha's birth
128r	Taming of the elephant Nālāgiri	Multiplication miracle at Śrāvastī	Descent from the Trāyastriṃśa heaven

²⁰³ Benoytosh Bhattacharyya, ed., *Nispannayogāvalī of Mahāpaṇḍita Abhayākaragupta* (Baroda: Oriental Institute, 1949), 58; Benoytosh Bhattacharyya, *The Indian Buddhist Iconography Mainly Based on the Sādhanamālā and Other Cognate Tāntric Texts of Rituals* (Calcutta: Firma K. L. Mukhopadhyay, 1958), 88-89.

multiplication miracle at Shravasti. The left panel portrays the taming of the elephant Nālāgiri, with the white elephant rendered in an animated manner: to convey its ferocity. The crimson-robed Buddha and his yellow-limbed attendant monks are depicted, also against a crimson background. The delineation of the body helps us identify the figures as distinct from the background. The right panel depicts the Buddha's descent from the Trāyastriṃśa heaven, with two figures paying homage: the figure on the Buddha's right, is coloured white, green-robed, and can be the deity Śiva, or it can also be the *bodhisattva* Avalokiteśvara; while the figure on his left may denote another *bodhisattva* paying homage. Other than the green coloured robe of the figure on the Buddha's right, there is no other variation in colour that can be observed.

The manuscript's style has been associated with the 'brittle style' hypothesised by Stella Kramrisch and supported by Sarasi Kumar Saraswati, characterised by its perceived rigidity in form and a limited colour palette. S. K. Saraswati's views are apposite here:

In consideration of style the paintings of the Cambridge University manuscript of year 5, in view of their brittle, tenuous and angular lines, thin and flat colour treatment with hardly any modelling or plasticity and, above all, by the 'further eye' in the figures presented in three-quarter profile into space, offer contrasts to those of the Asiatic Society manuscript of year 6. The paintings in the latter are characterised by flowing and sinuous lines, a charming sense of modelling and plasticity in line as well as in colour, soft and subtle tonalities, etc., qualities that are nearer to the classical tradition of 'the Ajanta family.' The miniatures in these two manuscripts present widely apart traditions, the Asiatic Society manuscript the 'classically Indian' and the Cambridge University manuscript the 'medievally Indian,' as Kramrisch rightly describes them. Kramrisch admits the possibility of the two existing simultaneously and side by side. In view of the marked contrasts in style, in character and also in aptitude, the paintings in these two manuscripts seem to be separated, however, by a distance of time. It is difficult to place them in the same period, within a year of each other, as the date- colophons of the respective manuscripts would lead one to believe. The Asiatic Society manuscript, presenting a style that is nearer to the classical tradition, is presumably earlier in date and may be referred to the reign of Mahipala I in the last quarter of the tenth century. The other two manuscripts with dates in the regnal years of Mahipāla, exhibiting an approximately analogous style and achievement, may also be referred to the reign of this monarch. But the Cambridge University

manuscript, on consideration of the features noted above and particularly on account of the emphatically projected 'further eye,' a characteristic that is itself late in appearance- is possibly to be assigned to the period of Mahipala II who is separated from the first ruler of that name by more than three-quarters of a century."²⁰⁴

The bodily proportions and delineations do not conform to ideals of aesthetic perfection, and may reflect a deliberate focus on iconographic functionality over decorative elaboration. Pal suggested that this manuscript is attributable to the second Mahipāla, along with an *AsP* manuscript at the Asiatic Society, Kolkata (G.4713)²⁰⁵. However Kim, concurring with Saraswati²⁰⁶, argued for an earlier date for the Asiatic Society manuscript, making it the earliest surviving dated illuminated manuscript, due to its stylistic affinity to Ajanta, and connection to Nepal as demonstrated through the use of visual motifs like plantain trees in the background, the title of the donor *śākyācarya*, and the name of the monastery Taḍivāḍi, implying: "... the influx from the northern neighbours [Nepal] sparked the production of illustrated manuscripts in Indian monastic centres." Kim further noted that the iconographic pattern of the Asiatic Society manuscript "... follows an archetypal pattern from which other later iconographic schemes developed."²⁰⁷ I concur with Pal and Bautze-Picron that the Asiatic Society manuscript is attributable to the second Mahipāla due to its stylistic similarities with late eleventh and twelfth century iconography that emerged in the *Magadha-Varendra-constellation* during the reign of Rāmapāla (like the Bodleian *AsP* inv. Ms. Sansk. a. 7, two folios of an *AsP* at the LACMA inv. M.72.1.19 a, b), but stylistically distinct from Add. 1464, which is proximate to manuscript illumination from the *Samataṭa-littoral*. I agree with Kim's observation that the active links between the *Magadha-Varendra-constellation* and Nepal often shaped the iconographic and stylistic evolution in the *Magadha-Varendra-constellation*. I also concur with Pal, Bautze-Picron,

²⁰⁴ S.K. Saraswati, "Eastern Indian Manuscript Painting," in *Chhavi Golden Jubilee Volume 1920–1970* (Varanasi: Bharat Kala Bhavan, 1971), 248–49.

²⁰⁵ Pratapaditya Pal and Julia Meech-Pekarik, *Buddhist Book Illuminations* (New York: Ravi Kumar, 1988), 64.

²⁰⁶ S.K. Saraswati, "Eastern Indian Manuscript Painting," in *Chhavi Golden Jubilee Volume 1920–1970* (Varanasi: Bharat Kala Bhavan, 1971), 248–49.

²⁰⁷ Kim, *Receptacle of the Sacred*, 223-224.

and Kim's indication that Add. 1464 was perhaps produced in the *Samataṭa-littoral* during the short rule of the latter Mahipāla²⁰⁸, dating this manuscript to the late-eleventh century CE.

J. CUL PrK (MS Add.1688)

The colophon of the CUL *PrK*²⁰⁹ indicates that it was produced during the fourteenth regnal year of the Pāla king Nayāpāla (ca. 1041 CE²¹⁰) for queen Uḍḍakā²¹¹. This information implies that the manuscript was produced under royal patronage. Comprising twelve illustrated folios, each with three painted panels within rectangular frames, the manuscript is strategically illuminated at the beginning of each *rakṣā* text and at the text's conclusion, with geometric symbols marking the end colophon of each *rakṣā* section (Plate 18). While the manuscript generally adheres to the iconographic prescriptions of the *Sādhanamālā* for the five *rakṣā* deities, it does not strictly follow all guidelines as mentioned in the *Sādhanamālā* or the *Niṣpannayogāvalī*. Not all conventional elements have however been dispensed with. The depiction of the five *rakṣā* deities which can be found at the beginning of each *rakṣā* text mostly follows the iconographic descriptions in the *Sādhanamālā* (*Sādhana* Nos. 194-200²¹²). However before progressing to look at the five *rakṣā* deities, which are located towards the interior of the manuscript, the manuscript opens with a depiction of the five *tathāgatas* (*pañcatathāgata*) on folio 1v (Plate 19 a) and 2r (Plate 19 b-e) positioned around the deity Mahāpratisarā²¹³, which is not common or conventional. This configuration suggests a unique emphasis on Mahāpratisarā, possibly reflecting her protective role within the *Pañcarakṣā* context. The next set of illustrated folios occur between 19v (Plate 20 a-c) and 20r (Plate 20 d-e). On folio

²⁰⁸ Bautze-Picron, "Buddhist Painting," 193; Kim, *Receptacle of the Sacred*, 224, 297.

²⁰⁹ Foucher, *Iconographie bouddhique*, 31–32, pl. IX.5 & 6, fig. 4; Saraswati, *Tantrayāna Art*, manuscript II, col. pl. 203–206, 245, 259–260; Saraswati, *Pāla-Yuger Citrakalā*, 41, 44, 47, 50, 53; Losty, *Art of the Book in India*, 31, cat. 4; Zwalf, *Buddhism: Art and Faith*, 70, cat. 83; Pal and Meech-Pekarik, *Buddhist Book Illuminations*, pl. 8; Bautze-Picron, "Buddhist Painting," 193; Kim, *Receptacle of the Sacred*, 133-139, 216, 229; Kim, "A Book of Buddhist Goddesses: Illustrated Manuscripts of the Pañcarakṣā Sūtra and Their Ritual Use," *Artibus Asiae* 70, no. 2 (2010): 259-329; Phyllis Granoff, "Reading Medieval Buddhist Manuscripts": 41-50.

²¹⁰ Kim, *Receptacle of the Sacred*, 216.

²¹¹ Losty, *The Art of the Book in India*, 31.

²¹² Bhattacharyya, *Sādhanamālā*, vol. 2, 386-401.

²¹³ Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 506; Bhattacharyya, *Sādhanamālā*, vol.2, 401-402; Bhattacharyya, *Niṣpannayogāvalī*, 42; Bhattacharyya, *The Indian Buddhist Iconography*, 243-244, 303.

20r, in the central panel, the deity Mahāmāyūrī (in Sanskrit, “Great Peacock²¹⁴”), one of the five *rakṣā* deities, is depicted, adhering to her *Sādhanamālā* descriptions (*Sādhana* No. 197)²¹⁵. The panel on the right depicts Khadiravaṇī-Tārā, while the panel on the left depicts Avalokiteśvara.

R.C. Majumdar noted that Candragomī, the Buddhist *mahāsiddha*, lay-scholar and poet, settled in Candradvīpa (assumed to be located in present Barisal, southeastern Bangladesh), where he composed a *strota* to the deity Tārā known as *Āryatārāntarbalividdhi*²¹⁶. Similarly Tārānātha noted that Candragomī had established a temple in Candradvīpa, which housed stone images of Tārā and Avalokiteśvara²¹⁷. On the right panel of Folio 157v in a Nepalese CUL *AsP* (Add. 1643) (Plate 21), is depicted Avalokiteśvara at Nalanda, as identifiable by the caption: *śrīnālendrāyāṃ candragomiṇalokanāthaḥ*, linking the image to Candragomī²¹⁸, while folio 80v of the same manuscript depicts an image of Bhagavatī Tārā in Candradvīpa²¹⁹.

Folio 19v includes three panels depicting Śākyamuni and Maitreya in the central and right panels, respectively, with a *bodhisattva* in the left panel. The presence of eight Buddhas across the manuscript may allude to the Aṣṭabuddhaka (or the eight Buddhas), a theme elaborated in the *Āryāṣṭabuddhakanāmahāyānasūtra*, suggesting a broader cosmological framework²²⁰. The *Āryāṣṭabuddhakanāmahāyānasūtra* gained popularity in Mahāyāna traditions due to its integration into ritual, soteriological and cultural frameworks²²¹. The *Āryāṣṭabuddhakanāmahāyānasūtra* is identified in the Tibetan *Kanjur*, as documented in the

²¹⁴ Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 499.

²¹⁵ Bhattacharyya, *Sādhanamālā*, vol.2, 400; Bhattacharyya, *Nispannayogāvalī*, 42; Bhattacharyya, *The Indian Buddhist Iconography*, 234, 305;

²¹⁶ R.C. Majumdar, ed., *History of Bengal (Vol. I): Hindu Period* (Patna: N. V. Publication, rep. 1971), 299; D.C. Sircar, "The Tārā of Candradvīpa," in D.C. Sircar (ed.) *The Śakti Cult and Tārā* (Calcutta: University of Calcutta, 1967), 130.

²¹⁷ D.P. Chattopadhyaya, ed., L. Chimpa and A. Chattopadhyaya (trs.), *Tārānātha's History of Buddhism in India* (Delhi: Motilal Banarsidass, rep. 1990), 199-209.

²¹⁸ Kim, *Receptacle of the Sacred*, 95.

²¹⁹ Kim, *Receptacle of the Sacred*, 89.

²²⁰ Huntington and Huntington, *Leaves from the Bodhi Tree*, 146.

²²¹ The text's main appeal lies in its emphasis on the recitation of the name of the eight Buddhas, which believed to purify negative *karma*, generate merit, and offer protection from worldly harms. It is incorporated in the *Gzungs bsdus* (Collection of *Dhāraṇīs*) in some Tibetan *Kanjur* editions. The veneration of multiple Buddhas, can also be seen in texts like the *Āryabhaisajyaguruvaiḍūryaprabhārājasūtra* (Documented in Tohoku 504 of the Tibetan *Kanjur*, Taisho 450 and 451 of the Chinese *Tripitaka*, and also in the Gilgit Corpus [Schopen, G. (1978), *Buddhist Manuscripts from Gilgit*, and Dutt, N. (1939), *Gilgit Manuscripts*]; a Sanskrit version is preserved in later Nepalese traditions, as noted by P.L. Vaidya [P.L. Vaidya, ed., *Mahāyānasūtrasaṃgraha*, Buddhist Sanskrit Texts 17 (Darbhanga: Mithila Institute, 1960)]).

Cambridge University Library (Add.1688)			
1v	pañcatathāgata	pañcatathāgata	pañcatathāgata
2r	pañcatathāgata	Mahāpratisarā	pañcatathāgata
19v	bodhisattva	Śākyamuni	Maitreya
20r	Avalokiteśvara	Mahāmāyūrī	Khadiravaṇī-Tārā

84000 project's translation of Tohoku 271²²². The text is titled *Phags pa sangs rgyas brgyad pa ĩ zhes bya ba ĩ theg pa chen po ĩ mdo* (*The Noble Mahāyāna Sūtra of the Eight Buddhas*) and is located in the *sūtra* section of the *Derge Kanjur*. Folio 46r (Plate 22 a-d), features a central panel depicting *stūpa* worship. The *stūpa* is depicted with two celestial beings on both sides making some offering. This panel is flanked on both sides by two illustrated panels depicting Virūpākṣa²²³ on the left, and Vaiśravaṇa²²⁴ holding a staff on the right. Folio 45v (Plate 23 a-d) depicts Mahāsāhasrapramardanī

²²² "The Noble Mahāyāna Sūtra of the Eight Buddhas," *84000: Translating the Words of the Buddha*, accessed July 25, 2025, <https://84000.co/translation/toh271>.

²²³ Buswell, Jr. and Lopez, Jr., 980.

²²⁴ Buswell, Jr. and Lopez, Jr., 951.

(*Sādhana* No. 198²²⁵) in the central panel, flanked by Dhṛtarāṣṭra ²²⁶holding a lute (vīṇā?) on the left, and Virūḍhaka²²⁷ with a sword on the right²²⁸. Several other Buddhist deities associated exclusively with the Vajrayāna tradition are also depicted, such as Vajrasattva, and various forms of Tārā. In folio 64v (Plate 24 b-e), the central panel depicts the deity Mahāśītavatī (*Sādhana* No. 200²²⁹), who is surrounded by Mañjuśrī on the left and Avalokiteśvara on the right. In folio 65r (Plate 25 a-d), on each of the three panels, are depicted three two-armed deities, who are not *rakṣā* deities. At the end of the manuscript, on folio 70r is depicted possibly a monk (Plate 16a) who is worshipping: which

Cambridge University Library (Add.1688)			
46r	Virūpākṣa	stūpa worship	Vaiśravaṇa
45v	Dhṛtarāṣṭra	Mahāsāhasrapramardanī	Virūḍhaka
64v	Mañjuśrī	Mahāśītavatī	Avalokiteśvara
65r	Vajrayāna deity	Vajrayāna deity	Vajrayāna deity

Kim suggested, since another set of *krodha* deities appear on the last two folios of the manuscript

²²⁵ Bhattacharyya, *Sāghanamālā*, vol. 2, 400; Bhattacharyya, *The Indian Buddhist Iconography*, 216-217, 303-304; Bhattacharyya, *Nispannayogāvalī*, 42.

²²⁶ Buswell, Jr. and Lopez, Jr., 255.

²²⁷ Buswell, Jr. and Lopez, Jr., 980.

²²⁸ Losty, *The Art of the Book in India*, 45.

²²⁹ Bhattacharyya, *Sāghanamālā*, vol. 2, 401; Bhattacharyya, *The Indian Buddhist Iconography*, 153, 305; Bhattacharyya, *Nispannayogāvalī*, 42.

(fol. 69v- 70r), may represent a consecration ritual that evoked the presence of the deities that reside in the book²³⁰.

Mevisen published two important studies where he meticulously outlined two different traditions of *Pañcarakṣā* imagery active in this period: which he identifies as the “Nepalese tradition” and the “Indian tradition”²³¹. Bautze-Picron noted the stylistic similarities between this manuscript, and the Rajshahi and Baroda manuscripts²³². In another study, Kim noted that the iconography of the five *rakṣā* goddesses align with their descriptions in the *Sādhanamālā*, which Kim interpreted as either the artists had the iconographic texts, especially their later Nepalese versions, easily at their disposal, or the imageries of the five *rakṣā* goddesses as encountered in this manuscript, might have informed the canonisation of these *sādhanas* as the development and evolution of the *sādhanas*, to quote Kim, “... was propelled not only by the doctrinal and institutional agenda but also by the practical desire to experience and realise the union between *bodhicitta* and *sūnya* ... especially when the text is a compilation of ritual manuals.”²³³

K. Chester Beatty Library Dublin PvP (InE 1463)

The *PvP* manuscript²³⁴, held at the Chester Beatty Library in Dublin, comprises seventeen illuminated folios out of a total of fifty-eight, along with two profusely illuminated wooden book covers, with the remaining folios housed at the Metropolitan Museum of Art and various private collections²³⁵. The absence of a colophon prevents precise dating, but stylistic features suggest a southeast Bengal production, around the turn of the twelfth century CE²³⁶. Folio 55:f.27r (Plate 26, a-b) depicts a central panel with a seated Avalokiteśvara venerating a *stūpa* within a simplistic shrine,

²³⁰ Kim, *Receptacle of the Sacred*, 136.

²³¹ Gerd Mevisen, “Studies in Pañcarakṣā Manuscript Painting,” *Berliner Indologische Studien* 4/5 (1989): 339–74; Gerd Mevisen, “Transmission of Iconographic Traditions: Pañcarakṣā Heading North,” in *South Asian Archaeology* 1989, 415–24.

²³² Bautze-Picron, “Buddhist Painting”: 160, 178.

²³³ Kim, “A Book of Buddhist Goddesses,”: 272-273.

²³⁴ Kim, *Receptacle of the Sacred*, 57, 103-106, 107f - 109.

²³⁵ Kim, *Receptacle of the Sacred*, 104.

²³⁶ Kim, *Receptacle of the Sacred*, 105.

flanked by two *stūpas* at the folio's extremities. The folio is divided into three segments by a thick decorative band featuring roundels within a design panel. Folio 102:f.50v (Plate 26, c-d) features a central panel depicting the Buddha in the *dharmacakrapravartanamūdra*, seated on two elephants,

Chester Beatty Library Dublin (InE 1463)

55:f.27r	No illumination (stūpa on extreme end)	Avalokiteśvara	No illumination (stūpa on extreme end)
102:f.50v	No illumination (stūpa on extreme end)	First Sermon at Sarnath	No illumination (stūpa on extreme end)
103:f.51r	No illumination (stūpa on extreme end)	bodhisattva (possibly Samantabhadra)	No illumination (stūpa on extreme end)

with two *stūpas* at the extremities. Folio 103:f.51r (Plate 26, e-f) portrays a *bodhisattva*, possibly Samantabhadra²³⁷ embodying universal compassion: as suggested by Kim²³⁸, riding an elephant in the central panel, with two *stūpas* at the extremities. The folios are accompanied by painted wooden covers, also in Dublin²³⁹. Kim noted that palaeographically and stylistically, the manuscript is extremely similar to the Baroda *PvP* manuscript, and concluded that the Dublin manuscript was possibly produced in southeastern Bengal, by the same group of artists who produced the Baroda *PvP*²⁴⁰, however also mentioning the fact that the Dublin folios may belong to a different manuscript

²³⁷ Kim, *Receptacle of the Sacred*, 173; Buswell, Jr. and Lopez, Jr., 745; Bhattacharyya, *Sādhnamālā*, vol. 1, 49; Bhattacharyya, *Nispannayogāvalī*, 58, 67, 85; Bhattacharyya, *The Indian Buddhist Iconography*, 83-84.

²³⁸ Kim, *Receptacle of the Sacred*, 107.

²³⁹ Kim, *Receptacle of the Sacred*, 104-105.

²⁴⁰ Kim, *Receptacle of the Sacred*, 105, 108.

because of their difference in colour schemes, especially the absence of bright yellow in the Baroda manuscript, which can be seen in the Dublin and Metropolitan folios²⁴¹.

L. LACMA *AsP* (M.72.1.24 a-c)

These are three illuminated folios (Plate 27a) of an *AsP* manuscript at the LACMA (Heeramanek collection), likely from the early thirteenth century CE²⁴². The absence of a colophon, typically located on the final folio (present in the R. H. Ellsworth Collection but lacking colophon details), precludes precise dating or identification of the scribe or donor²⁴³. A Newari inscription on one folio records its use in a ritual in Nepal around 1234 CE²⁴⁴. This manuscript also prioritises Vajrayāna deities over scenes from the Buddha's life in its iconographic programme. The elaborate ornamentation marks a departure from the compositional simplicity of earlier manuscripts towards decorative complexity. Pal also observed that the important Vajrayāna deities have been prioritised in this manuscript over the scenes from the Buddha's life, which are near the margins instead of occupying a central prominent place on a folio in many earlier manuscripts²⁴⁵. The manuscript in the collection of the LACMA includes three illuminated folios, with the remainder dispersed across collections, including the R. H. Ellsworth Collection, New York, five folios at the Asia Society, New York²⁴⁶, and six at the Virginia Museum of Fine Arts in Richmond²⁴⁷. These folios are profusely

²⁴¹ Kim, *Receptacle of the Sacred*, 312.

²⁴² Heeramanek, *The Arts of India and Nepal*, 106, 108, no. 117; *Handbook of the Mr. and Mrs. John D. Rockefeller 3rd Collection* (New York: The Asia Society, 1981), 1979.53.1.4, 27; Pratapaditya Pal and Julia Meech-Pekarik, *Buddhist Book Illuminations* (Hurstpierpoint: Ravi Kumar Publishers and Richard Lyon – Chimera Books, 1988), 72, pls. 82 (b/w), 10 (color); Susan L. Huntington and John C. Huntington, *Leaves from the Bodhi Tree: The Art of Pāla India (8th–12th Centuries) and Its International Legacy* (Seattle: The Dayton Art Institute in association with the University of Washington Press, 1990), 109–11, fig. 194.; Pal, *Indian Painting*, 64; Denis Patry Leidy, *Treasures of Asian Art: The Asia Society's Mr. and Mrs. John D. Rockefeller 3rd Collection* (New York: The Asia Society Galleries – Abbeville Press Publishers, 1994), 1979.53.1.4, 71.; Joseph M. Dye III, *The Arts of India* (Richmond: Virginia Museum of Fine Arts – Philip Wilson Publishers, 2001), no. 65, 158–59; Susan L. Huntington and Dina Bangdel, *The Circle of Bliss: Buddhist Meditational Art* (Columbus: Columbus Museum of Art; Chicago: Serindia Publications, 2003); Eva Allinger, "A Pāla-Period Aṣṭasāhasrikā Prajñāpāramitā Manuscript Distributed Between Five Collections," *Wiener Zeitschrift für die Kunde Südasiens / Vienna Journal of South Asian Studies* 51 (2007): 77-121.

²⁴³ Pal, *Indian Painting*, 68.

²⁴⁴ Pal, *Indian Painting*, 68.

²⁴⁵ Pal, *Indian Painting*, 68.

²⁴⁶ Pal and Meech-Pekarik, 69, 72, fig. 21, pl. 10.

²⁴⁷ Huntington and Huntington, 191-194, no. 60.

illustrated, rendering this manuscript one of the most elaborately decorated extant Pāla-period examples. The colour palette is dominated by reds, greens and oranges. The first folio (Plate 27c) features a single central panel depicting Khadiravaṇī-Tārā (*Sādhana* No. 89²⁴⁸), identifiable by her green hue, a form associated with compassion and protection²⁴⁹. The deity is described in the *Sādhanamālā* as a single-faced, two-armed figure holding a blue lotus in her left hand and displaying the *varadamudrā* in her right. The panel is decorated with ornate bands. The second folio (Plate 27b) contains three illuminated panels, with the central panel depicting Mañjuśrī (in Sanskrit, “Gentle Glory²⁵⁰”) in the Guhya-Mañjuvajra form²⁵¹. This form is described in the *Sādhanamālā* as a three-faced, six-armed figure holding *inter alia* a sword, book, and lotus, among other attributes. The deity is enshrined within a sophisticatedly rendered shrine which exhibit more detailing than in earlier manuscripts, with animals and figures depicted within medallions²⁵². Flanking the deity are two *bodhisattvas*, one of whom is identifiable as Avalokiteśvara by his lotus attribute. The third folio, like the second, features three illuminated panels. The central panel depicts a wrathful deity, possibly Vajrapāṇi (in Sanskrit, “Holder of the Vajra²⁵³”) or an angry emanation of Mañjuśrī, as suggested by Pal²⁵⁴. The deity is coloured in white, enshrined within a fiery, orange-hued nimbus, and the different attributes of each of his four hands can be identified as:

Elephant goad (*aṅkuśa*) | Elephant goad (*aṅkuśa*)

Thunderbolt (*vajra*) | Lasso (*pāśa*)

Staff (*khaṭvāṅga*) | Bell (*ghaṅṭikā*)

²⁴⁸ Bhattacharyya, *Sādhanamālā*, vol.1 , 176; Bhattacharyya, *The Indian Buddhist Iconography*, 226-227, 307.

²⁴⁹ Benoytosh Bhattacharyya, *The Indian Buddhist Iconography* (Calcutta: Firma K. L. Mukhopadhyay, 1958), 130–132.

²⁵⁰ Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 526-527.

²⁵¹ Pal, *Indian Painting*, 69.

²⁵² Pal, *Indian Painting*, 69.

²⁵³ Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 955; Bhattacharyya, *Sādhanamālā*, vol.1 , 49; Bhattacharyya, *The Indian Buddhist Iconography*, 53, 98-99.

²⁵⁴ Pal, *Indian Painting*, 69.

Los Angeles County Museum of Art (M.72.1.24 a-c)		
no illumination	Khadiravaṇī Tārā	no illumination
Extremity slightly damaged (possibly Avalokiteśvara)	Mañjuśrī in Guhya-Mañjuvajra form	Avalokiteśvara at extremity
Avalokiteśvara at extremity	Vajrapāṇi	Avalokiteśvara at extremity

Flanking the deity are two *bodhisattvas* holding flowers conveying homage. Stylistically, Pal noted the similarities (decorative detailing, animated posturing of Vajrayāna deities) between this manuscript and the illuminations in two folios of a *PrK* manuscript at the LACMA (Acc. No. (M.79.9.9a-b), however, noting that the style of the script is more akin to manuscripts produced in Bengal than those in Bihar²⁵⁵. Due to stylistic markers such as elaborate shrine designs, bold lines that delineate the figures, the minimal rendering of the throne, and a subtle balance between flatness and volume rendering the figuration aesthetically appealing, three-dimensional and animate; and due to the style of the script: as it is quite unlikely that the manuscript is written in one location, and its entire illustration programme is completed in another location, I differ from Pal's attribution, and suggest that this manuscript was produced in the *Samataṭa-littoral*.

²⁵⁵ Pal, *Indian Painting*, 69; Pal and Meech-Pekarik, pls. 17, 18, fig. 29.

M. LACMA PrK (M.79.9.9a-b)

This *PrK* manuscript at LACMA ²⁵⁶ (Heeramanek collection), comprising two illuminated folios, as per the colophon (folio 68), was produced during the seventeenth regnal year of Madanapāla (ca. 1160 CE²⁵⁷), and commissioned by Vikramamāna, a royal prince (*rājaputra*) whose father, Rūdrāmāna, is described as a lord (*sāmantādhipati*). The two illuminated folios, each include a central illustrated panel. Drawing from a report published by Rahul Sankrityayan in 1935, Kim noted that before arriving in the West, this manuscript was perhaps located in Tibet in the early twentieth century CE, at the Gu-rim-lha-khang Library of the Sakya Monastery, where Sankrityayan encountered it: from where few folios entered the collections of the LACMA²⁵⁸. The iconographic programme of this manuscript, following the convention of its time, prioritises the depiction of Vajrayāna deities. The margins and string holes are framed by decorative bands with intricate motifs, and the colour palette is dominated by bright reds and greens. The central panel of the first folio (Plate 28a) depicts the goddess Mahāmantrānusāriṇī within a bright red nimbus, characterised by a ferocious expression, paunchy belly, and green hue. The deity's six hands hold the following:

Hatchet (*paraśu*) | Arrow (*śara*)

Thunderbolt (*vajra*) | Leaves

Mudrā | Lasso (*pāśa*)

The iconography of the deity corresponds to *Sādhanamālā*'s description of Mahāmantrānusāriṇī as a six-armed, wrathful deity (*Sādhana* No. 199)²⁵⁹. Scholarly debate exists regarding the deity's identity, with some suggesting it to be Parṇasavarī due to the green hue and figures at the deity's feet,

²⁵⁶ Tucci, pl. A; Heeramanek, 106, no. 116; Saraswati, *Pāla Yuger Chitra Kalā*, 48; Pal, *Indian Painting*, 66-67, no. 7; Kim, *Receptacle of the Sacred*, 217, T-no. 25 (mentioned as M.79.9a-b); Kim, "A Book of Buddhist Goddesses": 309-310.

²⁵⁷ Kim, *Receptacle of the Sacred*, 217.

²⁵⁸ Kim noted that this might be attributed to the fact that since the manuscript was already incomplete, as mentioned by Sankrityayan (43 of at least 68 folios), and "Perhaps encouraged by its already incomplete condition and by the profit from the art market, someone in Tibet removed two illustrated folios, 36 and 68, enabling them to enter a western collection." (Kim, "A Book of Buddhist Goddesses": 310)

²⁵⁹ Bhattacharyya, *Sādhanamālā*, vol. 2, 401; Bhattacharyya, *Nispannayogāvalī*, 42; Bhattacharyya, *The Indian Buddhist Iconography*, 200, 304-305;

interpreted as trampled²⁶⁰. However, the manuscript's text, concluding with "here ends the charm describing the *rakṣā* goddess Mahāmantrānusāriṇī," supports Pal's identification over Parnaśavarī, who typically features three heads and leaf attire per the *Sādhanamālā* (*Sādhana* Nos. 148, 149²⁶¹). The central panel of the second folio (Plate 28b) depicts Mahāpratisarā, portrayed with a tranquil expression and eight hands with the following attributes:

Sword (*asi*) | Unidentifiable

Arrow (*śara*) | Bow (*cāpa*)

Unidentifiable | Thunderbolt (*vajra*)

Possibly discus (*cakra*) | *Varadamudrā*

The deity's third left hand from the top, if present, is not clearly identifiable²⁶². This depiction corresponds to the *Sādhanamālā*'s description of Mahāpratisarā as a four-armed deity associated with protection (*Sādhana* Nos. 194-196²⁶³), particularly for safe childbirth. Mevissen's analysis of the cult of Mahāpratisarā, emphasised Mahāpratisarā's prominence in Bengal and her iconographic consistency across South and East Asian art²⁶⁴. This manuscript possibly demonstrates the resilience

²⁶⁰ Gerd J. R. Mevissen, "Images of Mahāpratisarā in Bengal: Their Iconographic Links with Javanese, Central Asian and East Asian Images," *Journal of Bengal Art* 4 (1999): 108.

²⁶¹ Bhattacharyya, *Sādhanamālā*, vol. 2, 306-308; Bhattacharyya, *Indian Buddhist Iconography*, 196-197, 232-233.

²⁶² Pal, *Indian Painting*, 66

²⁶³ Bhattacharyya, *Sādhanamālā*, vol. 2, 396-398.

²⁶⁴ Mevissen, "Images of Mahāpratisarā," 99-129.

of manuscript production in late Pāla eastern India, despite the destruction of monastic centres like Nalanda and Vikramaśilā. Pal argued that the continued production of such manuscripts reflects the availability of trained craftsmen and scribes, supported by a culture of manuscript veneration²⁶⁵. I do not completely concur with Pal’s suggestion that Rūdrāmāna may be linked to a Magadha ruler and the manuscript produced in Magadha²⁶⁶, which as noted by Pal, had declined as a manuscript production centre. The curvilinear script further corresponds to southeastern Bengal. Stylistically, the rendering of the figures are very three-dimensional and animate, like the previous manuscript discussed. But it is also possible that artistic and stylistic exchanges between the *Magadha-Varendra-constellation* and the *Samataṭa-littoral* were so advanced and robust by the time of the production of this manuscript, that a strict delineation is very difficult.

N. Two LACMA Manuscript Covers (M.77.19.2a-b)

²⁶⁵ Pal, *Indian Painting*, 67.

²⁶⁶ Pal, *Indian Painting*, 66.

The two wooden manuscript covers at the LACMA²⁶⁷ (from the Heeramaneck collection) are likely dateable to the the mid-twelfth century. These covers (Plate 29a-e) lack associated folios and a colophon, rendering the specific text they protected, potentially a *PrK* or a *DnS*²⁶⁸, a bit oblivious. The covers feature a continuous series of shrine-like panels without distinct decorative bands, creating a unified iconographic narrative. The foliage is dominated by plantains and coconuts. The front cover (M.77.19.2a, Plate 29b–c) comprises nine panels²⁶⁹. The first panel shows Avalokiteśvara in a contrapposto pose, feeding ambrosia to *piśācas* (lowly beings), a compassionate motif paralleled in depictions of green Tārā. The second panel features a multi-armed *bodhisattva* with devotees²⁷⁰, the third depicts a four-armed Kurukullā²⁷¹, likely Oḍḍiyāna-Kurukullā, within a fiery nimbus, adhering to the *Sāadhanamālā*, which specify her bow and arrow attributes (*Sādhana* No. 179²⁷²). The depiction of six-armed Sugatisaṃdarśanalokeśvara²⁷³ in the fourth panel, white in colour, follows the *Sāadhanamālā* (*Sādhana* No. 42²⁷⁴). Bautze-Picron identified the image as a six-armed Avalokiteśvara²⁷⁵. The fifth panel depicts an eight-armed deity with a chequered garment, and is too damaged for identification, whom Bautze-Picron identified at Vajra-Tārā²⁷⁶. The sixth panel presents a twelve-armed Avalokiteśvara, yellow-hued with red garments, as prescribed in the *Sāadhanamālā*²⁷⁷. The seventh panel depicts Nairātmyā (In Sanskrit, “Selflessness²⁷⁸”), a blue deity dancing on a corpse, with two *ḍākinī* attendants, embodying *śūnyatā* (emptiness) as a female

²⁶⁷ Heeramaneck, 108, no. 120; Pal and Meech-Pekarik, 74-75, fig. 23a-b; Pal, *Indian Painting*, 71-73; Claudine Bautze-Picron, “The Los Angeles Manuscript Covers: Uncovering and Explaining Their Iconography,” *Journal of Bengal Art* 5 (2000): 95-128; Claudine Bautze-Picron, “The Los Angeles Manuscript Covers: Iconography and Style,” in *South Asian Archaeology 1999: Proceedings of the Fifteenth International Conference of the European Association of South Asian Archaeologists Held at the Universiteit Leiden, 5–9 July, 1999*, ed. Ellen M. Raven (Groningen: Egbert Forsten, 2008), 481-92.

²⁶⁸ Pal, *Indian Painting*, 72.

²⁶⁹ Pal, *Indian Painting*, 72.

²⁷⁰ Identified as Avalokiteśvara by Bautze-Picron, noting “The six-handed, seated representations as here are rather uncommon; they are mainly noticed in sculpture.” (Bautze-Picron, 481)

²⁷¹ Buswell, Jr. and Lopez, Jr., 456.

²⁷² Bhattacharyya, *Sāadhanamālā*, vol. 2, 358; Bhattacharyya, *The Indian Buddhist Iconography*, 149

²⁷³ Bautze-Picron prefers to term Avalokiteśvara.

²⁷⁴ Bhattacharyya, *Sāadhanamālā*, vol. 1, 88; Bhattacharyya, *The Indian Buddhist Iconography*, 141.

²⁷⁵ Bautze-Picron, “The Los Angeles Manuscript Covers”: 483.

²⁷⁶ Bautze-Picron, “The Los Angeles Manuscript Covers”: 482.

²⁷⁷ Bhattacharyya, *Sāadhanamālā*, vol. 2, 86; Bhattacharyya, *Indian Buddhist Iconography*, 139.

²⁷⁸ Buswell, Jr. and Lopez, Jr., 563-564.

emanation of Akṣobhya (In Sanskrit, “Immovable²⁷⁹”), per the *Sāghanamālā*²⁸⁰. Bautze-Picron identified this figure as Vajravarāhī. The eighth panel portrays another six-armed Avalokiteśvara accompanied by Hayagrīva and Sudhanakumāra²⁸¹. The ninth panel shows green Tārā in contrapposto, feeding *piśācas*, and supported by Ekajaṭā (In Sanskrit, “Having One Lock of Hair²⁸²”) in a tiger skin. Ekajaṭā’s *sādhana* in the *Sāghanamālā* (*Sādhana* Nos. 124-127), especially *Sādhana* No. 127²⁸³, reveals that Nāgārjuna embraced the deity’s worship from the inhabitants of Bhota²⁸⁴. Bhattacharyya associated Bhota with Tibet²⁸⁵, and proposed that Ekajaṭā, revered by Tibetans, gradually became integrated into the Tārā cult, and emerged as the most favoured companion of Tārā after the ninth century CE²⁸⁶. The description of Ekajaṭā in the *Sāghanamālā*, also closely aligns with the description of Mahācīnatārā (*Sādhana* Nos. 100-101²⁸⁷).

The back cover (M.77.19.2b, Plate 29d–e) features seven panels²⁸⁸: Tārā, Mañjuśrī, a female deity (whom Bautze-Picron identified as Mārīcī²⁸⁹), Mañjuśrīnāmasaṃgīti, Cundā²⁹⁰ (*Sādhana* Nos. 129-131²⁹¹) or Mañjuśrī, a green wrathful deity possibly Parṇasabārī, and Avalokiteśvara Siṃhanāda²⁹². The first panel depicts Tārā in contrapposto, feeding *piśācas*, mirroring the front cover. The second panel shows Mañjuśrī, possibly Mañjuvajra riding a lion (*Sādhana* Nos. 70, 76²⁹³). The third panel, heavily damaged, depicts a female deity against an orange background.

²⁷⁹ Buswell, Jr. and Lopez, Jr., 27.

²⁸⁰ Bhattacharyya, *Sāghanamālā*, vol. 2, 451; Bhattacharyya, *The Indian Buddhist Iconography*, 203-204.

²⁸¹ Buswell, Jr. and Lopez, Jr., 863; In his study of precedents of *siddha* imagery in Buddhist art, Linrothe mentioned a *Gaṇḍavyūhasūtra* manuscript at the Asia Society, New York (Acc. No. 1979.054.1-4) from the early eleventh-twelfth century CE, in which the depiction of *bodhisattva* Sudhanakumāra visiting a teacher is portrayed (Linrothe, *Holy Madness*, 184-187, Cat. No. 2).

²⁸² Buswell, Jr. and Lopez, Jr., 281.

²⁸³ Bhattacharyya, *Sāghanamālā*, vol. 1, 260-266; Bhattacharyya, *The Indian Buddhist Iconography*, 193.

²⁸⁴ Bhattacharyya, *Sāghanamālā*, vol. 1, 267.

²⁸⁵ Bhattacharyya, *Sāghanamālā*, vol. 2, cxli.

²⁸⁶ Cf. Jae-Eun Shin, "Transformation of the Goddess Tārā - with Special Reference to the Iconographical Features," in *Studies in South Asian Art and Archaeology*, vol. 31 (2009-2010), offprint (Indian Archaeological Society [Japan], 2010): 24.

²⁸⁷ Bhattacharyya, *Sāghanamālā*, vol. 1, 208-211; Bhattacharyya, *The Indian Buddhist Iconography*, 189-191.

²⁸⁸ Pal, *Indian Painting*, 72.

²⁸⁹ Bautze-Picron, “The Los Angeles Manuscript Covers”: 485.

²⁹⁰ Buswell, Jr. and Lopez, Jr., 203-204.

²⁹¹ Bhattacharyya, *Sāghanamālā*, vol. 1 & 2, 270-273, 352; Bhattacharyya, *The Indian Buddhist Iconography*, 219-224; Bhattacharyya, *Nispannayogāvalī*, 49, 57, 89.

²⁹² Bhattacharyya, *Sāghanamālā*, vol. 1, 63; Bhattacharyya, *The Indian Buddhist Iconography*, 127-128.

²⁹³ Bhattacharyya, *Sāghanamālā*, vol. 1, 142, 151; Bhattacharyya, *The Indian Buddhist Iconography*, 100-123.

The fourth panel features Mañjuśrīnāmasaṅgīti, a twelve-armed Mañjuśrī variant, yellow-hued on a red background, per the *Sādhanamālā* (*Sādhana* No. 82²⁹⁴). The fifth panel portrays the goddess Cundā seated with two attendants, but it was identified by Bautze-Picron as Mañjuśrī, accompanied by Sudhanakumāra and Yamāntaka (In Sanskrit, “Destroyer of Death”²⁹⁵). Bautze-Picron suggested that the sixth panel depicts a ten-armed Nāmasaṅgīti, who forms a pair with the twelve-armed goddess in the fourth panel²⁹⁶. The seventh panel depicts a green wrathful deity, possibly a Vajrayāna goddess, suggested by Bautze-Picron to depict Parṇaśabarī²⁹⁷, followed by Avalokiteśvara Siṃhanāda riding a lion. The final panel shows Tārā holding a tree branch, feeding *piśācas*.

²⁹⁴ Bhattacharyya, *Sādhanamālā*, vol. 1, 159-160; Bhattacharyya, *The Indian Buddhist Iconography*, 115-116.

²⁹⁵ Buswell, Jr. and Lopez, Jr., 1020.

²⁹⁶ Bautze-Picron, “The Los Angeles Manuscript Covers: Iconography and Style”: 485.

²⁹⁷ Bautze-Picron, “The Los Angeles Manuscript Covers: Iconography and Style”: 485.

Los Angeles County Museum of Art Manuscript Covers (M.77.19.2a-b)

Front cover	Avalokiteśvara	multi-armed bodhisattva	Kurukullā	Sugatasamdarśanal okeśvara	unidentified female deity	twelve-armed Avalokiteśvara	Nairātmā or Vajravārāhi	multi-armed bodhisattva	Tārā
	Back cover	Tārā	Mañjuśrī	Māricī	Mañjuśrīnāmasaṅgīti	Cundā or Mañjuśrī	Nāmasaṅgīti	Parṇasābarī	Avalokiteśvara Siṃhanāda

Pal noted similarities with a mid-twelfth century book cover at the Museum of Fine Arts, Boston²⁹⁸, and a dated *PrK* manuscript²⁹⁹ from 1160-1161 CE (M.79.9.9a-b). Bautze-Picron published two important studies on these manuscript covers³⁰⁰, in which she provided a detailed analysis of the iconographic depictions to the two boards, comparing³⁰¹ these covers to manuscripts from the reign of Rāmapāla and Gopāla IV (first half of the twelfth century CE³⁰²), highlighting distinctive iconographic features, like the rare use of animal medallions in the inner margins, the

²⁹⁸ Pratapaditya Pal, *Indian Painting: A Catalogue of the Los Angeles County Museum of Art Collection* (Los Angeles: LACMA, 1993), 62; Pratapaditya Pal and Julia Meech-Pekarik, *Buddhist Book Illuminations* (New York: Ravi Kumar, 1988), 71; Ananda K. Coomaraswamy, *Catalogue of the Indian Collections in the Museum of Fine Arts, Boston* (Boston: Museum of Fine Arts, 1923), 45.

²⁹⁹ Discussed previously in this section (E).

³⁰⁰ Claudine Bautze-Picron, "The Los Angeles Manuscript Covers: Uncovering and Explaining Their Iconography," *Journal of Bengal Art* 5 (2000): 95-128; Claudine Bautze-Picron, "The Los Angeles Manuscript Covers: Iconography and Style," in *South Asian Archaeology 1999: Proceedings of the Fifteenth International Conference of the European Association of South Asian Archaeologists Held at the Universiteit Leiden, 5–9 July, 1999*, ed. Ellen M. Raven (Groningen: Egbert Forsten, 2008), 481-92.

³⁰¹ Bautze-Picron, "The Los Angeles Manuscript Covers: Iconography and Style": 488.

³⁰² Bautze-Picron, "The Los Angeles Manuscript Covers: Iconography and Style": 490.

absence of traditional throne structures, and the presence of a cushion and flamed nimbus³⁰³, which differ from Bihar (*Magadha-Varendra-constellation*) manuscripts but align with stylistic trends in southern and southeastern Bengal³⁰⁴ (*Samataṭa-littoral*), arguing that these covers represent a transitional phase in manuscript illumination, bridging earlier and later artistic traditions in the region, and also suggest a connection to broader artistic exchanges, including influences seen in Burmese manuscripts³⁰⁵.

O. Some dispersed folios of *AsP* at the Metropolitan Museum of Art, New York (2001.445j; 2001.445h; 2001.445i; & 2001.445c)

These folios are some of the finest and most exquisite extant examples of Pāla-period manuscript illuminations from Bengal. Although these are dispersed folios, there are some stylistic resemblances which leads one to believe that were either parts of different manuscripts, produced in the same atelier, or are parts of the same manuscript. Acquired by the Metropolitan Museum as late as in 2001, as gift from the estate of Lt. Lila Acheson Wallace³⁰⁶, these illuminated folios at once highlight two stories: the heights of sophistication in manuscript production reached by Bengal in the late eleventh and early twelfth centuries, and second, their dispersed state being a reflection of the disparity between the perceived value of illuminated and non-illuminated folios, in the international art-market, and even within museum circles in South Asia, where non-illuminated folios are often not catalogued: contributing to the further fragmented existence of surviving manuscripts³⁰⁷.

Coming back to the illuminations themselves, they are considerably well-preserved which aids us in our appreciation. The first two folios³⁰⁸ (Plate 30 a-b) depict the deity Avalokiteśvara, possibly in the Ṣaḍakṣarīlokeśvara form³⁰⁹. Both the folios have one prominent illumination at the

³⁰³ Bautze-Picron, "The Los Angeles Manuscript Covers: Iconography and Style": 481-490..

³⁰⁴ Bautze-Picron, "The Los Angeles Manuscript Covers: Iconography and Style": 490.

³⁰⁵ Bautze-Picron, "The Los Angeles Manuscript Covers: Iconography and Style": 489, 490, 491.

³⁰⁶ American publisher and philanthropist. The modern art section of the Metropolitan Museum is named after her.

³⁰⁷ Kim, *Receptacle of the Sacred*, 291, note 25.

³⁰⁸ Kurt Behrendt, *Tibet and India: Buddhist Traditions and Transformations*, *The Metropolitan Museum of Art Bulletin*, vol. 71, no. 3 (New York: The Metropolitan Museum of Art, 2014), 25, 27-28, Pl. 20, 23, 24.

³⁰⁹ Bhattacharyya, *Sādhnamālā*, vol. 1, 27; Bhattacharyya, *The Indian Buddhist Iconography*, 125-127.

centre which is flanked by two broad decorative bands, which depict two vertically placed *stūpas* rendered in different colours. The left and right extremes of the folios are also decorated by thinner ornamental bands depicting vegetal motifs. The central illumination of the first folio depicts the *bodhisattva* Avalokiteśvara seated in the *lalitāsana* or the *ardhaparyāṅka* posture inside an elaborate shrine. The deity has six hands, with the following attributes:

Thread (*akṣamālā*) | Lotus (*utpala*)

Dharmacakrapravartanamudrā | *Dharmacakrapravartanamudrā*

Varadamudrā | Water pot (*kamaṇḍalu*)

The *bodhisattva* is depicted with a prominent *jaṭāmukūṭa*, with the matted hair falling gracefully on his shoulders, looking downward with a calm and serene composure. The deity is seated on a double-lotus pedestal which is rendered with alternating colours. The background depicts heavy foliage including plantain, coconuts and other tropical trees, commonly associate with the landscape of southeastern Bengal. Although the colour palette is limited, the depiction of foliage in a dark background adds to the aesthetic appeal of the image. The central illumination of the second folio also depicts a seated Avalokiteśvara on a *padmāsana*, flanked by Ṣaḍakṣarī (In Sanskrit, “six-syllable spell³¹⁰”) Mahāvidyā to his left, and Maṇidhara to his right. The depiction of the garment the deity wears is rendered extremely artistically. The deity is depicted with four hands, with the following attributes:

Thread (*akṣamālā*) | Lotus (*utpala*)

Añjalimudrā | *Añjalimudrā*

The portrayal of the deity’s *añjalimudrā* seems a bit different from the rest of the composition; and might plausibly be a later addition. The hands of Ṣaḍakṣarī Mahāvidyā and Maṇidhara are also depicted similarly. Often complex details like depicting a *mudrā* were done by senior and more skilled

³¹⁰ Buswell, Jr. and Lopez, Jr., 728.

artists in an atelier, after the junior artists have finished the simpler designs. This illumination has a similar depiction of dense background foliage like the illumination in the first folio.

Avalokiteśvara, meaning in Sanskrit, “Lord who Looks Down [in Empathy]³¹¹” has been called “cult of half Asia³¹²”, and is considered to be an embodiment of compassion and mercy, and enjoyed popularity across medieval eastern India and beyond, mainly as a protector deity.

The central panel of the third folio³¹³ (Plate 30c) contains an illumination³¹⁴ of the deity Aṣṭamahābhaya Tārā, depicted in a seated position, holding a lotus stalk with her left hand, and her right hand in the *varadamudrā*. The deity is shown wearing heavy jewellery, and is enclosed within a fiery nimbus within an elaborate shrine. She is flanked by Mārīcī (In Sanskrit, “Shining” or “Mirage³¹⁵”) (*Sādhana* No. 145³¹⁶) on her right, holding a vajra in her right hand, and Ekajaṭā on her left, holding a skull cup (*kapāla*). The foliage is similar to the first two folios, and the garment of the deity is sophisticatedly rendered to highlight its translucent qualities.

The fourth folio³¹⁷ (Plate 30d) depicts the deity Khadiravaṇī Tārā feeding ambrosia to pretas with her right hand, who are depicted ecstatically surrounding the goddess. The deity is depicted standing in a contrapposto, holding on to the branch of a tree with her left hand. The foliage in the background of this illumination, also depicts coconut trees and plantain motifs, however rendered very artistically in circular patterns, which can be observed in some sculptural examples from the *Varendra-confluens*.

The fifth folio³¹⁸ (Plate 30e) depicts the deity Oḍḍiyāna Kurukullā, dancing on a corpse within a fiery nimbus inside a very artistically rendered shrine resembling a mountainous grotto. The

³¹¹ Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 82-83.

³¹² C. N. Tay, "Kuan-Yin: The Cult of Half Asia," *History of Religions*, Vol. 16, No. 2 (Nov., 1976), pp. 147-177.

³¹³ *White Tara, Folio from a Dispersed Ashtasahasrika Prajnaparamita (Perfection of Wisdom) Manuscript*, ca. 11th century, India (Bengal), opaque watercolour and ink on palm leaf, The Metropolitan Museum of Art, Accession no. 2001.445h, <https://www.metmuseum.org/art/collection/search/74908>.

³¹⁴ Cf. The Metropolitan Museum of Art. *Green Tara, Folio from a Dispersed Ashtasahasrika Prajnaparamita (Perfection of Wisdom) Manuscript*. Accessed August 2, 2025. <https://www.metmuseum.org/art/collection/search/74905>.

³¹⁵ Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 533.

³¹⁶ Bhattacharyya, *Sāghanamālā*, vol. 1, 296; Bhattacharyya, *The Indian Buddhist Iconography*, 207-209.

³¹⁷ Behrendt, *Tibet and India*, 34, Pl. 31.

³¹⁸ Behrendt, *Tibet and India*, 36-38, Pl. 36.

deity is depicted wearing heavy jewellery and prominent facial expressions. The foliage is very similar to the first three folios discussed above.

1.4 Stone images³¹⁹

The inclusion of stone images in this chapter requires methodological justification, given the dissertation's primary focus on illuminated manuscripts. Stone sculptures and palm leaf manuscripts were produced within overlapping networks of patronage, artistic practice, and iconographic convention across the Pāla period, and the regional stylistic and iconographic variations I have identified in manuscripts are corroborated, as this section demonstrates, by analogous variations in contemporaneous stone images from the same geographical areas. Unlike manuscripts, which were produced in eastern India but preserved almost entirely in Nepal and Tibet, stone images remain, when their provenance is documented, geographically anchored to their production contexts, providing a fixed regional reference point that helps further understand the manuscript attributions proposed in the preceding sections. The sculptures discussed here have been selected according to four criteria: first, geographical distribution across the *Magadha-Varendra-constellation*, *Varendra-confluens*, and *Samatāṭa-littoral*, to test whether the regional semiotic distinctions visible in manuscripts extend across media; second, iconographic correspondence with the deity types and programmes analysed in the manuscript sections, enabling cross-media comparison; third, adequate

³¹⁹ Stone sculptures in the Pāla-period in eastern India were primarily carved from two types of stone: the well-known dense black stone (within which there are lighter grey varieties), and a lighter, yellowish-brown variety mainly found in some sculptures from Bihar. For stone images discussed here, I use the terms "black stone" and "greyish black stone" to refer to the two distinct types of stone, based on appearance. While museum labels across different district-level and state museums in West Bengal and Bangladesh may refer to this stone by different names, such as: basalt, chlorite, or Rajmahal schist, however, based on scientific studies, the stone has been identified to be chloritoid phyllite with different compositional variations [R. Newman, *The Stone Sculpture of India* (Cambridge, MA: Centre for Conservation and Technical Studies, Harvard University Art Museums, 1984)]. Initially, the black stone was thought to originate from the Rajmahal Hills near the present West Bengal-Bihar border. Frederick Asher addressed this issue through extensive field work in the region. Asher clarified that basalt is too hard for carving, chlorite is merely a mineral, and Rajmahal schist is a misnomer for local basalt used in road construction, not sculpture. Guided by Newman's hypothesis that the stone was a chloritoid phyllite from Munger in southern Bihar (around 150 kms. north of Rajmahal), Asher investigated the region. Despite initial skepticism from the Geological Survey of India, which denied the presence of chloritoid phyllite near Munger, Asher was eventually able to locate the correct source. By consulting local sculptors and showing them a sample of the black stone, he identified an active quarry near the village of Matadih (N25°17'16" E86°30'17") in Munger as the likely source of the material used in Bengal's stone sculptures [Frederick M. Asher, "Stone and the Production of Images," *East and West* 48, no. 3/4 (1998): 313–328].

documentation and scholarly literature to support reliable iconographic and stylistic analysis; and fourth, the inclusion of understudied material from district-level museums and regional collections in northern Bengal, accessed through fieldwork between 2017 and 2025. This selection is necessarily partial: as a comprehensive survey of Pāla-period stone images lies beyond this dissertation's scope and has been addressed authoritatively by Huntington, Asher, and Bautze-Picron among others; but this selection is governed by argumentative relevance to the *polycentric semiosis* framework rather than comprehensiveness.

1.4.a *Magadha-Varendra-constellation*

A. An image of the Buddha's birth at the Metropolitan Museum of Art, New York (Acc. No. 2007.305)

In this sculptural relief³²⁰ (Plate 31) showing the Buddha's birth, presently at the Metropolitan Museum of Art, Māyādevī is depicted in the pose of auspicious childbirth, grasping the branch of a *śāla*-tree, as the Buddha emerges from her right. The newborn Buddha is portrayed a second time within the same frame, standing upon an open flower, as he receives his first ablution. The composition places particular emphasis on Māyā, whose iconographic framing asserts her dual identity as both a *yakṣī*, a pre-Buddhist fertility and nature spirit, and the biological mother of the historical Buddha.

B. A seated crowned Buddha image at the Ashmolean Museum, Oxford (Acc. No. EA OS.67)

³²⁰ *Birth of the Buddha* (relief), India (Bihar or Bengal), Pāla-period, ca. 10th century; black schist, approximately 22 × 14 in. (56 × 36 cm); The Metropolitan Museum of Art, accession no. 2007.278, Purchase, Gift of Dr. Mortimer D. Sackler, Theresa Sackler and Family, and Joseph Pulitzer Bequest, 2007. <https://www.metmuseum.org/art/collection/search/73597>.

This greyish black stone sculpture³²¹ (Plate 32a), measuring 40 cm x 24 cm x 9 cm, housed at the Ashmolean, depicts a crowned Buddha in the *bhūmisparśamudrā*. The left foot of the deity showing the left sole has been damaged. The deity is depicted with an elaborate *jaṭāmukuta*, with conical projections. A faint halo and architectural niche are visible behind the deity, which appear unfinished. Framing the central image are seven small relief scenes from the Buddha's life, with the *mahāparinirvāṇa* prominently positioned at the stele's summit. Traces of vermillion on the principal and attendant figures attest to the sculpture's devotional use before it was acquired by the museum. There are two lines of inscription carved at the pedestal's base (Plate 32b). The continued inscription on both sides, is unreadable due to damage and unavailability of a higher resolution image.

C. A standing Buddha image at the Ashmolean Museum, Oxford (Acc. No. EA OS.56)

This exquisitely carved black stone sculpture (Plate 33), measuring 106 cm x 56 cm x 22 cm, presently housed at the Ashmolean, depicts the Buddha in the *samabhāṅga* composure, a gentle contrapposto³²². The deity is framed within a decorative aureole composed of an inner pearl-like garland followed by an interlocked flame motif. Behind the Buddha rises a stylised Bodhi tree, whose foliage does not quite capture the botanical fidelity of the leaves of *Ficus religiosa*, the species of the Bodhi tree, but bears a certain resemblance. The Buddha stands with his weight subtly shifted, creating a swelling of the abdomen just above the lower garment, which begins beneath the navel and descends in a precisely rendered double pleat, corresponding with the termination of the *uttarīya* (upper robe). The upper garment which is semi-transparent and has horizontal wavy lines, resembling the *upavīta*. The right hand, now lost, possibly depicted the *abhayamudrā*, while the left hand holds

³²¹ *Seated figure of a bodhisattva*, India (Bihar or Bengal), 10th–11th century AD; basalt, 40 × 24 × 9 cm; The Ashmolean Museum, Yousef Jameel Centre for Islamic and Asian Art, accession no. EAOS.67. <https://jameelcentre.ashmolean.org/object/EAOS.67>. The website incorrectly labels it a 'seated figure of a *bodhisattva*.' A similar relief at the V&A (Acc. No. IM.107-1920) is discussed in (E).

³²² *Statue of the Buddha beneath the Bodhi Tree*, Bodhgaya (India), Pāla-period, 2nd half of the 9th century–1st half of the 10th century AD; stone, 106 × 56 × 22 cm; Ashmolean Museum, University of Oxford (Yousef Jameel Centre for Islamic and Asian Art), accession no. EAOS.56. <https://jameelcentre.ashmolean.org/object/EAOS.56>; C. Harle and Andrew Topsfield, *Indian Art in the Ashmolean Museum* (Oxford: Ashmolean Museum, 1987), no. 46 on pp. 37–38; p. 29; pl. 7 (colour); and p. 38; Crispin Branfoot, "Pilgrimage in South Asia: Crossing Boundaries of Space and Faith," in *Pilgrimage: The Sacred Journey*, ed. Ruth Barnes and Crispin Branfoot (Oxford: Ashmolean Museum, 2006), 47; illus. 48, fig. 39.

the gathered folds of the *uttarīya*. The following iconographic details of the Śākyamuni can be noticed: *ūrṇā* (forehead mark of wisdom) and *uṣṇīṣa* (cranial protuberance). The sculpture depicts the deity in a certain way, which imparts the effects of *śānta-rasa* (serenity). The genital region is rendered with modest abstraction, in line with Pāla-period conventions. Stylistically, this sculpture has been suggested to be reminiscent of Gupta-period aesthetics, particularly those which are associated with Sarnath in the fifth century CE, while simultaneously manifesting distinctive formal idioms of the Pāla-period. Standing Buddha images can be found extensively in the Nalanda-Bodh Gaya region during the seventh to the eleventh centuries CE, but are rare in the sculptural repertoire of Bengal, including the *Varendra-confluens* and the *Samatāṭa-littoral*.

D. A seated Buddha image at the Metropolitan Museum of Art (Acc. No. 2009.541)

This intricately carved black stone sculpture³²³ in high relief (Plate 34) at the Metropolitan Museum of Art, measuring 28.1 cm x 17.8 cm x 1.9 cm, was found from Jagdishpur (Bhojpur district, Bihar), and was a gift of Raymond G. Handley (1923-2009) and Marsha Vargas Handley (born 1943)³²⁴, who owned a gallery called Xanadu (closed in 2015) in San Francisco, where this sculpture previously belonged. The sculpture depicts the Buddha seated in *bhūmisparśamudrā*, beneath the Bodhi tree at Bodh Gaya, represented here by the overhanging branches above his head. Encircling this main image are depictions of the eight major episodes from the Śākyamuni's life. Commencing from lower left, Māyādevī gives birth to the Buddha, who emerges from her right as she holds a *śāla* branch, in the gardens of Lumbini. Adjacent is the Buddha delivering the *dharmacakrapravartana* at Sarnath, followed above by his subjugation of the elephant Nāḷāgiri. In the lower right register, a monkey is seen offering honey to the Buddha: an act that secured his eventual enlightenment. Above this, the Buddha is depicted performing the great miracles at Shravasti. Next is his descent from

³²³ Behrendt, *Tibet and India*, 16-17, Pl. 13; *Stele with Eight Great Events from the Life of the Buddha*, India (Bihar, possibly from Nalanda), Pāla period, 10th century; black schist with traces of gilding, 11 1/16 in. x 7 in. x 3/4 in. (28.1 x 17.8 x 1.9 cm); The Metropolitan Museum of Art, accession no. 2009.541, gift of Raymond G. and Marsha Vargas Handley, 2009. <https://www.metmuseum.org/art/collection/search/38615>.

³²⁴ Behrendt, *Tibet and India*, 16.

Trāyastriṃśa heaven. At the top of the composition is the Buddha's *mahāparinirvāṇa* at Kushinagar. The architectural and ornamental elements, such as the elaborately decorated throne suggest that this relief was likely produced, in or near Nalanda. There is a two-line inscription at the back of this sculpture (Plate 35) which records the *Ye Dharmā Hetu* verse, also known as the "*pratītyasamutpāda*" stanza:

*ye dharmo hetuprabhavā teṣāṃ hetum tathāgato hyavadat,
teṣāṃ ca yo ni/rodha evaṃ vādī mahāśramaṇaḥ*³²⁵ ||

Translation: Of those phenomena which arise from causes, the Tathāgata (the Buddha) has stated their cause, and also their cessation, thus proclaims the Great Ascetic.

Although Buddha images have been considered to be an integral part of the Pāla visual idiom, the number of Buddha images found in present-day Bihar (especially the Bodh Gaya-Nalanda region) far exceeds their number in Bengal, in either the *Varendra-confluens* or the *Samataṭa-littoral*. One of the first comprehensive studies of Buddha images in the latter half of the twentieth century was done by David L. Snellgrove, whose study included some Buddha images from northern India (the Indo-Gangetic plains), Kashmir and Nepal³²⁶. The LACMA hosted an important exhibition in 1984 on Buddha images in Asian art, a catalogue of which was written by Pratapaditya Pal³²⁷. Bautze-Picron published an important iconographic study of Buddha images from Kukrihar, where through very rigorous stylistic analysis, she constructed a formal typology based on motifs, composition, and stylistic development, dividing the corpus into three stylistic phases (eight century to early ninth century CE, transitional phase, and late ninth century to tenth century CE) and four distinct stylistic strands in a stone images (upper back of the stele, throne, a transitional zone often undecorated, and the pedestal zone), concluding that while Kukrihar imagery shows influences from other centres like

³²⁵ I am thankful to Prof. Jinah Kim for this reading.

³²⁶ David L. Snellgrove, ed., *The Image of the Buddha* (Paris–Tokyo, 1978), 91-101, 167-177.

³²⁷ Pratapaditya Pal, *Light of Asia: Buddha Sakyamuni in Asian Art, exhibition catalogue* (Los Angeles: Los Angeles County Museum of Art, 1984).

Bodh Gaya, it developed its own distinct sculptural idiom³²⁸. In another study, focussing on the same region, Bautze-Picron re-examined the chronology, stylistic evolution, and iconographic development of Buddha images, challenging earlier assumptions that dated these sculptures from the ninth century CE onwards, she argued that the formative phase of Kurkihar's sculptural tradition began earlier, possibly in the late eighth century CE. This re-dating is supported by recently reinterpreted epigraphs and art historical evidence, particularly relating to the reign of Mahendrapāla, who was previously thought to have ruled earlier. She concluded by arguing that that although precise chronology remains elusive, stylistic details such as the development of the stele and motif-compositions suggest the gradual assimilation of Gupta artistic legacies into emerging Pāla idiom³²⁹.

E. A seated crowned Buddha image at the V&A, London (Acc. No. IM.107-1920)

Purchased in 1920 from Lt. H. J. Parker of Clapham Common, this finely executed relief in black stone, measuring 30.5 cm x 21.6 cm at the Victoria & Albert Museum³³⁰ (Plate 36), depicts the crowned Buddha, seated in *vajraparyāṅkāsa* upon a lotus pedestal. The deity is shown in the *bhūmisparśamudrā*, beneath a *bodhi* tree, here symbolically rendered by two stylised overhanging branches. The crown on the Buddha's head, with projections, is similar to the seated *bodhisattva* image at the Ashmolean discussed in (B). The central scene is surrounded by seven great episodes from the Buddha's life. At the centre of the pedestal, Bhūdevī is shown holding a water vessel, witnessing the Buddha's enlightenment while seated beside a slumped and defeated Māra. To the right of the Buddha, a donor couple is depicted kneeling in *añjalimudrā*. A single-line inscription engraved on the reverse of the relief in Sanskrit, written in the Gauḍīya script, reads:

³²⁸ Claudine Bautze-Picron, "The Stone Images of the Buddha at Kurkihar: Analysis of a Style," in *Nalinikanta Shatavashiki, Dr. N.K. Bhattasali Centenary Volume (1888–1988): Studies in Art and Archaeology of Bihar and Bengal*, ed. Debala Mitra and Gouriswar Bhattacharya (Delhi: Sri Satguru Publications, 1989), 41–59.

³²⁹ Claudine Bautze-Picron, "Early Buddhist Sculpture at Kurkihar: The Buddha Images," in *Makaranda: Essays in Honour of Dr. James C. Harle*, ed. Claudine Bautze-Picron (Delhi: Sri Satguru Publications, 1990), 145–52.

³³⁰ *Relief Plaque* (maker unknown), accession no. IM.107-1920, Victoria and Albert Museum, London. <https://collections.vam.ac.uk/item/O64465/relief-plaque-plaque-unknown/>; *Arts of Bengal: The Heritage of Bangladesh and Eastern India: An Exhibition Organized by the Whitechapel Art Gallery, in Collaboration with the Victoria and Albert Museum*, ed. Robert Skelton and Mark Francis (London: Whitechapel Art Gallery, 1979), 26.

“*siddham (symbol) deya-dharmme [correctly: rmmo] // sirokasya*”

Translation: this (image in question) is the meritorious gift of Siroka.³³¹”

F. A Mañjuśrī image at the LACMA, Los Angeles (Acc. No. M.79.188)

This black-stone sculpture, measuring 49.53 cm x 27.94 cm x 9.52 cm, presently housed at the LACMA (Plate 37), depicts the *bodhisattva* Mañjuśrī, here rendered in his youthful form known as Mañjuśrīkumāra³³². Adorned with a *mukuṭa* and ornate jewellery, he wears his distinctive tiger-claw necklace. The deity wears a finely patterned lower garment, an *upavīta* across the left shoulder, and a cloth around the waist. His right hand is raised in the *abhayamudrā*, while his left hand supports the stem of a *nīlotpala* (blue lotus), atop which rests a *pustaka*. This lotus, in turn, emerges from the head of a dwarf-like figure, representing the personification of Mañjuśrī’s weapon, which is a sword that cuts through *avidyā* (ignorance).

The *bodhisattva* stands within a *toraṇa*, flanked by two miniature *stūpas*. Architectural motifs include a *gavākṣa* (cow’s eye) in the upper register, and flanking *stambhas* rising from *kalaśas*, each adorned with an apotropaic *kīrtimukha*. Although this sculpture was most likely a component of a larger architectural ensemble, due to the presence of the *torāṇa* framing, flanking *stambhas*, and *gavākṣa*; its inclusion here serves to illustrate how Mañjuśrī worship was materially incorporated within the monastic and temple architecture of the *Magadha-Varendra-constellation*, beyond the portable media of manuscripts and copper-alloys. The elaborate rendering of the *pustaka* on *nīlotpala*

³³¹ “Relief Plaque,” Victoria and Albert Museum Collections, accessed July 30, 2025, <https://collections.vam.ac.uk/item/O64465/relief-plaque-plaque-unknown/>. The inscription was read by Gouriswar Bhattacharya on July 13, 2006: “The one-line inscription in Sanskrit and Gauḍīya script (a proto-Bengali script) reads: *siddham (symbol) deya-dharmme [correctly: rmmo] // sirokasya*, i.e. ‘success, this (image in question) is the meritorious gift of Siroka.’”

³³² *The Bodhisattva Manjushri*, India (Bihar, Patna District), 9th century; black schist, 19½ × 11 × 3¾ in. (49.5 × 27.9 × 9.5 cm); Los Angeles County Museum of Art, accession no. M.79.188, Gift of John MacDonald. <https://collections.lacma.org/node/241738>; Richard Newman, *The Stone Sculpture of India: A Study of the Materials Used by Indian Sculptors from ca. 2nd Century B.C. to the 16th Century* (Cambridge, MA: Center for Conservation and Technical Studies, Harvard University Art Museums, 1984); Pratapaditya Pal, *Indian Sculpture, vol. 2* (Los Angeles: Los Angeles County Museum of Art; Berkeley: University of California Press, 1988); Stephen Little and Tushara Bindu Gude, *Realms of the Dharma: Buddhist Art across Asia* (Los Angeles: Los Angeles County Museum of Art, 2025).

motif, here emerging from the deity's personified sword of wisdom, demonstrates that the visual encoding of *prajñā* through this compositional framing was well-established in the stone sculptural repertoire of the region by at least the ninth century CE.

G. A Mañjuvajra image at the Chittagong University Museum, Chittagong (Acc. No. CUM 770/Budd. 01)

Unearthed from an unspecified locale in undivided northern Bengal, this black stone relief³³³ (Plate 38), measuring 59 cm x 38 cm, depicts a *bodhisattva* seated upon a lion in the *lalitāsana* or the *ardhaparyāṅka* posture. His hands are conjoined against the chest and depict the *dharmacakrapravartanamudrā*. Behind the left and right arms of the deity, rise lotus stalks, with a manuscript reposing upon the lotus emerging from the left elbow, possibly a *Prajñāpāramitā* manuscript. The deity has a lion *vāhana*, and is ornamented with a *karaṇḍamukūṭa* crowning the head, *kuṇḍalas* adorning the ears, a *hāra* around the neck, *keyūras* on the arms, *kaṭakas* around the wrists, an *udarabandha* encircling the waist, and a pair of *khañjas* around the ankles. The deity's attire consists of: a draped cloth around the waist, an *uttarīya*, and an *upāvita*. Though the upper stele portion is lost, there are two miniature *stūpas* on either side. Two *haṃsas* are discernible on the architraves flanking the deity. The stele also has depictions of: an elephant accompanying its rider, and additional figures. At the lion's rear, kneeling, there is a figure offering prayers, with a manuscript under his left armpit. A monk is faintly visible at the right extremity. This sculpture was a gift to the Chittagong University Museum from the Varendra Research Museum in Rajshahi at an unspecified date.

H. A seated Avalokiteśvara image at the Balurghat College Museum, Balurghat (Acc. No. Unavailable)

³³³ Enamul Haque and Adalbert J. Gail, eds., *Sculptures in Bangladesh: An Inventory of Select Hindu, Buddhist and Jain Stone and Bronze Images in Museums and Collections of Bangladesh (up to the 13th Century)* (Dhaka: International Centre for Study of Bengal Art, 2008), 294; Shamsul Hossain, *A Descriptive Catalogue of Stone Sculptures Preserved in the Chittagong University Museum* (Chittagong: Chittagong University Press, 2009), 9, Pl. 01.

This unpublished greyish black stone sculpture (Plate 39) at the Balurghat College Museum portrays the *bodhisattva* Avalokiteśvara with a smiling expression, seated in the *lalitāsana* on a double-lotus throne. The *bodhisattva* is depicted with an elaborate *jaṭāmukūṭa*, and wearing a prominent *upavīta*, with depictions of Hayagrīva on the right, and Tārā on the left. The *pañca tathāgatas* in different *mudrās* appear at the top of the stele. Two lotus stalks (*utpala*) emerge from behind the deity whose right hand portrays the *abhayāmudrā*, while his left hand rests on his left knee. The main image is also situated within a flaming halo which is carved in high relief. On the pedestal, on the viewer’s extreme left, is depicted a kneeling female figure. Stylistically, this sculpture is attributable to the late-tenth to early-eleventh centuries CE.

One of the earliest writing focussing on stone images of Avalokiteśvara from eastern India, can be found in L.A. Waddell’s account³³⁴. Benoytosh Battacharyya wrote on the iconographic identification of Avalokiteśvara images³³⁵. Marie-Thérèse de Mallmann published extensively on Avalokiteśvara images³³⁶. Pratapaditya Pal published a study on Amoghapāśa Lokeśvara images³³⁷. Debala Mitra published some Avalokiteśvara images in southern Bengal³³⁸. Lokesh Chandra published an extensive study of the thousand-armed Avalokiteśvara³³⁹. Gouriswar Bhattacharya published two important studies focusing on Pretasantarpita-Lokeśvara³⁴⁰ and some “pensive *bodhisattva*” images from the northwest till southeastern Bengal³⁴¹. Bautze-Picron did an extensive analysis of the iconography of Avalokiteśvara in the tradition of stone-images from eastern India produced between the eighth and twelfth centuries CE, studying 131 images, and classifying them using a formal and iconographic typology: “physical” and “environmental”, studying the stylistic

³³⁴ L. A. Waddell, “The Indian Buddhist Cult of Avalokita and His Consort Tārā, the ‘Saviouress’, Illustrated from the Remains in Magadha,” *The Journal of the Royal Asiatic Society of Great Britain and Ireland* for 1894, 51–89.

³³⁵ Benoytosh Bhattacharyya, “Identification of Avalokiteśvara Images,” in *Proceedings and Transactions of the Second Oriental Conference, Calcutta, January 28th to February 1st 1922* (Calcutta, 1923), 285–90.

³³⁶ Marie-Thérèse de Mallmann, *Introduction à l’Étude d’Avalokiteśvara* (Paris, 1948–67).

³³⁷ Pratapaditya Pal, “The Iconography of Amoghapāśa Lokeśvara,” *Oriental Art* 12 (1966): 234–39; 13 (1967): 20–28.

³³⁸ Debala Mitra, “Images of Avalokiteśvara from Bhandarhati, Now in the Asutosh Museum of Indian Art,” in *Studies in Archaeology, Papers Presented in Memory of P. C. Dasgupta*, ed. A. Datta (New Delhi: Books & Books, 1991), 325–37.

³³⁹ Lokesh Chandra, *The Thousand-Armed Avalokiteśvara* (New Delhi: IGNC/Abhinav, 1988).

³⁴⁰ Gouriswar Bhattacharya, “Pretasantarpita-Lokeśvara,” *Journal of Bengal Art* 6 (2001): 21–44.

³⁴¹ Gouriswar Bhattacharya, “The ‘Pensive’ Bodhisattva from Uḍḍiyāna (Swat Valley) to Paṭṭikera (Mainamati) – A Unique Example from Magadha (South Bihar),” *Journal of Bengal Art* 7 (2002): 125–38.

categories within each of them and offering a pattern, finally arguing that the conventional approach of directly matching sculptural imagery with textual prescriptions, especially from sources like the *Sādhanamālā*, is limited, as *localised* styles and iconographic *variants* cannot be strictly codified by canonical texts³⁴², and a study on six-armed Avalokiteśvara images from Bihar and Bengal³⁴³. In another study of Avalokiteśvara images from eastern India, Bautze-Picron demonstrated how Avalokiteśvara's iconography evolved across three geographic regions: northwest (Gandhāra), western Deccan (Ajanta etc.), and eastern India, and three historical phases: early, intermediate, and late periods: noting the visual innovation in depicting the eight dangers/ or worldly threats (interpreting the iconography through the *Saddharmapuṇḍarīkasūtra*³⁴⁴), prominently found in Ajanta, Ellora and Kanheri, with this protective function shifting over time to the goddess Tārā, from sixth - eighth centuries CE. She also noted the *bodhisattva*'s transformation into a cosmic saviour, the thousand-armed Avalokiteśvara, whose iconography she re-interpreted through the *KvS*, instead of the *Niṣpannayogāvalī* or the *Sādhanamālā*³⁴⁵. Nandana Chutiwongs studied extensively the iconography of Avalokiteśvara in mainland Southeast Asia³⁴⁶.

I. Two Avalokiteśvara images at the Coochbehar Palace Museum, Coochbehar (Acc. No. Unavailable)

This large, elegant and beautifully carved greyish black stone sculpture at the Coochbehar Palace Museum (Plate 40a), depicts the *bodhisattva* Avalokiteśvara. Both the hands of the sculpture

³⁴² Claudine Bautze-Picron, "Some Aspects of the Iconography of Avalokiteśvara in 'Pāla-Sena' Stone Sculpture," in *South Asian Archaeology 1985: Papers from the Eighth International Conference of South Asian Archaeologists in Western Europe, Held at Moesgaard Museum, Denmark, 1–5 July 1985*, ed. K. Frifelt and P. Sørensen, Scandinavian Institute of Asian Studies Occasional Papers 4 (London: Curzon Press, The Riverdale Company, 1989), 327–49.

³⁴³ Claudine Bautze-Picron, "'Identification' or 'Classification' in Buddhist Iconography: The Case of the Six-Handed Avalokiteśvara Images in Bihar and Bengal, 8th to 12th Century," in *Shastric Traditions in Indian Arts*, vol. 1, ed. A. L. Dallapiccola, C. Walter-Mendy, and S. Zingel-Avé Lallemand (Stuttgart: Beiträge zur Südasiensforschung, Südasiens-Institut, Universität Heidelberg 125, 1989), 35–50.

³⁴⁴ Buswell, Jr. and Lopez, Jr., 729-730.

³⁴⁵ Claudine Bautze-Picron, "The Universal Compassionate Bodhisattva: Miscellaneous Aspects of Avalokiteśvara/Avalokiteśvara in India," *Silk Road Art and Archaeology* 10 (2004): 225–90. Kamakura: The Institute of Silk Road Studies.

³⁴⁶ Nandana Chutiwongs, *The Iconography of Avalokiteśvara in Mainland South East Asia* (PhD diss., Rijksuniversiteit te Leiden, 1984); Nandana Chutiwongs, "An Aspect of the Bodhisattva Avalokiteśvara in Ancient Indonesia," in *Ancient Indonesian Sculpture*, ed. Marijke J. Klokke and Pauline Lunsingh Scheurleer (Leiden: KITLV Press, 1994), 98–114.

are broken which must have depicted some *mudrā*. The large stele of the icon is finely carved and well-decorated with the *pañca tathāgatas* in different *mudrās* on the top, surrounded by birds and decorative motifs. The icon is also flanked by Hayagrīva on the right, and Tārā on the left, both seated on lotus in the *laitāsana* posture in *varadamudrā*. The deity is seated on a blossomed lotus, and has a *jaṭāmukuta*, with locks of hair falling down on his shoulder. His right foot is placed on a lotus pedestal. Below, in the left and right corners are two *vidyādhara*s. Stylistically, I ascribe this sculpture to the eleventh century CE.

The second Avalokiteśvara (Plate 40b) is heavily damaged, with its entire lower portion broken. The deity is depicted wearing heavy jewellery with a crown (*jaṭāmukuta*) on his head, that has filial projections. The stele behind the deity depicts the *pañca tathāgatas* in different *mudrās*, surrounded by birds, decorative roundels and motifs. The right hand of the *bodhisattva* is in the *varadamudrā*, below which a depiction of Hayagrīva can be spotted. The entire composition of the stele, with the *pañca tathāgatas* and the roundels encasing the *saptaratna*³⁴⁷ motifs like horses, seated deities etc.: evokes a large tree, one of whose branches the deity is holding with his left hand. This could possibly have been a standing sculpture of Avalokiteśvara, an iconographic depiction also often encountered in painting, in especially visually exquisite forms in later eleventh century manuscripts (Metropolitan Museum of Art, P). Standing Avalokiteśvara sculptures from the *Varendra-confluens* are not rare, but fewer than those that depict the deity seated. Stylistically, I attribute this sculpture to the late eleventh or early twelfth centuries CE, based on several formal characteristics consistent with the later phase of Pāla sculpture as delineated by Huntington³⁴⁸. The densely ornamented stele programme, incorporating the *pañca tathāgatas*, *saptaratna* medallions, birds, and decorative roundels within an arboreal compositional framework, and the heavy jewellery of the deity, reflect the increasingly elaborate subsidiary ornamentation characteristic of this later period. While certain compositional elements, such as the relatively restrained modelling of the deity: may suggest

³⁴⁷ See: Jinah Kim, "Lost Books in People's Hands: Looking for Illustrated Buddhist Manuscripts of Odisha in Stone," *Journal of Bengal Art* 26 (2021): 495, plate 31.10.

³⁴⁸ Susan L. Huntington, *The "Pāla-Sena" Schools of Sculpture* (Leiden: Brill, 2023), esp. p. 27-133, 155-187.

continuity with earlier sculptural conventions of the *Varendra-confluens*, the overall decorative programme and stele organisation fits more closely with late eleventh to twelfth century production. I also argue that both the sculptures to have been produced somewhere in the *Varendra-confluens*. Although the second sculpture may have stylistic parallels with standing Avalokiteśvara images depicted in painting in later eleventh century manuscripts that I ascribe to *Samataṭa-littoral*, I ascribe these two sculptures to the *Varendra-confluens* due to their distinctiveness from more voluminous and stylistically sophisticated examples of the *Samataṭa-littoral* (like the ex-Boston Avalokiteśvara to be discussed in V).

J. A seated Avalokiteśvara image at the South Dinajpur District Museum, Balurghat (Acc. No. SDDM DA 31)

This unpublished greyish black stone sculpture (Plate 41) at the South Dinajpur District Museum in Balurghat depicts the *bodhisattva* Avalokiteśvara. The deity has a slightly damaged face, and is depicted with two hands, wearing a semi-translucent *uttarīya*, and a heavily bejewelled loincloth, the *bodhisattva* is depicted with a *jaṭāmukuta*, and is shown wearing elaborate jewellery and a prominent *upavīta*. He holds a blue lotus (*utpala*) in his right hand, and his left hand portrays the *varadamudrā*. Behind the deity, at the top of the stele, are depicted five seated Buddha figures depicting different *mudrās*. The five Buddhas might represent the *pañca tathāgata*. Below the Buddha figures, are depicted two small *stūpas*, on either side. The deity is flanked by Hayagrīva on the right, who is depicted with matted hair holding a skull cap in his left hand. On the right of the deity, is depicted a figure in the *añjalimudrā*. There is an one line inscription at the base of the pedestal which possibly states the event of donation of the image. On the pedestal are depicted three figures in the *añjalimudrā*, with the figure on the extreme left represents *sūcīmukha*. Stylistically, this image is similar to the previous three Avalokiteśvara images discussed, and is perhaps dateable to the eleventh century CE.

K. A seated Buddha image at the Balurghat College Museum, Balurghat (Acc. No. Unavailable)

This unpublished black stone sculpture (Plate 42a), presently housed at the Balurghat College Museum, depicts the Buddha, who is seated in the *bhūmisparśamudrā*. The head of the sculpture was partially detached from the body when recovered. The figure of the deity is characterised by a gentle smile, elongated earlobes, and a prominent *uṣṇīṣa*, and a visible *upavīta*. Images of the Buddha are relatively common in the archaeological corpus of Bengal.

The Pāla-period witnessed a prolific production of Buddha images, across various media. Although there are some sculptural representations of the Buddha from the Pāla-period produced in the *Varendra-confluens* as well as in the *Samataṭa-littoral*, they are fewer in comparison to those produced in or near Bodh Gaya and Nalanda. Most museums that I visited in northern West Bengal have at least one Pāla-period Buddha image, except the Coochbehar Palace Museum and the Akshaya Kumar Maitreya Heritage Museum. Bhattasali recorded a few examples at the Dacca Museum (now the Bangladesh National Museum, Dhaka). The relative scarcity of Buddha images in Bengal may suggest that, while Buddhism had by then permeated various aspects of local culture, the hinterland of Bengal witnessed a stronger development of Vajrayāna Buddhism, with an iconographic emphasis on Vajrayāna deities. One of the earliest large-scale examples of a Buddha image from eastern India is the well-known Sultanganj Buddha, a large standing Buddha image made of copper-alloy, dating to the Gupta-Pāla transitional period, now housed at the Birmingham Museum & Art Gallery. Aside from such major commissions, numerous smaller, mostly votive Buddha images have been discovered around the Gaya region, produced between the seventh and the tenth centuries CE. These votive images were often shaped like the leaves of the Bodhi tree, with the Buddha seated at the centre, many of which, in terracotta, are presently held at the British Museum (Plate 42b).

L. A Tārā image at the Coochebehar Palace Museum, Coochebehar (Acc. No. Unavailable)

This greyish black stone sculpture of Tārā at the Coochbehar Palace Museum (Plate 43), depicts the goddess seated in the *lalitāsana*, with her right leg pendant, on a double-lotus throne

(*padmāsana*). The face of the deity is damaged. Both the hands showing the palms of the deity are also damaged, however from the outline, it seems that the right hand of the deity perhaps depicted the *varadamudrā*. The attribute of the left hand is not clear. A lotus stalk (*utpala*) emerges from behind the left hand of the goddess, behind whom two *vidyādhara*s with garlands are depicted at the top of the stele. The goddess is heavily adorned with jewellery: crown (*mukuṭa*), necklace (*kaṅṭhahara*), armlets (*keyuras*), broad wristlets and anklets (*nupuras*), and wears a semi-transparent lower garment which shows fine layering and design motifs. On the right of the deity is depicted Mārīcī, and on the left, Ekajaṭā, who is seated and has prominent single lock of matted hair (*eka-jaṭā*). He seems to be holding something in his hands, which is damaged, and could be a skull-cup. The pedestal is very ornately carved depicting different ornamental motifs. To the right of the deity's right foot, is depicted a small kneeling figure in the *añjalimudrā*. Stylistically, I ascribe this sculpture to the late tenth to early eleventh centuries CE.

There is no scholarly consensus on the historic origins of the deity Tārā, with some suggestions that Tārā might be a Brahmanical goddess appropriated by Buddhists³⁴⁹, while it has also been argued that the deity had strong historic connections with Tibet and China³⁵⁰, however the general view is that Tārā is a Buddhist deity as her distinct iconographic features appear in Buddhist texts and in artistic representations³⁵¹. The word Tārā is derived from the Sanskrit root *tr*, suggesting: to carry across, helping over a difficulty, rescuing or to be a saviour³⁵². In the Brahmanical pantheon, the *Mahabharata* mentions Tāriṇī as one of the names of the Devī³⁵³. One of the earliest Buddhist texts to mention a description of Tārā is the *Āryamañjuśrīmūlakalpa*³⁵⁴ composed in its present form between the fifth and eighth centuries CE, where the goddess is described as a personification of

³⁴⁹ K.K. Dasgupta, "Iconography of Tārā," in D. C. Sircar (ed.) 1967: 117; M. Ghosh, *Development of Buddhist Iconography in Eastern India: a Study of Tārā, Prajñās of Five Tathāgatas and Bhṛikuṭī* (Delhi: Munshiram Manoharlal Publisher, 1980), 17.

³⁵⁰ H. Shastri, *The Origin and Cult of Tārā, Memoirs of Archaeological Survey of India*, 20 (Calcutta: Archaeological Survey of India, 1925): 23; N.N. Bhattacharyya, "Tārā in Historical Perspective," in Bhattacharyya, N.N. and A. Ghosh (eds.) 1999: 195.

³⁵¹ Shin, "Transformation of the Goddess Tārā," 17.

³⁵² Buswell, Jr. and Lopez, Jr., 895-896.

³⁵³ V.S. Sukthankar et al. (eds.), *Mahābhārata* (Poona: Bhandarkar Oriental Research Institute, 1933–1963, rep.), 710.

³⁵⁴ Buswell, Jr. and Lopez, Jr., 527.

Avalokiteśvara's quality of *karuṇā*: *devīmāryāvalokiteśvarakaruṇāmāryatārām*³⁵⁵. Tārā transfigured into an important Brahmanical deity by the end of the twelfth century CE, incorporated into the ten *Mahāvīdyās*. It has been observed that the *sādhana* of Mahācīnatārā in the *Sādhanamālā* is very similar *dhyāna* of Tārā as promulgated in later Śākta texts of Brahmanical pantheon like the *Tantrasāra* of Krishnananda Agamavagisha and *Tārārahasya* of Brahmānanda³⁵⁶. The Chinese monk Xuanzang recorded the worship of Tārā as a companion to Avalokiteśvara to have been popular in and around Nalanda during the seventh century CE³⁵⁷, and some sculptural examples of Tārā from the sixth century CE, survive at Nalanda³⁵⁸. Over time, Tārā evolved beyond her earlier role as a consort of Avalokiteśvara, assuming instead an autonomous identity as a supreme saviour from the eight great perils (*aṣṭamahābhayā*): namely, shipwreck, fire, enraged elephant, brigand, ferocious lion, snake, imprisonment, and demon³⁵⁹. While protection from these dangers were generally attributed to Avalokiteśvara, their reattribution to Tārā suggests her ascension as an independent protector. It has been noted that from the eighth century CE onwards, her popularity as a protective saviour exceeded that of Avalokiteśvara³⁶⁰. Sculptural depictions of Tārā often portray her in a very tranquil demeanour, seated in the *lalitāsana* posture, holding an *utpala* (blue lotus) in her left hand while displaying the *varadamudrā* with her right. Jae-Eun Shin noted some sculptural examples of different types of Tārā, of which, there are two similar images at the Bangladesh National Museum³⁶¹, and can be stylistically assigned to the *Samataṭa-littoral*, while the standing Khadiravaṇī Tārā image at the Indian Museum³⁶² (Acc. No. A 25158) can be considered as belonging to the *Magadha-Varendra-constellation*.

³⁵⁵ Ghosh, *Development of Buddhist Iconography in Eastern India*, 11; Shin, "Transformation of the Goddess Tārā," 17-18.

³⁵⁶ B. Bhattacharyya, *The Indian Buddhist Iconography: Mainly Based on the Sādhanamālā and Cognate Tantric Texts of Rituals* (Calcutta: Firma K. L. Mukhopadhyay, 1958), 190-191; Shin, "Transformation of the Goddess Tārā," 28-29.

³⁵⁷ S. Beal, trans., *Si-Yu-Ki: Buddhist Records of the Western World* (Delhi: Motilal Banarsidass, rep. 1994), 103.

³⁵⁸ Shin, "Transformation of the Goddess Tārā," 18, Figs. 1-2.

³⁵⁹ Debala Mitra, "Aṣṭamahābhaya Tārā," *Journal of the Asiatic Society, Letters and Science* 23 (1): 19-22 (Calcutta, 1957),

³⁶⁰ Miranda Shaw, *Buddhist Goddesses of India* (Princeton: Princeton University Press, 2006), 318; Shin, "Transformation of the Goddess Tārā," 21.

³⁶¹ Shin, "Transformation of the Goddess Tārā," Figs. 5 & 6.

³⁶² Shin, "Transformation of the Goddess Tārā," Fig. 9

M. Three Tārā images at the Balurghat College Museum, Balurghat (Acc. No. Unavailable)

The following unpublished sculptures are three Tārā images housed at the Balurghat College Museum. The first sculpture (Plate 44) depicts Khadiravaṇī Tārā with her left hand holding the stalk of a lotus flower, and her right hand extended in the *varadamudrā*. The deity is depicted wearing heavy jewellery, with a prominent *upavīta*. Standing to the right of the deity is Aśokakāntā Mārīci holding a *vajra* with her right hand, while her left hand probably depicts an *aśokakāntā*, but it is unclear. To the left of the deity is depicted Ekajaṭā, holding a skull-cup in his left hand. The upper stele is damaged. The pedestal is intricately carved with vegetal motifs, and also depicts two kneeling devotees, a male and a female on either side depicted in the *añjalimudrā*. The *Sādhnāmālā* identifies Khadiravaṇī Tārā as an emanation of Amoghasiddhi (In Sanskrit, “He Whose Accomplishments are not in Vain³⁶³”), portrayed with two arms, her right hand extended in the *varadamudrā*, and her left hand grasping a blue *utpala* blossom. The deity can be recognised by her two attendants- Mārīci and Ekajaṭā: the former holding a *vajra*, and the latter holding a skull-cup.

The second sculpture (Plate 45a) depicts a Tārā image at the Balurghat College Museum. The deity has a very serene expression, looking downward with a light smile. There are two *stūpas* depicted on the two top corners of the stele, with the Buddha in the centre in the *dharmacakrapravartanamudrā*. The deity holds the stalk of a lotus flower with her left hand, while her right hand is in the *varadamudrā*. There is a small two line inscription on the pedestal (Plate 45b) which plausibly reads:

*dānapati -vyāta(?)/rocānokasyā*³⁶⁴

There is also a donor image on the right side of the pedestal, which portrays a woman.

³⁶³ Buswell, Jr. and Lopez, Jr., 36.

³⁶⁴ I am thankful to Prof. Jinah Kim for correcting my earlier incorrect reading of this inscription. Due to the unavailability of a higher resolution image at present, the reading still remains tentative.

The third image of Tārā at the Balurghat College Museum (Plate 46) is iconographically, mostly similar to the second, and there are two *stūpas* depicted on both sides of the stele, however the depiction of Buddha in the centre is missing. There are two *vidyādharas* at the top with a *kīrtimukha* in the middle.

N. A Mahāpratisarā image at the Metropolitan Museum of Art, New York (Acc. No. 1991.108)

This greyish black stone sculpture of Mahāpratisarā at the Metropolitan Museum of Art (Plate 47) was a gift to the Metropolitan Museum in 1991 from the Irving family of Brooklyn. It is stylistically attributable to the late tenth century CE³⁶⁵, and depicts the goddess in a profound meditative composure. She is seated upon a lotus pedestal that rests atop a richly carved lion-throne draped with cloth. The deity is eight-armed with the following attributes in each hand:

Sword (*asi*) | Staff (*khaṭvāṅga*)

Axe (*paraśu*) | Discus (*cakra*)

Damaged | Manuscript (*pustaka*)

Thunderbolt (*Vajra*) | Thread (*akṣamālā*)

One of her lowered hands supports a *pustaka*. An inscription carved on the back stele possibly refers to a *dhāraṇī* or a protective spell, however I was unable to access to it as a high definition image is not available in the public domain. A kneeling donor, in *añjalimudrā*, is depicted before the lion-throne, perhaps suggesting the image's votive function. The deity is surrounded by a large flaming halo.

³⁶⁵ Behrendt, *Tibet and India*, 37-38, Pl. 37; *Mahapratissara, the Buddhist Protectress*, India (Bihar), Pāla period, 10th century, black stone, 23 in. × 15 ½ in. × 7 in. (58.4 × 39.4 × 17.8 cm); The Metropolitan Museum of Art, accession no. 1991.108, purchase through the Florence and Herbert Irving Gift, 1991. <https://www.metmuseum.org/art/collection/search/38138>.

Bhattacharya was the first to publish, and incorrectly label an early eleventh century Mahāpratisāra image from Munshiganj (to be discussed in S) as Br̥kūti-Tārā³⁶⁶. Existing scholarship on Mahāpratisāra images from Bengal has elucidated her canonical iconography, based on *sādhana* nos. 194, 195 and 196³⁶⁷, as well as regional significances, especially Mevissen’s study of Mahāpratisāra’s formal affinities with Javanese, Central Asian, and East Asian Buddhist images, where it was noted that south and southeastern Bengal were well-connected with regions in Southeast Asia through different trade and pilgrimage routes, which is evident not only from the spread of the cult of Mahāpratisāra in Southeast Asian regions like Java, but also through similarities within the art and iconographic conception of the deity:

That the eastern Bengal region played an important role in the interactions between the Pāla world and Indonesia is also evident from the fact that several of the bronzes that were found in Java originate from the Comilla and Chittagong Districts. Furthermore, it has been stated that "in addition to the unmistakable stylistic and technical debt of Javanese metal images to Pāla works, there is a strong iconographic association. Interestingly, the Javanese idiom appears to be the only Pāla-dependent tradition that did not emphasize Śākyamuni Buddha, ... [but] rather emphasized the forms of Buddhism ... in which ... other Mahayāna and Tantric divinities predominated." All this may explain the presence of Mahāpratisāra images both in Java and in south-east Bengal.³⁶⁸

Being an important *dhāraṇī* deity, Mahapratissara was already widespread. Referring to the ritual use of the *dhāraṇī* of Mahāpratisāra throughout Buddhist Asia, Roderick Orlina noted in 2013:

Put to such uses, the *dhāraṇī* of Mahāpratisāra became very widespread throughout Buddhist Asia. Among the numerous tantric masters to have visited Indonesia, Amoghavajra was one of the key figures in the spread of Vajrayāna Buddhism in China and translated the *Mahāpratisāramahāvīdyārājñī* into Chinese (*Great Wish-Fulfilling Spell, Dasuiqiutuoluoni*

³⁶⁶ Nalini Kanta Bhattacharya, *Iconography of Buddhist and Brahmanical Sculptures in the Dacca Museum* (Dacca: Dacca Museum Committee, 1929), pl. 42, pp. 160–61.

³⁶⁷ Bhattacharya, *Sāghanamālā*, vol. II, 366–368.

³⁶⁸ Gerd J. R. Mevissen, "Images of Mahapratissara in Bengal: Their Iconographic Links with Javanese, Central Asian and East Asian Images," *Journal of Bengal Art* 4 (1997).

大随陀罗尼). He made two visits to Java (in 718 CE and between 741–746 CE), and since Java was a center of trade and political power in the sphere of insular Southeast Asia to which the Philippine islands integrally belonged, such foreign tantric masters will have propagated the *dhāraṇī* to monks as well as kings along the different trade routes ... Thus, it is likely that the cult of Mahāpratisarā spread from Java not long after Amoghavajra's missions. (Orlina, 2013)

Another recent study examined the cult of Mahāpratisāra along the Maritime Silk Route, focussing on epigraphic and iconographic evidence from Indonesia, including a ten-armed Mahāpratisāra bronze (copper-alloy) image from Java at the Museum für Asiatische Kunst in Berlin (artefacts palaeographically dated to the ninth- tenth centuries CE), where the goddess was particularly revered for offering protection during childbirth³⁶⁹.

O. An Aśokakāntā Mārīcī image at the Gurusaday Museum, Kolkata (Acc. No. GM536)

This black stone sculpture of *Śrī-Mārīcībhattarīkā* from Rajnagar, Birbhum district in southwestern West Bengal, now housed at the Gurusaday Museum, Kolkata (Plate 50), measuring 63.5 cm x 33 cm) represents an iconographically elaborate depiction of the Buddhist goddess Aśokakāntā Mārīcī³⁷⁰, dated to around the tenth or early eleventh century CE³⁷¹. A recent study was published on this Mārīcī sculpture, which was recovered from Rajnagar in Birbhum district of West Bengal (situated west of the Bhagirathi river: a region where there are no extant comparable examples

³⁶⁹ Thomas Cruijssen, Arlo Griffiths, and Marijke J. Klokke, "The Cult of the Buddhist Dhāraṇī Deity Mahāpratisarā Along the Maritime Silk Route: New Epigraphical and Iconographic Evidence from the Indonesian Archipelago," *Journal of the International Association of Buddhist Studies* 35, no. 1–2 (2012 [published 2013]): 71-157.

³⁷⁰ Bhattacharyya, *Sādhanaṁālā*, vol. 1, 306; Bhattacharyya, *The Indian Buddhist Iconography*, 209.

³⁷¹ Rajat Sanyal and Sharmila Saha, "An Inscribed Stone Sculpture of 'Mārīcī' from Birbhum (West Bengal) in the Gurusaday Museum (Kolkata)," *Pratna Samiksha*, New Series 9 (2018): 137–45; Sudipa Bandyopadhyay [also spelt Ray (Bandyopadhyay)], "Chaityagarbha Deul Motif in Pāla-Sena Art," *Kalyan Bharati: Journal on Indian History & Culture* 3 (1999): 96–99; Gerd J. R. Mevissen, "Images of Buddhist Goddesses Accompanied by Astral Deities," in *Kalhar (White Water-Lily): Studies in Art, Iconography, Architecture and Archaeology of India and Bangladesh, Professor Enamul Haque Felicitation Volume*, ed. Gouriswar Bhattacharya et al. (New Delhi: Kaveri Books, 2007), 154–203 and pls. 20.1–32.

of Pāla-period stone images of Mārīcī), signalling a distribution of Pāla-period Mārīcī stone images beyond heartland Varendra or Magadha³⁷².

Carved in high relief, and depicted within a concave *caitya* niche, the goddess appears in a canonical *tri-mukha-aṣṭabhujā* form: three-faced (two human and one sow faced), and eight armed with the following attributes:

Thunderbolt (*vajra*) | *Karaṇamudrā*

Arrow (*śara*) | Bow (*cāpa*)

Elephant goad (*aṅkuśa*) | *Aśoka* flower

Needle (*sūcī*) | Thread (*akṣamālā*)

Adorned with an elaborate *mukūṭa*, *keyūras*, *nūpurās*, and an *upavīta*, she stands in *pratyāliḍha* posture atop a *saptaratha* pedestal, interpreted as her chariot drawn by seven pigs. Flanking the goddess are five attendant sow-faced goddesses with similar iconography, including one seated beneath her legs in *padmāsana*. A *makara*-topped Rāhu head occupies the central *ratha*, evoking her cosmic triumph over darkness. What further distinguishes this image is a short Gaudīya-script Sanskrit inscription engraved along the lower register of the pedestal, which reads:

sa[?]papu[. .][bha]ddrakaritasrīmārīcībhattarīkāya

meaning: “the illustrious goddess Mārīcī made (i.e., donated) by ... *bhadra*”. The epigraph confirms the identity of the goddess explicitly as Mārīcībhattarīkā³⁷³. The accompanying donor figure suggests the image’s votive character. The high formal precision and stylised ornamentation in this image, mark the sculpture as a sophisticated product of the Pāla atelier in western Bengal, which is remarkable given the region’s general paucity of such imagery.

³⁷² Sanyal and Saha, “Inscribed Stone Sculpture of ‘Mārīcī,’” 137–145.

³⁷³ Sanyal and Saha, “Inscribed Stone Sculpture of ‘Mārīcī,’” 140–143.

Māricī is known as a goddess associated with ‘Life and Victory,’ and also associated with dawn. On Māricī images from eastern India, housed at different museums within Kolkata, Mallar Mitra published an extensive iconographic study³⁷⁴. Claudine-Bautze Picron carried out a comprehensive iconographic and iconological survey based on images of the goddess, across different sites in eastern India and Bangladesh³⁷⁵. In her study, Bautze-Picron further demonstrated the similarities and differences between the iconographic features of the goddess in north-Bengal-south Bihar (*Magadha-Varendra-constellation*) and south-east Bangladesh (*Samataṭa-littoral*), and assigned the goddess a soteriological position between Vairocana (In Sanskrit, “Resplendent³⁷⁶”) and Śākyamuni³⁷⁷. Studies in the iconography of the goddess from several parts of northern Bengal, southeastern Bengal and Odisha, have been published³⁷⁸, including, Kim’s study of the iconographic evolution of Māricī through a study of artistic representations of the deity’s three iconographic forms: a) Aśokāntā Māricī, b) an eight-armed warrior riding a chariot lead by seven pigs, and drawn by a porcine-headed female charioteer above Rāhu: with her martial pose resembling Durgā Mahiṣāsuramardinī in sculptural traditions of eastern India in the tenth and eleventh centuries CE, and c) Oḍḍiyāna Māricī, tracing her iconographic development from a tree spirit, to a warrior goddess

³⁷⁴ Mallar Mitra, “Images of Marichi found in the Museums of Calcutta,” in *Studies in Archaeology: Papers Presented in Memory of P.C. Dasgupta*, ed. Asok Datta (Delhi: Books & Books, n.d.), 343–54, photos 38–39, 43–50.

³⁷⁵ Claudine Bautze-Picron, “Between Śākyamuni and Vairocana: Marici, Goddess of Light and Victory,” *Silk Road Art and Archaeology (Journal of the Institute of Silk Road Studies, Kamakura)* 7: 263–310.

³⁷⁶ Buswell, Jr. and Lopez, Jr., 949-950.

³⁷⁷ Bautze-Picron, “Between Śākyamuni and Vairocana,” 286.

³⁷⁸ Thomas Eugene Donaldson, “Orissan Images of Vārāhī, Oddiyāna Marici, and Related Sow-Faced Goddesses,” *Artibus Asiae* 55, no. 1/2 (1995): 155–82; Thomas Eugene Donaldson, *Iconography of the Buddhist Sculpture of Orissa*, 2 vols. (New Delhi: Indira Gandhi National Centre for the Arts & Abhinav Publications, 2001): 306-328; Gerd J.R. Mevissen, “Images of Buddhist Goddesses Accompanied by Astral Deities,” ed. Gouriswar Bhattacharyya et al., *Kalhār (White Water-Lily): Studies in Art, Iconography, Architecture and Archaeology of India and Bangladesh, Professor Enamul Haque Felicitation Volume* (New Delhi: Kaveri Books, 2007), 154–203 and pls 20.1–32; Gerd J.R. Mevissen, “Two Unpublished Marici Sculptures in the Khulna Museum, Bangladesh, and Related Images from Mainamati,” ed. Devangana Desai and Arundhati Banerji, *Kalādarpaṇa: The Mirror of Indian Art, Essays in Memory of Shri Krishna Deva* (New Delhi: Aryan Books International, 2009), 273–84; Gerd J.R. Mevissen, “The Riddle of the Four-Armed Marici Image from Udala, Orissa,” in *South Asian Archaeology 2003: Proceedings of the Seventeenth International Conference of the European Association of South Asian Archaeologists (7–11 July 2003, Bonn)*, ed. Ute Franke-Vogt and Hans-Joachim Weisshaar (Aachen: Linden Soft, 2005), 501–507.

and finally a ‘tantric’ deity shaped by interactions with Śaivite, Vaiṣṇavite and pre-Buddhist traditions³⁷⁹.

P. An Aparājītā or Mahāpratisarā image at the Akshaya Kumar Maitreya Heritage Museum, Siliguri (Acc. No. 26)

This black stone sculpture³⁸⁰ (Plate 51), measuring 33.5 cm x 33.5 cm, whose upper half is lost, is presently housed at the Akshaya Kumar Maitreya Heritage Museum in North Bengal University, Siliguri. It was donated to the university by Lt. Nirmal Chowdhury of Jalpaiguri. The remaining lower section reveals the legs of a female deity, with her left leg bent at the knee in the *ālīḍha* pose. The legs of the deity are adorned with *nūpura* (anklets): indicating a heavily ornamented body. Beneath the goddess’ left foot is a small, trampled figure with an elephant head and three visible arms, the fourth (lower left) being broken. The upper right hand of this figure holds a knife-like object, while the broken hand may have held a shield. To the left of the principal deity is another figure in a similar posture, four-armed and bearing various weapons. The museum label identifies the sculpture as Aparājītā, however it can also be a standing sculpture of Mahāpratisarā. The deity Aparājītā is described in several *sādhana*s within the *Sāadhanamālā*³⁸¹, where she is invoked as a wrathful goddess trampling evil beings³⁸². Benoytosh Bhattacharyya, offered an early exposition on Aparājītā’s form and attributes, highlighting her trampling posture and aggressive iconography³⁸³. Similarly, Debala Mitra described an image of Aparājītā from Ratnagiri, Odisha, seated in *lalitāsana* on a lotus, her left foot resting on a prostrate elephant-headed figure, though she noted deviations from the prescriptions

³⁷⁹ Jinah Kim, “Emergence of a Buddhist Warrior Goddess and the Historical Development of Tantric Buddhism: The Case of Māricī,” *Journal of the Indian Society of Oriental Art, New Series*, Volumes XXVIII & XXIX (2011–2012 & 2012–2013), ed. Susnato Ganguly and Arundhati Banerji, 49-64.

³⁸⁰ P. K. Bhattacharyya, *Akshaya Kumar Maitreya Museum Catalogue, Part I (Sculptures, Terra Cotta Objects, Paintings, Folk Arts, Coins, etc.)* (Raja Rammohanpur, Darjeeling: University of North Bengal, 1981), 9; P. K. Bhattacharyya, *Iconography of Sculptures* (Darjeeling: Akshaya Kumar Maitreya Museum, University of North Bengal, 1983), 54-55, Pl. XII, fig. 29.

³⁸¹ Bhattacharyya, *Sāadhanamālā*, vol. 2, 403; Bhattacharyya, *The Indian Buddhist Iconography*, 245-246.

³⁸² Bhattacharyya, *The Indian Buddhist Iconography*, 151, 245–46.

³⁸³ Bhattacharyya, *The Indian Buddhist Iconography*, 151, 245–46.

in the *Sādhanamālā*³⁸⁴. Janice Leoshko undertook a detailed study of Aparājītā’s emergence and her association with Śākyamuni’s enlightenment. She traced her iconographic evolution to Gupta-period earth goddess figures at Sarnath, which later developed into tantric forms, ultimately culminating in the Pāla-period Aparājītā trampling Gaṇeśa³⁸⁵. Anasua Sengupta re-identified a sculpture from Bihar Sharif, formerly misidentified by Stella Kramrisch as Durgā, as Aparājītā, based on the iconography prescription of the *Sādhanamālā*, where she is described as a *aśeṣa-māra-nirdalanī* (destroyer of innumerable wicked beings)³⁸⁶. Sengupta also referred to another image at the Indian Museum, Kolkata, where the trampled figure is elephant-headed and holds a knife, consistent with *gaṇapati-samākrāntā*, or “she who tramples Gaṇapati³⁸⁷”. Marie-Thérèse de Mallmann³⁸⁸ and Mallar Mitra published on some Aparājītā images³⁸⁹. Claudine Bautze-Picron also elaborated this iconography, noting that while some early images, like from Ghosrawa, show Aparājītā trampling human figures, the more canonical form has her defeating an elephant-headed adversary, starting from as early as the eighth century stela from the Pachar Hills³⁹⁰. Giovanni Verardi documented the goddess in his survey of esoteric Buddhist deities from eastern India, noting her association with Heruka³⁹¹, Trailokyavijaya, and Parṇaśavarī: in a visual tradition of fierce deities trampling male or animal-headed enemies, often Gaṇeśa³⁹². In this context, it remains unclear whether this particular image at the Akshaya Kumar Maitreya Heritage Museum represents Aparājītā, Mahāpratisarā or the goddess Parṇaśavarī. However based on the textual and iconographic evidence and examples discussed above, the identification of this sculpture as either Aparājītā or Mahāpratisarā remains compelling.

³⁸⁴ Debala Mitra, *Ratnagiri* (New Delhi: Archaeological Survey of India, 1981), plate XXIV C.

³⁸⁵ Janice Leoshko, “The Case of the Two Witnesses to the Buddha’s Enlightenment,” in *A Pot-Pourri of Indian Art*, ed. Pratapaditya Pal (Bombay: Marg Publications, 1988), 39–52.

³⁸⁶ Anasua Sengupta, “Note on a Female Buddhist Deity,” *Journal of the Indian Museum*, 1991.

³⁸⁷ Sengupta, “Note on a Female Buddhist Deity.”

³⁸⁸ Marie-Thérèse de Mallmann, *Introduction à l’étude du Tāntrisme bouddhique, Bibliothèque du Centre de Recherches sur l’Asie Centrale et la Haute Asie*, vol. 1 (Paris: Adrien-Maisonneuve, 1975): 103-104.

³⁸⁹ Mallar Mitra, “Note on an Aparājītā Image,” *Pratna Samiksha* 1 (1992): 175–78; Mallar Mitra, “The Buddhist Goddess Aparājītā: Four-armed Form,” *Journal of Bengal Art* 1 (1996): 161–67; Mallar Mitra, “Four Images of the Buddhist Goddess Aparājītā,” in *Studies in Hindu and Buddhist Art*, ed. P. K. Mishra (New Delhi: Abhinav Publishers, 1999), 95–99.

³⁹⁰ Claudine Bautze-Picron, “Aparājītā and the Enlightenment of the Buddha: Some Observations,” *South Asian Archaeology* 1995, fig. 30.

³⁹¹ Buswell, Jr. and Lopez, Jr., 347.

³⁹² Verardi, *Hardships and Downfall of Buddhism in India*, 326.

Both these deities were prominent in the context of the development of tantric Buddhism in eastern India. Since this development was very much syncretic in nature, in lieu of existing socio-religious canons, often essentially local in their semantics, the development of iconography of these deities also should be studied with an awareness of the traditions that existed prior to the arrival of Mahāyānist Buddhism in eastern India.

1.4.b *Samataṭa-littoral*

Q. A seated Buddha image at the Bangladesh National Museum, Dhaka (Acc. No. 1.A(iii)a/1)³⁹³

This black stone sculpture³⁹⁴ of a seated Buddha was discovered at Ujani village in Muksudpur Upazila, Gopalganj District of Dhaka Division, and presented by Babu Mahim Chandra Ray of Ujani³⁹⁵. This imposing sculpture (Plate 52), measuring 257 cm x 53 cm, depicts the Buddha in a serene composure, seated in the *bhūmisparśamudrā*, on a double lotus throne. His robe, intricately folded, exposes the right hand and chest, with a second cloth on the left shoulder. In this sculpture, prominent *cakra* motifs mark the Buddha's soles and left palm. Below, a frieze depicts, from left: elephant, horse, squatting swordsman, seated female devotee, a *vajra* positioned in the centre signifying the *vajrāsana*, *cakra*, jewel, squatting male devotee, offerings, and a bearded figure with torch and censer. The first seven figures possibly represent the *saptaratna*. There are three *bodhi* tree branches above the Buddha, flanked by *vidyādhara*s with garlands³⁹⁶.

³⁹³ For the sculptures described in (R) and (U) I am using the old accession numbers of the Dacca Museum, as mentioned by Bhattasali. For this image, I was unable to locate the present accession number at the Bangladesh National Museum, Dhaka.

³⁹⁴ Bhattasali, *Iconography of Buddhist and Brahmanical Sculptures*, 30-31, Pl. VIII; Ananna Zulfiqar Showly, "Early Historic Costumes of Bangladesh Depicted on the Stone Sculptures and Coins," *South Asian History, Culture and Archaeology* 3, no. 2 (2023): Fig. 9.

³⁹⁵ Bhattasali, *Iconography of Buddhist and Brahmanical Sculptures*, 30.

³⁹⁶ Bhattasali, *Iconography of Buddhist and Brahmanical Sculptures*, 30.

Not many seated Buddha images are known from the *Samataṭa-littoral*, but some of the surviving examples are very exquisite and demonstrate extreme aesthetic sophistication in a style³⁹⁷, quite different from that encountered in the *Magadha-Varendra-constellation*.

R. A Mahāpratisarā image at the Bangladesh National Museum, Dhaka (BNM 69.111)

This black stone sculpture³⁹⁸ of Mahāpratisarā was unearthed at the site of Bikrampur in Munshiganj District, Dhaka Division in central Bangladesh, and was part of the private collection of Jiban Babu of Dalbazar, Dhaka, and is presently housed at the Bangladesh National Museum. This relief measuring 61 cm x 5 cm (Plate 53) depicts the eight-armed Mahāpratisarā, one of the *Pañcarakṣā* deities. Though the top is lost, the image aligns closely with descriptions in the *Sādhnamālā*: Mahāpratisarā, of fair complexion and youthful visage akin to a sixteen-year-old, bears three faces in this sculpture (contrary to the prescribed four, but as Bhattasali also noted, this omission of the face at the back of four-faced deities is not unusual): each with a serene expression, with her neck gently bent leftward. The attributes of the deity in each of her hands, are as follows:

Sword (*asi*) | Bow (*cāpa*)

Arrow (*śara*) | Thunderbolt (*vajra*)³⁹⁹

Trident (*triśūla*) | *Tarjani-mudrā* with lasso (*pāśa*)

Discus (*Cakra*) | Hatchet (*paraśu*)

The lasso with a ring tied end, is held by the third left hand in the *tarjanimudrā*, positioned between the deity's breasts. Her legs rest with the right over the left, and the sole of the left foot remains concealed.

³⁹⁷ Kim noted an exquisite seated copper-alloy Buddha image at the Indian Museum in Kolkata (Acc. No. No. A24317/8142), which was found in Jhewari, Chittagong (Kim, "Brahmanical-Buddhist sculptures": 404, Fig. 12). Due to constraints of length here, I am not delving into an elaborate comparative study of copper-alloy images.

³⁹⁸ Kim, "Buddhist-Brahmanical Sculptures": 411-412, Fig. 20.

³⁹⁹ And an aṅkuśa depicted below.

S. A Mahāpratisarā image at the Dhaka Zilla Parishad, Dhaka (Acc. No. Not Available)⁴⁰⁰

Discovered at Bhabanipur village in Sirajdikhan Upazila, Munshiganj District, Dhaka Division, central Bangladesh, and preserved, during Bhattasali's account, at the Dhaka Sahitya Parishad⁴⁰¹, this greyish black stone relief (Plate 54) measuring 117 cm x 76.2 cm, likely from the ninth-tenth century CE, depicts a Vajrayāna goddess, who has been identified as Mahāpratisarā. Bhattasali misidentified this image as Bṛkūti-Tārā, however it has been re-identified as Mahāpratisarā, based on the elephant-headed trampling motif⁴⁰². Seated on a lotus with legs crossed, she has three faces: the central face placid, the left with prominent teeth, and the right laughing with protruding teeth and a furrowed brow. She has eight arms, although some are broken. The attributes in each hand of the goddess are as follows:

Sword (*asi*) | Thunderbolt (*vajra*)

Broken | Damaged

Trident (*triśūla*) | Lasso (*pāśa*)

Damaged | Hatchet (*paraśu*)

Two roaring lions flank the base, with a crawling Ganeśa between them, perhaps suggesting her role as a Dharmapāla. A quiver of arrows, embedded in the ground to the right, evokes the arrow associated with Bṛkūṭī Tārā. The *dhyāni* Buddha Amitābha adorns the stele.

⁴⁰⁰ For this image, there is no accession number. I couldn't verify if the sculpture presently exists at the Bangladesh National Museum, Dhaka.

⁴⁰¹ In Bhattasali's account it was mentioned that this was kept at the Dhaka Sahitya Parishad, however I couldn't locate the present location of the erstwhile Sahitya Parishad in Dhaka. Instances of stone sculptures being housed at local thanas, zilla parishads, district libraries etc is a common practice across the Indian subcontinent, but more pronounced and visible in archaeologically rich regions, such as in important centres in the *Varendra-confluens* or the Dhaka-Munshiganj region of the *Samatāṭa-littoral*. Assuming it was considered an important sculpture, it should have been now housed at the National Museum in Dhaka. (Bhattasali, *Iconography of Buddhist and Brahmanical Sculptures*, Pl. XIX, 54-56).

⁴⁰² Gerd J. R. Mevissen, "Images of Mahapratishara in Bengal: Their Iconographic Links with Javanese, Central Asian and East Asian Images," *Journal of Bengal Art* 4 (1999): 99-129.

The ten-armed Mahāpratisāra bronze image from Java at the Museum für Asiatische Kunst in Berlin⁴⁰³ mentioned before, is stylistically very similar to Mahāpratisāra images from the *Samataṭa-littoral*.

T. Two Aśokakāntā Māricī images at the Bangladesh National Museum, Dhaka (Acc. No. 1.B(ii)a/1 & 1.B(ii)a/2)

The first sculpture was recovered from the Padma river at Panditsar in Naria Upazila of Shariatpur District under Dhaka Division of southern-central Bangladesh. This black stone relief⁴⁰⁴ (Plate 55a) measuring 122 cm x 61 cm, depicts Māricī. As per a *sādhana* cited by Foucher, which Bhattasali noted, Māricī is described as fair, with three faces, three eyes and eight arms. The attributes in each hands of the deity as described in the *sādhana* conform to those depicted in this sculpture:

Thunderbolt (*vajra*) | *Aśoka* leaf

Elephant goad (*aṅkuśa*) | Bow (*cāpa*)

Arrow (*śara*) | Lasso (*pāśa*)

Needle (*sūcī*) | *Tarjani mudrā*

There is a tiny Vairocana image on the *caitya* frame directly above her tall crown. Placed within a *caitya*, her right leg is bent, the left extended, on a chariot drawn by seven pigs, driven by Rāhu. Four attendant possesses surround her: Vattālī⁴⁰⁵ (east, boar-faced, holding needle and *aṅkuśa* in right hands, *pāśa* and *aśoka* leaf in left); Vadālī⁴⁰⁶ (south, same attributes in varied order); Varālī⁴⁰⁷ (west, as Vattālī), and Varāhamukhī⁴⁰⁸ (north, with *vajra* and arrow in right hands, *aśoka* leaf and bow in

⁴⁰³ Cruijsen et. al., "The Cult of the Buddhist Dhāraṇī Deity Mahāpratisarā Along the Maritime Silk Route," Fig. 1.

⁴⁰⁴ Bhattasali, *Iconography of Buddhist and Brahmanical Sculptures*, 43-44, Pl. XIV.

⁴⁰⁵ Bhattacharyya, *The Indian Buddhist Iconography*, 211.

⁴⁰⁶ Bhattacharyya, *The Indian Buddhist Iconography*, 211.

⁴⁰⁷ Bhattacharyya, *The Indian Buddhist Iconography*, 211.

⁴⁰⁸ Bhattacharyya, *The Indian Buddhist Iconography*, 211.

left). The *aśoka* branch in the main deity's left hand terminates in a floral cluster. A *caitya* spire crowns the deity, flanked by more *aśoka* branches⁴⁰⁹.

The second image of Māricī⁴¹⁰ (Plate 55b), measuring 79.2 cm x 54.8 cm was also found at Ujani, Gopalganj District along with the aforementioned Buddha image (R). The attributes of the deity are similar to the larger Māricī image discussed above. However Vairocana is absent, and the seven pigs drawing her chariot are roughly rendered, and are overlapping. Five attendant goddesses, each with two arms instead of four, surround her, deviating from the *sādhana*'s suggestion of four four-armed attendants.

U. A Mañjuvajra image at the Metropolitan Museum of Art, New York (Acc. No. 57.51.6)

This intricate greyish black stone relief⁴¹¹ (Plate 56), measuring 116.8 cm x 61 cm x 19.1 cm, depicts Mañjuvajra, an esoteric manifestation of Mañjuśrī⁴¹². It was bequeathed to the Metropolitan Museum in 1956 by Cora Timken Burnett (1872-1956), an American heiress, sculptor, and notable art collector. Likely from the eleventh century CE, the goddess appears in a *tri-mukha-ṣaḍbhujā* form, three-headed and six-armed. The *bodhisattva* is enthroned upon a richly articulated architectural base, flanked by leogryphs standing upon lions, with *makaras* issuing from the cusps of a triple-lobed nimbus. Crowning this superstructure are five *stūpas*, each enshrining an emanation of Mañjuśrī, collectively evoking the cosmic *maṇḍala* as envisioned in tantric Buddhist rituals. The entire architectural scheme might be read as a conceptual representation of a *mahāvihāra* from medieval Bengal. Below, a sculpted frieze portrays a group of kneeling figures in the *añjalimudrā*.

Bautze-Picron did an iconographic study of Mañjuśrī images from eastern India from the seventh century CE, with a focus on a Linden Museum Stuttgart Mañjuśrī image, in which it was noted that stone images of Mañjuśrī from this period integrated motifs from earlier stucco and bronze

⁴⁰⁹ Bhattasali, *Iconography of Buddhist and Brahmanical Sculptures*, 43-44.

⁴¹⁰ Bhattasali, *Iconography of Buddhist and Brahmanical Sculptures*, 44, Pl. XIII.

⁴¹¹ *Manjuvajra Mandala*, Pāla period (Bangladesh or India – Bengal), 11th century; black stone, 46 in. × 24 in. (116.8 × 61 cm); acc. no. 57.51.6, Bequest of Cora Timken Burnett, The Metropolitan Museum of Art. <https://www.metmuseum.org/art/collection/search/38124>.

⁴¹² Behrendt, *Tibet and India*, 39-41, Pl. 40.

(copper-alloy) images, and that the deity was particularly revered in Nalanda as evidenced by numerous stucco, bronze (copper-alloy) and stone images from the seventh-eighth centuries CE; however from the ninth century CE, the *bodhisattva*'s iconography evolves, which Bautze-Picron demonstrated through examples from Kukrihar and Bodh Gaya⁴¹³. Etienne Lamotte significantly advanced our understanding of the evolution of Mañjuśrī's persona⁴¹⁴. Marie-Thérèse de Mallmann analysed the deity's descriptions in the *Sādhanamālā* and the *Nispannayogāvalī*⁴¹⁵, while the *Mañjuśrīmūlakalpa* was studied by Marcello Lalou⁴¹⁶ and Ariane Macdonald⁴¹⁷ with regard to its iconographic description of Mañjuśrī. John S. Deyell's numismatic re-interpretation of a coin from southeastern Bengal (Samatāṭa), dated between the ninth and tenth centuries CE, marks it as one of the earliest numismatic depiction of *bodhisattva* Mañjuśrī, where the deity is portrayed with a three-pointed crown, elaborate jewellery and a prominent sword, which Deyell interpreted, based on the *Sādhanamālā*, as a representation of Arapacana Mañjuśrī⁴¹⁸. Another recent study examined Mañjuśrī images in central and east Java, made in bronze and silver, emphasising the distinct Javanese adaptation of Mañjuśrī which blended Pāla aesthetics and local craftsmanship: sartorial styles, textile patterns etc., and the flourishing of the cult of Arapacana Mañjuśrī in central Java, which persisted after the waning of the Pāla empire in the eastern Indian subcontinent⁴¹⁹.

V. An ex-Boston Avalokiteśvara Lokanātha image from unknown private collection

This black stone sculpture⁴²⁰ of a seated *bodhisattva* (height 147.4 cm) (Plate 57), was identified as Padmapāṇi by Ananda K. Coomaraswamy in the records of the Museum of Fine Arts,

⁴¹³ Claudine Bautze-Picron. "Some Aspects of Mañjuśrī's Iconography in Bihar from the 7th Century Onward." *TRIBUS* 38 (1989): 71–82.

⁴¹⁴ Étienne Lamotte, "Mañjuśrī," *T'oung Pao* 48 (1960): 1–96.

⁴¹⁵ Marie-Thérèse de Mallmann, *Étude iconographique sur Mañjuśrī* (Paris, 1964).

⁴¹⁶ Marcelle Lalou, *Iconographie des étoffes peintes (pata) dans le Mañjuśrīmūlakalpa* (Paris, 1930).

⁴¹⁷ Ariane MacDonald, *Le Maṇḍala du Mañjuśrīmūlakalpa* (Paris, 1962).

⁴¹⁸ John S. Deyell, "A Reinterpretation of a Rare Samatata Coin as the Earliest Numismatic Representation of Bodhisattva Mañjuśrī," in *Felicitas: Essays in Numismatics, Epigraphy and History in Honour of Joe Cribb*, ed. Shailendra Bhandare and Sanjay Garg (New Delhi: Reesha Books International, 2011), 101–18.

⁴¹⁹ Lesley S. Pullen, "Re-Interpretation of Mañjuśrī in Central and East Java," *Humaniora* 33, no. 2 (June 2021): 159–68.

⁴²⁰ *A Large and Important Black Stone Figure of Lokanatha Avalokiteshvara, northeastern India, Pāla period, 12th century; black stone, 58 in. (147.4 cm) high. Christie's sale of Indian, Himalayan and Southeast Asian Works of Art, lot 233, New York, 14 March 2017. <https://www.christies.com/lot/lot-a-large-and-important-black-stone-figure-6061734/>.*

Boston⁴²¹, where it once belonged, before being sold at a Christie's auction, to a private collector, in 2017. The deity is richly adorned, and exquisitely composed, seated in the *ardhaparyāṅkāśana*, with the right leg pendant and resting on a lotus bloom that emerges from vine-like waves. As noted by Pal, the extended right leg energises the composition, imparting a powerful sense of balance and motion⁴²². This depiction corresponds to canonical depictions of *lalitāsana*, as discussed in some examples before. Pal also noted that the lotus pedestal, which is fully open and rising from curling vegetation, contributes to a visual impression that the *bodhisattva* is suspended mid-air; further, detached from any architectural backdrop, the deity's outline and expressive modelling suggest a deliberate sculptural strategy to enhance three-dimensionality, which is a notable departure from the more densely packed narrative reliefs of the period. Although the arms are broken, iconographic logic and parallels suggest the right hand once formed the *varadamudrā*, while the left likely grasped the stem of a lotus rising above the shoulder. The *bodhisattva*'s torso is diagonally draped with a semi-transparent *uttarīya*, with its folds rendered with extreme finesse, to which Pal referenced the textile traditions of Bengal⁴²³. The *upavīta* is fashioned as a double-stranded pearl garland, and crosses the left shoulder. The *bodhisattva*'s head is crowned with an elaborate *jaṭāmukūṭa*, carved with remarkable detail into tight vertical coils resembling intertwined serpents: a stylistic device that suggests both ascetic and ornamental. The reverse of the sculpture is unfinished. The sculpture was perhaps once enshrined within a temple niche, or formed part of a triadic ensemble, flanking the central image of the Buddha, paired with a complementary image of Maitreya. Pal also noted the presence of temples dedicated to Avalokiteśvara in medieval Bihar and Bengal, which have not survived, but are extensively documented in illuminated manuscripts⁴²⁴. Despite the compositional

⁴²¹ Ananda K. Coomaraswamy, "Buddhist Sculpture: Recent Acquisitions," *Museum of Fine Arts Bulletin* 20, no. 120 (August 1922): 49, fig. 8.

⁴²² Pratapaditya Pal, "Lot Essay: A Large and Important Black Stone Figure of Lokanatha Avalokiteshvara," in "Lokanatha and Coomaraswamy: A Tale of a Divine World Savior and a Mortal Curator", *Christie's*, accessed July 23, 2025, <https://www.christies.com/lot/lot-a-large-and-important-black-stone-figure-6061734/>.

⁴²³ Pal, "Lot Essay: A Large and Important Black Stone Figure of Lokanatha Avalokiteshvara."

⁴²⁴ Pal, "Lot Essay: A Large and Important Black Stone Figure of Lokanatha Avalokiteshvara."

sophistication of this sculpture, Coomaraswamy refrained from extended commentary⁴²⁵. Pal noted the depiction of garments in sculptures from Bengal, attributing their finesse to the traditions of textile production in the region. Stylistically, I concur with Pal's dating of this sculpture to the eleventh century CE⁴²⁶. This sculpture may have some stylistic similarities with the standing Coochbehar Avalokiteśvara.

W. A sculpture of Candragomī at the LACMA (Acc. No. 1992.208.2)

This black stone sculpture at the LACMA⁴²⁷ (Plate 58), measuring 59.06 cm x 29.21 cm x 12.7 cm, was a gift from Paul F. Walter (1935-2017), a leading New York art collector and connoisseur. The sculpture depicts the *mahāsiddha* Candragomīn with a nimbus encircling his shorn head, a marker of his enlightened status, complemented by elongated earlobes and a distinctive sectarian mark adorning his forehead. Candragomīn was a celebrated *mahāsiddha*, lay poet and grammarian from eastern Bengal active in the fifth century CE, who significantly influenced Sanskrit grammar, founding the Cāndra school. A junior contemporary of Kālidāsa, he was among the most accomplished poets in Indian Buddhist history. His play *Lokānanda*, about the *bodhisattva* king Mañicūḍa, is the oldest surviving Buddhist drama and was widely performed for centuries. A devotee of Tārā, he wrote several hymns in her honour. Though Tibetan sources depict him as a Vijñānavāda proponent who debated Candrakīrti, little in his surviving works confirms this. His known writings include the *Letter to a Disciple (Śiṣyalekha)*, the *Confessional Praise (Deśanāstava)*, and possibly the *Twenty Verses on the Bodhisattva Precepts (Bodhisattvasaṃvaraviṃśaka)*⁴²⁸. According to

⁴²⁵ Ananda K. Coomaraswamy, *Catalogue of the Indian Collections in the Museum of Fine Arts, Boston, Part II: Sculpture* (Boston: Museum of Fine Arts, 1923), 78 and pl. XXXVI.

⁴²⁶ Pal, "Lokanatha and Coomaraswamy."

⁴²⁷ *The Mahasiddha (Great Adept) Chandragomin*, 12th century, Bangladesh, black schist, 23 1/4 × 11 1/2 × 5 in. (59.06 × 29.21 × 12.7 cm), Los Angeles County Museum of Art, Gift of Paul F. Walter, Accession no. AC1992.208.2, <https://collections.lacma.org/node/173626>; Rob Linrothe, ed., *Holy Madness: Portraits of Tantric Siddhas* (New York/Chicago: Rubin Museum of Art and Serindia Publications, 2006), cat. no. 4, 188–89; Stephen Little et al., *Las Huellas de Buda* (Ciudad de México: Instituto Nacional de Antropología e Historia, 2018); Stephen Little and Tushara Bindu Gude, *Realms of the Dharma: Buddhist Art across Asia* (Los Angeles: Los Angeles County Museum of Art, 2025).

⁴²⁸ Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 165; Cf. Rob Linrothe ed., *Holy Madness*, 195, 428.

Tārānātha's account, he subdued the spread of leprosy in Siṃhala (Sri Lanka), by building a temple dedicated to Siṃhanāda⁴²⁹.

In contrast to monastic attire, he is clad in a simple loincloth, with a prominent *upavīta* draped over his left shoulder. He is seated in the *siddhāsana* atop a double lotus throne, with his right knee stabilised by a *yogabandha*. The right hand of the sculpture is damaged, and it might have held an *akṣamālā*. At the sculpture's apex, a now-weathered depiction of Tārā presides, flanking her at the stele's two corners are two ascetic figures depicted with matted hair, likely also *mahāsiddhas*: both engaged in meditation, one beneath a tree and the other within a mountain cave. At the base of the sculpture, behind the pedestal, on either side, are depicted two figures: the male figure on the *mahāsiddha*'s right in the *añjalimudrā*, while the female figure depicted to the *mahāsiddha*'s left, holds her elongated ponytail, perhaps gesturing an offering. It has a one-line inscription at the bottom, which reads:

śrī Alasi-jñānaśrīyā dānam

Translation: A meritorious gift by Śrī Alasi-jñānaśrī⁴³⁰.

The inscription implies that it was donated by Alasi, who was knowledgeable (*jñānaśrī*).

Images of *mahāsiddhas* in the sculptural repertoire of Pāla-period art are rare, but occupy a prominent position in Himalayan art, especially Tibetan and Nepalese paintings and copper-alloy pieces⁴³¹. In the *Varendra-confluens*, images of Śaivite ascetics have been found in large numbers⁴³².

⁴²⁹ Kim, *Receptacle of the Sacred*, 129.

⁴³⁰ Gouriswar Bhattacharya, inscription translation on *The Mahasiddha (Great Adept) Chandragomin*, 12th century, Bangladesh, sculpture, Los Angeles County Museum of Art, <https://collections.lacma.org/node/173626>; Gouriswar Bhattacharya, "Two Interesting Items of the Pāla Period," *Berliner Indologische Studien* 1 (1985): 135–47.

⁴³¹ A bronze piece from the sixteenth century Tibet at the Rubin Museum (Acc. No. C2003.23.4), for example, depicts, the *mahāsiddha* Kāṇha, also supposed to be from eastern India, wearing a similar *yogabandha* around the waist. Appendix 2 provides a list of some well-known Buddhist monk-scholars (*siddhācaryas*) and *Mahāsiddhas*.

⁴³² Among Ranjusri Ghosh's extensive scholarship on this subject, Cf. Ranjusri Ghosh, "A Few Fierce Images of Śiva and Four Image Inscriptions from Northern Bengal," in *South Asian Archaeology and Art 2012*, vol. 2 (Turnhout, Belgium: Brepols Publishers, 2016); Ranjusri Ghosh, "Image of a Śaiva Teacher and an Inscription on Pedestal: New Evidence for Bangarh Śaivism," *Pratna Samiksha* 1 (Kolkata: Centre for Archaeological Studies and Training, Eastern India, 2010); Ranjusri Ghosh, "Śaiva Cult and Some Images at Bāṅgaḍ: Dakṣiṇ Dinājpur," in *Journal of the Asiatic Society* 48, no. 4, ed.

1.5 End remarks

While the above iconographic study is only representational and not exhaustive of the framework applied, this chapter attempted to forge a classification that can explain and mediate Pāla art's heterogeneity, applicable to different media, including Pāla copper-alloys, a huge corpus of which exists, but has been omitted from this study here due to constraints of scope and length. Copper-alloys being easily portable, enjoyed a high level of mobility, comparable to the manuscripts, if not more, in contrast to stone sculptures. Building on existing foundations, I proposed a regional framework in which Magadha and Varendra function as interconnected centres of production, while the *Samatāṭa-littoral*, connected to Southeast Asia through Bay of Bengal maritime networks, emerges as a co-equal zone with its own distinctive iconographic traditions.

Ramakanta Chakrabarty (Kolkata: The Asiatic Society, 2007). In his study of *mahāsiddhas* images from eastern India (especially the *Kāmārūpa-Interstice*) Linrothe mentioned a *mahāsiddha* image with a consort or female disciple, large greyish black stone sculpture at the Assam State Museum (Acc. No. 2747/68[5]) from the thirteenth-fourteenth century CE (Linrothe, *Holy Madness*, 133-135, Fig. 7.14). Also cf. R. K. Chattopadhyay, S. Ray, and S. Majumder, "The Kingdom of the Śaivācāryas," *Berliner Indologische Studien* 21 (2013): 173–256; Tamara Sears, *Worldly Gurus and Spiritual Kings: Architecture and Asceticism in Medieval India* (New Haven: Yale University Press, 2014).

Chapter 2: The image as event: The diasporic imagination of Prajñāpāramitā

In this chapter, I propose a methodology that conceptualises the iconographic elaboration and innovation of Prajñāpāramitā in the Pāla-period as an ‘event’⁴³³ within the diasporic trajectories of Mahāyāna Buddhism. Prajñāpāramitā, embodying both the philosophical concept of the perfection of wisdom (*prajñā*), and a deified female figure in Mahāyāna texts and art from the second century CE, has historically been primarily rooted in sophisticated textual, philosophical, and iconographic traditions rather than widespread devotional worship, which is a later phenomenon. The ‘event’ is framed in two ways. First, as a decisive transition: Prajñāpāramitā’s shift from an abstract philosophical concept in early *sūtra* literature to a depicted and worshipped deity in the Pāla period and in later Newari traditions. Second, as a gradual, centuries-long process shaped by trans-regional circulation of Mahāyāna Buddhism, in which textual, iconographic, and ritual developments unfolded across Central, South, and Southeast Asia over many centuries before culminating in the elaborate Pāla period formulations, integrating cycling cosmological time with linear historical consciousness⁴³⁴. This is evident in the circulation and exchange of cultural and doctrinal aspects of Prajñāpāramitā across Central, South, and Southeast Asia, offering a *longue durée*⁴³⁵ perspective on

⁴³³ I frame “event”, not as a specific historical moment or an abrupt singularity, but as a broader process condensed into an analytical category. Other definitions of “event” used in this chapter, such as: as a transformative moment (like the composition of the earliest *Prajñāpāramitā sūtras* in ca. 1st century BCE - 1st century CE, or the anthropomorphisation of Prajñāpāramitā in Gandhāran art in ca. 2nd century CE), as a rupture (like the transition of Prajñāpāramitā from abstract wisdom figure to a devotional deity), or as a protracted process or series of events (like the integration of Prajñāpāramitā into tantric and esoteric Buddhism in ca. 8th-12th centuries CE): are all subsets of this analytical category.

⁴³⁴ On myth and history in Buddhist and Brahmanical traditions as synthesised aptly by Romila Thapar, see: Romila Thapar, *Time as a Metaphor of History: Early India* (Delhi: Oxford University Press, 1996), 25–30. On historical time and gradual processes in early India, see: 31–37.

⁴³⁵ Fernand Braudel, *The Mediterranean and the Mediterranean World in the Age of Philip II*, trans. Siân Reynolds, vol. 1 (New York: Harper & Row, 1972), xi–xxviii, 3–21.

Prajñāpāramitā's evolution in these geographical regions; her rise as a narrative event⁴³⁶ is posited to be shaped by textual, iconographic, and ritual developments across centuries, where cultural and religious processes (such as, monastic networks, patronage) and narratives, mediated the rise of the deity through a synthesis of diverse temporalities⁴³⁷; and in the Pāla-period, the intensification and innovation of Prajñāpāramitā's iconography: as a historical juncture, facilitating a reflection on how narrative refigures and reconfigures time and thus temporal contexts⁴³⁸ to endow events with meaning⁴³⁹.

The philosophical distinction between objects, which endure through time with clear spatial boundaries, and events, which occur with precise temporal boundaries, has been extensively debated in analytical metaphysics⁴⁴⁰. Ricoeur's narrative theory engages with this debate by treating the

⁴³⁶ Paul Ricoeur, *Time and Narrative*, Volume 1, trans. Kathleen McLaughlin and David Pellauer (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 1984), 3–30. On the relation between narrative theory and chronology, Ricoeur observed that if contemporary narrative theory, spanning historiography, philosophy of history, and narratology, predominantly seeks to dismantle chronological frameworks, this resistance to linear time does not inevitably reduce narrative to a mere logical construct but may instead enrich its temporal essence. Chronology, finds its antithesis not solely in the atemporal realm of laws and models, but in temporality itself. Acknowledging elements beyond time proves essential to fully honour human temporality, advocating not its eradication but a deeper escalation, structuring it into stratified temporalisations that transition from “extended” to “intensely focussed,” showing consonance with the principle *non secundum distentionem sed secundum intensionem* (Ricoeur, *Time and Narrative*, Volume 1, 30).

⁴³⁷ Paul Ricoeur, *Time and Narrative*, Volume 2, trans. Kathleen McLaughlin and David Pellauer (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 1985), 52–100.

⁴³⁸ In the context of narration as a form of presentifying [*vergegenwartigen*] events that are not perceptible to the listener's senses,” Ricoeur observed: “This is therefore a phenomenological distinction by reason of which every narrating is narrating something (*erzählen von*), yet something which itself is not a narrative. From this basic distinction follows the possibility of distinguishing two times: the time taken to narrate and narrated time” (Ricoeur, *Time and Narrative*, Volume 2, 78).

⁴³⁹ Paul Ricoeur, *Time and Narrative*, Volume 3, trans. Kathleen McLaughlin and David Pellauer (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 1988), 101–150. On mythic time, historical time, cosmic time, psychological time, narrated time, chronicle time, and calendrical time, see: Ricoeur, *Time and Narrative*, Volume 3, 104–109.

⁴⁴⁰ For the full range of positions, see: W. V. O. Quine, “Identity, Ostension and Hypostasis,” *Journal of Philosophy* 47 (1950): 621–33; D. K. Lewis, *On the Plurality of Worlds* (Oxford: Blackwell, 1986); M. Heller, *The Ontology of Physical Objects: Four Dimensional Hunks of Matter* (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 1990); T. Sider, *Four-Dimensionalism: An Ontology of Persistence and Time* (New York: Oxford University Press, 2001); N. Goodman, *The Structure of Appearance* (Cambridge, MA: Harvard University Press, 1951); . B. Lombard, *Events: A Metaphysical Study* (London: Routledge, 1986); J. Bennett, *Events and Their Names* (Oxford: Clarendon Press, 1988); . Deleuze, *Logique du sens* (Paris: Minuit, 1969); English trans. by M. Lester with C. Stivale, *The Logic of Sense* (New York: Columbia University Press, 1990); T. Parsons, “Tropes and Supervenience,” *Philosophy and Phenomenological Research* 51 (1991): 629–32; D. Costa, “The Transcendentist Theory of Persistence,” *The Journal of Philosophy* 114 (2017): 57–75; Moravcsik, J. M. E., 1968, ‘Strawson and Ontological Priority’, in R. J. Butler (ed.), *Analytical Philosophy*, Second Series, New York: Barnes and Noble, pp. 106–119; D. Davidson, “The Individuation of Events,” in *Essays in Honor of Carl G. Hempel*, ed. N. Rescher (Dordrecht: Reidel, 1969), 216–34; reprinted in *Events*, 265–83, and in Davidson 1980, 163–80; W. G. Lycan, “Identifiability-Dependence and Ontological Priority,” *The Personalist* 51 (1970): 502–13; I. Thalberg, “The Irreducibility of Events,” *Analysis* 38 (1978): 1–9; J. E. Tiles, *Things that Happen* (Aberdeen: Aberdeen University Press, 1981); “Events

relationship between object and event as something configured through narrative itself, implying in the context of this study, that it is the act of narration that constitutes the temporal structure within which Prajñāpāramitā's iconographic development can be understood as an event, and not merely as a succession of objects.

At first, I briefly trace the textual, ideological and visual transmission of *Prajñāpāramitā* literature and concepts across south⁴⁴¹ and Central Asia, with a particular focus on: the Gilgit manuscripts and Kashmiri Buddhist traditions (a hub of Mahāyāna scholarship in the early centuries CE: facilitating the transmission of *Prajñāpāramitā* texts to Central Asia); and Central Asian conduits like Khotan. I then proceed to analyse the proliferation of Prajñāpāramitā in the context of the Pāla-period, especially in its interactions with Brahmanical *māṭṛkā* and female goddess traditions of eastern India, iconographic innovations, and very briefly the evolution of Prajñāpāramitā in the ritual contexts⁴⁴² of Newari Buddhism⁴⁴³ in the Kathmandu valley. Through this historical reconstruction of Prajñāpāramitā's diasporic trajectories, including texts, iconography and ritual practices, I argue

vs. Objects," first published April 22, 2002; substantive revision May 12, 2025, *Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy* (accessed August 9, 2025), <https://plato.stanford.edu/entries/events/>.

⁴⁴¹ Excluding Indochina in Southeastern Asia, which has been the subject of study in a recent publication by Jinah Kim: Jinah Kim, "Goddess Prajñāpāramitā and Esoteric Buddhism in Jayavarman VII's Angkor," in *The Creative South: Buddhist and Hindu Art in Mediaeval Maritime Asia*, ed. Andrea Acri and Peter Sharrock (Singapore: ISEAS–Yusof Ishak Institute, 2022). Also see: Lesley S. Pullen, "Vajravārāhī in Khara Khoto and Prajñāpāramitā in East Java: Connected by Pearl Ornaments," *Religions* 16, no. 1 (2025): 84. Although I refer to this piece several times in this chapter, I will not be particularly delving into the proliferation of Prajñāpāramitā doctrine and imagery in Southeastern Asia. Due to constraints of scope, this discussion also doesn't go into Tibet. On the stylistic and iconographic trajectories of Nepal and Tibet, alongside the influence of Pāla art, through examples of Prajñāpāramitā's sculpted and painted representations from Central Asian, Nepalese and Tibetan contexts in different temporal phases, see: Abira Bhattacharya, "Motherhood in the Realm of Eastern Indian and Himalayan Art: An Iconographic Study of Visual Forms of Prajñāpāramitā from the National Museum, Delhi," *Izvestiya Uralskogo Federalnogo Universiteta. Seriya 2: Gumanitarnye Nauki* 23, no. 4 (2021): 9–22. However, the same "event" model, as I hypothesise, can of course, be used to interpret the rise in veneration and popularity of the deity Prajñāpāramitā in medieval southeastern Asia and Tibet as well.

⁴⁴² Ricoeur's distinction between myth and ritual is apposite here: "... myth enlarges ordinary time (and space), whereas ritual brings together mythic time and the profane sphere of life and action" (Ricoeur, *Time and Narrative*, Volume 3, 105).

⁴⁴³ The evolution of Prajñāpāramitā in Newari Buddhist ritual contexts in the Kathmandu valley is treated here not as a tradition to be analysed comprehensively, but as the terminal point of the diasporic trajectory originating in eastern India: the region where Pāla period iconographic innovations were received, preserved, and ritually elaborated after the decline of Buddhism in the subcontinent. My treatment is selective, focusing on some Newari ritual developments that might help us better understand the Pāla period practices that preceded them.

that the imagination of Prajñāpāramitā can be interpreted as a series of protracted narrative events⁴⁴⁴, unfolding from Mahāyāna⁴⁴⁵ to Vajrayāna⁴⁴⁶ Buddhism, which are constituted by significant moments of philosophical and ritual innovation. These moments of irruption, are marked by textual proliferation, iconographic innovation, and ritual elaboration, in the context of interactions with other religious traditions, especially Brahmanical tantrism, which culminated in the sophisticated visual and doctrinal articulations in the Pāla-period. This pattern of development, marked by discontinuous but significant intensifications across different regions, produced the distinctive forms of Prajñāpāramitā veneration found in the Pāla period. By tracing this history, I aim to show how the cult of Prajñāpāramitā was inseparable from the material practices of manuscript production, image-

⁴⁴⁴ Ricoeur observed that narrative is defined in contrast to discourse as a sequence of events appearing self-linked without a primary agency, referring to Emile Benveniste's view that the concept of past, whether historical or imagined, excludes self-referentiality from the point of view of expression, unlike discourse (Ricoeur, *Time and Narrative*, Volume 2, 63).

⁴⁴⁵ Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 513-514; Standard Buddhist terminology throughout this chapter is referenced for convenience to Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr.'s dictionary, with specialist sources cited where concepts are directly relevant to the argument. For a recent discussion on the term Mahāyāna, see: Tilmann Vetter and Anne MacDonald, "Once Again on the Origin of Mahāyāna Buddhism," *Wiener Zeitschrift für die Kunde Südasiens / Vienna Journal of South Asian Studies* 45 (2001): 59–90, esp. 62-70.

⁴⁴⁶ Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 957; Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr.'s comments are apposite here: "The vajrayāna, however, is considered by its adherents to be not a separate vehicle but a form of the Mahāyāna; such adherents would speak instead of the three vehicles (*triyāna*) of hīnayāna, pāramitāyāna, and vajrayāna, with the latter two referring respectively to an exoteric and an esoteric path by which the bodhisattva achieves buddhahood, with the pāramitāyāna set forth in the Mahāyāna *sūtras* and the vajrayāna set forth in the tantras."

making, and ritual performance, and how its doctrinal and visual forms adapted to different local contexts as they moved across regions.

Fig. 1. Map illustrating the diasporic proliferation of Prajñāpāramitā in parts of South and Central Asia.

2.1 Situating *Prajñāpāramitā* literature

2.1.a Introduction

Rather than surveying comprehensively the textual history of Prajñāpāramitā literature, which has been authoritatively traced by Conze, Lamotte, and more recently Apple, this section identifies the specific moments of irruption within that history that constitute events in the analytical

sense this chapter employs: junctures at which the diasporic trajectory of Prajñāpāramitā’s elaboration was transformed rather than merely continued, and which cumulatively produced the iconographic and ritual intensification visible in the Pāla period. The criterion for selection is not chronological comprehensiveness but argumentative relevance: each moment discussed here marks a phase transition in the *evental continuum* this chapter outlines.

Within Buddhist thought, the concept of *Prajñāpāramitā*⁴⁴⁷, who has been referred to as the “*philosophiae regina*, the Buddhist Sophia⁴⁴⁸” etymologically derived from the Sanskrit *pra* (“superior”) and *jñā* (“knowing, knowledge, perception”)⁴⁴⁹, has profound epistemological and soteriological implications. Literally translated, “Perfection of Insight” or “Perfection of Discernment,” and often rendered as “Perfection of Wisdom,” it denotes a non-dual, luminous, and non-conceptual state of awareness⁴⁵⁰. As an embodiment of the telos of complete enlightenment (*sambodhi*⁴⁵¹), *prajñāpāramitā* is the quintessence of omniscient knowledge (*sarvajñatā*⁴⁵²), which is non-dual (*advaya*⁴⁵³) awareness, that transcends conceptual constructs (*vikalpa*⁴⁵⁴), suffused with absolute purity (*atyantaviśuddhi*), unborn and unceasing (*anutpāda*⁴⁵⁵-*nirodha*⁴⁵⁶), and imperishable (*akṣaya*). *Prajñāpāramitā* is synonymous with *nirvāṇa*⁴⁵⁷, *tathatā*⁴⁵⁸ (suchness), luminous *citta*⁴⁵⁹ (“mind”), and *buddhatā*⁴⁶⁰ (Buddhahood), yet revealing phenomena as they are (*yathābhūtata*⁴⁶¹),

⁴⁴⁷ Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 656-657.

⁴⁴⁸ Miranda Eberle Shaw, *Buddhist Goddesses of India* (Princeton: Princeton University Press, 2006), 166.

⁴⁴⁹ Alex Wayman, “Nescience and Insight According to Asaṅga’s Yogācārabhūmi,” in *Buddhist Insight*, ed. George Elder (Delhi: Motilal Banarsidass, 1984), 193–214, es. 209.

⁴⁵⁰ Tadeusz Skorupski, *The Six Perfections: An Abridged Version of E. Lamotte’s French Translation of Nāgārjuna’s Mahāprajñāpāramitāsāstra, Chapters XVI–XXX*, Buddhica Britannica, Series Continua IX (Tring, UK: The Institute of Buddhist Studies, 2002), 127-134.

⁴⁵¹ Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 750.

⁴⁵² Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 779.

⁴⁵³ Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 18-19.

⁴⁵⁴ Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 970.

⁴⁵⁵ Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 54.

⁴⁵⁶ Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 588.

⁴⁵⁷ Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 589-590; Étienne Lamotte, *History of Indian Buddhism: From the Origins to the Śaka Era*, trans. Sara Webb-Boin, supervised by Jean Dantinne (Louvain-la-Neuve: Université Catholique de Louvain, Institut Orientaliste, 1988), 44.

⁴⁵⁸ Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 899.

⁴⁵⁹ Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 194.

⁴⁶⁰ Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 155, 151-152.

⁴⁶¹ Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 1024-1025.

fundamentally articulating the realisation of *sūnyatā*⁴⁶² (emptiness)⁴⁶³, and the essencelessness of phenomena (*dharmanairātmya*⁴⁶⁴) and people (*pudgalanairātmya*⁴⁶⁵). The doctrine of *Prajñāpāramitā* delineates *bodhisattva*-hood through the six or ten *pāramitās*⁴⁶⁶ (perfection): *dānapāramitā*⁴⁶⁷ (perfection of giving), *śīlapāramitā*⁴⁶⁸ (perfection of morality), *kṣāntipāramitā*⁴⁶⁹ (perfection of patience), *vīryapāramitā*⁴⁷⁰ (perfection of energy), *dhyānapāramitā*⁴⁷¹ (perfection of meditative absorption) and *prajñāpāramitā*⁴⁷² (wisdom)⁴⁷³. The *sūtras* regard *prajñā* as the guiding principle of the other five virtues, as without it, they are like a group of lost blind people. In both practice and philosophy, *prajñā* is given the highest importance. The term *pāramitā*, as applied to *prajñā*, signifies her traversal to the “other shore” (*pāra*) of insight⁴⁷⁴, reaching the utmost limit (*anta*) and summit (*niṣṭhāgata*⁴⁷⁵) of all knowledge⁴⁷⁶.

In the formative epochs of Buddhist history, possibly during King Aśoka’s reign (268-233 BCE), certain *nikāya*⁴⁷⁷ (groups/ collections) with a focus on *prajñā* likely crafted mnemonic

⁴⁶² Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 871-872

⁴⁶³ Erich Frauwallner and Lodrö Sangpo, *The Philosophy of Buddhism = Die Philosophie des Buddhismus* (New Delhi: Motilal Banarsidass Publishers, 2010).

⁴⁶⁴ Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 248-249.

⁴⁶⁵ Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 678.

⁴⁶⁶ Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 624; In the *Daśabhūmikasūtra*, four more *pāramitās* are added: “method (*upāya*), vow (*pranidhāna*), power (*bala*), and knowledge (*jñāna*), with the explanation that the bodhisattva practices the perfections in this order on each of the ten *bodhisattva* stages or grounds (*bhūmi*). Thus, giving is perfected on the first *bhūmi*, morality on the second, and so on.” (Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 624).

⁴⁶⁷ Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 212; Bhattacharyya, *Nispannayogāvalī*, 56; Bhattacharyya, *The Indian Buddhist Iconography*, 324-325.

⁴⁶⁸ Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 822; Bhattacharyya, *Nispannayogāvalī*, 56; Bhattacharyya, *The Indian Buddhist Iconography*, 325.

⁴⁶⁹ Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 446; Bhattacharyya, *The Indian Buddhist Iconography*, 325.

⁴⁷⁰ Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 980; Bhattacharyya, *Nispannayogāvalī*, 56; Bhattacharyya, *The Indian Buddhist Iconography*, 325-326.

⁴⁷¹ Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 257; Bhattacharyya, *Nispannayogāvalī*, 56; Bhattacharyya, *The Indian Buddhist Iconography*, 326.

⁴⁷² Bhattacharyya, *Nispannayogāvalī*, 65; Bhattacharyya, *The Indian Buddhist Iconography*, 326-327.

⁴⁷³ Williams, *Mahayana Buddhism*, 51; Skorupski, *The Six Perfections*, 17-134.

⁴⁷⁴ Har Dayal, *The Bodhisattva Doctrine in Buddhist Sanskrit Literature* (Delhi: Motilal Banarsidass, 1970), 166.

⁴⁷⁵ Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 594

⁴⁷⁶ James B. Apple, “Prajñāpāramitā,” in *Encyclopedia of Indian Religions*, ed. Arvind Sharma (Dordrecht: Springer, 2019), 1-2, 6-7. <https://www.academia.edu/2249249/Prajñāpāramitā> (accessed August 17, 2025); Étienne Lamotte, *Le Traité de la Grande Vertu de Sagesse de Nāgārjuna*, vol. 2 (Louvain: Institut Orientaliste, 1949), 1066 [translated to English by author]; Ronald Davidson noted that virtually all schools of Buddhism, maintain a trifurcation of insight: construction of insight from learning, reflection on what has been learnt, and its cultivation until omniscience is reached: *śruta*, *cintā*, *bhāvanā*, and *prajñā* (Davidson, *Indian Esoteric Buddhism*, 14).

⁴⁷⁷ Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 585.

*mātrkā*⁴⁷⁸ (matrix) to encode and analyse the Buddha’s teachings (*dharma*)⁴⁷⁹. These analytical discourses, centred on *prajñā*, were instrumental in the creation of both the *Abhidharma*⁴⁸⁰ and *Prajñāpāramitā* corpora. These texts emphasise a *samādhi* (concentration⁴⁸¹), without grasping anything at all (*sarvadharmāparigrhīta*)⁴⁸², possibly tracing back to *bhikṣus* who dwelt in non-strife (*araṇavihārin*⁴⁸³) and avoided conceptual determinations, as exemplified by the Buddha’s disciple Subhūti⁴⁸⁴. The precise geographical cradle of *Prajñāpāramitā*’s literature and practices remains elusive. Edward Conze posited the origins of *Prajñāpāramitā* among Mahāsāṃghika⁴⁸⁵ (Great Congregation) lineages in southern India’s Andhra region, along the Kṛṣṇa river⁴⁸⁶. Étienne Lamotte advocated for northwest South Asia and Central Asia⁴⁸⁷. Several Mahāyāna Buddhist scriptures point to a southern origin. The *AsP* states that after the Tāthāgata’s passing, the perfection of wisdom will “proceed to the south.”⁴⁸⁸ The *Mañjuśrīmūlatantra* assigns four regions for reciting various Mahāyāna *sūtras*, with the *Prajñāpāramitā* to be recited in the south. This corresponds with traditional Mahāyāna accounts, which attribute the scriptures to the Buddha’s second major teaching cycle in the fifth or sixth century BCE, lost until their rediscovery by Nāgārjuna in southern India in the first century CE⁴⁸⁹.

⁴⁷⁸ Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 535.

⁴⁷⁹ Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 242-243; André Migot, “Un grand disciple du Buddha: Sāriputra. Son rôle dans l’histoire du bouddhisme et dans le développement de l’Abhidharma,” *Bulletin de l’École française d’Extrême-Orient* 46 (1954): 511–514.

⁴⁸⁰ Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 4; Paul Williams, *Mahayana Buddhism: The Doctrinal Foundations*, 2nd rev. ed. (London: Routledge, 2008), 15-18.

⁴⁸¹ Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 743. Also see: Yoke Meei Choong, “The ‘Prajñāpāramitā’ in Relation to the Three ‘Samādhis,’” *Journal of Indian Philosophy* 44, no. 4 (September 2016): 727–56.

⁴⁸² A. Verboom, “A Text-Comparative Research on “The Perfection of Discriminating Insight in Eight Thousand Lines, Chapter I” (PhD diss., Leiden University, 1998), 80–81.

⁴⁸³ Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 61.

⁴⁸⁴ Tilmann Vetter, “Once Again on the Origin of Mahāyāna Buddhism,” *Wiener Zeitschrift für die Kunde Südasiens* 45 (2001): 72.

⁴⁸⁵ Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 507.

⁴⁸⁶ Edward Conze, *The Prajñāpāramitā Literature* (s-Gravenhage: Mouton, 1960), 10–11.

⁴⁸⁷ Étienne Lamotte, “Sur la formation du Mahāyāna,” in *Asiatica: Festschrift Friedrich Weller zum 65. Geburtstag*, (Leipzig: Otto Harrassowitz, 1954), 386 [translated to English by author].

⁴⁸⁸ Conze, *The Prajñāpāramitā Literature*, 11.

⁴⁸⁹ Apple, “Prajñāpāramitā,” 2-3; Krishnia Venkata Ramanan, *Nāgārjuna’s Philosophy as Presented in the Mahāprajñāpāramitā-śāstra* (Tokyo: Charles E. Tuttle, 1966); Williams, *Mahayana Buddhism*, 47-49.

As a literary genre, *Prajñāpāramitā* encompasses teachings, techniques and practices, which gradually became associated with invocation rituals and visualisation. Historically, *prajñā*⁴⁹⁰ - cognate with Pāli *paññā*; Tibetan *shes rab*, signified a superior analytical knowledge⁴⁹¹ within early Buddhist *nikāya* traditions, encompassing a comprehensive understanding (*abhisamaya*⁴⁹²) of conditioned existence (*samsāra*⁴⁹³), its governing forces (*karma*), the path to liberation (*mārga*⁴⁹⁴), and the unconditioned reality (*nirvāṇa*). According to Conze's delineation, the *Prajñāpāramitā* literary corpus evolved through four main transformative phases⁴⁹⁵. The compositional history of *Prajñāpāramitā* literature, as conventionally periodised by Conze, is significant for this chapter not as a chronological background but as the record of a series of textual events: moments at which the corpus expanded, contracted, or transformed in ways that reflect shifting soteriological priorities and geographical contexts. Each phase constitutes an irruption in the evental continuum: not merely an accumulation of text but a reconfiguration of what *Prajñāpāramitā* meant, who it was for, and how it was to be used. The first phase, from roughly 100 BCE to 100 CE, marked the creation of the foundational root text, the *Aṣṭasāhasrikā Prajñāpāramitā* (8000 verses)⁴⁹⁶. Its earliest extant version is preserved in the Chinese translation by the Indo-Scythian translator Lokakṣema: the *Daoxing Banruo Jing*, dated to 179 CE⁴⁹⁷. Chinese translations of *Prajñāpāramitā* corpus, like the *Daoxing Banruo Jing* are referred to here not as evidence of East Asian Buddhist developments, which lie

⁴⁹⁰ Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 655.

⁴⁹¹ While some wisdom is non-analytical, such as the meditative equipoise on emptiness, scholastic tradition holds that analytical enquiry is essential to all forms of wisdom, and as rightly noted by Cabezon, the notion that only non-rational or "mystical" gnosis is associated with the feminine, is unfounded (José Ignacio Cabezon, "Mother Wisdom, Father Love: Gender-Based Imagery in Mahayana Buddhist Thought," in *Buddhism, Sexuality, and Gender*, ed. José Ignacio Cabezon (Albany, NY: State University of New York Press, 1992), 195).

⁴⁹² Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 10-11.

⁴⁹³ Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 757-758.

⁴⁹⁴ Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 532.

⁴⁹⁵ Conze, *The Prajñāpāramitā Literature*, 1-25.

⁴⁹⁶ Lewis Lancaster, "The Oldest Mahayana Sutra," *The Eastern Buddhist* 8 (1975): 30-41.

⁴⁹⁷ Paul M. Harrison, "The Earliest Chinese Translations of Mahayana Buddhist Sutras: Some Notes on the Works of Lokakṣema," *Buddhist Studies Review* 10, no. 2 (1993): 135-77; Bhikkhu Anālayo, "Orality and Writing in Early *Prajñāpāramitā*," *Annual Report of The International Research Institute for Advanced Buddhology at Soka University for the Academic Year 2023*, vol. 27 (Tokyo: The International Research Institute for Advanced Buddhology, Soka University, 2024), 77-93; Jan Nattier, *A Guide to the Earliest Chinese Buddhist Translations: Texts from the Eastern Han 東漢 and Three Kingdoms 三國 Periods*, *Bibliotheca Philologica et Philosophica Buddhica X* (Tokyo: The International Research Institute for Advanced Buddhology, Soka University, 2008), Text: T224, 75-76, 79, 80-83, 85, 107, 137-139, 176.

beyond this study’s scope, but as one of the earliest dateable witnesses to the textual form that circulated in South and Central Asia during the formative phase of Prajñāpāramitā’s literary history, before those forms were elaborated into the iconographic and ritual traditions that culminate in the Pāla period.

Some other known early versions include: a first century Gāndhārī manuscript (*prañaparamida*)⁴⁹⁸, and Kuṣāṇa-period fragments from Bamiyan⁴⁹⁹. Over the next two centuries, this text expanded into longer versions forming a textual family known as the “*Larger Prajñāpāramitā*,” including redactions such as the *Aṣṭādaśasāhasrikāprajñāpāramitāsūtra* (18,000 verses), *Pañcaviṃśatisāhasrikāprajñāpāramitāsūtra* (25,000 verses), and the *Śatasāhasrikāprajñāpāramitāsūtra* (100,000 verses)⁵⁰⁰. The next two centuries, up to around 500 CE, marked a phase of contraction, during which the essential teachings of *Prajñāpāramitā* were condensed into shorter *sūtras* and versified summaries. Among the well-known texts from this period are the *Vajracchedikāprajñāpāramitāsūtra*⁵⁰¹ (“*Diamond Sūtra*”), possibly composed in the third century CE, known through nine published editions, and sixth-seventh century CE manuscripts from Bamiyan and northern Pakistan, with Kumārajīva’s (344-409/413 CE⁵⁰²) *Jingang Boruo Bolumi Jing* as the earliest of six Chinese translations⁵⁰³; and the *Prajñāpāramitāhṛdaya* (“*Heart Sūtra*”), cherished by Mahāyāna Buddhists in China, Tibet and Japan, which exists in long and short Sanskrit versions from Japan, Tibet, and Nepal, and in Chinese, Khotanese, Sogdian, Uighur, and Tibetan translations⁵⁰⁴. The most contracted *Prajñāpāramitā* scripture is the

⁴⁹⁸ Seishi Karashima, *A Glossary of Lokakṣema’s Translation of the Aṣṭasāhasrikā Prajñāpāramitā* (Tokyo: International Research Institute for Advanced Buddhology, Soka University, 2010), 13.

⁴⁹⁹ Lore Sander, “Fragments of an Aṣṭasāhasrikā Manuscript from the Kuṣāṇa Period,” in *Buddhist Manuscripts*, vol. 1, ed. Jens Braarvig (Oslo: Hermes Academic Publishing, 2000).

⁵⁰⁰ Stefano Zacchetti, *In Praise of the Light: A Critical Synoptic Edition with an Annotated Translation of Chapters 1–3 of Dharmarakṣa’s Guang zan jing, Being the Earliest Chinese Translation of the Larger Prajñāpāramitā* (Tokyo: The International Research Institute for Advanced Buddhology, Soka University, 2005).

⁵⁰¹ Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 953.

⁵⁰² Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 452-453.

⁵⁰³ Paul Harrison, “Vajracchedikā Prajñāpāramitā: A New English Translation of the Sanskrit Text Based on Two Manuscripts from Greater Gandhāra,” in *Buddhist Manuscripts in the Schøyen Collection*, ed. Jens Braarvig, Paul Harrison, Jens-Uwe Hartmann, Kazunobu Matsuda, and Lore Sander (Oslo: Hermes Publishing, 2006)

⁵⁰⁴ Edward Conze, “Text, Sources, and Bibliography of the Prajñāpāramitā-hṛdaya,” *Journal of the Royal Asiatic Society*, n.s., 80 (1948): 33–51.

*Prajñāpāramitāsarvatathāgatamātā-Ekāksarā*⁵⁰⁵, whose entire doctrinal content is the single letter “A”. Technical commentaries (*śāstra*) were also composed during this period, notable among which are the *Mahāprajñāpāramitāsāstra*⁵⁰⁶, attributed to Nāgārjuna, and preserved in Kumārajīva’s Chinese translation (*Dazhidulun*)⁵⁰⁷, and the *Abhisamayālaṅkāra*⁵⁰⁸ (*Ornament of Realisation*): the most renowned versified summary, attributed to the *bodhisattva* Maitreya⁵⁰⁹. The final phase, spanning 600 to 1200 CE, coincided with the rise of tantric Buddhism, transfiguring *Prajñāpāramitā* into a hypostasised⁵¹⁰ deity. Texts like the *Prajñāpāramitānayasatapañcaśatikā*⁵¹¹ (*Way of the Perfection of Wisdom in 150 Lines*), incorporate tantric terms like *guhya*, and *siddhi*; alongside *Prajñāpāramitānāmāṣṭaśataka* (“The 108 qualities”) and the *Prajñāpāramitāstrotra* (“Hymn to the Goddess”), demonstrate the deification of *Prajñāpāramitā* during this period⁵¹². *Maṇḍala* texts, such as the *Prajñāpāramitāmaṇḍalavidhi*, and *sādhanas* in the *Sādhanamālā* and the Tibetan canon prescribe rituals for visualising her. After this third phase, around 1200 CE, the presence of *Prajñāpāramitā* as scripture or religious practice waned with the institutional disappearance of Buddhism in India⁵¹³. The movement from the foundational Aṣṭasāhasrikā *Prajñāpāramitā* through the longer recensions to the condensed *Heart* and *Diamond Sūtras* represents not linear development but a series of discontinuous elaborations: each one an event in the sense this chapter employs, reshaping the tradition’s soteriological and ritual possibilities in ways that prefigure the iconographic intensifications of the Pāla period.

Unlike the Theravāda, Sarvāstivāda, Dharmaguptaka and other early mainstream Buddhist schools that initially depended on oral dissemination of scriptures, Mahāyāna communities

⁵⁰⁵ Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 658.

⁵⁰⁶ Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 505, 227.

⁵⁰⁷ Cf. Étienne Lamotte, *Le Traité de la Grande Vertu de Sagesse de Nāgārjuna*, vols. 1–5 (Louvain: Institut Orientaliste, 1944–1980).

⁵⁰⁸ Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 11.

⁵⁰⁹ Gareth Sparham, *Abhisamayālaṅkāra with Vṛtti and Ālokā*, 3 vols. (California: Jain Publishing, 2006–2009).

⁵¹⁰ Quine, “Identity, Ostension and Hypostasis,” 625–628.

⁵¹¹ Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 657.

⁵¹² Edward Conze, *Perfection of Wisdom: The Short Prajñāpāramitā Texts* (Totnes, Devon, England: Buddhist Publishing Group, 2002).

⁵¹³ Apple, “Prajñāpāramitā,” 1, 3–6.

emerged alongside specific written works, notably the *Prajñāpāramitāsūtras*, which do not have any clear sign of oral transmission, but rather culminate as outcomes of vigorous literary traditions producing extensive, intricate texts, many now lost⁵¹⁴. Nāgārjuna’s *Mūlamadhyamakakārikā* and the *Saddharmapuṇḍarīkasūtra* demonstrate the complex and often uneasy relationship between *Prajñāpāramitā* discourse and early Mahāyāna identification, where Mahāyāna adherents often ignored or superficially incorporated *Prajñāpāramitā*. The *Kārikās* (ca. 200 CE) valorise *Prajñāpāramitā* as the means to immediate *nirvāṇa* and the cessation of rebirth, yet without advancing a distinct Mahāyāna framework. The *Saddharmapuṇḍarīkasūtra*, by contrast, grounds liberation in a universal *bodhisattva* vocation, resisting *Prajñāpāramitā* in its formative chapters while only sporadically acknowledging it elsewhere. What has been termed the ‘*bodhisattva* movement,’ which later self-identified as Mahāyāna, encountered accusations of illegitimacy and faced significant opposition, as suggested by recurring phrases in its literature branding the rejection of Mahāyāna or its texts as a serious transgression, and labelling efforts to divert *bodhisattvas* from the *Prajñāpāramitā* as “the words of Māra⁵¹⁵.” Later traditions such as the Tiantai (“Terrace of Heaven School”⁵¹⁶) effected a synthesis, but within the *Saddharmapuṇḍarīkasūtra* itself *Prajñāpāramitā* remains peripheral, surviving largely as nominal or liturgical residue rather than doctrinal core⁵¹⁷. Ratnākaraśānti, active in the early eleventh century CE, portrayed the author who performs the redaction of a text like the *AsP* as “the Great Bodhisattva Vajrapāṇi, residing in Aḍakavatī, who trails the Tathāgatas of the Bhadrakalpa to safeguard their corporeal and doctrinal forms⁵¹⁸.” Late Indian Mahāyāna scholasticism recognised two primary exegeses of *Prajñāpāramitā*: Nāgārjuna’s Madhyamaka treatises, which expound the explicit teaching of *śūnyatā* across all

⁵¹⁴ Edward Conze, *Buddhist Thought in India: Three Phases of Buddhist Philosophy* (Ann Arbor: University of Michigan Press, 1967), 199-200; Stephen C. Berkwitz, Juliane Schober, and Claudia Brown, “Introduction: Rethinking Buddhist Manuscript Cultures,” in *Buddhist Manuscript Cultures: Knowledge, Ritual, and Art*, ed. Stephen C. Berkwitz, Juliane Schober, and Claudia Brown (London and New York: Routledge, 2009), 2.

⁵¹⁵ P. S. Jaini, “A Note on ‘Mārabhāṣita’ in the Abhidharmadīpa [235d],” in *Early Buddhism and Abhidharma Thought: In Honor of Doctor Hajime Sakurabe on His Seventy-Seventh Birthday* (Kyoto: Heirakuji Shoten, 2002), 105–6; Peter Skilling, “Redaction, Recitation, and Writing,” in *Buddhist Manuscript Cultures*, 55.

⁵¹⁶ Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 912-913.

⁵¹⁷ Vetter and Anne MacDonald, “Once Again on the Origin of Mahāyāna Buddhism”: 82-87.

⁵¹⁸ Peter Skilling, “Redaction, Recitation, and Writing,” in *Buddhist Manuscript Cultures*, 60.

elements of existence, and the *Abhisamayālaṅkāra* and its commentators⁵¹⁹. Within this scholastic tradition, *Prajñāpāramitā* was used in several senses, as stated in Dignāga’s *Prajñāpāramitārthasaṃgraha*: (a) the supreme wisdom, personified as the Buddha in his *dharmakāya*⁵²⁰ aspect, free from subject-object duality (*grāhyagrāhakavikalpa*⁵²¹); (b) the path to this wisdom; and (c) the *sūtras* that facilitate both. Sometimes a fourth sense was added: self-nature (*svabhāva*⁵²²), which identified *Prajñāpāramitā* with *śūnyatā*, the ultimate nature of all phenomena⁵²³. The *Abhisamayālaṅkāra*⁵²⁴, a key scholastic treatise in Mahāyāna Buddhism, opens with an homage to *Prajñāpāramitā*, honouring wisdom as the “mother” of spiritually accomplished beings: disciples (*śrāvakas*), *bodhisattvas* and Buddhas⁵²⁵. The *Abhisamayālaṅkāra* and its commentators defined this supreme knowledge as comprising three forms of omniscience: *sarvajñatājñāna*⁵²⁶ (omniscient knowledge), *mārgajñatā*⁵²⁷ (knowledge of all the paths), and *sarvākārajñatā*⁵²⁸ (knowledge of all aspects)⁵²⁹. This perfection of wisdom is described as the “source of all good,” urging the practitioner to cultivate a desire for the qualities of the *bhagavati*⁵³⁰. Tibetan commentators have explained that the term ‘mother’ here signifies three aspects: manifestation as scripture (*Prajñāpāramitāsūtras*), the path, and the result (enlightenment)⁵³¹. Sometimes, a fourth aspect, essence (*rang bzhin*) is added, identifying wisdom’s ultimate nature as emptiness. Others have interpreted the “three aspects” as the three primary *Prajñāpāramitāsūtras* underlying the *Abhisamayālaṅkāra*⁵³².

⁵¹⁹ James B. Apple, *Stairway to Nirvāṇa: A Study of the Twenty Saṅghas Based on the Works of Tsong kha pa* (Albany: State University of New York Press, 2008).

⁵²⁰ Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 246.

⁵²¹ Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 326-327.

⁵²² Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 879.

⁵²³ Eugène Obermiller, *The Doctrine of Prajñāpāramitā as Exposed in the Abhisamayālaṅkāra of Maitreya* (Talent, OR: Canon Publications, 1984), 7.

⁵²⁴ Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 11.

⁵²⁵ *Abhisamayālaṅkāra*, ed. R. Tripathi (Sarnath: Central Institute for Higher Tibetan Studies, 1988), 4.

⁵²⁶ Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 779.

⁵²⁷ Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 532.

⁵²⁸ Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 779-780.

⁵²⁹ Eugène Obermiller and Haracarana Singh Sobat, *Prajñāpāramitā in Tibetan Buddhism* (Delhi, India: Classics India Publications, 1988), 58.

⁵³⁰ Haribhadra, *Grel ba don gsal (Sphutārtha)*, Tibetan translation (Sarnath: Pleasure of Elegant Sayings, 1978), 3.

⁵³¹ Edward Conze, *Thirty Years of Buddhist Studies* (Columbia: University of South Carolina Press, 1968), 189.

⁵³² Apple, “Prajñāpāramitā,” 7-8; Cabezón, “Mother Wisdom, Father Love,” 185.

The expansion of the *Prajñāpāramitā* literature into extensive texts comprising thousands of verses stemmed from her veneration as the progenitor of the omniscience that characterises Buddhahood. Worship of *Prajñāpāramitā* is believed to surpass the merit gained from venerating a Buddha, Buddha relics⁵³³, or a reliquary monument (*stūpa*⁵³⁴), as she was considered the true source of a Buddha's omniscience. Early in this discursive tradition, *Prajñāpāramitā* transcended mere doctrinal subtlety, with her manuscripts (*pustaka*) revered and worshipped as sacred objects⁵³⁵. The *AsP* prescribes writing, reading, reciting, contemplating, copying, and distributing the text as acts of profound merit⁵³⁶. Practitioners, termed “sons and daughters of good family,” are urged to enshrine these texts on altars, offering reverence through flowers, incense, powders, umbrellas, banners, bells, and rows of burning lamps⁵³⁷. In this manner, practitioners are instructed to “study it prayerfully and venerate its visible symbol, the scriptural text, through traditional modes of worship, thereby absorbing its subtle energy more fully and directly, as nourishment is absorbed into the bloodstream.⁵³⁸”

2.1.b *Prajñāpāramitā* literature in Kashmir and the northwest

The manuscript cultures of Gilgit and Khotan are significant for this study not as subjects to be analysed comprehensively in their own right, but as relay points in the diasporic transmission

⁵³³ In the context of the *AsP* prescribing the worship of relics, Schopen noted: “... the *Aṣṭasāhasrikā* on two occasions concedes that there are good reasons for worshipping relics, and, in so doing, uses much the same vocabulary as is found in our two inscriptions and in *Aśvaghōṣa's* *Buddhacarita*. It is stated quite explicitly that: the relics of the *Tathāgata* are worshipped because they are saturated with the Perfection of Wisdom: *api tu khalu punar bhagavaṃs tāni tathāgataśarīrāṇi prajñāpāramitāparibhāvitāt pūjāṃ labhyante.*” See: Gregory Schopen, “Burial Ad Sanctos and the Physical Presence of the Buddha in Early Indian Buddhism: A Study in the Archaeology of Religions,” in *Bones, Stones, and Buddhist Monks: Collected Papers on the Archaeology, Epigraphy, and Texts of Monastic Buddhism in India* (Honolulu: University of Hawai'i Press, 1997), 127.

⁵³⁴ Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 859-860.

⁵³⁵ Miranda Shaw, *Buddhist Goddesses of India*, 169-171.

⁵³⁶ Edward Conze, *The Perfection of Wisdom in Eight Thousand Lines & Its Verse Summary* (Bollingen, CA: Four Seasons Foundation; distributed by Book People, Berkeley, 1973), 107-108, 116-117, 266-267; Jens-Uwe Hartmann, “From Words to Books: Indian Buddhist Manuscripts in the First Millennium CE,” in *Buddhist Manuscript Cultures: Knowledge, Ritual, and Art*, ed. Stephen C. Berkwitz, Juliane Schober, and Claudia Brown (London and New York: Routledge, 2009), 103-4.

⁵³⁷ Edward Conze, *The Perfection of Wisdom in Eight Thousand Lines & Its Verse Summary* (Bollingen, CA: Four Seasons Foundation; distributed by Book People, Berkeley, 1973), 299.

⁵³⁸ Apple, “*Prajñāpāramitā*,” 9; Lex Hixon, *Mother of the Buddhas: Meditation on the *Prajñāpāramitā Sūtra** (Wheaton, IL: Quest Books, 1993), 22 (although Hixon's comment was made from a very devotional perspective).

of Prajñāpāramitā's textual and visual traditions: sites where Indian manuscript practices encountered Central Asian devotional contexts and were transformed in ways that anticipate certain features of the Pāla-period book cult.

Buddhist manuscripts, palaeographically dateable between the sixth and ninth centuries CE, were discovered in Gilgit in 1931 and 1938⁵³⁹, "... revealing a literature which was used in a much smaller area and in a shorter period of time." The discoveries were unearthed from the ruins of a presumed *stūpa*⁵⁴⁰ in Naupur (Navapura), nestled in the Karakoram mountains⁵⁴¹. All these manuscripts were written in Sanskrit in two principal variations of the Brāhmī script, written in folios made from birch-bark, a material predominant in the region. One exception in these discoveries was a palm-leaf manuscript of the *Sarvadharmaguṇavyūharājasūtra*⁵⁴². The 'Northern Areas',

⁵³⁹ See: Madhusudan S. Kaul Shastri (Madhusudan Koul), "Report on the Gilgit Excavation in 1938," *The Quarterly Journal of the Mythic Society* 30 (1939): 1–12; Madhusudan Koul, "Report on the Manuscripts Found at Navapura (Gilgit)," in *The Seventh All-India Oriental Conference, Baroda December 1933* (Baroda: Oriental Institute, 1935), 6–10; Karl Jettmar, "The Gilgit Manuscripts: Discovery by Instalments," *Journal of Central Asia* 4, no. 2 (1981): 1–18.

⁵⁴⁰ Oskar von Hinüber in his 2012 study suggested that "*stūpa*" is a misnomer and misidentification in this case, citing the studies of Gérard Fussman, who proposed, based on sparse archaeological records, that the edifice was a modest, possibly two-storey residential tower akin to Gandhāran architectural depictions, inhabited by monks. These monks likely served the local Buddhist community as religious counsellors, ritual practitioners, and healers, as suggested by two medical texts among the Naupur/ Gilgit manuscripts. Hinüber noted that Gregory Schopen's findings complement Fussman's, emphasising the monks' role as scribes and copyists of Buddhist texts. The site is now overlaid by a Muslim cemetery. See: Oskar von Hinüber, "The Saddharmapuṇḍarīkasūtra at Gilgit: Manuscripts, Worshippers, and Artists," *The Journal of Oriental Studies* 22 (2012): 52–67; Giuseppe De Marco, "The Stūpa as a Funerary Monument: New Iconographic Evidence," *East and West*, n.s. 37 (1987): 191–246, esp. 202–3 and fig. 6; Isao Kurita, *Gandhāran Art: A Revised and Enlarged Edition, Ancient Buddhist Art Series*, vol. 1 (Tokyo: Nigensha, 2003), 260f; Gérard Fussman, "Dans quel type de bâtiment furent trouvés les manuscrits de Gilgit?," *Journal Asiatique* 292 (2004): 101–50; Gregory Schopen, "On the Absence of Urtext and Otiose Ācāryas: Books, Buildings, and Lay Buddhist Ritual at Gilgit," in *Écrire et transmettre en Inde classique*, ed. Gérard Colas and Gerdi Gerschheimer, *Études thématiques* 23 (Paris: École française d'Extrême-Orient, 2009), 189–219; Oskar von Hinüber, "The Gilgit Manuscripts: An Ancient Buddhist Library in Modern Research," in *From Birch Bark to Digital Data*, 79–136.

⁵⁴¹ The majority of the 1931 Naupur finds are in the collections of the National Archives of India in New Delhi. The rest of it are divided between: Srinagar (Jammu & Kashmir State Government Libraries and Research Department, Jammu & Kashmir; Acc. nos.: 2689/A, 2689/B, and 2689/C), Ujjain (Scindia Oriental Museum, Scindia Oriental Research Institute, Vikram University; Acc. no. Bauddhāgama no. 4737), London (British Library; Or. 11878A-G), and Karachi (National Museum of Pakistan; Acc. No. Not available; also known as the Tucci collection and contains forty-nine folios of the *Prajñāpāramitāsūtra*). For a comprehensive study of the Naupur finds at the National Archives, New Delhi, see: Noriyuki Kudo, "On and around the Gilgit Manuscripts in the National Archives of India," *The Journal of Oriental Studies* 29 (2019): 168–81. Also see: Lokesh Chandra, "Unpublished Gilgit Fragment of the Prātimokṣasūtra," *Wiener Zeitschrift für die Kunde Südasiens und Archiv für indische Philosophie* 4 (1960): 1–13; Lokesh Chandra, *Gilgit Buddhist Manuscripts (Facsimile Edition)*, *Śata-Piṭaka Series*, vol. 10, 1–10 (Delhi: International Academy of Indian Culture, 1959–74; repr., *Gilgit Buddhist Manuscripts: Revised and Enlarged Compact Facsimile Edition*, Bibliotheca Indo-Buddhica Series 150–52, Delhi: Sri Satguru Publications, 1995); Lokesh Chandra, "A Note on the Gilgit Manuscripts," *Journal of the Oriental Institute* 9, no. 2 (1959): 135–40.

⁵⁴² Jens-Uwe Hartmann, "Studies on the Gilgit Texts: The Sarvadharmaguṇavyūharājasūtra," in *Dharmadūta: Mélanges offerts au Vénérable Thich Huyèn-Vi à l'occasion de son soixante-dixième anniversaire*, ed. Bhikkhu Tampalawela

historically consisted of: the Gilgit Wazarat, colonial Gilgit agency, and Baltistan, now federally administered by Pakistan as Gilgit-Baltistan since 2009. Anciently termed Uttarāpatha, as suggested by inscriptions at Shing Nala and Thalpan, this region⁵⁴³ was known as the “northern region” in Buddhist history⁵⁴⁴. Chinese sources confirm the Mahāsāṃghikas’ role in disseminating Mahāyāna doctrines, including the *Prajñāpāramitāsūtra*. Recent manuscript discoveries indicate that Mahāyāna *sūtra* fragments, in both Kharoṣṭhī and Brāhmī scripts⁵⁴⁵, date from the first to third centuries CE⁵⁴⁶. Geo-climatically, the conditions in the northwestern Indian subcontinent, were akin to those in the Central Asian Tarim basin and conducive to manuscript preservation, which presaged further significant finds. In the 1930s, alongside the Gilgit discovery⁵⁴⁷, and the recovery of Sanskrit

Dhammaratana and Bhikkhu Pāsādika (Paris: Éditions You-Feng, 1997), 67–74; Paul Harrison and Jens-Uwe Hartmann, “Introduction,” in *From Birch Bark to Digital Data: Recent Advances in Buddhist Manuscript Research. Papers Presented at the Conference “Indic Buddhist Manuscripts: The State of the Field,” Stanford, June 15–19, 2009*, ed. Paul Harrison and Jens-Uwe Hartmann, Beiträge zur Kultur- und Geistesgeschichte Asiens 80, Denkschriften der philosophisch-historischen Klasse 460 (Vienna: Österreichische Akademie der Wissenschaften, 2014), x; Oskar von Hinüber, “Die Erforschung der Gilgit-Handschriften,” *Funde buddhistischer Sanskrit-Handschriften, I*, NAWG 1979, Nr. 12: 329–360; Cai Yaoming, “The Buddhist Manuscripts Found at Gilgit and the Research on Buddhism,” *Foxue Yanjiu Zazhi* 13 (Taipei, 2006): 4–126; Oskar von Hinüber, “The Gilgit Manuscripts: An Ancient Buddhist Library in Modern Research,” in *From Birch Bark to Digital Data*, 79–136; Noriyuki Kudo, “Newly Identified Manuscripts in the Gilgit Buddhist Manuscripts: Avadānas and Dhāraṇīs,” *Annual Report of The International Research Institute for Advanced Buddhology at Soka University* 18 (2015): 253–262; Noriyuki Kudo, “Gilgit Saddharmapūṇḍarīkasūtra Manuscript in the British Library, Or.11878B–G,” *Annual Report of The International Research Institute for Advanced Buddhology at Soka University* 18 (2015): 197–214.

⁵⁴³ Gilgit-Baltistan comprises eight districts: Astor, Diamer, Ghizer, Gilgit, and Hunza-Nager (Gilgit Division), and Ghanche, Kharmang, Shigar, and Skardu (Baltistan Division). The Hindukush-Karakoram, consisting of western Kohistan, Nuristan, Chitral, and Shina-Barusho-speaking areas around Gilgit and Diamer (excluding Baltistan and Kashmir), is poetically dubbed Peristan, or “fairies’ land.” Baltistan, historically “Baltī” in Central Asian records and “Little Tibet” (Tibbat-I khurd) in sixteenth-seventeenth century Mughal and Kashmiri annals, is located within the Karakoram along the upper Indus. Formerly part of Jammu and Kashmir until 1948, it includes Kharmang, Khaplu, Shigar, Skardu, and Rondu districts, with Skardu as the administrative hub. Khaplu, the capital of the Balti kingdom, serves as a origin for a route along the Shyok river’s left bank, extending to Ladakh or through the Saltoro valley to the Karakoram pass and onward to Yarkand. A southern pathway linking Baltistan to Ladakh traces the Indus River’s left bank from Kartaksho, one of Kharmang’s five kingdoms, known as Gar-dag-ša. See: Harald Hauptmann, *Lords of the Mountains: Pre-Islamic Heritage along the Upper Indus in Pakistan*, ed. Luca Maria Olivieri (Heidelberg: Heidelberg University Publishing, 2017), 7, 13.

⁵⁴⁴ Hauptmann, *Lords of the Mountains*, 7.

⁵⁴⁵ See: Jens-Uwe Hartmann, “From Words to Books: Indian Buddhist Manuscripts in the First Millennium CE,” in *Buddhist Manuscript Cultures: Knowledge, Ritual, and Art*, ed. Stephen C. Berkwitz, Juliane Schober, and Claudia Brown (London and New York: Routledge, 2009), 97–100.

⁵⁴⁶ Lore Sander, “Dating and Localizing Undated Manuscripts,” in *From Birch Bark to Digital Data*, 174–75.

⁵⁴⁷ The seventh century CE emergence of the Gilgit script, also termed Bamiyan Type II or proto-Śāradā also marked a shift towards greater aesthetic experimentation in scribal practice. Lore Sander noted that evolving stylus technology enabled scribes to employ strokes of varying thickness, in contrast to the uniform stroke width of earlier manuscripts. This innovation, Sander argued, catalysed the development of highly ornamental scripts like Rañjanā in northern India, often rendering them challenging for modern scholars to decipher. See: Lore Sander, *Paläographisches zu den Sanskrithandschriften der Berliner Turfansammlung* (Wiesbaden: Franz Steiner, 1968).

manuscripts in Tibet by Rahul Sankrityayan, several other discoveries were made in the Greater Gandhāra region. In 1932, Sylvain Lévi analysed birch-bark fragments unearthed by Joseph Hackin in 1930 from a Bamiyan valley cave near the smaller colossal Buddha statue⁵⁴⁸. Yet archaeological and textual evidence suggested Kashmir and the northwest as vital hubs for doctrinal innovation and the cultivation of Buddhist cultic traditions, centred in monasteries and *mahāvihāras* like Taxila, a key pilgrimage node for Buddhists from the subcontinent and beyond.

The emergence of painted manuscript covers at Gilgit, incorporating buddhas and *bodhisattvas* with donor figures in a devotional programme, anticipates the more elaborate iconographic integration of text and image that characterises Pāla-period illuminated manuscripts: suggesting that the Pāla book cult did not merge in isolation but as part of a longer diasporic process of ritual and visual elaboration that this chapter maps as an *evental continuum*.

Hackin's discovery hinted at substantial Indian Buddhist textual remains in Afghanistan⁵⁴⁹. Manuscripts from the subcontinent's northern and northwestern regions: south and south-west of the trans-Himalaya, are scarce, with the notable exception of the Gāndhārī

⁵⁴⁸ Sylvain Lévi, "Note sur des manuscrits sanscrits provenant de Bamiyan (Afghanistan), et de Gilgit (Cachemire)," *Journal asiatique* 220 (1932): 1–45.

⁵⁴⁹ Hackin's retrieval in 1930 had already adumbrated the presence of Brāhmī manuscripts in Bamiyan, which was reaffirmed during the 1990s. In 1996, the Norwegian bibliophile Martin Schøyen obtained 108 fragments originating from a Bamiyan grotto, forming the core of a vast collection of thousands of fragments on palm leaf, leather, and birch-bark, but no scrolls. Palaeographically dateable from the second to the eighth or ninth centuries CE, these manuscripts are predominantly in Brāhmī, with several hundred Gāndhārī Kharoṣṭhī fragments on palm leaf. Most Brāhmī texts are in Sanskrit, with many in Buddhist Hybrid Sanskrit. Traded mainly in London, with some via Japan, they reside in at least four collections: the Schøyen (Norway), Hirayama and Hayashidera (Japan) (Kazunobu Matsuda, "Japanese Collections of Buddhist Manuscript Fragments from the Same Region as the Schøyen Collection," in *From Birch Bark to Digital Data*, 165–70), and an anonymous European holding (Jens Braarvig, "The Schøyen Collection," in *From Birch Bark to Digital Data*, 157–64). Hackin's 1930 fragments were held in the Kabul Museum until looted by the Taliban. (Lore Sander, "Dating and Localizing Undated Manuscripts," in *From Birch Bark to Digital Data*, 171–86). The Schøyen collection offers some of the earliest insights into Mahāyāna texts, including the *AsP*, *Bhadrakalpika*, and *Bodhisattvapīṭaka*, the latter two in Kharoṣṭhī script. The discoveries, however, are now eclipsed by the first-century CE Kharoṣṭhī *Prajñāpāramitā*. (Braarvig, "The Schøyen Collection," 160). The *AsP* in the Schøyen collection, inscribed on palm leaf in a later Kuṣāṇa Brāhmī, likely originates from the third century CE. (Sander, "Dating and Localizing Undated Manuscripts," 175). Davidson observed that post-sixth century, in the context of Islam's ascendancy following Yazdgird III's demise in 651 CE at Merv, the Sassanian decline and the subsequent Umayyad efforts to subdue rebellious Iranian populations, Buddhist sites in Bactria and Afghanistan, such as Tepe Sardār, Bāmiyān, Hadda, Balkh, and Kapisa: experienced a modest revival, alongside minor activity in Transoxiana at Ajina Tepe, Kuva, and Ak-Beshim post-sixth century CE, though this resurgence, except at Bāmiyān and Hadda, remained limited in scope and longevity, fading entirely after the ninth century (Davidson, *Indian Esoteric Buddhism*, 81).

*Dharmapada*⁵⁵⁰, which was brought to prominence by John Brough’s 1962 edition⁵⁵¹. Long-standing scholarly conjecture of a manuscript production centre in the Greater Gandhāra region were confirmed sixty years later by the discovery of twenty-nine fragmentary birch-bark scrolls, inscribed with Buddhist doctrinal treatises in Gāndhārī, dating to the early CE, revealing a lost corpus of the oldest extant Buddhist and Indian manuscripts. These were dubbed the “Dead Sea Scrolls of Buddhism” in the media⁵⁵². Birch-bark, abundant in the northwest, served as the primary medium, akin to the *corypha* palm in eastern India and Bengal. These scrolls have been preserved at the British Library since their acquiring from eastern Afghanistan in 1995. Numbering to seventy-seven, they are co-eval with the finds in Qumran (in the West Bank managed by Isarel’s Qumran National Park), and include canonical texts, rich exegesis, and notably Mahāyāna *sūtras*, such as a version of the *AsP*, among the earliest Mahāyāna works⁵⁵³. Fragment 10 at the British Library, is of particular interest. It comprises roughly ninety-four lines, segmented into three parts. While the original text’s structure remains unclear, the extant portion presents “... a continuous exposition of praxis-related topics possibly unified by the term “insight” [prajñā].⁵⁵⁴” In 2013, Falk and Karashima published a critical edition of a Gāndhārī *Prajñāpāramitā*, whose second part parallels the latter half of the fifth *parivarta* of the *AsP*, which challenged earlier assumptions, as Conze omitted separate chapter titles for *parivartas* 3, 4 and 5 in Lokakṣema’s (c. 178-198 CE⁵⁵⁵) translation, a misinterpretation by Sander as evidence of their absence⁵⁵⁶. Several subsequent discoveries, especially those known as the ‘Bajaur’ and ‘Split’ collections, have illuminated the literary landscape of Gandhāra from the first century BCE to the fourth century CE. The ‘Bajaur’ collection of Kharoṣṭhī manuscripts, discovered in 1999

⁵⁵⁰ Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 240.

⁵⁵¹ John Brough, *The Gāndhārī Dharmapada* (Delhi: Motilal Banarsidass, 2000); Also see: Harry Falk, “A New Gāndhārī Dharmapada (Texts from the Split Collection 3),” *Annual Report of The International Research Institute for Advanced Buddhology at Soka University* 18 (2015): 23–62.

⁵⁵² As rightly pointed out by Harrison and Hartmann, this was perhaps an overstated label, nonetheless they sparked public interest and high market values, likely encouraging preservation of additional scrolls in Afghanistan and Pakistan.

⁵⁵³ Harrison and Hartmann, “Introduction,” xv–xvii.

⁵⁵⁴ Collett Cox, “Gāndhārī Kharoṣṭhī Manuscripts: Exegetical Texts,” in *From Birch Bark to Digital Data*, 41.

⁵⁵⁵ Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 480.

⁵⁵⁶ Lore Sander, “Die ‘Schøyen Collection’ und einige Bemerkungen zu der ältesten Aṣṭasāhasrikā-Handschrift,” *Wiener Zeitschrift für die Kunde Südasiens* 44 (2000): 93f; Harry Falk and Seishi Karashima, “A First-Century Prajñāpāramitā Manuscript from Gandhāra,” *ARIRIAB* 15 (2011): 19–61; continued in *ARIRIAB* 16 (2012): 97–169 (*parivarta* 5).

at a Buddhist monastery ruin near Mian Kili, Dir district, opposite the Rud river marking the Dir-Bajaur boundary, was named for its proximity to Bajaur. Situated along a trade route⁵⁵⁷ linking Swat valley to Kunar and beyond to Nangahar and Chitral, the unexcavated monastery lacks secondary documentation⁵⁵⁸. The ‘Split’ collection, which contains the earliest known manuscript of a *Prajñāpāramitā* text, came to light in 2005, when Harry Falk examined several birch-bark rolls in Pakistan, initially dismissed as forgeries by a European manuscript dealer. Vague provenance hints pointed to Mohmand or Bajaur, but the find proved more extensive than these few rolls⁵⁵⁹. The Bajaur collection contains the largest known Gāndhārī Mahāyāna *sūtra* manuscript, akin to early Mahāyāna genres like *Prajñāpāramitā* and Pure Land texts such as the *Akṣobhavyūha*, yet distinct from any identified *sūtra*. Radiocarbon tests on fragments from two scrolls yielded dates of ca. 184-46 BCE (95% probability) and 47-127 CE (81% probability): the earlier date challenging current Kharoṣṭhī chronology, while the latter confirms established views on the script’s evolution⁵⁶⁰. In his 2009 study, Richard Salomon mentioned a private collection of Gāndhārī birch-bark scrolls, accessible for research but of uncertain Afghan origin and previously held in Kabul, which remains largely unrolled and fragmented, obscuring the exact number, though likely exceeding twelve. The related ‘Split’ collection includes a Mahāyāna *Prajñāpāramitā* *śāstram*, radiocarbon-dated to 24-43 CE (14.3% probability) or 47-147 CE (81.1% probability)⁵⁶¹. The Central Asian manuscripts in St. Petersburg’s

⁵⁵⁷ Evidence also reveals a trade-influenced ordination lineage etched along a Gilgit caravan route, where two monks, Satyaśreṣṭhi and Dharmasreṣṭhi, respectively titled “Guildmaster of Truth” and “Guildmaster of the Dharma”, carved their names into stone (Davidson, *Indian Esoteric Buddhism*, 78); See: Helmut Humbach, “Hybrid Sanskrit in the Gilgit Brahmi Inscriptions,” *Studien zur Indologie und Iranistik* 5–6 (1980): 109.

⁵⁵⁸ These manuscripts were entrusted to M. Nasim Khan, Professor and Head of the Department of Archaeology at University of Peshawar. In March-April 2004, during lectures at Peshawar University, Khan showed Harry Falk and Ingo Strauch numerous birch-bark fragments, which prompted the “Bajaur Collection Project” under the “Pakistan-German projects” framework, initiated with preliminary cataloguing by Ingo Strauch. The project was funded by the Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft, the project began in October 2005 at Freie Universität Berlin, led by Harry Falk, with Ingo Strauch and Andrea Schlosser, and supported by M. Nasim Khan and Sohail Khan in Pakistan. A preliminary catalogue with extracts and translations was published online in August 2007, revised in May 2008 following feedback. Collaboration with Peshawar University ceased in 2007, leaving the project independent. See Harry Falk and Ingo Strauch, “The Bajaur and Split Collections of Kharoṣṭhī Manuscripts within the Context of Buddhist Gāndhārī Literature,” in *From Birch Bark to Digital Data*, 52.

⁵⁵⁹ For a comprehensive list of known manuscript collections and single manuscripts discovered from Gandhāra, see Falk and Strauch, “The Bajaur and Split Collections,” 55.

⁵⁶⁰ Falk and Strauch, “The Bajaur and Split Collections of Kharoṣṭhī Manuscripts within the Context of Buddhist Gāndhārī Literature,” 51-75, esp. 51-56.

⁵⁶¹ Richard Salomon, “Gāndhārī Manuscripts in the British Library, Schøyen and Other Collections,” in *From Birch Bark to Digital Data*, 9-10.

Institute of Oriental Manuscripts at the Russian Academy of Sciences, catalogued by Bongard-Levin and Vorobyova-Desyatovskaya, were gathered by diplomats and scholars around the late nineteenth and early twentieth centuries⁵⁶². In 1985, new *Mahāyāna-Mahāparinirvāṇasūtra* and *Saddharmapuṇḍarīka* were published, followed in 1990, which included texts like the *Śārdūlakarṇāvadāna*, *Prātimokṣasūtra*, *Bodharājakumārasūtra*, *Nagaropamasūtra*, *Samādhirāja*, *Vajracchedikā*, and *Buddhanāmasūtra*. Post-Perestroika, Soviet and non-Soviet collaborations produced articles, which featured texts like *Kāśyapaparivarta*, the *Śīlapāramitā*, the *Suvarṇabhāsottama*, and the expansive *Prajñāpāramitā*, alongside a *Vinaya* codex from Bairam-Ali⁵⁶³.

The prominence of the *Prajñāpāramitā* textual tradition in northwestern Kashmir is also evidenced by regional inscriptions invoking *Prajñāpāramitā* and a remarkable copper-alloy piece, donated by Queen Maṅgalaḥṃsikā⁵⁶⁴, depicting the goddess in a standing posture, grasping the text, which, unlike later examples from eastern India, is depicted as opened, identifiable by an inscription

⁵⁶² Most of these fragments, bought from dealers, lack find-spots. Petrovsky fragments mainly stem from the Southern Silk Road, some from Northern Turkestan; Malov fragments use Early or Southern Turkestan Brāhmī; Krotkov fragments are mostly Northern. See: Jens-Uwe Hartmann, "From Words to Books: Indian Buddhist Manuscripts in the First Millennium CE," in *Buddhist Manuscript Cultures: Knowledge, Ritual, and Art*, ed. Stephen C. Berkwitz, Juliane Schober, and Claudia Brown (London and New York: Routledge, 2009), 100–101; Margarita Iosifovna Vorobyova-Desyatovskaya, "The S.E. Malov Collection of Manuscripts in the St. Petersburg Branch of the Institute of Oriental Studies," *Manuscripta Orientalia* 1, no. 2 (October 1995): 29–39; Julia Elikhina, "Some Buddhist Finds from Khotan: Materials in the Collections of the State Hermitage Museum, St. Petersburg," *The Silk Road* 6, no. 1 (2008): 29–37; Irina Fyodorovna Popova, "The Buddhist Manuscripts in the Collection of the St. Petersburg Branch of the Institute of Oriental Studies, Russian Academy of Sciences," *The Journal of Oriental Studies* 17 (2007): 126–36; Shin'ichirō Hori, "From the Kathmandu Valley to the Tarim Basin," in *From Birch Bark to Digital Data*, 260; Olga Lundysheva, Dieter Maue, and Klaus Wille, "Miscellanea in the Brāhmī Script from the Berezovsky and Krotkov Collections (IOM, RAS) with an Appendix: BΦ-4190," *Written Monuments of the Orient* 7, no. 1 (2021): 3–70.

⁵⁶³ Hori, "From the Kathmandu Valley to the Tarim Basin," 259–260.

⁵⁶⁴ See: Oskar von Hinüber, "Four Donations Made by Maṅgalaḥṃsikā, Queen of Palola (Gilgit)," *Annual Report of the International Research Institute for Advanced Buddhology at Soka University* 14 (2011): 3–6. For a comprehensive study of art under the Palola/ Paṭola Śāhis see: John Siudmak, "Bronzes Inscribed with the Names of the Paṭola Śāhis and Related Examples," in *The Hindu-Buddhist Sculpture of Ancient Kashmir and Its Influences*, Handbook of Oriental Studies, Section Two: South Asia, vol. 28, ed. Johannes Bronkhorst (Leiden: Brill, 2013), 311; and Siudmak, *Hindu-Buddhist Sculpture of Ancient Kashmir*, 303–305, Pl. 141; Also see: Lobsang Nyima Laurent, "Lha bla ma Zhi ba 'od's Eighth Century Bronze from Gilgit," *Revue d'Études Tibétaines*, no. 26 (April 2013): 195–214; Another epigraph, noted by von Hinüber on a Rubin collection lion pedestal, dateable to ca. 600–625 CE cites a dedication by Queen Maṅgalaḥṃsikā alongside her spouse, the inaugural Paṭola Śāhi ruler Vajrādityanandi, marking it as the dynasty's earliest dated sculpture. Siudmak noted that though the pedestal lacks a Buddha figure, it embodies Swat's stylistic hallmarks, with two forward-facing lions, their slender, twisted forms flanking an inscribed, tasselled drapery, garlands suspended from the throne's extremities, set upon a double lotus pedestal atop a stylised rocky plinth. Another recently acquired Metropolitan Museum seated Buddha image in the *varadamudrā* (Acc. No. 2011.19), with a lion pedestal bearing a pentagonal cartouche inscribed with Maṅgalaḥṃsikā's dedication, can also be considered a part of this Swat valley corpus. (Siudmak, *Hindu-Buddhist Sculpture of Ancient Kashmir*, 305.)

inside the *pustaka*, in the goddess' left hand⁵⁶⁵ (Plate 88). The deity is depicted subtly inclined with her right hand displaying the *vitarkamudrā*, with a lithe, constricted waist adorned in a close-fitting *uttarīya* and a long floor-length lower garment, compressed at the sides and between the thighs, and ornamented with fine, cascading pleats: together giving the impression of a long tunic, but revealing the abdomen. A pleated shawl-like garment extend past her knees. The goddess has a very serene expression, and is depicted wearing elaborate jewellery: layered necklaces (*kañṭhahāra*): two short ones, and a longer one converging at the chest and forming an expansive loop below, multiple bangles (*keyūra*), serpentine armlets (*valaya*), an ear ornament (*kuṇḍala*) with a floral motif, and another trumpet-shaped earpiece with an *aśoka* flower. The elongated, oval visage features silver-inlaid, almond-shaped eyes and copper-hued lips, crowned by a damaged diadem with a partial *vidyādhara* figure⁵⁶⁶ clutching a garland. The deity stands on a similarly exquisitely executed double lotus pedestal. In his 2013 study, Siudmak suggested that aesthetically, this particular piece is different from Kashmiri examples, however it corresponds closely to a seventh-eighth century CE Swat valley copper-alloy Tārā image at the British Museum (Acc. No. 1939.1-19.1), having similarities in attire, shawl, and the layered lopped necklaces, facial traits and the double-lotus pedestal which Siudmak mentioned are emblematic of Swat's sculptural idiom, concluding that this piece was executed by an artist trained in the Swat valley, but was commissioned or crafted locally⁵⁶⁷. Plate 95 is another example of a copper-alloy Tārā image produced in the Swat valley in the seventh-eighth centuries CE, presently housed at the Ashmolean. Predating eastern Indian manuscripts by approximately five

⁵⁶⁵ Oskar von Hinüber, "Three New Bronzes from Gilgit," Annual Report of the International Research Institute for Advanced Buddhology at Soka University 10 (2007): 39–43; Jinah Kim, "Goddess Prajñāpāramitā and Esoteric Buddhism in Jayavarman VII's Angkor," in *The Creative South: Buddhist and Hindu Art in Mediaeval Maritime Asia*, ed. Andrea Aciri and Peter Sharrock (Singapore: ISEAS–Yusof Ishak Institute, 2022), 175, Fig. 5.10.

⁵⁶⁶ Davidson observed that medieval texts like *Harṣacarita* articulate the aspiration of non-Buddhist *siddhas* to ascend to the *vidyādhara* realm through cemetery rituals believed to bestow attributes such as distinctive hair locks, diadems, pearl necklaces, armlets, belts, hammers, and swords, often depicted iconographically *inter alia*. Buddhist literature, however, predates these texts in referencing *vidyādhara*s, portraying them as manipulators of incantations (*vidyā*) for personal power, as seen in the *Śārdūlakarṇāvadāna*, where a *mātāṅgī* sorceress (*mahāvīdyādhārī*) ensnares Ānanda with a lie spell, or in the *Ratnaguṇasamcayagāthā*, which likens a *bodhisattva*'s extraordinary abilities to those of a *vidyādhara*, navigating emptiness or performing feats like flight or out-of-season blooming, situating such figures alongside *siddhas*, *ṛṣis*, and physicians, in celestial and marginal terrestrial locales like skies, mountains, caves, cemeteries, and societal peripheries (Davidson, *Indian Esoteric Buddhism*, 194-195).

⁵⁶⁷ Siudmak, *Hindu-Buddhist Sculpture of Ancient Kashmir*, 303-305.

centuries, this artefact suggests the expansive geographic scope of Prajñāpāramitā. In the ninth and tenth centuries CE, Buddhism persisted in segments of the Upper Indus Valley, notably Puniā and Gilgit, as evidenced by the later tenth-century CE “Saka itinerary,” which records active Buddhist monasteries in Baubura (Bubur) and Gidagitti (Gilgit)⁵⁶⁸.

In Gandhāran Buddhism, the ritual burial of manuscripts is documented; however, evidence of textual entombment extends beyond Gandhāra, as manuscripts and fragments are frequently interred within *stūpas*, as exemplified by the Gilgit manuscripts. Within the Jetavanarama monastic precinct in Anurādhapura, a segment of the *Pañcaviṃśatisāhasrikā Prajñāpāramitā*, etched on golden folia, was excavated from an interred vessel⁵⁶⁹. It has been suggested that this practice in Gandhāra may trace its origins to the Buddhist heartland in eastern India:

For, if the archaeological record of early Buddhism is spotty in Gāndhāra, it is far more so in the Indian heartland, where, due to rigours of the monsoon climate, nothing at all survives of early manuscript material. Therefore, there is no reason to assume that scripture interment was uniquely Gāndhāran, and in fact, this practice, like so much of Gāndhāran Buddhism, probably had roots and predecessors in India proper⁵⁷⁰.

The Senior manuscripts⁵⁷¹, also commissioned for ritual interment, within a *stūpa*, functioned as *dharma*-relics; unlike bodily or contact relics deriving potency from physical association with the Buddha, these *dharma*-relics, embodying his teachings, gain sanctity from the principle that

⁵⁶⁸ Hauptmann, *Lords of the Mountains*, 275-279.

⁵⁶⁹ Oskar von Hinüber, “Sieben Goldblätter einer Pañcaviṃśatisāhasrikā Prajñāpāramitā aus Anurādhapura,” *Nachrichten der Akademie der Wissenschaften in Göttingen, I. Philologisch-Historische Klasse* (1983), no. 7: 189–207; Bhikkhu Ñāṇatusita, “Pali Manuscripts of Sri Lanka,” in *From Birch Bark to Digital Data*, 367. Certain codices were ritually deposited within *stūpas*. In the nineteenth century, a *Tipiṭaka* corpus: including *Vinayapiṭaka*, *Abhidhammapiṭaka*, *Dīghanikāya*, and other texts on silver folia and on palm leaves, alongside the *Satipaṭṭhāna-sutta* and other *sūtras* on 37 golden plates, a *Jātaka* exegesis on 900 copper sheets, and gem-adorned silver and gold book boards were consecrated in the Hanguranketa Vihāra *stūpa*. Additionally, 91 copper plates bearing the *PvP*, dated to the 8th–9th centuries, were excavated from Mihintale’s Indikatusāya *stūpa*. (Bhikkhu Ñāṇatusita, “Pali Manuscripts of Sri Lanka,” 368).

⁵⁷⁰ Richard Salomon, “Why Did the Gandhāran Buddhists Bury Their Manuscripts?” in *Buddhist Manuscript Cultures: Knowledge, Ritual, and Art*, ed. Stephen C. Berkwitz, Juliane Schober, and Claudia Brown (London and New York: Routledge, 2009), 32.

⁵⁷¹ “Introduction: The Senior Manuscripts,” in *Four Gāndhārī Saṃyuktāgama Sūtras: Senior Kharoṣṭhī Fragment 5, Gandhāran Buddhist Texts 4* (Seattle: University of Washington Press, 2003), 3–25; Richard Salomon, “The Senior Manuscripts: Another Collection of Gandhāran Buddhist Scrolls,” *Journal of the American Oriental Society* 123 (2003): 73–92.

perceiving the *dharmā* equates to encountering the Buddha⁵⁷². In the context of the equation of the Buddha's bodily relics with the *Prajñāpāramitā*, Schopen pointed out an example from the *AsP* itself:

A particularly interesting example comes from the *Aṣṭasāhasrikāprajñāpāramitā*, which some have associated—though not necessarily convincingly—with South India and the area around Nāgārjunikoṇḍa. Here we find it said that:

itaḥ prajñāpāramitāto nirjatāni tāni tathāgataśārīrāṇi pūjāṃ labhante yad uta prajñāpāramitāparibhāvitāt.

These relics of the Tathāgata, being born from the Perfection of Wisdom, receive worship—that is to say from the fact that they are invigorated by the Perfection of Wisdom.

Here, *paribhāvita* is glossed by *nirjāta*, “to be born, given life.” Elsewhere in the text it is, for example, the “all knowledge” of the Buddha that is said to be “born from the Perfection of Wisdom” (*prajñāpāramitānirjatā hi . . . tathāgatānām arhatāṃ samyaksambuddhānām sarvajñatā*). What gives life to and animates the “all knowledge” of the Buddha, gives life to and animates the relic⁵⁷³.

It is important to distinguish between two distinct functions of manuscript interment within stūpas: when texts were deposited at the time of the stūpa's construction, they served as *dharmā*-relics (*dharmakāya-dhātu*), constituting the consecrating presence within the reliquary structure: the textual body of the Buddha installed in place of, or alongside, corporeal relics; when manuscripts were interred within an already-existing stūpa at a later date, the purpose was not merit accumulation but the ritually appropriate disposal of sacred scriptures that had deteriorated or fallen out of use,

⁵⁷² As noted by Kim in her 2013 publication, within the South Asian Buddhist book cult, texts strive to preserve their status as venerated artefacts, their creation and reverence mirroring the traditions of *stūpas* and icons, likely to avoid diminishing into mere *dharmā*-relics given the emphasis on textual materiality, materialising into Tibetan customs of encasing manuscripts within *stūpas* or images. A book's cultic strength may surpass other sacred items, embodying the paradox of an absent presence through the juxtaposition of visible and invisible elements, its fluid spatial structure, defined by movable palm-leaf folios, offering a less rigid sense of interior and exterior compared to the fixed confines of *stūpas* or images (Kim, *Receptacle of the Sacred*, 40).

⁵⁷³ Gregory Schopen, “On the Buddha and His Bones: The Conception of a Relic in the Inscriptions from Nāgārjunikoṇḍa,” in *Bones, Stones, and Buddhist Monks: Collected Papers on the Archaeology, Epigraphy, and Texts of Monastic Buddhism in India* (Honolulu: University of Hawai'i Press, 1997), 155.

interment being one of two sanctioned methods of retiring such texts, the other being consignment to fire⁵⁷⁴.

As rightly noted by Mark Allon, critical to understanding manuscripts is identifying their regional origin, precise find location, associated structure, its place within the monastery, burial method, accompanying artefacts, monastery size and status, and the producing community's social status. A text prepared for ritual burial may differ from one crafted for monastic study, sometimes with omitted sections deemed representative, or wording adjusted to fit specific birch bark dimensions⁵⁷⁵.

2.1.c *Prajñāpāramitā* literature in Central Asia and China

In the historiography of modern Buddhist studies drawing upon textual sources, Central Asia occupies a prominent place, primarily because of the immense significance of the discovery of important texts and other cultural artefacts relating to the history of Buddhism in Central Asia in the late ninth and early twentieth centuries CE, distributed over a wide geographical region extending “from Tumšūq in the west to Dunhuang in the east⁵⁷⁶, and from Turfan in the north to Khotan in the south.” Prior to these discoveries, the study of Buddhist texts was primarily restricted to manuscripts from two surviving Buddhist traditions: Vajrayāna Buddhism in Nepal, and Theravāda Buddhism of

⁵⁷⁴ I am thankful to Prof. Christian Luczanits for pointing this out.

⁵⁷⁵ Mark Allon, “The Senior Kharoṣṭhī Manuscripts,” in *From Birch Bark to Digital Data*, 23, 27.

⁵⁷⁶ Alongside the rich artistic corpus of murals, several textual and varied cultural artefacts discovered at Dunhuang, it is also known to be the source of the earliest known dated printed book, a Chinese scroll from 868 CE preserving the *Vajracchedikā Prajñāpāramitā*, was also discovered in Dunhuang and is currently preserved in the British Library, London (Or.8210/P.2), erroneously mentioned in Harrison and Hartmann, “Introduction,” ix, as being present at the British Museum. Also see: Zeng Zeng, Shouqian Sun, Ting Li, Jing Yin, Yimin Shen, and Qunying Huang, “Exploring the Topic Evolution of Dunhuang Murals through Image Classification,” *Journal of Information Science* 50, no. 1 (2022): 35–52. For different known versions of *Prajñāpāramitā* manuscripts recovered from Dunhuang, see: International Dunhuang Programme, International Dunhuang Project: Manuscripts (The British Library), accessed August 5, 2025, <https://idp.bl.uk/manuscripts/>; Kenta Suzuki and Jundo Nagashima, “The Dunhuang Manuscript of the Larger *Prajñāpāramitā*,” in *Buddhist Manuscripts from Central Asia: The British Library Sanskrit Fragments (BLSF)*, vol. 1, ed. Seishi Karashima and Klaus Wille (Tokyo: The International Research Institute for Advanced Buddhology, Soka University, 2006), 593–822; Noriyuki Kudo, “A Sanskrit Fragment of the Larger *Prajñāpāramitā* in the Stein Collection,” in *BLSF*, vol. 1, 173–176; Kenta Suzuki, “A Sanskrit Fragment of the *Prajñāpāramitāstotra* in the Stein Collection,” in *BLSF*, vol. 1, 261–262; Gertraud Taenzer, “Śatasāhasrikā-*Prajñāpāramitā* Sūtras Discovered at Dunhuang: The Scriptorium at Thang kar and Related Aspects. A Preliminary Investigation,” *Revue d'Études Tibétaines*, no. 60 (August 2021): 239–81; James B. Apple, “A Late Old Tibetan Version of the Heart Sūtra Preserved in Dunhuang IOL Tib J 751,” *Annual Report of The International Research Institute for Advanced Buddhology at Soka University for the Academic Year 2023*, vol. 27 (Tokyo: The International Research Institute for Advanced Buddhology, Soka University, 2024), 117–33.

Sri Lanka and Southeast Asia. These manuscripts were all written in Buddhist Sanskrit in different types of Indian and Central Asian Brāhmī, with the exception of the well-known *Dharmapada* manuscript from Khotan which was written in Gāndhārī language in the Kharoṣṭhī script. However some of the oldest manuscripts found in Central Asia were written on palm-leaf, a material not available in the region, suggesting that these manuscripts were likely produced in India and imported to Central Asia. The manuscript corpus of Central Asia spans a long temporal scale, from around the second century CE, and flourishing until the eleventh century, and perhaps continuing till the twelfth and thirteenth centuries CE⁵⁷⁷. The historiography of Buddhism in Central Asia, constitutes a profound lacuna in our comprehension of the tradition's broader metamorphosis, as vast swaths of data have vanished, or perchance never materialised in textual or iconography forms, hindering any comprehensive depiction of Buddhism's propagation and transmutation in this pivotal corridor. Scholars endeavouring to synthesise a coherent chronicle of Central Asian Buddhism have repeatedly had to confront the paucity of evidentiary material, rendering a holistic reconstruction impossible and elusive⁵⁷⁸. The dominant hypothesis on Buddhism's spread in Central Asia, originating with E. Waldschmidt's 1932 observation, asserts that the Chinese *Dīrghāgama*⁵⁷⁹, translated by Dharmaguptaka⁵⁸⁰ monk Buddhayaśas (from Kashmir, ca. early fifth century⁵⁸¹), employs a Prākṛit, later identified by H.W. Bailey in 1946 as Gāndhārī, linked to Kharoṣṭhī inscriptions, rather than Sanskrit: which suggests that in the Tarim basin, early Buddhism was affiliated to the Dharmaguptaka school⁵⁸², which was later overtaken by Sanskrit Sarvāstivāda⁵⁸³ (like in Kučā, Agni), or Mahāyāna

⁵⁷⁷ Harrison and Hartmann, "Introduction," x.

⁵⁷⁸ John Brough, "Comments on Third-Century Shan-shan and the History of Buddhism," *Bulletin of the School of Oriental and African Studies* 28 (1965): 582; Jan Nattier, "Church Language and Vernacular Language in Central Asian Buddhism," *Numen* 36, no. 2 (1989): 195.

⁵⁷⁹ Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 261.

⁵⁸⁰ Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 245-246.

⁵⁸¹ Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 157.

⁵⁸² Initial "esoteric" canons, primarily comprising of compilations of spells (*mantra-* or *dhāraṇī-piṭaka*), with attributions to early schools such as the Mahāsāṃghikas and Dharmaguptakas. The early canon of spells was closely related to the region spanning Kashmir to Swat, the latter also known as Uḍḍiyāna or Oḍiyāna, with surviving early texts reflecting the use of birchbark manuscripts prevalent in these locales. The *Abhidharmakośabhāṣya* confirms this regional association, referring to two spell types: *gāndhārī vidyā* from Gandhāra and *īkṣaṇikā vidyā*, linked to visionary foresight (Davidson, *Indian Esoteric Buddhism*, 144-145).

⁵⁸³ Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 780-781.

(like in Khotan)⁵⁸⁴. Davidson poignantly noted that the profound transformations in global trade patterns, spurred by the concurrent emergence of Islam and the Tang dynasty in China, have received scant attention from scholars of Indian Buddhism, possibly due to the unrecognised yet significant role of Sassanian governance from Gandhāra to Transoxiana, which fostered Buddhist mercantile activities until being disrupted by Hephthalite incursions the fifth to sixth centuries CE⁵⁸⁵.

The *Prajñāpāramitāhṛdayasūtra*, also known as the *Heart Sūtra*⁵⁸⁶, is one of the most popular Buddhist *sūtras* in China, East Asia, and around the world, revered by both the laity and the clergy as a succinct encapsulation of Mahāyāna doctrines, and as a “*dharma* of immense supernatural power.” It has been the subject of diverse commentaries from Yogācāra, Madhyamaka, and Ch’an perspectives. In her 1992 study, Jan Nattier argued, resonating John McRae’s earlier, albeit figurative observation on the *Prajñāpāramitāhṛdayasūtra*’s Chinese origins⁵⁸⁷, and grounding in philological analysis: that the text’s lineage flows uniquely from the Sanskrit *Large Sūtra* to Kumārajīva’s Chinese *Large Sūtra*, then to Xuanzang’s popularised Chinese *Prajñāpāramitāhṛdayasūtra*, and finally to the Sanskrit *Prajñāpāramitāhṛdayasūtra*. A secondary claim, not essential to the Chinese-to-Sanskrit hypotheses, suggests Xuanzang’s role in conveying the text to India and possibly translating it, supported by his documented recitation en route, though the core assertion of the *Prajñāpāramitāhṛdayasūtra*’s Sanskrit derivation from Chinese stands independently. It gained prominence in China prior to Indian commentarial focus, remaining a cornerstone of East Asian Buddhism since at least the seventh century CE. Nattier’s observation suggests a *reverse diaspora* in the context of the *Prajñāpāramitāhṛdayasūtra* and its deep integration into Chinese Buddhist

⁵⁸⁴ Xavier Tremblay, “The Spread of Buddhism in Serindia—Buddhism among Iranians, Tocharians and Turks before the 13th Century,” in *The Spread of Buddhism*, ed. Ann Heirman and Stephan Peter Bumbacher (Leiden and Boston: Brill, 2007), 99-101; For a comprehensive data on the manuscripts, see: Meshezhnikov, Artiom, and Safarali Shomakhmadov. “The Updated Data on Sanskrit Manuscripts of the Serindia Collection (IOM, RAS): Perspectives of the Study.” *Written Monuments of the Orient* 6, no. 2 (February 2021): 22–42.

⁵⁸⁵ Davidson, *Indian Esoteric Buddhism*, 81.

⁵⁸⁶ Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 657.

⁵⁸⁷ John R. McRae, “Ch’an Commentaries on the Heart Sūtra: Preliminary Inferences on the Permutation of Chinese Buddhism,” *Journal of the International Association of Buddhist Studies* 11, no. 2 (1988): 87.

traditions⁵⁸⁸. This phenomenon of reverse cultural transmission from China to South Asia has been further substantiated in the material and visual domain by Kim, who demonstrated through the study of China-inspired images in medieval South Asian Buddhist contexts that the circulation of Buddhist artistic and iconographic forms was not unidirectional but involved significant flows from China back into the South Asian Buddhist milieu, which complicates conventional *diffusionist* models of Buddhist transmission⁵⁸⁹.

Studies on the beginnings of Buddhism in Khotan⁵⁹⁰, an “Indo-European oasis kingdom at the southern edge of the Taklamakhan Desert in Central Asia ... which served as a major centre of Buddhism in Central Asia and an important conduit for the transmission of Buddhism from India to China,” which was colonised first by Indians, when Kunāla, the eldest son of King Aśoka, is said to have left the northwest Indian city and capital of Gandhāra, Taksaśilā (Taxila⁵⁹¹) for Khotan in the third century BCE” and “through about the tenth century CE ... a bastion of Indian urban culture in the Tarim Basin,” where “Gāndhārī Prakrit (in the Kharosthī script) in much of its written communications until the relatively late rise in the use of indigenous vernacular Khotanese (probably sometime after the sixth century CE)⁵⁹²”— are however primarily based on legendary accounts. Sparse contemporary Chinese records indicate that Khotan adhered to Mazdeism (or Zoroastrianism) during General Ban Chao’s (32-102 CE⁵⁹³) visit in 73 CE. However, Indian cultural influence has

⁵⁸⁸ Jan Nattier, “The Heart Sūtra: A Chinese Apocryphal Text?” *Journal of the International Association of Buddhist Studies* 15 (1992): 153–223. Also see: Dan Lusthaus, “The Heart Sūtra in Chinese Yogācāra: Some Comparative Comments on the Heart Sūtra Commentaries of Wōnch’ūk and K’uei-chi,” *International Journal of Buddhist Thought & Culture* 3 (2003): 59–103; Minoru Kiyota, *Mahayana Buddhist Meditation: Theory and Practice* (Honolulu: University of Hawai’i Press, 1978), esp. Francis H. Cook, “Fa-tsang’s Brief Commentary on the Prajñāpāramitā-hṛdaya-sūtra,” 167–206; Donald S. Lopez Jr., *The Heart Sūtra Explained: Indian and Tibetan Commentaries* (Albany: State University of New York Press, 1988); Donald S. Lopez Jr., *Elaborations on Emptiness: Uses of the Heart Sūtra* (Princeton, NJ: Princeton University Press, 1996); John McRae, “Heart Sutra,” in *Encyclopedia of Buddhism*, ed. Robert E. Buswell Jr. (New York: Macmillan, 2004); Heng-Ching Shih and Dan Lusthaus, *A Comprehensive Commentary on the Heart Sutra (Prajñāpāramitā-hṛdaya-sūtra)* (Berkeley: Numata Center for Buddhist Translation & Research, 2006); Kazuki Tanahashi, *The Heart Sutra: A Comprehensive Guide to the Classic of Mahayana Buddhism* (Boston: Shambhala Publications, 2014).

⁵⁸⁹ Jinah Kim, “China in Medieval Indian Imagination: ‘China’-Inspired Images in Medieval South Asia,” *International Journal of Asian Studies* 19, no. 2 (July 2022): 187-214, esp. 189-91, 199-210.

⁵⁹⁰ “Since the mid-eighteenth century, during the Qing dynasty (1644–1912), Khotan has been under the political control of China and currently is located in the Uighur Autonomous Region of Xinjiang province.” (Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 434)

⁵⁹¹ Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 892.

⁵⁹² Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 433-434.

⁵⁹³ Rafe de Crespigny, *A Biographical Dictionary of Later Han to the Three Kingdoms (23–220 AD)* (Leiden: Brill, 2007), 4–5.

been suggested to have aerated Khotan earlier, predating its presence in Kučā⁵⁹⁴ by the second century CE. By 260 CE, the Chinese monk Zhu Shixing⁵⁹⁵ retrieved the Sanskrit *Prajñāpāramitā* in 25,000 verses from Khotan, despite resistance from local Hīnayānists⁵⁹⁶ who deemed it heterodox; he subsequently dispatched it to Luoyang⁵⁹⁷, where it was translated by the Khotanese monk Mokṣala⁵⁹⁸. In 296 CE, the Khotanese monk Gautamitra brought another copy to Chang’an. While Hīnayānism dominated Khotanese monasticism during Zhu Shixing’s era, the Chinese pilgrim Faxian (337-422 CE⁵⁹⁹) noted in 401 CE that Khotan’s populace had largely embraced Buddhism, predominantly Mahāyāna⁶⁰⁰. In 2013, the Institute of Oriental Manuscripts (Russian Academy of Sciences), Soka Gakkai, and the Institute of Oriental Philosophy (Hachioji, Tokyo) co-published a facsimile edition of *Saddharmapuṇḍarīkasūtra* manuscripts held in St. Petersburg, including the extensive “Khotan Manuscript” (formerly “Kashgar Manuscript”). Subsequently, in Hachioji, a British Library fragment published by P. O. Skjærvø was identified as the missing left half of the manuscript’s final folio⁶⁰¹. Numerous Buddhist manuscripts in Sanskrit and Khotanese, unearthed at Khādalik⁶⁰², predominantly

⁵⁹⁴ Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 449-450.

⁵⁹⁵ Tanya Storch, “Fei Changfang’s Lidai sanbao ji and Its Role in the Formation of the Chinese Buddhist Canon,” in *Spreading Buddha’s Word in East Asia: The Formation and Transformation of the Chinese Buddhist Canon*, ed. Jiang Wu and Lucille Chia (New York: Columbia University Press, 2016), 112.

⁵⁹⁶ Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 351.

⁵⁹⁷ Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 484.

⁵⁹⁸ Prods Oktor Skjærvø, “Khotan, An Early Center of Buddhism in Chinese Turkestan,” in *Collection of Essays 1993: Buddhism across Boundaries—Chinese Buddhism and the Western Regions*, ed. John McRae and Jan Nattier (Sanchung [Taipei]: Foguangshan Foundation for Buddhist & Culture Education, 1999), 277.

⁵⁹⁹ Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 297.

⁶⁰⁰ Tremblay, “The Spread of Buddhism in Serindia,” 100.

⁶⁰¹ Oskar von Hinüber, “Three Saddharmapuṇḍarīkasūtra Manuscripts from Khotan and Their Donors,” *Annual Report of The International Research Institute for Advanced Buddhology at Soka University* 18 (2015): 215–34; Lokesh Chandra, *Saddharma-Puṇḍarīka-Sūtra: Kashgar Manuscript*, with a foreword by Heinz Bechert (Tokyo, 1977); Oskar von Hinüber, “A Saddharmapuṇḍarīkasūtra Manuscript from Khotan: The Gift of a Pious Family,” in *Saddharmapuṇḍarīkasūtram. Sanskrit Lotus Sutra Manuscripts from the Institute of Oriental Manuscripts of the Russian Academy of Sciences (SI P/5, etc.). Facsimile Edition (Lotus Sutra Manuscript Series 13)* (Hachioji: Soka Gakkai, Institute of Oriental Philosophy, 2013), CXXIII–CXL; Oskar von Hinüber, “A Saddharmapuṇḍarīkasūtra Manuscript from Khotan: The Gift of a Pious Family,” *The Journal of Oriental Studies* 24 (2014): 134–56 = idem, “Hōtan shutsudo bonbun Hokekyō shahon – Hōtan no tokushin ikka karano okurimono,” *Tōyō Gakujutsu Kenkyū (The Journal of Oriental Studies)* 52, no. 2 (2013): 223(30)–198(55); Huaiyu Chen, “Newly Identified Khotanese Fragments in the British Library and Their Chinese Parallels,” *Journal of the Royal Asiatic Society* 22 (2012): 265–79.

⁶⁰² Khādalik, ranks among the most thoroughly documented archaeological sites in the Khotan region, owing to the detailed account provided by Marc Aurel Stein (1862–1943), during his excavations from September to October 1907. See: Marc A. Stein, *Serindia: Detailed Report of Explorations in Central Asia and Westernmost China*, vol. 1 (London: Oxford University Press, 1921), 154–63; Marc A. Stein, *Ruins of Desert Cathay: Personal Narrative of Explorations in Central Asia and Westernmost China* (London: Macmillan & Co., 1912), 236–46.

feature Mahāyāna texts⁶⁰³, alongside non-Mahāyāna works such as *belle-lettres*, narrative collections, and mainstream canonical texts⁶⁰⁴, reflecting the eclectic literary tastes of the local monastic community. Only the Stein collection manuscripts, archaeologically excavated, bear site marks, but most others lack precise provenance. The Stein collection primarily derives from two major ‘shrines,’ likely used for votive offerings, with additional manuscripts found near the entrances of two dilapidated square cellae, possibly also votive in nature due to decorative similarities with the shrines. Khādalik’s cultic character is further suggested by frescoed walls and painted panels depicting an Indo-Buddhist pantheon, including buddhas (e.g., Vairocana), *bodhisattvas* (e.g., Avalokiteśvara, Kṣitigarbha), guardian deities (e.g., Vaiśravaṇa), non-Buddhist Indian deities (e.g., Maheśvara, Gaṇeśa) etc⁶⁰⁵. This diverse iconography suggests a reciprocal ritual engagement between the pantheon and Khotan’s Buddhist donors, lay and monastic, sustaining Khādalik as a regional worship centre through the seventh-eighth centuries CE, until its probable abandonment by the early ninth century CE under Tibetan dominion⁶⁰⁶. In her 1989 study, Jan Nattier observed that Central Asian Buddhist literature was disseminated solely in Indian languages until the early sixth century CE, and that the ensuing proliferation of vernacular Buddhist texts in the eastern sections of this region, but not the western, likely stemmed from Chinese influence; suggesting that the linguistic strategies of Buddhist practitioners were far from uniform, but adapted to local cultural milieus, and while China

⁶⁰³ Klaus Wille, “Survey of the Identified Sanskrit Manuscripts in the Hoernle, Stein, and Skrine Collections of the British Library (London),” in *From Birch Bark to Digital Data*, 226-227.

⁶⁰⁴ Louis de la Vallée Poussin, “Documents sanscrits de la seconde collection M.A. Stein,” *Journal of the Royal Asiatic Society* (1911): 770–72, 1064–67; Louis de la Vallée Poussin, “Documents sanscrits de la seconde collection M.A. Stein,” *Journal of the Royal Asiatic Society* (1913): 569–80; Klaus Wille, “Some Recently Identified Sanskrit Fragments from the Stein and Hoernle Collections in the British Library, London,” *Annual Report of the International Research Institute for Advanced Buddhism at Soka University* 8 (2005): 62–68; Seishi Karashima, “The Sanskrit Fragments Or.15010 in the Hoernle Collection,” in *The British Library Sanskrit Fragments Volume II.1: Buddhist Manuscripts from Central Asia*, ed. Seishi Karashima et al. (Tōkyō: International Research Institute for Advanced Buddhism at Soka University, 2009), 494–95; Klaus Wille, “Survey of the Identified Sanskrit Manuscripts in the Hoernle, Stein, and Skrine Collections of the British Library (London),” in *From Birch Bark to Digital Data*, 226; Diego Loukota Sanclemente, “The Goods that Cannot Be Stolen: Mercantile Faith in Kumāralāta’s Garland of Examples Adorned by Poetic Fancy” (PhD diss., University of California Los Angeles, 2019), 72–73; Klaus Wille, “Some Recently Identified Sanskrit Fragments from the Stein and Hoernle Collections in the British Library, London (2),” in *The British Library Sanskrit Fragments Volume I: Buddhist Manuscripts from Central Asia*, ed. Seishi Karashima et al. (Tokyo: International Research Institute for Advanced Buddhism, 2006), 49.

⁶⁰⁵ Joanna Williams, “Iconography of Khotanese Painting,” *East and West* 23 (1973): 109–54.

⁶⁰⁶ Ruixuan Chen, “Inside Out: The Social Life of a Pair of Inscribed Book Covers from Ancient Khotan,” *BuddhistRoad Paper* 6.3 (2021), 8-11.

initially functioned as a passive recipient of Central Asian Buddhist transmissions in the early first millennium, it assumed a more pronounced role from the sixth century CE onwards. Nattier concluded that by the eighth century CE, for certain Central Asian communities, particularly the Sogdians and Uighurs, the epicentre of Buddhist inspiration had shifted from India to China, a situation which continued until Islam's eventual arrival⁶⁰⁷.

As suggested by Ruixuan Chen, manuscript covers in seventh-eighth century CE Khotan and Gilgit served as vital ritual components, notably for related *dhāraṇī* practices, though evidence for a Buddhist book cult in first-millennium CE in the Indian subcontinent remains scant, concluding that fully developed book worship akin to modern Nepalese practices was unlikely⁶⁰⁸. Three Gilgit manuscripts have been found between wooden covers, the latter featuring paintings of buddhas and *bodhisattvas* with kneeling donors: two vertically painted cover pairs, tentatively dated to the seventh-eighth centuries CE under the Palola Śāhi rulers, and a third with a horizontal composition, studied by Deborah Klimburg-Salter in 1999 and 2016⁶⁰⁹. In Gilgit and Khotan, which were allied as Chinese vassals against the Tibetan empire's late eighth century CE expansion, shared Buddhist manuscript cultures which flourished via Karakoram corridor exchanges. Khotanese painted tablets from sites like Khādalik, dated to the sixth-eighth centuries CE, mirror or predate Gilgit's covers⁶¹⁰. In Mongolia, based on Korean accounts, it has been confirmed that manuscript production was already prevalent on a large scale in the thirteenth century CE. There are several paper manuscripts of *Prajñāpāramitāsūtra* produced in Mongolia in the sixteenth-seventeenth centuries CE, which suggest

⁶⁰⁷ Jan Nattier, "Church Language and Vernacular Language in Central Asian Buddhism": 212.

⁶⁰⁸ Nonetheless, as noted by Chen, certain elements such as inner cover surfaces, predate later innovations (Chen, "Inside Out: The Social Life of a Pair of Inscribed Book Covers," 17-20). Also see: Losty, *The Art of the Book in India*, 23; Kim, *Receptacle of the Sacred*, 63-64; Martin Lerner, *The Flame and the Lotus: Indian and Southeast Asian Art from the Kronos Collections* (New York: The Metropolitan Museum of Art, 1984), 87; Jens-Uwe Hartmann, "From Words to Books: Indian Buddhist Manuscripts in the First Millennium CE," in *Buddhist Manuscript Cultures: Knowledge, Ritual, and Art*, ed. Stephen C. Berkwitz (London and New York: Routledge, 2009), 104.

⁶⁰⁹ Klimburg-Salter compared these to vertically painted wooden tablets from Kuča and Khotan, likely votive offerings. See: Deborah Klimburg-Salter, "Along the Pilgrimage Routes Between Uḍḍiyāna and Tibet: The Gilgit MSS Covers and the Tibetan Decorated Book Covers," in *Tibet in Dialogue with Its Neighbours: History, Culture and Art of Central and Western Tibet*, ed. Erika Forte et al. (Beijing: China Tibetology Publishing House, 2016), 396–400; Deborah Klimburg-Salter, "The Gilgit Manuscript Covers and the 'Cult of the Book'," in *South Asian Archaeology 1987*, ed. Maurizio Taddei (Rome: Istituto Italiano per il Medio ed Estremo Oriente, 1990), 815–30.

⁶¹⁰ Chen, "Inside Out: The Social Life of a Pair of Inscribed Book Covers," 3-22; Ruixuan Chen, *The Nandimitrāvādāna: A Living Text from the Buddhist Tradition* (PhD diss., Universiteit Leiden, 2018), 35–52.

that the production of Buddhist paper manuscripts in Mongolia flourished from the sixteenth century onwards. The meeting between Altan Khan (1507-1583 CE⁶¹¹) and the third Dalai Lama marked a significant phase in Mongolian Buddhism⁶¹². Analysis of twentieth century discoveries on birch-bark manuscripts in monastery and *stūpa* ruins across Mongolia largely indicate that their usage spanned from the thirteenth century to the mid-seventeenth century CE. Birch-bark was favoured by northern Mongols for its durability and suitability, while also deemed spiritually superior due to its unrefined purity compared to paper. The earliest known specimen, the “Birch-bark Manuscripts of the Golden Horde,” unearthed in 1930 near the Ijil river by farmers, and housed at the State Hermitage Museum in St. Petersburg, dates to the late thirteenth century. A 1970 Mongol-Soviet expedition at Kharbukhyn Balgas uncovered a seventeenth century collection of over a thousand items, predominantly in Mongolian, and Tibetan, suggesting widespread birch-bark use, rivalling the sixteenth-seventeenth century CE finds from Olon Süme: both comprising of worn, often charred fragments likely interred or ritually burnt in *stūpas* during consecration⁶¹³. Evidence indicates that Buddhism persisted in Mongolia post-Yuan, albeit diminished, as demonstrated by the continuous translation of Buddhist texts, including the *Prajñāpāramitā* and the *Sūtra of Golden Light* (*Suvarnaprabhāsottamasūtra*⁶¹⁴) at Altan Khan’s behest⁶¹⁵. The proficiency of translators like Bandida Siregetü Gūüsi norúi (1570–1638 CE) suggests a reliance on pre-existing translations, likely preserved from the Yuan era, as seen in the re-edited versions of these texts. Manuscript discoveries at Olon Süme and Kharbukhyn Balgas, have been dated to around 1600 CE, which further attest to a continuous tradition, reflecting a period when Mongolian served prominently as a religious language, more so than in subsequent times⁶¹⁶. The reach of *Prajñāpāramitā* manuscript culture beyond South

⁶¹¹ Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 912-913.

⁶¹² Henry Serruys, “Early Lamaism in Mongolia,” *Oriens Extremus* 10 (1963): 181–216.

⁶¹³ Vesna A. Wallace, “Diverse Aspects of the Mongolian Buddhist Manuscript Culture,” in *Buddhist Manuscript Cultures*, 82-83.

⁶¹⁴ Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 877.

⁶¹⁵ Serruys, “Early Lamaism in Mongolia,” 186.

⁶¹⁶ Klaus Sagaster, “The History of Buddhism among the Mongols,” in *The Spread of Buddhism*, ed. Ann Heirman and Stephan Peter Bumbacher (Leiden and Boston: Brill, 2007), 397-398; Also see: Vesna A. Wallace, “Diverse Aspects of the Mongolian Buddhist Manuscript Culture,” in *Buddhist Manuscript Cultures*, 75–94. In this study, Wallace mentioned a

and Central Asia: attested as far as Mongolia by the thirteenth century CE, where birch-bark manuscripts of Buddhist texts circulated under the Golden Horde and later flourished under Altan Khan's patronage, confirms the diasporic trajectory this chapter traces, while lying beyond its geographical scope. Thus what mainly concerns us here is the earlier, formative phase of that diaspora: the South and Central Asian networks through which Prajñāpāramitā's iconographic elaboration was shaped before and during the Pāla period.

2.2 The religious turn

Following Prajñāpāramitā's ascension within the Mahāyāna pantheon, a proliferation of female divinities came into being⁶¹⁷. Her historical precedence positions her as the ancestress and archetype for all ensuing *dhāraṇī* goddesses and female Buddhas. Consequently, the appellations "Prajñāpāramitā" and "Mother of all Buddhas" invariably feature amongst the epithets of Mahāyāna female deities, expressing the recognition that, as her descendants, they partake of her essence. In contrast to Prajñāpāramitā, other Mahāyāna goddesses possess defined areas of specialisation, mainly nurturance, and protection from human, natural and supernatural dangers. Similarly, every female deity, regardless of how she assists practitioners and devotees, thereby aids their progression towards Buddhahood, and is thus 'mother of Buddhas.' Although the association with wisdom, in most instances, constitutes a minor facet of their persona, the gift of wisdom and liberation is implicitly their ultimate goal. The embodiment of wisdom as a female figure also reconfigured Mahāyāna doctrine in different ways, as seen in the use of the feminine term *vidyā*⁶¹⁸ (polysemous knowledge) for female deities and their *mantras*, and the related term *vidyā-dhāraṇī* for the *mantras* themselves. *Dhāraṇī* literature seeks to reconcile *saṃvṛti-satya* and *paramārtha-satya*⁶¹⁹ by treating both

palm-leaf *AsP* manuscript in the rāñjana script, reputed to be Nāgārjuna's legendary manuscript, among other severe palm leaf manuscripts, now kept at the State Central Library in Ulaanbaatar (Wallace, "Diverse Aspects of the Mongolian Buddhist Manuscript Culture," 81).

⁶¹⁷ Bhattacharya, "Motherhood in the realm of eastern Indian and Himalayan Art": 12-13.

⁶¹⁸ Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 967.

⁶¹⁹ . W. de Jong, ed., *Mūlamadhyamakakārikā*, *Adyar Library Series 109* (Madras: The Adyar Library and Research Centre, 1977), 24:8.

analogously, presenting the former as a conduit to the latter. In Brahmanical literature, the concept of *vāc* (speech) serves as a unifying motif, encompassing sounds from the natural world: spanning inanimate objects, animals, humans, and celestial beings, to the identification of *brāhman* with *śabda* (sound). This dual nature of language, bridging phenomenal and noumenal realms (as *samāropa* to the *noumenon* in Madhyamaka terms), is evident in the Brahmanical notion of *akṣara* (syllable), denoting an indivisible phonic unit fundamental to *mantras*. Scholars have noted that “*mantra*,” derived from “*man*” (related to *manas*, mind) and “*-tra*” (indicating instrumentality or function), translates literally as “instrument of thought⁶²⁰,” and in Brahmanical contexts, *mantras* are words imbued with power to invoke cosmic or divine forces for ritual purposes⁶²¹. This concept of evocative speech and sound, a shared thread across Indian traditions, manifests in medieval Buddhist *dhāraṇī* literature, which employs these principles to bridge conventional and ultimate truths.

In the scholarly examination of the cultic veneration surrounding the deity Prajñāpāramitā, one encounters an interpretative ambivalence inherent within the textual corpus and the devotional framework that forms around it, rendering the object of worship notably uncertain. Such intrinsic equivocality facilitated a smooth incorporation of iconographic representations into its ritual structure, particularly as their use became established within the broader soteriological practices of Buddhism. Some scholars like Snellgrove, suggested that Prajñāpāramitā attained “no great cult⁶²²” (Snellgrove, 1987) due to the scarcity of Prajñāpāramitā images in the Pāla-period. However, as noted by Ronald M. Davidson, majority of writings on Buddhist history till the late twentieth century, propagated a rather limited view: for example, the emergence of the emptiness doctrine in the *Prajñāpāramitā* scriptures and the expositions on meditative practices correspondent with the *bodhisattva* vow stem solely from internal Buddhist principles, independent of non-Buddhist

⁶²⁰ Robert A. Yelle, *Explaining Mantras: Ritual, Rhetoric and the Dream of a Natural Language in Hindu Tantra* (New York: Routledge, 2003).

⁶²¹ Jan Gonda, “The Indian Mantra,” *Oriens* 16, no. 1 (1963): 244–97.

⁶²² David Snellgrove, *Indo-Tibetan Buddhism* (Boston: Shambhala Publications, 1987), 150–51.

discourse or sociopolitical influences⁶²³. Given that this religious shift constituted a predominantly socio-cultural phenomenon, the ensuing section offers a very concise reflection on the laity and the relation between doctrinal frameworks and lay engagement, to construct a framework for an analysis of *siddha* literature and esoteric Buddhist practices as a sophisticated synthesis of social, linguistic, and cultural elements, as laid out in the later part of this chapter.

I will begin with the examination of the Pāla-period in eastern India, known for its expansive growth of esoteric Buddhist texts and iconography, in the light of Brahmanical-Buddhist inter-exchanges in the context of the Brahmanical *mātrkā* traditions, before proceeding to an exploration of ritual practices linked to Prajñāpāramitā within the living traditions of Newar Buddhism. Subsequently, I will delve into a reconsideration of Prajñāpāramitā's association with feminine attributes, a linkage sustained in certain ritual contexts despite textual and ceremonial emphases on an androgynous essence, and posit that this gendered framing parallels modern scholarly comparisons with mother goddesses by Conze, stemming from constrained interpretations of the text. Such readings, I contend, reflect a reductive narrative trajectory, also relevant in the context of Prajñāpāramitā's evolution through esoteric developments in eastern India and Nepal, and narrows the scope of comprehension, thus limiting our understanding of the breadth of religious subjectivity in both pre-modern and contemporary contexts.

It also has to be mentioned that the spiritual aspiration of the *upāsaka* (lay disciple⁶²⁴) is considered subordinate to that of the *bhikṣu* (monk⁶²⁵), who pursues *nirvāṇa* through the noble eightfold path (*āryāṣṭāṅgamārga*⁶²⁶), which includes *śīla*⁶²⁷, *samādhi*⁶²⁸ and *prajñā*. Conversely, the *upāsaka* seeks rebirth in the divine or the human realms, following a distinct practice of virtues that enabled the *devatās* (deities⁶²⁹) to transcend this world, rather than the eightfold path leading to

⁶²³ Ronald M. Davidson, *Indian Esoteric Buddhism: A Social History of the Tantric Movement* (New York: Columbia University Press, 2002), 9.

⁶²⁴ Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 941.

⁶²⁵ Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 115.

⁶²⁶ Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 65.

⁶²⁷ Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 821.

⁶²⁸ Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 743.

⁶²⁹ Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 235.

nirvāṇa. These five virtues: faith (*śraddhā*⁶³⁰), morality (*śīla*), generosity (*tyāga*), wisdom derived from hearing viz., learning (*śruta*⁶³¹), and wisdom (*prajñā*), are demanded of both the *bhikṣu* and the noble disciples (*ārya śrāvaka*), and are broadly delineated into various *sūtras*, notably the discourse on the three kinds of *upavasatha*⁶³². A householder, burdened by worldly concerns, cannot attain the truth accessible only to the wise (such as a monk aspiring to be a great scholar, a *bahuśruta*). The lay person can only be a petty scholar (*śruta*), who can gain knowledge from monks and sermon attendance, as illustrated by the character of Ugra⁶³³, who served as a monk diligently and listened with focus. Although not elaborated in detail, an understanding of *prajñā*, as expected of the laity, “.. relates to the most important aspects of Buddhist truths” which include: a foundational grasp of the rise and fall of phenomena (*udayavyayagāminī paṭipadā*) and noble insight (*āryanibbedhikā*) into the cessation of suffering (*sammādukkhakkhaya*)⁶³⁴. Some reflection on the notion of death, which affects everyone, is appropriate here. As noted by Lamotte, in Buddhist and broader Indian traditions, the “thought at the time of dying” (*maranacitta*⁶³⁵) shapes the “thought at the time of conception” (*upapatticitta*), influencing rebirth. The Buddha instructed his cousin, the *upāsaka* Mahānāman, on preparing the faithful for death, beginning with consolation, and then urged to relinquish attachments to family, sensual pleasures, and even the transient joys of lower and higher paradises, including the *brahmaloka*⁶³⁶, redirecting his focus toward the cessation of self. *Prajñā* and *bhakti* (devotion) are thus emphasised for the laity⁶³⁷.

2.2.a Prajñāpāramitā and the *māṭṛkā* tradition

⁶³⁰ Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 847-848.

⁶³¹ Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 846.

⁶³² Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 942, 943-944; Lamotte, *History of Indian Buddhism*, 67.

⁶³³ Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 934-935.

⁶³⁴ Lamotte, *History of Indian Buddhism*, 74.

⁶³⁵ See Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 531.

⁶³⁶ Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 142.

⁶³⁷ Lamotte, *History of Indian Buddhism*, 73.

In the *AsP*, the term “*mātā*” is employed as a laudatory epithet for “Prajñāpāramitā”, without explicitly mentioning whether the latter signifies the discourse, the physical text, or both; and neither indicating a deified figure: rendering the precise denotation of the term ambiguous. As pointed out by Kinnard: in his publication, *A Catena of Buddhist Scriptures from the Chinese* (1871), Samuel Beal initiated the “Buddha Mother” interpretation, designating Cundā⁶³⁸, often conflated with Prajñāpāramitā, as the “Mother of the Seven Kotis of Buddhas” based on Chinese translations of Sanskrit terms like “*bhagavatī*”, “*devī*”, and “*mātrkā*”. This literal translation was critiqued by scholars like S.D. Singhal. However this interpretation was echoed by Alice Getty and Edward Conze, who similarly framed Prajñāpāramitā as a mother goddess. While Conze interpreted the term “*mātā*” literally, situating Prajñāpāramitā in the cult of a Mother Goddess⁶³⁹, the text’s rhetorical context, such as analogies between Prajñāpāramitā and a mother whose sons venerate her for their existence, suggests a metaphorical usage, emphasising Prajñāpāramitā’s role as the source of *bodhisattvas* and Buddhas⁶⁴⁰. Cabezón observed that the deliberate use of the term “*mātā*” in the *AsP* reflects a purposeful rhetorical strategy, drawing upon a broader lexicon of feminine terms available.

In the Mahāyāna Buddhist imagination, Prajñāpāramitā is considered as the primordial “mother” (In Sanskrit, *matṛ*, and in Tibetan, *yum*) of *śrāvakas* (“listener”; viz., a direct “disciple” of the Buddha who “listened” to his teachings⁶⁴¹), *bodhisattvas* (enlightenment being⁶⁴²), and buddhas (awakened ones⁶⁴³), embodying three forms of omniscience. This maternal designation casts her as a nurturing force, guiding *śrāvakas* or *bodhisattvas* towards their soteriological telos. As a causal origin, *prajñāpāramitā*, or *prajñā* (wisdom), parallels the mother’s role in biological generation, alongside *upāya* (stratagem⁶⁴⁴), as one of the two primary catalysts for awakening. Analogous to a mother gestating a child through ten lunar months, *prajñāpāramitā* sustains the adept across the ten

⁶³⁸ See Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 203-204.

⁶³⁹ Conze, “The Iconography of the Prajñāpāramitā” in *Thirty Years of Buddhist Studies*, 243-244.

⁶⁴⁰ Kinnard, *Imaging Wisdom*, 102-106; Also see: Kim, “Goddess Prajñāpāramitā and Esoteric Buddhism in Jayavarman VII’s Angkor,” 184-185.

⁶⁴¹ Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 850.

⁶⁴² Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 134.

⁶⁴³ Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 148-149.

⁶⁴⁴ Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 942.

bhūmis (stages⁶⁴⁵) of the *bodhisattva* path. In the *Prajñāpāramitāratnagaṇasamcayagāthā*⁶⁴⁶, wisdom is compared to a mother, from whom past, present, and future Buddhas arise. She reveals reality, is the mother of the Jinas⁶⁴⁷, and discloses the thoughts and actions of beings⁶⁴⁸. The *AsP* similarly depicts perfect wisdom as the teacher of all Buddhas, instructing them on the nature of emptiness in the five aggregates, akin to a mother guiding her children. Whether apprehended as scripture, cognitive state, soteriological aim, or *śūnyatā* (emptiness), *prajñāpāramitā* is therefore not just a feminine force, but the generative source of Buddhahood⁶⁴⁹.

There exists a pervasive *mātrkā* tradition within Brahmanism, alongside analogous corpora of qualitative and quantitative personifications across subcontinental religious landscapes, including Brahmanism. Within the Buddhist canon, *prajñā* resonates with the Brahmanical concept of *śakti*, however with different attributions: in Brahmanism, rooted in Sāṃkhya philosophy, *śakti/prakṛti* is the active principle, while *puruṣa* is passive, conversely, in Mahāyāna thought, the feminine aspect or *prajñā* is considered passive. Maternal imagery is a central feature in the conceptualisation of South Asian goddesses. Numerous deities are addressed with maternal epithets such as: *mātrī*, *mātā*, or *mā*. Analogous to *yakṣas* and *yakṣīs/yakṣiṇīs*, i.e., divinities closely associated with the natural world, the *mātrīs* were widely venerated in ancient India, their identity and worship transcending affiliation with any single religious tradition, including Buddhism and the emerging theistic sects of the early common era. By the fifth century CE, a distinct group of seven Brahmanical mother goddesses, known as the *saptamātrī* or *saptamātrkā* had materialised, often accompanied by an eighth figure. In this form, the *mātrīs* became the focus of a pan-Indian temple cult closely associated with Śiva. Their shrines were integral to the major temple complexes of the fifth to eighth centuries CE, including Ellora, Aihole, and Elephanta in the western Deccan. Parallel to their public cult, the

⁶⁴⁵ Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 116-117, 218-220; Bhattacharyya, *The Indian Buddhist Iconography*, 333-336.

⁶⁴⁶ See Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 658, 702.

⁶⁴⁷ See Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 388.

⁶⁴⁸ *Prajñāpāramitā-Ratnagaṇasamcayagāthā* XII, 1–2, trans. Edward Conze, *The Perfection of Wisdom in Eight Thousand Lines and Its Verse Summary* (Bollinas, CA: Four Seasons Foundation, 1973), 31.

⁶⁴⁹ Apple, “Prajñāpāramitā,” 8-9; José I. Cabezón, *Buddhism, Sexuality, and Gender* (Albany, NY: State University of New York Press, 1992), 185.

Seven Mothers assumed important roles within early medieval tantric, or “esoteric” Buddhism and Śaivism⁶⁵⁰.

In tantric Buddhism, mother goddesses appear as minor deities, as can be seen in the *Mahāvairocanābhisaṃbodhisūtra*⁶⁵¹ (ca. 640 CE), in which, the second chapter describes a unique heptad of “wrathful mothers”: Kālarātri, Raudrī, Brahmī, Kaumārī, Vaiṣṇavī, Cāmuṇḍā, and Kauberī (2.50, 13.89), forming the cortège of Yama⁶⁵². Elsewhere, Kālarātri and seven unspecified *mātrī* accompany Śākyamuni⁶⁵³, while chapter six associates them with *mantras* for inducing illness, linking their mythological origins as Skanda’s *grahas* to tantric practices. The text also refers to *ḍākinīs*, grouping them with malevolent beings like *rākṣasas*, *yakṣas*, and *piśācas*, distinct from their later prominence in the *Yoginītantras*⁶⁵⁴. The *Mañjuśrīmūlakalpa*, partially extant by the mid-eight century CE⁶⁵⁵, lists a broader array of female divinities, including: *pūtanās*, *bhaginīs*, *ḍākinīs*⁶⁵⁶,

⁶⁵⁰ Evidence of Buddhist-Śaiva exchanges can be found in Robert Louis Gross’ 1992 study showing ascetics at shared pilgrimage sites like Devikoṭa, Kāmākhya, Bhubanesvara, Vārāṇasī, and Jālandhara-*pīṭha* where Buddhist also encountered diverse ascetics, and in records of conversion, such as the nine Nāthas in the Kubjikāmata system and Śaivas like Uruvilvā Kāśyapa’s group adopting Buddhism. Davidson noted that the Jayadrathayāmala, possibly citing the Guhyasamāja post-eighth century CE, suggests mutual influence between Buddhism and Śaivism, as do *siddhas* like Kāṇhapa and Saudāminī, who retained Kāpālīka traits like skulls and ashes, reflecting a complex system where Buddhist *tantras* absorbed Śaiva elements while reciprocally shaping local traditions, despite occasional antagonism. However, unlike the *Guhyasamāja*’s systematic coded hermeneutics, *siddha* texts used Apabhraṃśa verses more loosely, reflecting alternative writing systems. Scholars have noted that Prakrit and Apabhraṃśa in Buddhist and non-Buddhist contexts carried intentional semantic indeterminacy, aesthetic appeal, and polyvalence, with some suggestions like those by David Seyfort Rugg, that *siddhas* used Apabhraṃśa partly for stylistic and symbolic purposes, though he rejects the idea that it was merely for popularity. While distinguishing exact meanings is challenging, this ambiguity may have been central to its attraction and function (Davidson, *Indian Esoteric Buddhism*, 217-218, 270). Also see: Robert Lewis Gross, *The Sādhus of India: A Study of Hindu Asceticism* (Jaipur and New Delhi: Rawat Publications, 1992); J. A. Schoterman, “The Śaṭsāhasra Saṃhitā: Chapters 1–5,” *Orientalia Rheno-Traiectina* 27 (Leiden: Brill, 1982), 37-38; David Seyfort Rugg, “Allusiveness and Obliqueness in Buddhist Texts: Saṃdhā, Saṃdhi, Saṃdhyā and Abhisamdhī,” in *Dialectes dans les littératures indo-aryennes*, ed. C. Caillat, Publications de l’Institut de Civilisation Indienne, Fascicule 55 (Paris: E. de Boccard, 1989), 321–22.

⁶⁵¹ Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 511-512.

⁶⁵² Stephen Hodge, trans., *The Mahā-Vairocana-Abhisambodhi Tantra: With Buddhaguhya’s Commentary* (New York and London: RoutledgeCurzon, 2003), 14–17.

⁶⁵³ Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 741-742.

⁶⁵⁴ Davidson noted that tantric commentaries often reflect a deliberate effort to temper radical scriptures. While the *Yoginītantras*’ creative audacity contrasts with the commentarial push for institutional conformity, the *siddha* status of commentators like Saraha, Padmavajra, Virūpa, Nāropa, and Maitrīpa, some monastically trained, others like Ḍombīheruka and Lūhipā from non-monastic backgrounds, reveals a heterogeneous *siddha* landscape (Davidson, *Indian Esoteric Buddhism*, 252).

⁶⁵⁵ Yūkei Matsunaga, “On the Date of the Mañjuśrīmūlakalpa,” in *Tantric and Taoist Studies in Honour of R. A. Stein*, ed. Michel Strickmann, *Mélanges chinois et bouddhiques* 22 (1985): 882–94.

⁶⁵⁶ Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 209; Bhattacharyya, *Sādhanaṃālā*, vol. 2, 425; Bhattacharyya, *The Indian Buddhist Iconography*, 321-322.

*rūpiṇīs*⁶⁵⁷, *yakṣiṇīs*⁶⁵⁸, and *ākāśamātrīs* (sky mothers), suggestive of the *yoginī* cult. The last category comprises both the standard *saptamātarah* and additional figures such as Yāmyā, Vāruṇī, and Pūtanā, and innumerable unnamed *mātrīs*⁶⁵⁹. As in the *Mahāvairocanābhisaṃbodhisūtra*, the *saptamātarah* appear in Yama’s retinue within the *maṇḍala*’s outer circles⁶⁶⁰, with “Vajracāmuṇḍi” added to confer a Buddhist identity⁶⁶¹. A more thorough incorporation of these goddesses occurs in the *Sarvatathāgatattvasaṃgraha*⁶⁶² (late seventh century CE), where mother goddesses are systematically classified as: *antarīkṣacāri* (aetherial), *khecarī* (aerial), *bhūcarī* (terrestrial) and *pātālavāsini* (netherworldly): categories later applied to *yoginīs*. Deities from the Brahmanical pantheon, who were previously considered hostile, received tantric initiation and new names: Jātahāriṇī (stealer of Newborns) becomes Vajramekhalā, Māraṇī (slayer) becomes Vajravilayā, Kauberī becomes Vajravikaṭā, and Cāmuṇḍā become Vajrakālī⁶⁶³. In this transformation, the mothers relinquish their identities as *grahas* or Brahmanical deities and enter the Vajrayāna pantheon. The *Tattvasaṃgraha* also recounts the conversion of *ḍākinīs*⁶⁶⁴, which is continued in the *Guhyasamājatantra*⁶⁶⁵, which introduces *vajraḍākinīs* as Vajrayāna deities⁶⁶⁶.

The emergence of the *Yoginītantra* corpus, whose chronology and geographical origins remain subjects of scholarly discussion, represents a gradual rather than abrupt displacement of earlier *mātrīkā*-oriented tantric formations. Elizabeth English argued that the Cakrasaṃvara⁶⁶⁷ root tantra

⁶⁵⁷ Bhattacharyya, *Sādhnamālā*, vol. 2, 425; Bhattacharyya, *The Indian Buddhist Iconography*, 321-322.

⁶⁵⁸ Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 1018.

⁶⁵⁹ T. Gaṇapati Śāstrī, ed., *The Āryamañjuśrīmūlakalpa*, vol. 1, Trivandrum Sanskrit Series, nos. 70, 76, 84 (Trivandrum: Government Press, 1920–1925), 20–21.

⁶⁶⁰ For a study on Buddhist maṇḍalas as “sacralised form of early medieval Sāmanta feudalism,” see: Davidson, *Indian Esoteric Buddhism*, 294-303.

⁶⁶¹ T. Gaṇapati Śāstrī, ed., *The Āryamañjuśrīmūlakalpa*, vol. 2, Trivandrum Sanskrit Series, nos. 70, 76, 84 (Trivandrum: Government Press, 1920–1925), 510.

⁶⁶² Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 781.

⁶⁶³ Isshi Yamada, ed., *Sarva-tathāgata-tattva-saṅgraha 6: A Critical Edition Based on a Sanskrit Manuscript and Chinese and Tibetan Translations, Śatapīṭakam: Indo-Asian Literature*, vol. 262 (New Delhi: International Academy of Indian Culture, 1981), 173.

⁶⁶⁴ Isshi Yamada, ed., *Sarva-tathāgata-tattva-saṅgraha 6: A Critical Edition Based on a Sanskrit Manuscript and Chinese and Tibetan Translations, Śatapīṭakam: Indo-Asian Literature*, vol. 262 (New Delhi: International Academy of Indian Culture, 1981), 180-188.

⁶⁶⁵ Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 334-335.

⁶⁶⁶ Benoytosh Bhattacharya, ed., *Guhyasamāja Tantra or Tathāgataguhyaka*, Gaekwad Oriental Series, no. 53 (Baroda: Oriental Institute, 1967), 130.

⁶⁶⁷ Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 162-163.

likely reached its compiled form no earlier than the late ninth or tenth century CE, with the fully developed Vajravārāhī/Vajrayoginī cult emerging subsequently as a secondary elaboration of the Cakrasaṃvara *maṇḍala* system⁶⁶⁸. Alexis Sanderson has demonstrated that the Buddhist *Yoginītantras* drew substantially on earlier Śaiva Vidyāpīṭha materials dateable to the seventh through ninth centuries, placing the Buddhist appropriation and transformation of these sources in the late ninth to tenth century at the earliest⁶⁶⁹. The *pīṭha* geography incorporated into the Cakrasaṃvara system: including sites such as: Jālandhara, Oḍḍiyāna, Pullīramalaya, and Arbuda, suggests a development distributed across multiple regions rather than localised at a single centre, with particular significance being attached to frontier zones and the intersections of Śaiva and Buddhist practice⁶⁷⁰. In the *Laghucakrasaṃvaratantra*, the cult centres on Cakrasaṃvara and his consort Vajravārāhī, a transformed *mātrī* Vārāhī who emerged as a central Vajrayāna deity. The *maṇḍala* comprises *ḍākinīs*, *vajraḍākinīs*, and *dūtīs*, organised into matriarchal clans akin to Śaiva *yoginī* classifications⁶⁷¹, reflecting the broader process by which the earlier mother goddess cult was progressively reoriented around *yoginī* and *ḍākinīs* figures over the course of the tenth and eleventh centuries CE.

Benoytosh Bhattacharyya noted:

It is not a fact that Hindu gods were unknown in the Buddhist pantheon or that the Buddhist pantheon wholly consisted of Buddhist gods. It is already well-known that several Hindu gods, especially Sarasvatī and Gaṇapati, were given independent forms as principal gods in the Sādhanas, besides a large number as companion deities or as vāhanas or vehicles of important Buddhist deities. They were also given humiliating roles to be trampled upon by angry Buddhist gods. A perusal of the Niṣpannayogāvalī and especially the Dharmadhātuvāgiśvara Maṇḍala will show what a large number of Hindu deities was incorporated in the Maṇḍala, and how this large number was tackled intelligently and fitted into the scheme of the Buddhist Maṇḍalas. How these Hindu gods were

⁶⁶⁸ Elizabeth English, *Vajrayoginī: Her Visualizations, Rituals, and Forms: A Study of the Cult of Vajrayoginī in India* (Boston: Wisdom Publications, 2002), 43–49.

⁶⁶⁹ Alexis Sanderson, “The Śaiva Age: The Rise and Dominance of Śaivism during the Early Medieval Period,” in *Genesis and Development of Tantrism*, ed. Shingo Einoo (Tokyo: Institute of Oriental Culture, University of Tokyo, 2009).

⁶⁷⁰ English, *Vajrayoginī*; Davidson, *Indian Esoteric Buddhism*, 230–268.

⁶⁷¹ Shaman Hatley, “From Mātrī to Yoginī: Continuity and Transformation in the South Asian Cults of the Mother Goddesses,” in *Transformations and Transfer of Tantra in Asia and Beyond*, ed. István Keul (Berlin: Walter de Gruyter, 2012), 99–129.

classified and how directions and colours were assigned to them, and how they were put under a Dhyāni Buddha family, represent a study interesting to the extreme⁶⁷².

Sarasvatī, who is revered as the deity of learning, music, and fine arts, is often addressed with epithets such as: Vāc, Vāk, Vāgdevī, Vāgdevatā, Vāgīśvarī, Varṇeśvarī, Vāgadhīdevatā, Vāgadhīśā, Vāṇī, Śāradā, Bhāratī, Vīṇāpāṇī, Puṣṭi, Śatarūpā, Aṅgajā, Ātmajā, Sāvitrī, Gāyatrī, and Brahmāṇī, and holds a prominent place in three major subcontinental religious traditions: Brahmanism, Buddhism, and Jainism. In the Buddhist tradition, Sarasvatī is often considered the consort of Mañjuśrī, while Brahmanical narratives associate her with Brahmā or Viṣṇu⁶⁷³. The deity is generally depicted standing or seated on a lotus, with one leg pendant, playing a *vīṇā*⁶⁷⁴ (chordophone), and accompanied by her goose (*haṃsa*) *vāhana* near her feet or pedestal. The goddess's iconography gets more diversified in later tantric texts, which describe multiple forms of the goddess. Shaw noted that Sarasvatī's association with intellectual faculties such as mental clarity, reasoning, memory, and oratorical powers, resonated deeply with Buddhist reverence for wisdom, which is why she is revered by the Buddhists, suggesting a keen similarity with Prajñāpāramitā, who also embodies perfect wisdom; further observing that "Sarasvatī is the only Hindu goddess adopted into the Mahāyāna pantheon without without a change in name or significant alteration of divine

⁶⁷² Bhattacharyya, *The Indian Buddhist Iconography*, 344.

⁶⁷³ See Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 777; Bijan Mondal and Gerd J. R. Mevissen, "Meṣavāhinī Sarasvatī in the Sculptural Art of Bengal," *Berliner Indologische Studien / Berlin Indological Studies* 22 (2015): 173; Cf. T. A. Gopinatha Rao, *Elements of Hindu Iconography*, vol. 1, part II (Madras: Law Printing House, 1914), 377–378; Nalinikanta Bhattacharyya, *Iconography of the Buddhist and Brahmanical Sculptures in the Dacca Museum* (Dacca: Dacca Museum, 1929), 181–190; Satish Chandra Vidyabhusan, *Medieval Bengali Sculptures* (Calcutta: University of Calcutta, 1933), 376–380; Jitendra Nath Banerjea, *The Development of Hindu Iconography*, 2nd ed. (Calcutta: University of Calcutta, 1956), 349–352; B. Bhattacharyya, *The Indian Buddhist Iconography* (Calcutta: Firma K. L. Mukhopadhyay, 1974), 122–123, pls. XL–XLII; Raghunath Aiyar, *Concept of Sarasvatī (In Vedic Literature)* (Rohtak, 1977), 18–31; M. A. K. Shamsul Khan, *Sculptural Art of Bangladesh, Pre-Muslim Period* (Dhaka, 1978), 284–285; K. Bhattacharyya, *Indian Images* (New Delhi, 1983), 53–64; David Kinsley, *Hindu Goddesses: Visions of the Divine Feminine in the Hindu Religious Tradition* (Berkeley: University of California Press, 1986), 239–337; Enamul Haque, *Bengal Sculptures: Hindu Iconography up to c. 1250 A.D.*, vol. 1 (Dhaka: The Art Heritage of Bangladesh, 1992), 315–319, figs. 77–80; vol. 2, pls. 168–172; Gudrun Bühnemann, *The Iconography of Hindu Tantric Deities, vol. 1, The Pantheon of the Śrīmatottara and the Śāradātilaka* (Groningen: Egbert Forsten, 2000–01), 63–64, nos. 3–6 & 19–20, 75–77, 101–103, figs. 3, 19–20; vol. 2, 23, nos. 2 & 4–5, 31–36, figs. 4ab, 5, 6abcd, 19ab; 165–167, nos. 2–4 & 12–17, 177–182, 188–193; Thomas E. Donaldson, *Iconographical Development in Bengal (c. 10th–19th Centuries)* (New Delhi, 2002), 286–300, figs. 170–174, 598, 666–667, 674–675; Catherine Ludvik, *Sarasvatī: Riverine Goddess of Knowledge* (Leiden: Brill, 2007), 18–193; G. Bhattacharyya, *Inscriptions of Bengal, vol. 3, containing inscriptions of the Chandelas, the Karnatas and the Senas and of Visvarupa and Damodara*, rev. ed., ed. Debarchana Sarkar (Kolkata: Jadavpur University, 2015), a & 2015b.

⁶⁷⁴ Bhattacharyya, *The Indian Buddhist Iconography*, 315.

persona”. Their shared invocation through identical *mantras* reinforces the intrinsic connection between Sarasvatī and Prajñāpāramitā⁶⁷⁵. As a wisdom deity, there are some iconographic similarities between Sarasvatī and Prajñāpāramitā, primarily the depiction of a manuscript (*pustaka*) as one of her attributes, which is also often depicted in Prajñāpāramitā images as resting on top of a lotus (*utpala*)⁶⁷⁶.

In the section below, I will be briefly discussing two images, in the context of the different forms of *mātrkā* or feminine power worship in Pāla-period Buddhism.

(A) Meṣavāhinī Sarasvatī

Plate 89 illustrates a back stone sculpture of Meṣavāhinī Sarasvatī (ram-mounted Sarasvatī), housed at the Coochbehar Palace Museum (Acc. No. unavailable), measuring 36 x 19 x 9 cm. The stele is adorned with a *kīrtimukha* at the top, flanked by two *vidyādharas* on both sides. The goddess is depicted with a halo behind her head, and is wearing an elaborately ornamented *mukūṭa*, dual necklaces (the longer extending over her breasts), *pattra-kunḍala* (earrings), *keyūra* (bracelets), *valaya* (armlets), and *nūpura* (anklets). The goddess is seated with her right leg pendant and supported by a *meṣa* (ram). The pedestal is intricately carved and features a small kneeling male on the proper left, possibly presenting an offering. The deity is depicted with four hands, which have the following attributes:

Thread (*akṣamālā*) | Manuscript (*pustaka*)

Chordophone (*vīṇā*) | Chordophone (*vīṇā*)

Bhattacharya elucidated the ram’s association with Sarasvatī, referring to the *Śatapatha Brāhmaṇa* (12.7.1.12) which narrates that Indra’s vital energy, escaping through his nostrils, manifested as a ram. Sarasvatī was summoned with the Aśvins to restore Indra, and received the ram

⁶⁷⁵ Shaw, *Buddhist Goddesses of India*, 236.

⁶⁷⁶ Jinah Kim, “Goddess Prajñāpāramitā and Esoteric Buddhism in Jayavarman VII’s Angkor,” in *The Creative South: Buddhist and Hindu Art in Mediaeval Maritime Asia*, ed. Andrea Acri and Peter Sharrock (Singapore: ISEAS–Yusof Ishak Institute, 2022), 175.

as recompense. Further, *Śatapatha Brāhmaṇa* 12.7.2.3 and 12.7.2.7 document the sacrificial offering of rams and ewes to Sarasvatī, a ritual Bhattasali noted persisted in Dhaka district during his time, where ram fights marked her festival⁶⁷⁷. Subsequent scholarship, including those by A. Vidyabhushan⁶⁷⁸, J.N. Banerjea⁶⁷⁹, and K. Bhattacharyya⁶⁸⁰, briefly addressed Meṣavāhinī Sarasvatī. Enamul Haque catalogued nine Meṣavāhinī Sarasvatī images in his study as “Type 2.”⁶⁸¹ Catherine Ludvik situated the ram/ ewe association of Sarasvatī within *Yajur Vedic* developments (twelfth to ninth centuries BCE)⁶⁸². A 2015 study by Mondal and Mevissen documented the Coochbehar sculpture for the first time⁶⁸³. Stylistically, the Coochbehar image resembles the sculpture recovered from Kalanja⁶⁸⁴. Among catalogued Meṣavāhinī Sarasvatī sculptures, the one from Gajole at the Malda Museum⁶⁸⁵, and the one from Chhatingram at the Varendra Research Museum⁶⁸⁶, both from the *Varendra-confluens* north of the Padma, are notable for their scale. The image from Deopara at the Varendra Research Museum⁶⁸⁷ however exhibits distinct, elaborate carving, suggesting a letter stylistic evolution. The image from Bhagalpur at the Bangiya Sahitya Parishad Museum uniquely integrates the iconography of Sarasvatī and another Brahmanical goddess, Lakṣmī⁶⁸⁸.

Iconographically, the development of the cult of Meṣavāhinī Sarasvatī demonstrates a progression from earlier images from southern Bihar, possibly originating near the Gaya region, to its proliferation in the *Varendra-confluens* as well as the *Samataṭa-littoral*. Early images, such as the

⁶⁷⁷ Nalini Kanta Bhattasali, *Iconography of Buddhist and Brahmanical Sculptures in the Dacca Museum* (Dacca: Dacca Museum, 1929), 187.

⁶⁷⁸ Amulyacharan Vidyabhushan, *Sarasvatī* (Kolkata: Sāhityaloka, 1340 B.S. [1933], in Bengali), 74–75.

⁶⁷⁹ J. N. Banerjea, “Iconography,” in *The History of Bengal*, Vol. I: Hindu Period, ed. R. C. Majumdar (Dhaka: University of Dacca, 1943),

⁶⁸⁰ Kanailal Bhattacharyya, *Sarasvatī—A Study on Her Concept and Iconography* (Calcutta: Saraswat Library, 1983), 82–83.

⁶⁸¹ Enamul Haque, *Bengal Sculptures: Hindu Iconography up to c. 1250 A.D.* (Dhaka: Bangladesh National Museum, 1992), 284–85, 379.

⁶⁸² Catherine Ludvik, *Sarasvatī: Riverine Goddess of Knowledge: From the Manuscript-Carrying Viṇā-Player to the Weapon-Wielding Defender of the Dharma*, Brill’s Indological Library 27 (Leiden/Boston: Brill, 2007), 53.

⁶⁸³ Bijan Mondal and Gerd J. R. Mevissen, “Meṣavāhinī Sarasvatī in the Sculptural Art of Bengal,” *Berliner Indologische Studien / Berlin Indological Studies* 22 (2015): 173–90, at 182 (Berlin: Weidler Buchverlag).

⁶⁸⁴ Mondal and Mevissen, “Meṣavāhinī Sarasvatī in the Sculptural Art of Bengal,” 178–79, fig. 8.

⁶⁸⁵ Mondal and Mevissen, “Meṣavāhinī Sarasvatī in the Sculptural Art of Bengal,” 181–82, fig. 11.

⁶⁸⁶ Mondal and Mevissen, “Meṣavāhinī Sarasvatī in the Sculptural Art of Bengal,” 178–79, fig. 5.

⁶⁸⁷ Mondal and Mevissen, “Meṣavāhinī Sarasvatī in the Sculptural Art of Bengal,” 178–79, fig. 6.

⁶⁸⁸ Mondal and Mevissen, “Meṣavāhinī Sarasvatī in the Sculptural Art of Bengal,” 184–85, fig. 14.

sculpture from Agradigun at the Varendra Research Museum⁶⁸⁹ feature a developed lotus-seat, in contrast to simpler oval cushions in earlier images⁶⁹⁰. Images from the later Pāla-period, including the Coochbehar, Depart and Kalanja icons, demonstrate refined compositional clarity and expressiveness.

(B) Sadyojāta

Plate 90 depicts an unpublished Sadyojāta⁶⁹¹ sculpture, made of greyish-black stone at the Coochbehar Palace Museum (Acc. No. unavailable). The sculpture, of considerable scale, centres on a reclining female figure, opulently adorned with jewellery, and crowned with an ornamental *mukūṭa* featuring a prominent hair-bun. The deity is depicted wearing a diaphanous *uttarīya* draped over her left shoulder, a long *upavīta* which is grasped by an infant with his right hand, circular *pattra-kuṇḍala* (earrings), *keyūra* (bracelets), *valaya* (armlets), and *nūpura* (anklets). Her left hand supports her head, while her right hand holds an *utpala* (blue lotus). A small cushion supports the infant's head, who is also ornamented. The goddess's right leg is extended, while her left leg is bent, and attended to by a female attendant. Two additional attendants, less elaborately adorned, flank the central figure: the attendant on the left holding a *cāmara* (fly-whisk) in her right hand and an unidentified object in her left, while the one on the right holds a *vyajana* (fan) in her right hand and a small container-like object in her left. The upper panel of the sculpture is intricately carved, featuring a *liṅga*, Kārttikeya on a peacock, a moustached figure: possibly Sūrya, given the chariot wheels below, and Gaṇeśa. Eight small seated figures, possibly the Aṣṭadīkṣpālas, are depicted between Gaṇeśa and Kārttikeya. There are eight additional figures flanking the *liṅga*, at the top left of which, the deity who is depicted with four hands, may represent Viṣṇu. There is an ornate band beneath, which is adorned with animal and amphibian motifs. Plate 91 shows a comparable example in black-stone from the South Dinajpur District Museum, depicting an adorned reclining female figure whose iconography is quite similar to

⁶⁸⁹ Mondal and Mevissen, "Meṣavāhinī Sarasvatī in the Sculptural Art of Bengal," 177, 179, fig. 4.

⁶⁹⁰ Mondal and Mevissen, "Meṣavāhinī Sarasvatī in the Sculptural Art of Bengal," 177, fig. 3.

⁶⁹¹ Scholarly nomenclature is contentious. Mevissen advocated for its designation as a "reclining Gaurī image."

the previous sculpture. The sculpture features only two attendants of the goddess, the infant is unornamented and depicted without a cushion beneath his head, and the goddess wears a longer necklace instead of an *uttarīya*. The composition of this sculpture is simpler compared to the first, with the upper panel depicting a *liṅga*, Gaṇeśa, and a seated figure. There are two more examples at the Balurghat College Museum (Plates 92 and 93), which are unpublished.

Bhattacharya noted the prevalence of such “Mother and Child” sculptures in the Varendra region (*Varendra-confluens*), arguing their Śaiva character, as evidenced by the presence of Kārttikeya, Gaṇeśa, and the *liṅga*. He interpreted them as depicting Śiva as Sadyojāta (newborn), alongside Pārvatī⁶⁹², which he observed corresponds with Vaivāhika imagery. The *Liṅgapurāṇa* narrates the divine emergence of Sadyojāta, an infant with white eyes and red nails, conceived from Brahma’s deep meditation. Recognising this infant as Sadyojāta, Brahma reverently embraced and worshipped him⁶⁹³. A similar incident is also narrated in the *Skandapurāṇa*⁶⁹⁴. The *Brahmapurāṇa* describes an episode during Śiva and Pārvatī’s marriage, where Śiva, to test Pārvatī, assumes an infant’s form, sleeping on her lap in the divine assembly (*svayamvara*), where she was to choose her husband. Through meditation, Pārvatī discerned the infant’s true identity as Śiva, and joyfully accepted him, departing the assembly with the child held tenderly to her breast⁶⁹⁵. Remarking on the accuracy of referring to the *Purāṇic* texts for deciphering such images, Mevissen noted that the iconography described in these three texts:

[...] reveals so many iconographic differences between the texts and the actual images that it is still doubtful whether the images represent an adaptation of the pan-Indian tradition reflected in these

⁶⁹² Also see: Enamul Haque, *Bengal Sculptures: Hindu Iconography up to c. 1250 A.D.* (Dhaka, 1992), 295–98; Britta Zehmke, *Die liegende Frau mit Kind in der indischen Steinplastik*, 2 vols. (M.A. thesis, Freie Universität Berlin, 1994; rev. ed., unpublished), 1:1–11, 70–71; Gouriswar Bhattacharya, “The Munificence of Lady Catuṣamā,” in *Akṣayan itī: Essays Presented to Dr. Debala Mitra in Admiration of Her Scholarly Contributions*, ed. Gouriswar Bhattacharya (Delhi, 1991), 315–17, repr. in *Essays on Buddhist Hindu Jain Iconography & Epigraphy*, ed. Enamul Haque (Dhaka, 2000), 284–86.

⁶⁹³ Pañcānana Tarkaratna, ed. and trans., *Liṅgapurāṇa*, by *Kṛṣṇadvaipāyana Vedavyāsa* (Calcutta: Vaṅgabāsī Steam Machine Press, pub. Śrī Nutbihārī Rāy, 1903–4), 17. [Bengali version, trans. by author]

⁶⁹⁴ Pañcānana Tarkaratna, ed. and trans., *Skanda-Purāṇa*, Vol. 7, *Maheśvara-Khaṇḍa*, by *Veda Vyāsa* (Calcutta: Vaṅgabāsī Electromachine, by Śrī Natabar Chakrabarti, 8/2 Bhabanicharan Datta Street, 1911), 340–348. [Bengali version, trans. by author]

⁶⁹⁵ Gaurinath Sastri, gen. ed., and Ashok Kumar Chattopadhyay, ed., *Brahmapurāṇa*, trans. Annadashankar Pahari (Kolkata: Nabapatra Prakashan, 1975), Chapter 36, 81–86, esp. 82.

Purāṇas. This rather points to a separate local tradition prevalent in North Bengal during the 10th through 12th centuries for which the textual source is still to be discovered⁶⁹⁶.

Bhattachali further documented eight such sculptures at the Varendra Research Society Museum in Rajshahi, one at the Dacca Museum (Bangladesh National Museum) and one at the Indian Museum in Kolkata⁶⁹⁷. In his 2006 study, Mevissen comprehensively identified some examples from north Bengal, significantly noting two sculptures which feature a combination of the *liṅga*, Gaṇeśa, Kārttikeya, and the Aṣṭadikpālas⁶⁹⁸.

The Sadyojāta iconography, is very specific to the Pāla-period artistic canon, and lacks parallels in broader subcontinental traditions, rendering its conceptual origins obscure. However its prevalence in the *Varendra-confluens* suggests a regional significance.

2.3 Unborn, unbound: Prajñāpāramitā in ‘esoteric’ Buddhism

It has been demonstrated by Davidson that esoteric Buddhist texts likely emerged within a communal context, with monks and *siddhas* collaboratively contributing to the monastic enterprise of canonical compilation and exegesis. These scriptures were deemed important for the enduring vitality of the monastic institutions⁶⁹⁹. Davidson argued that while in the history of Mahāyāna Buddhism, individual visions of buddhas and *bodhisattvas* were the source from which novel doctrines emerged over time, which were compiled and synthesised into a canon, esoteric Buddhism likely diverged from this model, with *siddha* texts arising from social interactions rather than solitary inspiration. Despite the rhetoric of seclusion, as seen with ‘tribal’ deities, these scriptures developed

⁶⁹⁶ Gerd J. R. Mevissen, “A Reclining Gaurī Image with ‘Pañcadikpālas’ in the Khulna Museum, Bangladesh,” in *Sahṛdaya: Studies in Indian and South East Asian Art in Honour of Dr. R. Nagaswamy*, ed. Bettina Baumer, Chirapat Prapandvidya, R. N. Misra, and Devendra Handa (Chennai: Tamil Arts Academy, 2006), note 2, 328.

⁶⁹⁷ Bhattachali, *Iconography of Buddhist and Brahmanical Sculptures*, 134-142.

⁶⁹⁸ Mevissen, “A Reclining Gaurī Image”, 319–30; reprint. Gerd J. R. Mevissen, “A Unique Image of Gaurī with Sadyojāta Śiva in the Khulna Museum,” *Journal of Bengal Art* 9–10 (2004–5): 303–14 (Dhaka: The International Centre for Study of Bengal Art, 2007).

⁶⁹⁹ Davidson, *Indian Esoteric Buddhism*, 144.

in regional sociopolitical hubs, where Sanskritic cultural influence, vernacular literary styles⁷⁰⁰, wandering *siddhas*, and indigenous communities thrived⁷⁰¹; concluding that, “... the esoteric (especially *siddha*) scriptures arose as preeminently social events⁷⁰².” Furthermore, the often provocative practices of Buddhist *siddhas*, at times rooted in non-Buddhist ritual connotations, necessitated sophisticated interpretive strategies for codification into acceptable scriptures⁷⁰³. Such hermeneutics had to reconcile contradictions with Buddhist virtues like *vinaya* and *śīla*, interpret erotic elements, and balance conservative monastic reassurance with evolving religious trends in the Indian subcontinent. This situation was met with the claim that societal decline or unworthy prior audiences justified such radical methods, rendering disciplined eroticism as a path to liberation, which *siddha* literature argues is the ‘highest yoga’ for rapid awakening. The assumed supremacy of *siddha* literature is further exemplified in the *Hevajratāntra*’s dismissal of skeptics as heretics⁷⁰⁴. From the seventh-eight century CE onwards, emerging from sociopolitical upheavals, new Buddhist scriptures reflected novel linguistic and aesthetic communities, shaped by population displacements and the integration of newly converted indigenous and village groups, deriving from varied social, linguistic,

⁷⁰⁰ *Siddha* Sanskrit shows diglossia, with speakers often demonstrating their vernacular grammar when lacking formal training. While sometimes used for prestige or ritual, it usually appeared in loose, localised forms rather than as refined Buddhist Hybrid Sanskrit. Regional Sanskrit and Apabhraṃśa were both employed in esoteric Buddhist writings, often integrated within ritual contexts. It has been argued that this language was not just pedagogical but also a genuine medium expression, enabling freedom in composition of texts (Davidson, *Indian Esoteric Buddhism*, 274). Also see: Teun Goudriaan, “Speech of the Gurus: Instances of Treatment of Sanskrit in Tantric Literature,” in *Ideology and Status of Sanskrit: Contributions to the History of the Sanskrit Language*, ed. Jan E. M. Houben, Brill’s Indological Library, vol. 13 (Leiden: E. J. Brill, 1996), 267–74.

⁷⁰¹ Excluding sacred cities like Vārāṇasī, place names *siddha* literature point to ‘peripheral’ but non-forested regions, with the performative nature of *Mahāyoga* and *Yoginī-tantras*, integrating ritual, song, dance, and narrative, likely emerged from socially engaged singers, performers, and itinerant troupes, comparable to the modern Bauls, who often inhabit urban margins. (Davidson, *Indian Esoteric Buddhism*, 238).

⁷⁰² Davidson, *Indian Esoteric Buddhism*, 238.

⁷⁰³ The connection of coded language to indigenous vernaculars, including Apabhraṃśa, Old Bengali, and Prakrit, distinguished Buddhist *siddha tantras* from Śaiva traditions through enriched vernacular use. *Yoginītantras* embed Apabhraṃśa verses in nonstandard Sanskrit rituals with coded elements, as seen in the *Hevajratāntra*’s preface, Buddhakapāla’s *Vajragīti*, and texts like *Khasamatāntra*, *Dākaraṇavatāntra*, *Caṇḍamahāroṣaṇa*, and *Samvarodayatantra*, while *Mahāyogatantras* like *Kṛṣṇayamāri* employ them minimally (Davidson, *Indian Esoteric Buddhism*, 267).

⁷⁰⁴ Davidson, *Indian Esoteric Buddhism*, 239-240; Davidson also noted that Buddhist monks were pivotal in supporting, enacting, interpreting, and transmitting the scriptures and rituals of institutional esotericism. External *siddha*, tribal, lay, and political sources, often lacking sacred authority, shaped many practices, reflected in certain antinomian elements in canonical texts like cemetery rituals and seduction rites, which monastic hermeneutics refined using elite philosophical frameworks, embedding new doctrines within the monasteries (Davidson, *Indian Esoteric Buddhism*, 153).

and performative traditions⁷⁰⁵. *Siddha* literature embraced local cultures through rituals tied to forests and peripheries of the society, employing provocative imagery and narratives in *Yoginītantras* that defied Brahmanical norms, while playfully manipulating Sanskrit, Apabhraṃśa, Prakrit and coded languages (*sandhyā-bhāṣā/sandhyā-bhāṣita*⁷⁰⁶), thus attracting patrons seeking intellectual and social legitimacy through Brahmanical allegiance, while transforming Buddhist canonical syntheses⁷⁰⁷. In mainland India, the prolific era of esoteric scripture creation spanned a remarkably brief period from the mid-seventh to mid-eleventh century CE, yielding a rapid proliferation of texts: commentaries, *sādhana* practices, consecration guides, yogic treatises, and home rites, defying gradualist models with the evidence of composition and acceptance of these texts within decades rather than centuries; by the late eighth century CE, even the radical *Yoginītantras* were assimilated into major north and central Indian monastic curricula, fully integrated by early eleventh century CE as Tibetan translators arrived, institutionalising thousands of works through innovative hermeneutics that embraced tribal, outcast, and antinomian elements, alongside new tantric Sanskrit and ritualised vernacular forms like Apabhraṃśa and old Bengali⁷⁰⁸.

In tantric praxis, *prajñāpāramitā* epitomises the feminine essence, where *prajñā* is explicitly identified with *nirvāṇa*, and *upāya* (means) with *saṃsāra*. Tantric texts describes ultimate reality as the *yuganaddha* (yoked together⁷⁰⁹) of wisdom and means, a synthesis considered essential for the attainment of Buddhahood⁷¹⁰. In ritual contexts⁷¹¹, *prajñā* is symbolised by a *ghaṇṭā* (bell⁷¹²),

⁷⁰⁵ On polycentric religious imagination in the Indian subcontinent, see: Diana L. Eck, *Darśan: Seeing the Divine Image in India* (Delhi: Motilal Banarsidass Publishing House, 2007), 22-31.

⁷⁰⁶ In specific contexts, esoteric messages correspond to coded language formulae, exhibiting a marked shift in significance. Such language bifurcates in its role: it serves as a hermeneutical tool to elucidate socially or textually challenging passages, while also containing linguistic acts of ambiguous or problematic meaning. The aim of *sandhyā-bhāṣā/sandhyā-bhāṣita*, frequently employed in texts the *Pradīpodyotana* and Munidatta's commentary on the *Caryāgītikoṣa*, is to uncover latent meanings beneath linguistic structures. Davidson cites an example of Munidatta's reinterpretation of Vīrūpa's drinking song, which humorously depict the *mahāsiddha's* preference for taverns over sacred spaces (Davidson, *Indian Esoteric Buddhism*, 257-258). In the Tibetan context, see: Michael Broido, "Does Tibetan Hermeneutics Throw Any Light on Sandhābhāṣā?" *Journal of the Tibet Society* 2 (1982): 5–39.

⁷⁰⁷ Davidson, *Indian Esoteric Buddhism*, 290-291.

⁷⁰⁸ Davidson, *Indian Esoteric Buddhism*, 339.

⁷⁰⁹ Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 1042.

⁷¹⁰ James B. Apple, "Spiritual Discipline in Buddhism," in *Encyclopedia of Love in World Religions*, ed. Yudit K. Greenberg, vol. 1 (Santa Barbara, CA: ABC-CLIO, 2008), 599–600.

⁷¹¹ On the ritual use of images in the Indian subcontinent, see: Eck, *Darśan*, 22-31.

⁷¹² Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 319-320.

padma (lotus⁷¹³), *sūrya* (sun), or by the vowels of the Sanskrit alphabet (*āli*⁷¹⁴), while *upāya* is represented by a *vajra*, *candra* (moon), or the consonants (*kāli*⁷¹⁵). In yogic ritual practices involving a female partner, *prajñā* is embodied by a *yoginī*, with *Nairātmyā* (selflessness) as her synonym. In the union of *prajñā* and *upāya*, the former is held to be dominant: although Buddhahood could not be attained without means, it is *prajñā* which is the vessel of *śūnyat'ās* ultimate reality⁷¹⁶. With this rise of devotion to the *Prajñāpāramitā* texts themselves, *Prajñāpāramitā*'s hypostatisation as a feminine deity crystallised. Her scholastic designation as the “Mother of the Buddhas,” denoting the all-knowledge that gives rise to Buddhahood, took on devotional significance in her worship. The *Prajñāpāramitāstrotra* describes her as possessing a flawless body, unclothed like space, and as radiant as moonlight. In this praise, she is extolled as the sole mother and the singular path to liberation⁷¹⁷.

The Mahāyāna Buddhist formation of the “three bodies” (*trikāya*⁷¹⁸) doctrine was developed to provide a unified explanation of the relationship between Buddhas and *bodhisattvas*, and to clarify the role of the historical Śākyamuni. The emanation body or transformation body (*nirmāṇakāya*⁷¹⁹) is identified with the Śākyamuni Buddha appearing in human form; the enjoyment body (*saṃbhogakāya*⁷²⁰) is the Buddha manifesting in celestial realms; and the truth body (*dharmakāya*⁷²¹) is the Buddha as the absolute, identical with *nirvāṇa*. Material representations such as *stūpas*, *caityas*, and *dharmadhātu*⁷²² images correspond to the truth body, while images of Śākyamuni or depictions of his life as *sarvārthasiddha* belong to *nirmāṇakāya*. Iconographically, however, it is primarily the *saṃbhogakāya* that is represented. In tantric Buddhism, a fourth and more

⁷¹³ Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 606-607.

⁷¹⁴ Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 32.

⁷¹⁵ Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 32.

⁷¹⁶ Alex Wayman, “Female Energy and Symbolism in the Buddhist Tantras,” *History of Religions* 2, no. 1 (1962): 73–111; Gellner, *Monk, Householder, and Tantric Priest*, 280.

⁷¹⁷ Apple, “*Prajñāpāramitā*,” 10-11; Edward Conze, *Buddhist Texts Through the Ages* (New York: Harper and Row, 1964), 147–49.

⁷¹⁸ Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 923.

⁷¹⁹ Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 587.

⁷²⁰ Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 749-750.

⁷²¹ Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 246.

⁷²² Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 244.

esoteric category is sometimes added: the innate/ connate body (*sahajakāya*⁷²³), the body of great bliss (*mahāsukhakāya*⁷²⁴) or the self-nature body (*svabhāvikakāya*⁷²⁵). Furthermore, in Vajrayāna, which is both a yogic system and a means of identifying with the ultimate, these bodies of the Buddha are associated with specific parts of the practitioner’s body or *cakra*⁷²⁶, ranging from locating *nirmāṇakāya* in the navel to the *mahāsukhakāya* in the head. There is also a correlation of the Three Jewels with different doctrines: in the Śrāvakayāna⁷²⁷, these are Śākyamuni, Dharma and the Saṅgha⁷²⁸; in the Mahāyāna context, they are Svayambhū⁷²⁹, Prajñāpāramitā (goddess and text), and Amoghapāśa Lokeśvara⁷³⁰; while in Vajrayāna, they are: Vajrasattva⁷³¹, Vajrayoginī⁷³², and Ṣaḍakṣarī Lokeśvara⁷³³.

The extant esoteric Buddhist literature reveals a male-centric ritual framework, with examples from many Sanskrit ritual manuals and exegeses, translated into Tibetan, Chinese, Newari and Uighur, and spread through lineages across Tibet, Nepal, Myanmar, and beyond, which all lack any text or tradition addressing women’s roles in yogic or sexual practices, which are often described

⁷²³ See Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 735.

⁷²⁴ See Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 510.

⁷²⁵ Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 879.

⁷²⁶ Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr.’s synoptic observation is apposite here: “According to various systems of tantric physiognomy, a central channel (*avadhūtī*) runs from either the tip of the genitals or the base of the spine to either the crown of the head or the point between the eyebrows, with a number of “wheels” (*cakra*) along its course. In one of the systems, these wheels are located at the point between the eyebrows, the crown of the head, the throat, the heart, the navel, the base of the spine, and the opening of the sexual organ. Running parallel to the central channel to the right and left are two channels, both smaller in diameter, the *lalanā* and the *rasanā*. It is said that the right and left channels wrap around the central channel, forming knots at the *cakras*. Much tantric practice is devoted to techniques for loosening these knots in order to allow the winds (*prāna*) or energies that course through the other channels to flow freely and enter into the central channel.” (Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 162).

⁷²⁷ Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 851.

⁷²⁸ Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 750-751.

⁷²⁹ Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 883.

⁷³⁰ Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 35-36.

⁷³¹ Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 956; In her 2021 study, Abira Bhattacharya mentioned an eleventh-twelfth century stele from Nalanda kept at the National Museum in New Delhi (Acc. No. 60.567), which depicts the worship of an *AsP* manuscript and Vajrasattva by devotees. In this stele, Vajrasattva emerges as a ritual overseer, depicted cross-legged with a *vajra* and *ghaṇṭā*, embodying non dual wisdom and emptiness, and serving as the guide to the five Tathāgatas, or the pinnacle of meditative visualisation, as mentioned in the *Sādhanamālā*. Bhattacharya argued that this imagery suggests Vajrasattva facilitating a transition from worldly devotion to spiritual elevation, and also aptly observed that representations of rituals involving a *pustaka* with a Vajrācārya holding a *vajra* and a *ghaṇṭā* can be often encountered in Pāla-period Buddhist sculptures from Bihar, Bengal, and Odisha (Bhattacharya, “Motherhood in the realm of eastern Indian and Himalayan art”: 19, Fig. 2).

⁷³² Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 957.

⁷³³ Gellner, *Monk, Householder, and Tantric Priest*, 293-294.

as anatomically infeasible for female agency. Even texts attributed to women, such as the *Vyaktabhāvānugatatattvasiddhi*, lauded as affirming the female body, adopt a male perspective, focussing on its manipulation for male yogic aims, indicating that medieval Indian women, influenced by societal and religious pressures towards domesticity, navigated constrained roles within a Buddhist tradition increasingly reflecting the *Varṇāśramadharmā*, and “... saw the doors of Buddhist religion grow narrower before their eyes⁷³⁴.” However, this generalisation, drawn primarily from normative textual sources, has been challenged by Kim, who demonstrated through material evidence, including manuscript colophons, donor inscriptions, and patterns of artistic patronage: that women played active roles as donors, patrons, and participants in Buddhist artistic production and religious practice in the Pāla period⁷³⁵. The colophon evidence from the manuscripts discussed in this dissertation corroborates this more complex picture: The LACMA *AsP* was commissioned by Tejokām, a female householder; the CUL Add. 1464 by a lay woman named Lāḍokā; and the CUL *PrK* under the patronage of queen Uḍḍakā. While the ritual manuals and exegetical literature undoubtedly reflect a male-centric framework, the material record suggests that women’s engagement with Buddhist institutions, particularly through patronage and manuscript commissioning, was more substantive than the textual sources alone would indicate. In their 2024 study, Giovanni Verardi and Bhikkhunī Dhammadinnā mentioned a Gāndhārī stucco figurine in Milan’s Civico Museo Archeologico (inv. no. A 1988.02.01), likely originating from Hadda, which portrays a *bhikṣuṇī*, offering a scarce iconographic glimpse into the presence of female Buddhist monastics in Gandhāra, tentatively dated to the second century CE or, more plausibly, a later period⁷³⁶.

The concept of dialectical androgyny attained its most developed expression in Vajrayāna Buddhism after the sixth century CE, though its antecedents are discernible in *Prajñāpāramitā*

⁷³⁴ Davidson, *Indian Esoteric Buddhism*, 91-98.

⁷³⁵ Jinah Kim, “Unheard Voices: Women’s Roles in Medieval Buddhist Artistic Production and Religious Practices in South Asia,” *Journal of the American Academy of Religion* 80, no. 1 (2012): 200–232.

⁷³⁶ Giovanni Verardi and Bhikkhunī Dhammadinnā, “The Nun of Milan: A Gandhāran Bhikṣuṇī Figurine in the Civico Museo Archeologico,” *Annual Report of The International Research Institute for Advanced Buddhology at Soka University for the Academic Year 2023*, vol. 27 (Tokyo: The International Research Institute for Advanced Buddhology, Soka University, 2024), 179–86.

literature of the early Mahāyāna tradition. This development, which likely originated around the beginning of the Common Era, incorporated symbolic and visual elements from the tantric symbolism in Brahmanical traditions, while reconfiguring them within a distinctly Buddhist framework. Within this early Mahāyāna corpus, wisdom was explicitly feminised through its personification as Prajñāpāramitā, a term, as noted by Spoonberg, is grammatically feminine in both Sanskrit and Pāli, and described as the “the mother of all Buddhas.” Such characterisation reflects not a rigid dualistic sexual dichotomy but an affirmation of the feminine dimension of wisdom, later embodied in the deities Prajñāpāramitā and Tārā. This feminine wisdom is defined by the capacity to perceive with clarity and without attachment, rather than in terms of sheltering and protection⁷³⁷. In the *Mañjuśrīmūlakalpa*, Tārā embodies the attributes of an advanced *bodhisattva*, later evolving into the saviouress from the eight perils (*aṣṭamābhayatārā*), while inheriting the nurturing essence of Prajñāpāramitā, similarly earning the title “mother of all Buddhas.” Her veneration in the Indian subcontinent is evidenced by the seventh century text *Tārāmūlakalpa*, a four hundred folio ritual anthology detailing her iconographic manifestations and practices, where she is revered as Bhagavatī Mahāvidyārājñī, linked to *vidyās*, sacred syllabic sequences summoning her divine presence⁷³⁸, with her role as a *mahāvidya* symbolising a liberating awareness⁷³⁹. Within esoteric Mahāyoga and *Yoginītantras*, Tārā emerges as the consort of the *tathāgata* Amoghasiddhi, embodying the wind element, paralleling the multifaceted worship of Vajrayoginī⁷⁴⁰, and by the twelfth century, in the

⁷³⁷ Joanna Macy, “Perfection of Wisdom: Mother of All Buddhas,” *Anima* 3, no. 1 (1977): 75–80; reprinted in *Beyond Androcentrism*, ed. Rita Gross (Missoula, MT: Scholars Press, 1977).

⁷³⁸ Susan A. Landesman, *The Tārā Tantra: Tārā’s Fundamental Ritual Text (Tārā-mūla-kalpa)* (New York: Co-published by The American Institute of Buddhist Studies and Wisdom Publications in association with the Columbia University Center for Buddhist Studies and Tibet House US, 2020).

⁷³⁹ Susan S. Landesman, “Goddess Tārā: Silence and Secrecy on the Path to Enlightenment,” *Journal of Feminist Studies in Religion* 24, no. 1 (2008): 55; For a study of the later development of Tārā as one of the ten *mahāvidyās* in Brahmanism, see: S. Shankararayanan, *The Ten Great Cosmic Powers: Daśa Mahāvidyās*, 4th ed. (Chennai: Samata Books, 1972); David R. Kinsley, *Tantric Visions of the Divine Feminine: The Ten Mahavidyas* (Berkeley: University of California Press, 1997); For a recent study on *Yoginīs* and *Mahāvidyās* in the *Kāmarūpa-interstice* see: Jae-Eun Shin, “Yoni, Yoginīs and Mahāvidyās: Feminine Divinities from Early Medieval Kāmarūpa to Medieval Koch Behar,” *Studies in History* 26, no. 1 (2010): 1–29; Jae-Eun Shin, *Change, Continuity and Complexity: The Mahavidyas in East Indian Śākta Traditions* (London: Routledge, 2018).

⁷⁴⁰ Elizabeth English, *Vajrayoginī: Her Visualizations, Rituals & Forms: A Study of the Cult of Vajrayoginī in India* (Boston: Wisdom Publications, 2002).

Sādhnamālā, she manifests in up to twenty-five distinct forms⁷⁴¹. In the Vajrayāna context, these conceptual developments were elaborated through psychosexual symbolism: masculine and feminine deities, each with consorts, symbolising mental states, and their union representing enlightened androgyny. As also very astutely observed by Alan Spoonberg, Vajrayāna masters recognised that undeveloped psychic energy could be simultaneously destructive and transformative, and they devised complex visualisation practices enabling qualified practitioners to manifest and integrate even the most demonic aspect of their psyche: the liberate potential of such subterranean forces was often personified in the *ḍākinī* (sky dancer), whose manifestations range from terrifying and demonic to seductively enchanting⁷⁴².

The Newari ritual elaboration of Prajñāpāramitā represents the final irruption in the *evental continuum* this chapter has traced: a moment in which the iconographic and doctrinal intensifications of the Pāla period were not just preserved but actively transformed within a living ritual tradition, demonstrating that the event of Prajñāpāramitā's diasporic imagination did not conclude with the end of Pāla period patronage but continued to thrive in new forms and in new contexts. Within the Newar Buddhist traditions, which continue to provide a rare surviving instance of Prajñāpāramitā devotion, the deity's interpretation is principally rooted in a tantric framework, frequently depicted as a feminine divine figure during ritual observances. However, as a communal and societal practice, the principles of *prajñāpāramitā* are deeply embedded in Newar Buddhist communities, where the acts of transcribing, revering, preserving, and honouring the *Prajñāpāramitā* manuscript are regarded as acts of great merit, with many upper-caste Newar households possessing such a text, as extensively documented in Kim's study of the manuscript cult in Nepal. Beyond textual

⁷⁴¹ James B. Apple, "Atiśa's System of Twenty-One Tārās," *Revue d'Études Tibétaines*, no. 66 (April 2023): 425.

⁷⁴² Alan Sponberg, "Attitudes toward Women and the Feminine in Early Buddhism," in *Buddhism, Sexuality, and Gender*, ed. José Ignacio Cabezón (Albany, NY: State University of New York Press, 1992), 27; Anne C. Klein, "Nondualism and the Great Bliss Queen," *Journal of Feminist Studies in Religion* 1, no. 1 (Spring 1985): 73–98; Reginald A. Ray, "Accomplished Women in Tantric Buddhism of Medieval India and Tibet," in *Unspoken Worlds*, ed. Nancy Auer Falk and Rita M. Gross (San Francisco: Harper & Row, 1980); Keith Dowman, *Masters of the Mahamudra: Songs and Histories of the Eighty-Four Buddhist Siddhas* (Albany: State University of New York Press, 1985); Keith Dowman, *Sky Dancer: The Secret Life and Songs of the Lady Yeshe Tsogyel* (London: Routledge & Kegan Paul, 1984); Tsultrim Allione, *Women of Wisdom* (London: Routledge & Kegan Paul, 1984).

artefacts, the conceptual essence of Prajñāpāramitā manifests in numerous Newar rites and ceremonies, including birth, death, and matrimonial events, exemplifying the ingrained reverence for the Prajñāpāramitā cult and the veneration of *prajñā* within Newar society. In his 1992 study, Gellner provided some examples on how Prajñāpāramitā is imagined in contemporary Nepal. The first is a conversation with a priest:

People say that those who know what is right and wrong (tyah and ma tyah), and do what is good (bhigu), have the Perfection of Wisdom or have seen the Perfection of Wisdom. Those people who are always fighting haven't, and don't know any dharma. But you can't actually see her, or if you do see her, there's nothing there (chu ma ru). She's emptiness (śūnyatā) and dharma. (Jog Maya Shakyā)⁷⁴³

At the Kvābhāḥ or the Hiranyavarṇa Mahāvihāra in Patan (Lalitpur) Nepal, where ritual veneration and a restoration ceremony of a *Prajñāpāramitā* manuscript is performed⁷⁴⁴, while the ultimate perfection is embodied as a goddess and equated with the Dharma or Buddhist doctrine in general, the ten elders of the monastery are commonly designated as the 'Ten Perfections,' whereas in smaller monasteries housing only five elders, these figures are associated with the Five Buddhas⁷⁴⁵. As noted by Gellner, The *Svayambhūpurāṇa*, a fourteenth-sixteenth century CE Buddhist scripture about the origin and development of Kathmandu valley from a quasi-mythic historical perspective⁷⁴⁶, appropriates the deity Prajñāpāramitā, referred to as "Guhyeśvarī Prajñāpāramitā" within the sacred geography of the Kathmandu valley:

⁷⁴³ David N. Gellner, *Monk, Householder, and Tantric Priest: Newar Buddhism and Its Hierarchy of Ritual* (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 1992), 117.

⁷⁴⁴ See: Kim, *Receptacle of the Sacred*, 271-285; Christoph Emmrich, "Emending Perfection: Prescript, Postscript, and Practice in Newar Buddhist Manuscript Culture," in *Buddhist Manuscript Cultures*, 140-156.

⁷⁴⁵ Gellner, *Monk, Householder, and Tantric Priest*, 120.

⁷⁴⁶ The text, not particularly a *purāṇa* in the Brahmanical sense of the word, but an "*uddesa*," has been extolled as a *mahātmya* tailored for Buddhists. Gellner noted the text's important role in delineating and validating the sacred historical and geographical milieu within which Newar Buddhists reside, a framework articulated in the recited 'Ādya Mahādāna,' influencing subsequent texts and ritual cycles, rendering its narratives more familiar to lay Buddhists than the contents of other canonical works (Gellner, *Monk, Householder, and Tantric Priest*, 196, 366). Also see: Sylvain Lévi, *Le Népal: Étude historique d'un royaume hindou*, 3 vols. (Paris: Leroux, 1905; reissued Kathmandu and Paris: Raj de Condappa, Le Toit du Monde, and Éditions Errance, 1986).

[...] in the place of the caitya Śrī Svayambhūti, which is presided over (adhiṣṭhita) by Śrī Guhyeśvarī Prajñāpāramitā, in the land presided over by Śrī Mañjuśrī, in the land (or maṇḍala) of Nepāla, which has the form of the maṇḍala of Śrī Saṃvara [i.e., Cakrasaṃvara, the main Buddhist Tantric deity]⁷⁴⁷.

The precise taxonomic situating of Newar Buddhist feminine deities within the doctrinal triptych of Mahāyāna, exoteric Vajrayāna, and esoteric Vajrayāna, is a hermeneutic challenge. In the ritual veneration context, as noted by Gellner, Vajrayoginī emerges as an anchor, orchestrating a synthesis that unites exoteric deities, such as Tārā, Kumārī, and the Eight Mothers, with their esoteric counterparts, the consorts Vajravārāhī (paired with Cakrasaṃvara), Jñānadākinī (paired with Yogāmbara), and Nairātmyā (paired with Hevajra). Gellner mentioned an example from Sankhu, where Vajrayoginī is the tutelary deity, who is “simultaneously identified” with Prajñāpāramitā, Ugrātārā and Durgā⁷⁴⁸. Within a ritual framework, cited as an example by Gellner, a singular liturgical structure is deployed, with nominal substitutions applied to both the *dharma maṇḍala*, where Prajñāpāramitā assumes the central role, and the *saṅgha maṇḍala*, entered on Avalokiteśvara⁷⁴⁹.

Gellner also provided some interesting observations on Newari matrimonial ceremonies. The powder container, used in Newari marriage rituals is linked to the bride’s mother, as it resembles a tiered *stūpa* symbolising feminine ultimate wisdom (*prajñā*), while the mirror, representing the impermanent world and masculine means (*upāya*) to the ultimate, is associated with the father⁷⁵⁰. In the Newari Buddhist tradition, it is often maintained that as a householder, one cannot attain either worldly or otherworldly fruits (*bhukti mukti phala*) without observing the family *dharma*. To fulfil this duty, one must marry and have a wife (*śakti*⁷⁵¹), as without her, no rites and rituals, such as the observances (*vrata*) can be deemed complete. Thus the family *dharma* must be practiced in

⁷⁴⁷ Gellner, *Monk, Householder, and Tantric Priest*, 191.

⁷⁴⁸ Gellner, *Monk, Householder, and Tantric Priest*, 256.

⁷⁴⁹ Gellner, *Monk, Householder, and Tantric Priest*, 222.

⁷⁵⁰ Gellner, *Monk, Householder, and Tantric Priest*, 367.

⁷⁵¹ The female consort of a male deity is termed *śakti*, a usage originating in the Hindu *Tantras* and underlying the designation of a tantric devotee of the Hindu goddess as a Śākta. Although the term does not occur in Buddhist tantric scriptures, Newar Buddhists employ it in this sense. By extension, they also use *śakti*, at times “half-jocularly” to denote a wife (Gellner, *Monk, Householder, and Tantric Priest*, 130-131).

conjunction with a *śakti*. As taught by the Buddha, even a man endowed with all virtues cannot sustain his family *dharma* without *śakti* or *prajñā*. This principle is also affirmed in the *nīti śāstras* (treatises on conduct)⁷⁵². The contemporary Nepalese association of *prajñā* or *śakti* with the matrimonial figure of the wife is a dual-edged phenomenon: on the one hand, it exemplifies a constrictive narrative paradigm that constrains the feminine conceptualisation of *Prajñāpāramitā*, and, I argue, also suggests a diminished agency for women within the religious and social fabric of Buddhist life, where their roles are predominantly confined to sanctioned, legitimate functions within a male-centric patriarchal order. On the other hand, this serves as an example of the enduring veneration of *prajñā* in modern Newari society, albeit a reverence that manifests as an elevated pedestalisation of the feminine, a tribute exacted at the steep price of their social marginalisation and, in certain lived contexts, their exploitation, exposing a sophisticated relationship between ideological exaltation and material subjugation.

A full account of *Prajñāpāramitā*'s transmission into East Asian Buddhist traditions lies beyond the scope of this study, which focusses on the South and Central Asian trajectories most directly relevant to the Pāla period manuscripts under examination. In the context of Chinese Buddhism, Miriam L. Levering noted that Chinese Chan Buddhism⁷⁵³, later known in Japan as Zen, has since the time of Ma-tsu Tao-i's disciples (709-788 CE) emphasised equality, suggesting that wealth, status, or age are irrelevant to achieving enlightenment. Rooted in the *Prajñāpāramitā* tradition, this view primarily propagated that distinguishing characteristics (*lakṣaṇa*⁷⁵⁴) exist only in the transient, relative realm and lack inherent substance. Huang-p'o Hsi-yun (?-849 CE) warned that focussing on such distinctions can foster attachment and delusion. This also corresponds with the Chan belief that all beings have an "originally enlightened mind," which doesn't require any further attainment or perfection. Before 1005 CE, references to gender equality in relation to enlightenment are rare, appearing notably in accounts of Sung dynasty masters Ta-hui Tsung-kao (1089-1163 CE)

⁷⁵² Gellner, *Monk, Householder, and Tantric Priest*, 229.

⁷⁵³ Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 174-175.

⁷⁵⁴ Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 463.

and Hung-chih Cheng-chüeh (1091-1157 CE), both of whom were leading figures in the Linji⁷⁵⁵ lineage⁷⁵⁶.

2.4 Imaging Prajñāpāramitā in the Pāla-period

Within the continuum of narrative temporality, including both textual and visual articulations, the conceptualisation of Prajñāpāramitā during the Pāla-period can be positioned within the sustained proliferation of its thematic and doctrinal motifs across the Indian subcontinent and beyond, antecedent to and concurrent with this epoch. In eastern India, this period was marked by a surge in devotional fervour, and importantly, the inclusive engagement of diverse social groups through the praxis offered by esoteric imagery and *siddha* literature. This evolution unfolded gradually, as Prajñāpāramitā became engrained into the Pāla iconographic lexicon, as seen in different examples of manuscript illuminations of the deity in the previous chapter. This also paralleled the development of *prajñā* visualisation, which often manifested through symbolic elements such as the *pustaka* and the *utpala*. The inherent ambivalence and fluidity of Prajñāpāramitā's conceptualisation, further facilitated expansive interpretations, rendering the goddess adaptable to different contexts and amenable to syncretic assimilations with other deities.

On some of the earliest visual motifs found on the medallions at Bharhut, which depict scenes from the *jātakas*, portraying *bodhisattvas* performing different virtuous deeds, which later came to be associated with the six *pāramitās*, when *dhyāna* and *prajñā* were added to it, Lamotte noted:

On the medallions of the balustrade at Bhārhut, a good forty jātakas have been identified during which the future Buddha, embodied in human or animal form, sometimes male and sometimes female, performs virtuous deeds of giving (*dāna*), morality (*śīla*), patience (*kṣānti*) and vigour (*vīrya*) which were one day to lead him to supreme and perfect Enlightenment. The representation at

⁷⁵⁵ Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 475-476.

⁷⁵⁶ Miriam L. Levering, "Lin-chi (Rinzai) Ch'an and Gender: The Rhetoric of Equality and the Rhetoric of Heroism," in *Buddhism, Sexuality, and Gender*, ed. José Ignacio Cabezón (Albany, NY: State University of New York Press, 1991), 137–58.

Bhārhut of the Bodhisattva in a female form is a demonstrated fact: over this point, the old sculptors plainly part company from the monastic compilers of the Jātaka, who excluded any female rebirth from their collection. Of the great deeds of the Bodhisattva, the artists at Bhārhut gave preference to the exploits illustrating the “lay” virtues of the future Buddha: morality, patience, vigour and especially giving. The Mahāyānist theoreticians were to incorporate those virtues into the list of six perfections (pāramitā) which in their eyes constitute the crux of the bodhisattva path; they were to add the virtues of ecstasy (dhyāna) and wisdom (prajñā), more appropriate to the religious and, for that very reason, not illustrated by the old artists⁷⁵⁷.

Kinnard argued that during the Pāla-period, when *Prajñāpāramitā* concepts had already permeated Buddhist thought and culture, an image of the Buddha in the *dharmacakrapravartanamudrā* perhaps conveyed more than just the Śākyamuni’s first sermon: also signifying the centrality of *prajñā*, as the core of the Dharma, which enables its revelation and the turning of the *dharmacakra*. While not equating the Buddha directly with *prajñā*, Kinnard noted that the *AsP* mentions Ānanda being instructed to venerate the *Prajñāpāramitā* similar to a Buddha, further observing that the *dharmacakrapravartanamudrā*, as described by James Burgess a century ago, symbolises the embodiment of wisdom in material form, a view Kinnard found apt due to its effective capturing of how abstract *prajñā* is concretely represented. The Śākyamuni’s association with *prajñā*, central to his triumph over Māra and enlightenment, dates to early Buddhist imagery. Through what Kinnard terms “resonant iconography,” he suggested that Pāla-period Buddha images visually expressed *prajñā*⁷⁵⁸.

While *Prajñāpāramitā*’s conceptualisation as mother, teacher, and guide to Buddhahood predates her iconographic emergence, it is not until the seventh century CE, within the Pāla dynasty’s cultural matrix, that her visual forms proliferate, as evidenced by textual and archaeological records. Tantric meditations evoke *Prajñāpāramitā* from *bīja* (seed ⁷⁵⁹) *mantras*, visualising her in

⁷⁵⁷ Lamotte, *History of Indian Buddhism*, 404.

⁷⁵⁸ Kinnard, *Imaging Wisdom*, 95-96.

⁷⁵⁹ Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 119.

anthropomorphic forms. By dissolving individuality into *sūnyatā* and reconstituting identity as divine, practitioners absorb her enlightened attributes, advancing towards awakening. The embodiment of wisdom within Mahāyāna traditions manifested female deities with titles such as *dhāraṇī* (“the holder”) and *vidyā*, where associated deities and their *mantras* were designated *vidyā-dhāraṇī*⁷⁶⁰. The *Prajñāpāramitā* texts introduced *bija-mantras*, *vidyā*, and *dhāraṇī*, incorporating tantric elements and ritualistic potency for penance, pestilence alleviation, and merit accrual⁷⁶¹. The *Prajñāpāramitāhṛdayasūtrā* highlights the *mantra*: “*Om gaté gaté paragate parasamgaté bodhi svāhā*” as encapsulating the entire *Prajñāpāramitā* doctrine, and hence also termed “*Prajñāpāramitā-dhāraṇī*”⁷⁶². Although some early thinkers like Nāgārjuna, Asaṅga, and Vasubandhu extolled the maternal essence tied to *prajñā*, in tantric contexts, these terms evolved into *prajñā*, redefining goddesses as spiritual partners of the *dhyāni* Buddhas or counterparts to tantric practitioners, translating into depictions imbued with esoteric attributes⁷⁶³. These practices, encoded in *sādhanas*⁷⁶⁴, guide *sādhakas* or *siddhas* (accomplished⁷⁶⁵) through intricate mental, verbal, and physical rituals: *mantra* (spell/ charm⁷⁶⁶), *mudrā* (seal/ mark/ sign⁷⁶⁷), and visionary panoramas which constitute the *devatā yoga* (deity yoga⁷⁶⁸), primarily preserved in the *Sādhanamālā*⁷⁶⁹.

The *Sādhanamālā* preserves nine *sādhanas* for invoking the goddess *Prajñāpāramitā*, with a tenth, attributed to Kamalaśīla (ca. 740-795 CE⁷⁷⁰), found in the Tibetan Buddhist canon. In

⁷⁶⁰ Shaw, *Buddhist Goddesses of India*, 185.

⁷⁶¹ Conze, *The Prajñāpāramitā Literature*, 12-13.

⁷⁶² Hixon, *Mother of the Buddhas*, 81; In the Newari context, for a study of the *saptavāra* tradition of Newar Buddhists, where a group of *dhāraṇīs* is associated with seven days of the week, with each *dhāraṇī* recited on a specific day, and also represented in miniature paintings in manuscripts and wood carvings in Newar Buddhist monasteries, see: Gudrun Bühnemann, “A Dhāraṇī for Each Day of the Week: The Saptavāra Tradition of the Newar Buddhists,” *Bulletin of the School of Oriental and African Studies* 77, no. 1 (2014): 119–36. In this study, Bühnemann demonstrated that despite the initial male identity of two *saptavāra* group members, the collective perception eventually shifted to a feminine conceptualisation in the Kathmandu valley.

⁷⁶³ Bhattacharya, “Motherhood in the realm of eastern Indian and Himalayan Art”: 12.

⁷⁶⁴ Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 731-732.

⁷⁶⁵ Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 816.

⁷⁶⁶ Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 529.

⁷⁶⁷ Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 551.

⁷⁶⁸ Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 235.

⁷⁶⁹ Apple, “*Prajñāpāramitā*,” 11-12; Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 732; Daniel Cozort, “*Sādhana* (sgrub thabs): Means of Achievement for Deity Yoga,” in *Tibetan Literature: Studies in Genre*, ed. José Ignacio Cabezón and Roger R. Jackson (Ithaca, NY: Snow Lion Publications, 1996), 331–43.

⁷⁷⁰ Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 411-412.

these texts, Prajñāpāramitā is predominantly depicted in golden colour, though occasionally in white, and visualised with either two or four arms, one face, and all the characteristic ornaments of a goddess. She is described as seated in the *vajraparyāṅka*⁷⁷¹ (*vajra* posture), signifying meditative concentration (*samādhi*) that, like a diamond, cuts through all forms of delusion and dualistic thought. Her iconographic features: *mudrās*, attributes, and ritual implements, correspond with awakened qualities. Prajñāpāramitā is often shown performing the *dharmacakramudrā*⁷⁷², symbolising the *dharmacakrapravartana* (turning of the wheel of Dharma⁷⁷³) and her role in expounding the Buddha's teachings. The *vitarkamudrā*⁷⁷⁴, with the hand raised, and ring finger touching the thumb, signifies the dialectical method of the *Prajñāpāramitāsūtras* in disrupting logical and discursive preconceptions, which is indispensable for achieving a state of *nirvikalpa* (non-conceptual⁷⁷⁵) and *advayajñāna* (non-dual knowledge⁷⁷⁶). The *abhayamudrā*⁷⁷⁷, with raised arm and outward palm signifies Prajñāpāramitā as the ultimate source of fearlessness that arises from the realisation of her teachings. Attributes of the deity include the *utpala* (lotus), denoting purity, and the *pustaka* (book) of *Prajñāpāramitāsūtras*, held in the left hand (*vāmahaste*), which embodies her doctrinal core⁷⁷⁸.

Sporadic finds of Prajñāpāramitā images have been reported from throughout the Gangetic plains, northwestern, eastern and northeastern Indian subcontinent: mostly at sites associated with scholastic monasticism. A number of small bronze images associated with the deity Prajñāpāramitā have been found in the Magadha region (Patna-Nalanda-Gaya circuit), especially at monastic sites like Nalanda and Kukrihar, mostly from around the ninth-tenth centuries CE. Most of these images are similar, seated four-armed Prajñāpāramitās, with some depictions of the deity with two arms. The iconography remains very conventional: her lower hands in the *dhyānamudrā* or the *varadamudrā*;

⁷⁷¹ Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 955-956.

⁷⁷² Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 243.

⁷⁷³ Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 243.

⁷⁷⁴ Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 983.

⁷⁷⁵ Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 591.

⁷⁷⁶ Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 19.

⁷⁷⁷ Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 2.

⁷⁷⁸ Bhattacharyya, *The Indian Buddhist Iconography*, 107-199; Marie-Thérèse de Mallmann, *Introduction à l'Iconographie du Tāntrisme Bouddhique* (Paris: Librairie Adrien-Maisonneuve, 1975), 305-7; Dipak Chandra Bhattacharyya, *Studies in Buddhist Iconography* (New Delhi: Manohar, 2004), 29-67; Apple, "Prajñāpāramitā," 12-13; Edward Conze, "On the Iconography of the Prajñāpāramitā," *Oriental Art* 3 (1949): 47-52; 3 (1950-51).

with the upper hands often depicted as holding a lotus, on which is represented a book; or an *akṣamālā*⁷⁷⁹.

The iconographic evolution of Prajñāpāramitā imagery within the eastern Indian milieu, has been discussed in the first chapter with regards to the assimilation of the attendants of Tārā: Jaṅgulī and Mahāmāyūrī as her own consorts. The continuities between Prajñāpāramitā and another popular wisdom deity: Sarasvatī, has also been discussed previously. This evolution, can be seen as part of a broader conceptual fluidity that permeates the ontology of depiction of these images, rendering the category of deities associated with wisdom, or *prajñā*, as a permeable and mutable construct, wherein the attributes and intrinsic qualities of these female divinities merge into one another. As discussed before, Kinnard suggested the interpretive elasticity of *prajñā* itself, when it comes to Pāla-period images, elucidating how even the archetypal Buddha image transcends its nominal form to articulate the profound ideals of *prajñā*, expanding the semiotic horizon beyond anthropomorphic confines into a realm of intellectual abstraction. Similarly, *prajñā* as an emblematic attribute, materialises through a repertoire of signifying motifs: objects, visual idioms, gestures, composure etc., that circulate with interchangeability among the deities associated with *prajñā* in the Pāla repertoire: Prajñāpāramitā, Cundā, and Mañjuśrī. One such example of depiction of *prajñā* is the book on top of an *utpala* motif:

The book on top of an utpala became a ubiquitous marker of the Wisdom related deities in Pāla Buddhist art, including Mañjuśrī, Cundā, and Prajñāpāramitā ... established as a visual code to signal wisdom in Buddhist iconography, including that of Mañjuśrī as bodhisattva of wisdom⁷⁸⁰.

In terms of the attributes associated with Prajñāpāramitā, these same attributes (*utpala*, *pustaka*, *akṣamālā* etc.) are often depicted *inter alia*, for some other female divinities as well, especially Cundā⁷⁸¹, a female divinity who was particularly popular and revered during the Pāla-

⁷⁷⁹ Debjani Paul, *The Art of Nālandā: Development of Buddhist Sculpture, A.D. 600–1200* (New Delhi: Munshiram Manoharlal Publishers, 1995), [page number].

⁷⁸⁰ Kim, "Goddess Prajñāpāramitā and Esoteric Buddhism in Jayavarman VII's Angkor," 174.

⁷⁸¹ Bhattacharyya, *Sādhanamālā*, vol. 1, 271, 352; Bhattacharyya, *Nispannayogāvalī*, 49, 57, 89; Bhattacharyya, *The Indian Buddhist Iconography*, 219-224, 340.

period, and Cundā images have been found, although disproportionately, across both the *Magadha-Varendra-constellation*, as well as the *Samataṭa-littoral*⁷⁸². Cundā has previously often been subject to a very limited interpretation as a precursor to Durgā⁷⁸³. One iconographic distinction which is often used, is the presence of the *pātra* (container) which can be an indication of the deity Cundā, which leaves open the interpretive window that many of these images discussed below as Prajñāpāramitā, may well be interpreted as Cundā⁷⁸⁴. Miranda Shaw noted that most depictions represent Cundā with four arms, and the following attributes: an alms bowl, the *varadamudrā*, and a *pustaka* on an *utpala*. Shaw suggested that the vessel: in different forms (*kamaṇḍalu*, *pātra* etc), is Cundā's most characteristic feature⁷⁸⁵. Puspa Niyogi similarly observed that Cundā's imagery typically feature the *dhyanamudrā* or the *varadamudrā*, and the *pātra* as her attributes, distinguishable from Prajñāpāramitā⁷⁸⁶. As pointed out by Kinnard, Cundā is textually described in the *Nispannayogāvalī* and the *Śikṣasamuccaya*, using the same “mother of all Buddhas” language associated with the description of Prajñāpāramitā⁷⁸⁷. Kinnard suggested that the lesser number of surviving Cundā images from the Bihar and Bengal regions (most are smaller copper-alloy pieces, and some examples in stone, mainly from Nalanda and Kukrihar), and the relatively large number of Cundā images recovered from Odisha⁷⁸⁸ may suggest the deity's popularity beyond the “Pāla region

⁷⁸² J. E. van Lohuizen-de Leeuw, “The Pattikerā Chundā and Variation of Her Image,” in *Nalini Kanta Bhattasali Commemoration Volume*, ed. A. B. M. Habibullah (Dacca: Dacca Museum, 1966), 117–43; Marie-Thérèse de Mallmann, Introduction à l'iconographie du tantrisme bouddhique (Paris: Librairie Adrien-Maisonneuve, 1975), 143; Thomas E. Donaldson, *Iconography of the Buddhist Sculpture of Orissa*, vol. 1 (New Delhi: Abhinav Publications, 2001), 282–287; Puspa Niyogi, “Cundā—A Popular Buddhist Goddess,” *East and West* 27 (1977): 299–310; Janice Leoshko, “The Iconography of Buddhist Sculptures of the Pāla and Sena Periods from Bodhgaya” (PhD diss., The Ohio State University, 1987), 303–305; Sudarshan Devi Singhal, “Iconography of Cundā,” in *The Art and Culture of South-East Asia*, ed. Lokesh Chandra (New Delhi: Academy of Indian Culture and Aditya Prakashan, 1991), 385–410.

⁷⁸³ Alice Getty, *The Gods of Northern Buddhism: Their History and Iconography* (New York: Dover Publications, 1928), 93; Edward Conze, *Thirty Years of Buddhist Studies* (Columbia: University of South Carolina Press, 1968), 254–55;

⁷⁸⁴ Kinnard, *Imaging Wisdom*, 125, Note: 22, 128: Note 76.

⁷⁸⁵ Shaw, *Buddhist Goddesses of India*, 267–268.

⁷⁸⁶ Niyogi, “Cundā—A Popular Buddhist Goddess”: 308.

⁷⁸⁷ Kinnard, *Imaging Wisdom*, 127.

⁷⁸⁸ See Thomas E. Donaldson, *Iconography of the Buddhist Sculpture of Orissa*, vol. 1 (New Delhi: Abhinav Publications, 2001), 282–287; In his study of Cundā images from Odisha, Donaldson identified the *pātra* as Cundā's primary attribute. He described two main iconographic forms: with the deity's principal hands holding a vessel on her lap; in the other, often multi-armed, she performs the distinctive *mudrā*. In four-armed images she typically carries a bowl and a book, while in two-armed forms she holds a rosary and a *kamaṇḍalu* (Donaldson, *Iconography of the Buddhist Sculpture*, 284); for Prajñāpāramitā images from Odisha, see 270–281, esp. 276–281.

proper”. The motif of the *pustaka* is constant across all depictions of Cundā, which is also often found as attributes of Mañjuśrī and a range of female divinities in the Pāla-period, including Tārā (who also merges with Cundā to evolve into Cundā-Tārā, an emanation of Tārā, considered only second in importance to the “original Tārā⁷⁸⁹”): all of whom can be linked with *prajñā*, rendering the motif of the *pustaka* to become “... the signifier of *prajñā*, to the point that it is quite literally placed on a pedestal.”⁷⁹⁰ Based on the deity’s three main attributes: the *pātra*, *pustaka* and *varadamudrā*, Cundā has also been argued to have evolved from the prototype of Sujātā, a young girl who served rice-milk to the Buddha following his *nirvāṇa*⁷⁹¹.

Similarly, Mañjuśrī is also described as a *bodhisattva* quintessentially associated with *prajñā*⁷⁹², referred to in some textual sources, as the “mother and father” of all Buddhas⁷⁹³. Mañjuśrī is closely associated with *prajñā* from the earliest *Prajñāpāramitā* texts, considered to be second in prominence only to *Prajñāpāramitā* herself⁷⁹⁴. Kinnard suggested that Mañjuśrī came to be associated visually with *prajñā* from the eight-ninth centuries CE onwards. Two of the primary attributes of Mañjuśrī are the *pustaka* and a sword, the latter signifying how *prajñā* slashes through the veil of ignorance⁷⁹⁵. However in some images from the early Pāla-period, provenanced to Nalanda, these iconographic attributes (*pustaka* or sword) are absent, which have been argued to be based on earlier artistic models of Mañjuśrī, notable examples of which can be found at sites such as Ellora. In the Pāla-period however, most Mañjuśrī images are depicted with the standard attributes of a sword and a *pustaka*⁷⁹⁶.

⁷⁸⁹ Juyan Zhang, “Tārā, Cundā, and Their Prototypes: Exploring the Origins of the Two Buddhist Goddesses,” *Journal of Feminist Studies in Religion* 39, no. 1 (April 2023): 30,

⁷⁹⁰ Kinnard, *Imaging Wisdom*, 122-124.

⁷⁹¹ Zhang, “Tārā, Cundā, and Their Prototypes”: 34-43.

⁷⁹² Williams, *Mahāyāna Buddhism*, 238.

⁷⁹³ Akira Hirakawa, *A History of Indian Buddhism from Śākyamuni to Early Mahāyāna*, ed. and trans. Paul Groner (Honolulu: University of Hawaii Press, 1990), 251.

⁷⁹⁴ Marie-Thérèse de Mallmann, *Etude iconographique sur Mañjuśrī*, *Publications de l'École Française d'Extrême-Orient*, vol. 55 (Paris: École Française d'Extrême-Orient, 1964), esp. 23-46 [translated to English by author]; Cf. Etienne Lamotte, “Mañjuśrī,” *T'oung Pao* 78 (1969): 1–96.

⁷⁹⁵ Bhattacharyya, *Sādhnamālā*, vol. 1, 49; Bhattacharyya, *Nispannayogāvalī*, 48; Bhattacharyya, *The Indian Buddhist Iconography*, 94-95, 100-123.

⁷⁹⁶ Kinnard, *Imaging Wisdom*, 136-139.

In the section below, I will be briefly exploring some iconographic representations of Prajñāpāramitā from eastern India, other than those encountered in manuscript illustrations, discussed in the first chapter.

(A) Stone Prajñāpāramitā image at the Asian Art Museum in San Francisco (Acc. No. B62S32+)

This Prajñāpāramitā image⁷⁹⁷, measuring 66 cm x 30.5 cm x 16.5 cm, made of a greyish-black stone, presently housed in the Avery Brundage Collection at the Asian Art Museum in San Francisco (Plate 59), is from eastern India (Bihar) speculated to be from Nalanda. It is devoid of an inscription that mentions the date, but based on stylistic analysis, scholars tend to date it to the mid-ninth century (ca. 825-875 CE). The mandorla behind the deity is inscribed with the conventional Pāla Buddhist epithet, “y(e) dharmmā hetuprabhavā he(tun) te shā(m) ...,” and also contains information about its dedication, which reads: “kikābhap(ū)rvasya”, which has been interpreted as: the donor of the image was a person called Kikābhapurva. The goddess is seated in the *vajraparyāṅkāśana*, is depicted with *śaṅkukarṇas*, is two armed which are held in the gesture of the *dharmacakrapravartanamudrā*, and is flanked on both sides by two *nīlotpalas* (blue lotus), which emerge from beneath her both arms, and on top of each of these lotuses is a *pustaka* (book). The goddess is depicted with elaborate ornamentation, including *kaṅṭhahara*, *keyūra*, and large circular *patrakuṇḍalas*. She wears a very translucent *uttarīya* and lower garment, both of which are decorated with ornate patterns. Both the *uttarīya* and the *upavīta*, the latter having a beaded appearance, are draped over the deity’s left shoulder. The goddess is flanked on both sides by two attendants, who can be Jāṅgulī on the deity’s left, holding a stalk of lotus, and Mahāmāyūrī on the deity’s right, holding a bunch of peacock tail-feathers in her left hand. At the base of the stele, below the double lotus throne, are depicted four pillar-like structures which spatially segregate this area, within a

⁷⁹⁷ “Prajnaparamita, the Buddhist deity of transcendent wisdom,” *Asian Art Museum Collection*, accessed July 27, 2025, Asian Art Museum, <https://searchcollection.asianart.org/objects/11183/prajnaparamita-the-buddhist-deity-of-transcendent-wisdom>; Kinnard, *Imaging Wisdom*, 117-118, Fig. 1; Shaw, *Buddhist Goddesses of India*, 174, Fig. 8.1.

cavity-like structure: resembling a *caitya* cave, between two lions, two devotees, and a deer. The mandorla is surrounded by a thick decorative pattern, and a band of flaming fire. Stylistically, the overall execution of the sculpture is very refined, and renders an elegance of appearance.

(B) Two copper-alloy Prajñāpāramitā images at the Nalanda Museum (Acc. No. Not available)

Plate 60 is a ninth century copper-alloy image of Prajñāpāramitā from Nalanda at the Nalanda Museum⁷⁹⁸. The goddess is depicted with four hands, seated in *vajraparyāṅka* on a double-petalled lotus throne. The four hands of the goddess have the following attributes:

Thread (*akṣamālā*) | Lotus (*utpala*) with manuscript (*pustaka*)

Vardamudrā | Shallow dish (*pātra*)

She is portrayed with elaborate ornamentation: wearing an elaborate *mukuṭa* with intricate designing; and *kañṭhahara*, *keyūra*, and *kuṇḍala*. The goddess has her eyes wide open, but when viewed from specific angles gives the impression of a serene downward looking gesture. The folds of her *uttarīya* which is flung over left shoulder is portrayed very exquisitely. She has a prominent *ūrṇā*, and locks of hair fall on her shoulder. The mandorla behind the goddess is surrounded by interlocked beads and a band of flaming fire, reminiscent of depictions in manuscripts. At the top of this structure is a filial which has a forward extending projection, which could have originally extended upwards but has been bent, or might be a later addition, perhaps used to hold and carry the image: the latter having a much lesser possibility.

⁷⁹⁸ Kinnard, *Imaging Wisdom*, 121, Fig. 3.

The second image (Plate 61) is also a copper-alloy image of Prajñāpāramitā from Nalanda presently at the Nalanda Museum⁷⁹⁹, which shows the deity with two hands, also heavily ornamented, seated in *vajraparyāṅka* on a double-petalled lotus throne which is stylistically akin to the previous example. The two arms of the deity display the *dharmacakrapravartanamudrā*. Behind the deity on both sides are depicted two stalks of lotuses. The mandorla behind the goddess is also surrounded by interlocked beads and a band of flaming fire, which differ in design and execution from the previous example. This structure has a small filial protrusion at the top. Although the polish and the outer surface of these images are corroded: when compared to some other extant examples, these two images are in a considerably better state of preservation.

(C) Three copper-alloy Prajñāpāramitā images at the Patna Museum

These are three copper-alloy Prajñāpāramitā images presently at the Patna Museum, recovered from the vicinity of Nalanda, stylistically dateable to the ninth-tenth centuries CE. The first image⁸⁰⁰ (Plate 62; Patna Museum Acc. No. 8356; American Institute of Indian Studies [henceforth AIIS]⁸⁰¹ Acc. No. 8752, 110.56) measuring 15.5 cm in height, depicts the deity with four hands, seated in *vajraparyāṅka* on a double-petalled lotus throne. The four hands of the deity have the following attributes:

Thread (*akṣamālā*) | Lotus (*utpala*) with manuscript (*pustaka*)

Vardamudrā | Shallow dish (*pātra*)

The deity is similarly depicted with a serene expression, and elaborate ornamentation. A lock of hair falls on her left shoulder. The mandorla behind the goddess is surrounded by a wavy decorative pattern and a band of flaming fire, with the structure having a filial projection at the top in the shape

⁷⁹⁹ Kinnard, *Imaging Wisdom*, 121-122, Fig. 4; Shaw, *Buddhist Goddesses of India*, 174, Fig. 8.2.

⁸⁰⁰ Center for Art and Archaeology, "Prajnaparamita Seated, varadamudra", no. 8441, Patna Museum, ca. 800–899 CE, Virtual Museum of Images and Sounds (VMIS), accessed July 30, 2025, https://vmis.in/ArchiveCategories/collection_gallery_zoom?id=67&siteid=301&minrange=0&maxrange=0&assetid=96284&self_archive_id=172309&index=15&page=&count=24#focused_div_image.

⁸⁰¹ American Institute of Indian Studies (Digitised with financial support from the Ministry of Culture, Govt. of India).

of a *chatra* (parasol). A stalk of lotus with a lotus bud emerges from behind the deity's left side, which is held gracefully. A full-bloomed lotus is depicted atop behind this, supported by an extended frame which connects the outer structure with the inner structure i.e., the body of the deity, upon which is placed a *pustaka*. There could have been another stalk of lotus behind the deity's right side, which has been damaged, but can be discerned from the remnant of a similar extended structure of the frame. Stylistically, although there are similarities in the depiction of the *mukuṭa* and the lotus pedestal, with the Nalanda Museum examples, overall the execution is more voluminous, the figuration not very proportionate, but stylistically more elaborate than the previous examples, which lends to the image's aesthetic exquisiteness and graceful subtlety.

The second image⁸⁰² (Plate 63; Patna Museum Acc. No. 8441; AIIS Acc. No. 8754, 110.58), measuring 11 cm in height also shows the goddess with four hands, with the upper right hand damaged, seated in *vajraparyāṅka* on a double-petalled lotus throne. The remaining three hands have the following attributes:

Damaged | Lotus (*utpala*)

Vardamudrā | Shallow dish (*pātra*)

Although heavily damaged due to corrosion, the serene expression of the goddess can be discerned. The deity is similarly depicted with elaborate ornamentation, with the *mukuṭa* rendered slightly differently than the previous examples. The stele behind the deity which shows a mandorla, surrounded by interlocked bead patterns and a flaming band of fire, is executed uniquely compared to the previous examples discussed, as the stele is solid, unlike the previous examples, and lends a certain structural compositeness to the piece. Similar to the previous examples, there is a small filial projection at the top of the frame. Although the figuration is not precisely proportionate, there is a

⁸⁰² Center for Art and Archaeology, "Prajnaparamita seated, varadamudra", no. 8441, Patna Museum, ca. 800–899 CE. Virtual Museum of Images and Sounds (VMIS). Accessed July 30, 2025. https://vmis.in/ArchiveCategories/collection_gallery_zoom?id=67&siteid=301&minrange=0&maxrange=0&assetid=96284&self_archive_id=172309&index=15&page=&count=24#focused_div_image.

subtle balance between linearity and voluminousness. The large eyes, and prominent smiling expression of the deity, make this image stylistically different from any of the previous examples discussed. In the lotus throne, the petals have a more prominent edge, which is also a minor noticeable difference from the previous examples.

The third image⁸⁰³ (Plate 64; Patna Museum Acc. No. 8442; AIIS Acc. No. 8750, 110.59) measures 11.5 cm in height, and depicts the deity seated in *vajraparyāṅka* on a double-petalled lotus throne, with four hands which have the following attributes:

Thread (*akṣamālā*) | Lotus (*utpala*)

Vardamudrā | Shallow dish (*pātra*)

Although all of these copper-alloy pieces have been provenanced to the Nalanda region and its vicinity, this piece is also stylistically unique and different from the previous examples discussed. The deity is rendered with a serene composure, captured prominently by the eyes, even though damaged significantly due to corrosion. The stele behind the deity which shows a mandorla, is surrounded by interlocked bead patterns and there is an absence of a flaming band of fire: all of these are depicted on a solid stele, like the previous example. The deity is similarly depicted with elaborate ornamentation, with the *mukūṭa* rendered quite differently than the previous examples. The depiction of the goddess' jewellery, especially the *kañṭhahara*, has a unique design, and the *patrakuṇḍalas* which are more elaborate and ornamental, and *keyūras* which are executed very slenderly. The *uttarīya* features a thin piece of cloth flung on the deity's left shoulder, while locks of hair fall on her left shoulder. The figuration is very sophisticated and proportionate, neither very voluminous, not quite linear, but has been executed in a very angular and delicate manner, that lends to the image's overall slender appearance. The lotus stalk held by the goddess' upper left hand, is also executed

⁸⁰³ Center for Art and Archaeology, "Prajnaparamita seated, varadamudra", no. 8441, Patna Museum, ca. 800–899 CE. Virtual Museum of Images and Sounds (VMIS). Accessed July 30, 2025. https://vmis.in/ArchiveCategories/collection_gallery_zoom?id=67&siteid=301&minrange=0&maxrange=0&assetid=96284&self_archive_id=172309&index=15&page=&count=24#focused_div_image.

uniquely, with the lotus being not too overtly ornamental, but rendered in a minimal by stylistically sophisticated manner. There is a similar filial projection at the top of the frame. The lotus pedestal is very damaged which hinders its stylistic study, but from a very preliminary observation, it can be noticed, that unlike the previous examples, the upper half of the lotus pedestal is depicted more elaborately than the lower half, the latter having a crude unfinished appearance: this also might be due corrosion, and general wear and tear.

(D) A copper-alloy Prajñāpāramitā image at the Indian Museum (Acc. No. 9430/A24285)

Plate 65 is a ninth century copper-alloy image of Prajñāpāramitā, also recovered from the vicinity of Nalanda at the Indian Museum⁸⁰⁴. The four-armed deity is depicted seated in *vajraparyāṅka* on a double-petalled lotus throne. Similar to the iconography of some other examples discussed above, her lower right hand displays the *varadamudrā*, while her upper right hand holds an *akṣamālā*. The lower left hand rests upon her lap, palm outward, supporting a shallow dish (*pātra*), while the upper left hand grasps the stem of a lotus that supports a manuscript (*pustaka*), illustrated as follows:

Thread (*akṣamālā*) | Lotus (*utpala*)

Vardamudrā | Shallow dish (*pātra*)

Stylistically although there are several continuities with the previously discussed examples, for example the serene composure, and the elaborate ornamentation of the goddess, a double lotus pedestal, and the depiction of the mandorla surrounded by a pattern of interlocked beads and a flaming band of fire. But there are several differences as well, for example the depiction of the jewellery, especially the *kaṇṭhahara* which has a unique stringed-beads appearance and the *patrakuṇḍalas* which are depicted prominently falling on the deity's shoulders, along with locks of hair. The *uttarīya* and the lower garment feature decorative patterns, rendered through striations and small perforations.

⁸⁰⁴ Indian Museum, Kolkata, *Indian Buddhist Art*, archived exhibition, Google Arts & Culture, Indian Museum, Kolkata, February 2–May 31, 2016, accessed July 29, 2025, <https://artsandculture.google.com/story/indian-buddhist-art-indian-museum-kolkata/ZwWx9A-7JPwzJQ>.

The mandorla behind the deity is neither hollow, nor completely solid, but is stylistically rendered: with the outer band of flaming fire also depicted punctuated by spherical bead-like structures. The double lotus pedestal upon which the deity is seated, the top of which is also surrounded by interlocked beads, has been rendered very skilfully and exquisitely with both the upper and the lower parts of the pedestal receiving detailed artistic attention. The presence of the *akṣamālā* and *pustaka* would suggest an identification with Prajñāpāramitā. However, due to presence of the *varadamudrā* of the right hand and the *pātra* in the left, the image may also be interpreted depicting the goddess Cundā.

(E) A stone Prajñāpāramitā image at the Indian Museum

Plate 66 is a greyish stone image of Prajñāpāramitā from the vicinity of Nalanda at the Indian Museum⁸⁰⁵, and has been dated stylistically to the eleventh century CE. The stele behind the deity and the pedestal are both inscribed. The inscription records that the image was donated by Dharmasīrīpāla, and inhabitant of Banavāsī-Karṇnāṭa (North Kanara/ Canara). The deity is depicted with four hands, with the following attributes:

Lotus (*utpala*) | Lotus (*utpala*)

Shallow dish (*pātra*) | Shallow dish (*pātra*)

The two stalks of lotus which flank the deity on both sides, are gracefully held in the deity's hands. Each of these lotuses support a *pustaka*, rendered a bit linearly through striations in low relief, compared to the high relief of the lotuses and the deity herself. The goddess is depicted having a serene insightful composure and facial expression, and with elaborate ornamentation, especially large round *patrakuṇḍalas*, seated in *vajraparyāṅka* on a double-petalled lotus throne. A lock of hair falls on her right shoulder. The style of execution of the *kañṭhahara*, with bead-like motifs, is very similar to the copper-alloy example previously discussed. The *uttarīya* is depicted as very translucent and

⁸⁰⁵ *Archaeological Survey of India, Annual Reports of the Archaeological Survey of India for the Years 1930–31, 1931–32, 1932–33 & 1933–34*, ed. C. L. Fabri (Delhi: Manager of Publications, 1936), pt. 2, 257, pl. 127a; Shaw, *Buddhist Goddesses of India*, 176, Fig. 8.3.

fine slightly draped over the goddess's left shoulder. The deity's abdomen is depicted with very sharp preciseness, as it captures the muscular contractions of the abdominal muscles caused by deep inhalation. The figuration is very skilful and proportionate, rendering aesthetic exquisiteness to this large stone image. The double lotus pedestal has been executed a bit more linearly, contrary to the appearance of volume in the rest of the sculpture. The upper section of the stele behind the deity, features a band of flaming fire.

2.5 End remarks

The veneration of Prajñāpāramitā during the Pāla-period and her dissemination through the cult of manuscripts⁸⁰⁶, when the textual embodiment of Prajñāpāramitā had already reached a pinnacle of devotional and intellectual elaboration, can thus be positioned within a developmental continuum spanning the nascent phases of Mahāyāna to the transcultural exchanges that have shaped the historical trajectory of Buddhism. Through our analysis of different examples, from Nattier's important exposition of the *Prajñāpāramitāhṛdayasūtra*'s Chinese origins, suggesting a *reverse diaspora*, the anthropomorphic depictions of Prajñāpāramitā that emerged from the artistic ateliers of the Pāḷola Śāhis, the reverential manuscript burial practices and the equivalence drawn from the manuscripts, and the relics of the Buddha, or the iconographic assimilation practices of the Pāla-period: it is clear that the inherent fluidity and ambivalence deeply engrained within the conceptualisation of *prajñā* and Prajñāpāramitā have exerted a transformative and far-reaching influence upon its evolutionary arc across a multiplicity of temporalities, narratives, historical epochs and geographic domains. This conceptual pliability and an extraordinary capacity to absorb and refract a spectrum of interpretive frameworks, while adapting to the cultural, linguistic, and ritualistic milieus of the Indian subcontinent and beyond, has allowed and facilitated the sustained process of

⁸⁰⁶ On Buddhist books and their cultic use, see: Kim, *Receptacle of the Sacred*, 23-41; on innovations of the medieval book cult, see Kim, *Receptacle of the Sacred*, 43-70. Also see: Florinda De Simini, *Of Gods and Books: Ritual and Knowledge Transmission in the Manuscript Cultures of Premodern India* (Berlin: Walter de Gruyter GmbH, 2016), 2-22.

doctrinal and artistic metamorphoses, allowing Prajñāpāramitā to transcend the confines of rigid sectarian boundaries and resonate as a unifying theological motif across diverse Buddhist traditions.

To end, I quote Ricoeur:

[...] the refiguration of time by history and fiction becomes concrete thanks to the borrowings each mode of narrative makes from the other mode. These borrowings will lie in the fact that historical intentionality only becomes effective by incorporating into its intended object the resources of fictionalization stemming from the narrative form of imagination, while the intentionality of fiction produces its effects of detecting and transforming acting and suffering only by symmetrically assuming the resources of historicization presented it by attempts to reconstruct the actual past. From these intimate exchanges between the historicization of the fictional narrative and the fictionalization of the historical narrative is born what we call human time, which is nothing other than narrated time⁸⁰⁷.

⁸⁰⁷ Ricoeur, *Time and Narrative*, Volume 3, 101-102.

Chapter 3: Dependent arising in material form: Pāla-period illuminated manuscripts as *dharma*-relics, ritual instruments, and embodiments of emptiness

Before proceeding, it is necessary to acknowledge that the terms Madhyamaka, *śūnyatā*, and *pratītyasamutpāda* are not stable or unitary concepts but carry significantly different meanings and valences across the Buddhist traditions and historical periods that this dissertation spans. *Śūnyatā* as articulated in Nāgārjuna's second-century *Mūlamadhyamakakārikā*, a dialectical negation of *svabhāva* (inherent existence) through logical analysis, differs in both method and emphasis from *śūnyatā* as it was understood and practised in the late Pāla monastic context, where Yogācāra-Madhyamaka syntheses of the kind developed by Śāntarakṣita and Kamalaśīla had become dominant at institutions like Vikramaśīla, and where *śūnyatā* was experienced not primarily as a philosophical proposition but as a soteriological reality enacted through Vajrayāna ritual practice: visualisation, mantra recitation, and *maṇḍala* construction. Similarly, *pratītyasamutpāda*, while retaining its fundamental sense of dependent co-arising, acquired in the tantric context a specifically ritual significance: it underpinned the logic of deity yoga, in which the practitioner's ordinary appearance is dissolved and reconstituted as the body of the deity, and it informed the understanding of the manuscript itself as an object whose meaning and power arose dependently through the convergence of material support, textual content, iconographic programme, and ritual activation. The discussion that follows employs these terms in this late Pāla Vajrayāna sense unless otherwise specified, while recognising that this usage represents one layer within a rich and contested philosophical tradition.

This chapter presents a framework for analysing Pāla-period Buddhist manuscripts as ritually activated artefacts that instantiate Madhyamaka's⁸⁰⁸ non-dual ontology of emptiness

⁸⁰⁸ Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 487; Standard Buddhist terminology throughout this chapter is referenced for convenience to Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr.'s dictionary which includes a fuller treatment of these terms, with specialist sources cited where concepts are directly relevant to the argument.

(*śūnyatā*⁸⁰⁹) and dependent co-arising (*pratītyasamutpāda*⁸¹⁰), as understood within the late Pāla Vajrayāna context. The concept of ritual activation positions the manuscripts within a Vajrayāna soteriological system, in which ritual practices like recitation, visualisation, consecration transformed the manuscript from a material object into a sacred artefact. The chapter argues that the manuscript's ritual significance arises from the interdependence of its material, textual, visual⁸¹¹, iconographic, and ritual⁸¹² dimensions, an interdependence that *pratītyasamutpāda* explicitly describes. Within the Prāsaṅgika-Madhyamaka tradition that was dominant at late Pāla institutions, phenomena are understood to lack inherent essence (*svabhāva*) and to arise only in dependence on causes, conditions, and conceptual imputation.

3.1 Situating *prajñāpāramitā* in Buddhist cosmology and soteriology

The conceptualisation of a cosmos, as an ontological construct that encapsulates the intrinsic disarray and fissures of phenomenal reality through the mediation of extrinsic spatial and temporal dimensions, has found articulate expression within the different philosophical and religious traditions of the Indian subcontinent. W. Randolph Kloetzli, an authority on Buddhist cosmology and comparative religious and philosophical inquiry, delineated the introspective locus of the cosmos in Buddhist discourse as follows: “it must not be understood primarily as the physical universe, but rather as structured reality at every level, whether physical or spiritual.” In his comparative exposition on Plotinus's *Enneads* and Buddhist cosmological schemas, Kloetzli observed the ubiquity of such cosmological lexicon across philosophical traditions:

In the Classical world, the language of cosmology was a means for framing philosophical concerns. Among these were issues of time, motion, and soul; concepts of the limited and the unlimited; and the nature and basis of number. This is no less true of Indian thought—

⁸⁰⁹ Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 871-872.

⁸¹⁰ Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 669-670.

⁸¹¹ Also see: Eck, *Darśan: Seeing the Divine Image in India*, 3-9, 16-21, 32-43.

⁸¹² Also see: Eck, *Darśan: Seeing the Divine Image in India*, 44-50.

Hindu, Buddhist, Jain, and Ājivika—where the prestige of the cosmological idiom for organizing philosophical and theological thought cannot be overstated⁸¹³.

Foundational Buddhist cosmological schemas exhibit homology with Brahmanical and Jain analogues, undergoing transformations as Buddhist doctrine assimilated, adapted, and proliferated through the medieval period. This evolution is parsed into two primary distinctions: the pre-Mahāyāna “single-world-system⁸¹⁴,” characterised by a unitary cosmic domain, and the Mahāyānist “multiple-world-systems” or “cosmology of innumerable” (*asaṃkhyeya*⁸¹⁵), which posits an infinitude of interlinked realms. Within the corpus of Pāla-period illuminated manuscripts from eastern India, alongside Nepalese, Tibetan and Central Asian examples, including manuscripts and murals, the *asaṃkhyeya* predominates at the representational nucleus; nevertheless, other hegemonic trajectories also emerge, for example the medieval dissemination of Amitābha’s pure land cosmology, a variation of the multiple-worlds system, across East Asia, whereas Vairocana-centric portrayals in Tibetan and Nepalese manuscripts syncretise single-world motifs with Mahāyānist spatial delineations. Vasubandhu’s *Abhidharmakośa*⁸¹⁶ (fourth-fifth centuries CE), systematised the pre-Mahāyāna cosmological axioms, which postulated the substrata tier as a monolithic, circular disc girded by an impenetrable perimeter (*cakravāla*), circumscribed by concentric bands of elemental primordia: empty space (*ākāśa*), wind (*vāyumaṇḍala*), and water (*ābmaṇḍala*). Embedded within this volumetric *cakravāla* are discontinuous annular mountain formations (Īśadhāra, Khadirika, Sudarśana, Aśvakarṇa, Vinataka, Nimindhāra, *inter alia*) superimposed upon a golden substratum (*kāñcanamayībhūmi*), disposed concentrically in three dimensions yet conventionally flattened into

⁸¹³ W. Randolph Kloetzli, “Nous and Nirvana: Conversations with Plotinus—An Essay in Buddhist Cosmology,” *Philosophy East and West* 57, no. 2 (April 2007): 140–177.

⁸¹⁴ “World” as equivalent to Sanskrit *loka*, or planes of existence. Also known as the ‘vertical cosmology’, triple-world system (*trailokya*; Pāli. *tiloka*) because the world is divided into three realms from bottom to top: the realms of desire (*kāmadhātu*), form (*rūpadhātu*), and formlessness (*arūpadhātu*); also known as the *cakravāla* because of the circular iron mountain that surrounds it. It is one of the oldest known systems of Buddhist cosmology. See: Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 254, 479-480.

⁸¹⁵ Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 68.

⁸¹⁶ Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 5-6.

circular schemata in pictorial renderings. The *axil pivot*, Mount Meru⁸¹⁷, resides at the disc's epicentre, enveloped by the *cakravāla* and these orographic interruptions, with cosmological oceans filling the interstices. Peripheral to this oceanic expanse extend four cardinal landmasses: Pūrvavideha⁸¹⁸, Jambudvīpa⁸¹⁹, Aparagodānīya⁸²⁰, and Uttarakuru⁸²¹. These terrains, comprising the *kāmadhātu*⁸²² (realm of desire), accommodate five principal existential categories: *devas* (celestials), humans, animals, *piśācas*⁸²³ (famished spectres), and hell denizens: occasionally augmented by a sixth, *asuras* (titans). Entities of diminished spiritual attainment occupy inferior strata. *Nāgas*⁸²⁴ (serpentine guardians) fortify the *axis mundi* throughout, bridging the superior *deva* realms (with six heavens surmounting it) to the nadir of lower existences. This vertical stratification defines pre-Mahāyāna cosmology's architectonic imagination. Salient among these celestial strata (Cāturmahārājakāyika⁸²⁵, Trāyastriṃśa⁸²⁶, Yāma⁸²⁷, Tuṣita⁸²⁸, Nirmānarati⁸²⁹, Paranirmitavaśavartī⁸³⁰) are Trāyastriṃśa, the summit abode of Indra atop Meru⁸³¹, and Tuṣita, the preparatory locus for the *bodhisattva*'s incarnation antecedent to Śākyamuni's advent in Jambudvīpa. Ascending beyond *kāmadhātu* unfold seventeen *rūpadhātu*⁸³² (form-realm) heavens, succeeded by four *ārūpyadhātu*⁸³³ (formless) infinities. Within this schema, soteriological dialectics of causality, natality, and renascence transpire across *kalpas*⁸³⁴ (aeons), propelling beings upwards through iterative transformations grounded in karmic interdependence. The second century CE

⁸¹⁷ Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 869.

⁸¹⁸ Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 685, 967.

⁸¹⁹ Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 377-378.

⁸²⁰ Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 57, 323.

⁸²¹ Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 946.

⁸²² Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 411.

⁸²³ Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 646.

⁸²⁴ Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 561.

⁸²⁵ Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 171.

⁸²⁶ Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 921-922.

⁸²⁷ Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 1018.

⁸²⁸ Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 930.

⁸²⁹ Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 588.

⁸³⁰ Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 625.

⁸³¹ Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 538, 869.

⁸³² Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 722.

⁸³³ Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 63-64.

⁸³⁴ Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 409.

*Divyāvadāna*⁸³⁵, emanating from Mūlasarvāstivādin *vinaya*⁸³⁶ traditions, elucidates the *bhavacakra*'s schematic principles through Śākyamuni's colloquy with King Rudrāyaṇa. This emblematic wheel of *samsāra* (cyclic existence) pervades Tibetan and Nepalese mural, *thangka* and manuscript traditions. In *Tabo: A Lamp for the Kingdom*, Deborah Klimburg-Salter demonstrated the *bhavacakra*⁸³⁷ as distinguishing *samsāra*'s⁸³⁸ essence, with attendant cosmologies charting cosmic expanses, conjointly mapping microcosmic and macrocosmic interfaces, delimiting profane externalities from sacral *maṇḍala*⁸³⁹ interiors⁸⁴⁰. The *bhavacakra*, as a diagrammatic encapsulation of cyclical cosmic temporality, incorporating vertical progressions and regressions across stratified universal domains in a being's journey towards liberation, poses representational challenges in two-dimensional planar media such as paintings and murals. Adaptive strategies frequently reorient verticality along horizontal axes, as elucidated by Joseph E. Schwartzberg:

The implication of this, from a cartographic perspective, is that the visual representation of the multi-dimensional universe in a two-dimensional image sees it extended along a vertical rather than a horizontal plane⁸⁴¹.

A fifteenth century CE Japanese Buddhist cartographic example for instance, employs alternating avian and planar perspectives to schematise multidimensional universes, resorting to elemental geometric circlets for *ārūpyadhātu* heavens (Plate 94). A sacred topology, including *devas* in the *arūpaloka* down to *naraka* denizens in *Avīci*⁸⁴²: corresponds with Theravāda's enumeration of thirty-

⁸³⁵ Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 262.

⁸³⁶ Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 555.

⁸³⁷ Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 111-112.

⁸³⁸ Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 757-758.

⁸³⁹ Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 523-524.

⁸⁴⁰ Deborah E. Klimburg-Salter and Christian Luczanits, eds., *Tabo: A Lamp for the Kingdom: Early Indo-Tibetan Buddhist Art in the Western Himalaya* (Milan: Skira, 1997). Also see the works of Jinah Kim, and Louis Copplestone, who demonstrated how manuscripts and monasteries can be representations of sacral cosmographic *maṇḍalas* respectively: Jinah Kim, *Receptacle of the Sacred: Illustrated Manuscripts and the Buddhist Book Cult in South Asia* (Berkeley: University of California Press, 2013), 149-162; Louis Copplestone, *Monasteries, Mountains, and Maṇḍalas: Buddhist Architecture and its Landscape Contexts in Eastern India, c. 700–1100* (PhD diss., Harvard University, 2024), 151-191.

⁸⁴¹ Joseph E. Schwartzberg, "Part Two: South Asian Cartography (Chs. 15–19)," in *The History of Cartography, Volume 2, Book 1: Cartography in the Traditional Islamic and South Asian Societies*, ed. J. B. Harley and David Woodward (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 1992).

⁸⁴² Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 86.

one existential planes⁸⁴³. Although pre-Mahāyāna cosmology provides the foundation for Mahāyānist developments, its orientation privileges soteriological experiences over literal geographic topologies. Divergences can one observed within *Abhidharmic* expositions, such as Vasubandhu’s “*Lokanirdeśa*” (World Description) in the *Abhidharmakośa*, which contrast with utopian idealisations in *Sukhāvātīvyūhasūtras*⁸⁴⁴, late Tibetan pictorial narratives, or didactic anecdotes like “Moggallāna Rescues His Mother⁸⁴⁵.” The *Karuṇāpuṇḍarīkasūtra*⁸⁴⁶ interrogates *buddhakṣetras*⁸⁴⁷ from a Mahāyānist standpoint. The *lokadhātu*, aggregating innumerable *cakravālas*, constitutes the elemental cosmic unit, with doctrinal variations across Theravāda, Sarvāstivāda, Mahāsāṃghika, and Mahāyāna lineages. *Trisāhasramahāsāhasralokadhātu*⁸⁴⁸ signifies a “three-thousand great-thousand world-system,” pervasive in the *Mahāvastu*⁸⁴⁹ and Mahāyāna literature. Kloetzli designated these aggregations as “*sāhasra* cosmology” or “cosmology of thousands⁸⁵⁰”; Luis Gomez specified a

⁸⁴³ See: Francis Story, *Gods and the Universe in Buddhist Perspective: Essays on Buddhist Cosmology and Related Subjects*, *The Wheel Publication no. 180/181* (Kandy: Buddhist Publication Society, 1972; 2nd repr., 1983); Nyanatiloka and Nyanaponika, *Buddhist Dictionary: Manual of Buddhist Terms and Doctrines*, 4th rev. ed. (Kandy: Buddhist Publication Society, 1980), accessed August 10, 2025, https://www.budsas.org/ebud/bud-dict/dic_idx.htm.

⁸⁴⁴ Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 867-868.

⁸⁴⁵ First found in a manuscript from Dunhuang, relatable to the ninth century CE.

⁸⁴⁶ Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 424; Isshi Yamada, *Karuṇāpuṇḍarīka*, vol. 1 (London: School of Oriental and African Studies; Luzac, 1968)

⁸⁴⁷ Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 153; Pāli “*buddhakhetta*,” it denotes a region, typically a world or world-system, wherein a specific Buddha resides and conducts activities; for an in-depth analysis, see: Teresina Rowell, “The Background and Early Use of the *Buddhakṣetra* Concept,” *The Eastern Buddhist* 6 (1973): 199–430; 7 (1974): 131–76, which provides a detailed examination of the term. Notable instances of its usage include: *Saddharmapuṇḍarīka* 65.9 ff.; 144.9 ff.; *Saddharmapuṇḍarīka* 66.3; *Mahāvastu* ii.301.16; *Mahāvastu* 3065; *Mahāvastu* ii.319.11; 349.17; iii.139.3; 342.1; *Mahāvastu* i.123.4 ff.; *Mahāvastu* i.283.3; *Mahāvastu* ii.295.9; *Mahāvastu* i.121.14 ff.; *Śikṣāsamuccaya* 147.15; *Saddharmapuṇḍarīka* 68.2 (verse; cf. 66.3 ff., prose, same topic). The concept of *buddhakṣetra* is explicitly aligned with *lokadhātu*, signifying a world-system, likely serving as a potential domain for a Buddha, though not necessarily inhabited by one, a point further elaborated by Rowell, op. cit., 415. The concept of the *buddhakṣetra*, frequently misconstrued as an exclusively Mahāyāna notion due to its intricate visual representations in Mahāyānist Buddhist art, was first rigorously examined through interdisciplinary lenses, encompassing philosophy, religious studies, literature, and art, by Teresina Rowell in the 1930s. This cosmological framework, articulated in the theory of *Buddhakṣetrasūtras*, reconfigures the universe as a spatial, three-dimensional model of cosmic time, comprising an infinite array of distinct existential planes within cohesive cosmological wholes, grounded solely in soteriological principles; notably, this theory underpins the spiritual and religious tenets of Amidaism, or Pure Land Buddhism, a major Far Eastern denomination (encompassing Korea, Japan, and China), which centres on the *buddhakṣetra* of Amitābha Buddha.

⁸⁴⁸ Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 924.

⁸⁴⁹ Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 512.

⁸⁵⁰ W. Randolph Kloetzli, *Buddhist Cosmology: Science and Theology in the Images of Motion and Light* (Delhi: Motilal Banarsidass, 1989).

billion-fold *cakravālas*⁸⁵¹, while Franklin Edgerton highlighted *mahāsāhasra*'s interpretive indeterminacy, refraining from *trisāhasra* quantifications⁸⁵². A singular *buddhakṣetra* encompasses “*ekaṣaṣṭiṃ trisaharāṇi*”. *Upakṣetras* evade extensive elaboration in subsequent *buddhakṣetra* elaborations but has an enduring presence within Vajrayāna tantric topologies. The *Hevajratantra*⁸⁵³ delineates *melāpakasthānas* (congregational loci) for *siddhas* and *yoginīs*, recapitulating *Daśabhūmika*⁸⁵⁴ motifs including *pīṭhas*⁸⁵⁵, *upapīṭhas*, *kṣetras*, *upakṣetras*, and eight ancillary topological variants within the *dvādaśabhūmayah* (twelve strata). Each autarchic domain is centred upon a buddha or denominated *buddhakṣetra*. Mahāyāna's spatiotemporal sophistication escalates soteriological potentials, proffering innumerable *buddhakṣetras* for karmic enactments⁸⁵⁶. *Buddhakṣetras* are divided into *visuddha*⁸⁵⁷ (purified), *avisuddha* (impure), and *miśraka* (hybrid). Humanity resides in Jambudvīpa's austral continent, the *sahāloka*⁸⁵⁸, also ambivalently classified as *avisuddha* or *miśraka*: impure owing to karmic cyclicity and malefic presences. It also concurrently enables metamorphosis: as Śākyamuni's nativity site, it accommodates *bodhisattva* embodiments for

⁸⁵¹ Luis O. Gómez, *The Land of Bliss, The Paradise of the Buddha of Measureless Light: Sanskrit and Chinese Versions of the Sukhāvativyūha Sūtras* (Honolulu: University of Hawaii Press, 1996).

⁸⁵² Franklin Edgerton, *Buddhist Hybrid Sanskrit Reader* (Delhi: Motilal Banarsidass, 1953; repr., 2002).

⁸⁵³ G. W. Farrow and I. Menon, eds., *The Concealed Essence of the Hevajra Tantra: With the Commentary Yogaratnamala* (English and Sanskrit Edition) (Delhi: Motilal Banarsidass, 1992), 1.7.10–18; R. S. Tripathi and T. S. Negi, eds., *Hevajratantram with Yogaratnamālāpāñjikā by Kṛṣṇapāda* (Sarnath: Central Institute of Higher Tibetan Studies, 2006).

⁸⁵⁴ Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 218-220.

⁸⁵⁵ Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 647.

⁸⁵⁶ Five *buddhakṣetras*, each associated with its respective Buddha, are situated along the eastern segment of the temporal axis (*purastime diśo bhāge*), three in the southern segment (*dakṣiṇasmim diśo bhāge*), one in the western segment (*paścimasim diśo bhāge*), one in the northern segment (*uttarasim diśo bhāge*), one at the lowest point of the temporal axis (*heṣṭimasim diśo bhāge*), and one at the highest point (*upariṣṭā diśo bhāge*). The philosophical and cosmological principle, well-attested in Pāli literature as *apubbaṃ acarimaṃ*, posits that two Buddhas cannot coexist within a single delineated cosmological region, a concept potentially foundational to Theravādin *Buddhakṣetrasūtra* theory, though in these texts the term employed is *lokadhātu*. The *Milindapañha* (Miln 236–239), offering significant insight into this doctrine, draws a parallel with the *Mahāvastu* by comparing the implausibility of two Buddhas or Tathāgatas coexisting in one cosmological unit to two individuals attempting to board a single-person sailing vessel (*nāvā ekapurisasandhāraṇī*). Numerous responses attributed to Mahākāśyapa in the *Daśabhūmikā* section of the *Mahāvastu*, particularly those delineating his conception of the boundless nature of *buddhakṣetras*, reflect a foundation in Mahāsāṅghika philosophy, asserting the universe's infinite expanse and positing the Buddha's infinitude as central to its ontological and structural framework. The text highlights this through the phrase *ataḥ param* (beyond), indicating the existence of over a thousand *buddhakṣetras*, and employs the refrain *pūrvā koṭī na prajñāyate* (literally “the farthest back point, the beginning is not known,” signifying an unknowable starting point), which enumerates twenty-five key events in Śākyamuni's life as the primary narrative thread of the *Mahāvastu*, suggesting a multivalent semantic layer where the narrative encompasses a generic Buddha applicable across infinite cosmic time and space.

⁸⁵⁷ Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 982.

⁸⁵⁸ Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 736.

autotelic and altruistic advancement amid *duḥkha*⁸⁵⁹ (affliction). These different cosmological imaginaries, which materialised across different artistic representations, originate from the fundamental soteriological telos: the orchestration of sentient beings towards buddha-like emancipation and liberation. Manuscript narratives, including *jātakas*⁸⁶⁰, *avadānas*⁸⁶¹, the Buddha's octad of cardinal episodes, discourses (e.g., at Gṛdhrakūṭa for the *Saddharmapuṇḍarīka Sūtra*), and Mahāyāna *sūtric* narratives, can be all contextualised within *sahāloka*. *Bodhisattva* domiciles, such as Mañjuśrī's Wutai⁸⁶² or Avalokiteśvara's Potalaka⁸⁶³, recur in depictions from palm-leaf manuscripts to Tibetan *thangkas*. Foremost among *viśuddha buddhakṣetras*, Amitābha's pure land, manifest through ornate distinctions from *sahāloka*, evolving pictorially from Tibetan to Chinese idioms.

The *bodhisattva* maintains focus on *sarvajñatā* by directing consciousness toward *śūnyatā/prajñāpāramitā*⁸⁶⁴, especially during emergence from the three *samādhis*⁸⁶⁵, or through aspirations for all-knowing and merit transposition, reinforced by *karuṇā*⁸⁶⁶ and *vipassanā*⁸⁶⁷. In profound meditative absorption, where *śūnyatā* engagement or vow formulation is not feasible, the *bodhisattva* preserves this focus through a cultivated predisposition towards *sarvajñatā*, achieved via training in *prajñāpāramitā* and other resolute aspirations, allowing consciousness to incline towards all-knowing without effort. As *vipassanā*, *prajñāpāramitā* manifests primarily at, or, post-emergence from the triad of *samādhis*, where insight enables *buddhatā*⁸⁶⁸. It may also arise in consciousness not fully disengaged from higher *samādhi* or in lower *samādhis*, where prior *śūnyatā* training supports concentration corresponding to *sarvajñatā*, mirroring the experience of emergence, and explaining

⁸⁵⁹ Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 270-271.

⁸⁶⁰ Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 381.

⁸⁶¹ Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 81.

⁸⁶² Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 1003-1004.

⁸⁶³ Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 652.

⁸⁶⁴ Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 656-657.

⁸⁶⁵ Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 743.

⁸⁶⁶ Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 424.

⁸⁶⁷ Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 978.

⁸⁶⁸ Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 151-152, 155.

the occasional conflation of the triad with *prajñāpāramitā*, as insight persists where consciousness and appearance coexist. Post-emergence, the *bodhisattva* realises *sarvajñatā* and *buddhakṣetra* solely through *prajñāpāramitā*, either immediately upon emergence or by sustaining the emergent state, with insight homologous to that during emergence or in lower absorptions. *Prajñāpāramitā*, as *vipassanā*, operates in cognitive states of limited activity, during emergence from elevated *samādhis* lacking consciousness and appearances, in prolonged post-emergence insight, or within lower *samādhis* where both persist⁸⁶⁹. The *Sāgaramatipariprcchā* follows the *Prajñāpāramitāsūtra*'s view that the *prajñāpāramitā* is accomplished at the margins shared by the set of three *samādhis* and *nirvāṇa*⁸⁷⁰. According to the *Sāgaramatipariprcchā*, emptiness or the *prajñāpāramitā* could occur to a mind that is still under the influence of very deep concentration. It is an insight experientially similar to that of the mind that leaps forward to *nirvāṇa* before full emergence from deep concentration⁸⁷¹.

3.2 The manuscript as *dharmā*-relic

The manuscripts examined in Chapter 1, from the LACMA *AsP* commissioned by the householder Tejokā during Mahipāla I's twenty-seventh regnal year, to the V&A *AsP* donated by Udaya Siṃha in Rāmapāla's thirty-sixth year, to the Baroda *PvP* produced under Harivarman in southeastern Bengal, were not simply produced as inert repositories of philosophical content. Their colophons, their iconographic programmes, and the material investment lavished upon their execution all point to a conception of the manuscript that exceeds the category of simple textual transmission. The questions this chapter addresses is what these objects were understood to be within the doctrinal and ritual frameworks of the communities that produced them.

Prajñāpāramitā literature itself perhaps supplies the most direct answer. As discussed in Chapter 2, the *AsP* asserts a relationship between text and relic that goes beyond basic analogy.

⁸⁶⁹ Yoke Meei Choong, "The 'Prajñāpāramit' āin Relation to the Three 'Samādhis,'" *Journal of Indian Philosophy* 44, no. 4 (September 2016): 750-753.

⁸⁷⁰ For a discussion on the comparisons between the concept of "Brahman" in Brahmanism and "*nirvāṇa*" in Buddhism, see: Christian Lindtner, "From Brahmanism to Buddhism," *Asian Philosophy* 9, no. 1 (1999): 5–37.

⁸⁷¹ Choong, "The 'Prajñāpāramit' āin Relation to the Three 'Samādhis,'" : 753.

Schopen, in his study of the relic inscriptions at Nāgārjunikoṇḍā, drew attention to the passage: “*itaḥ prajñāpāramitāto nirjatāni tāni tathāgataśarīrāṇi pūjāṃ labhante yad uta prajñāpāramitāparibhāvitavāt*”, meaning, that the relics of the Tathāgata, being born from the Perfection of Wisdom, receive worship because they are animated by it⁸⁷². The verb *paribhāvita*, explicated by *nirjāta* (“to be born/ given life”), establishes a productive relationship: as the relics derive their potency from the Prajñāpāramitā⁸⁷³. A manuscript containing this text was therefore not a record about the dharma but, in the doctrinal logic of the tradition, a primary locus of wisdom, from which the Buddha’s relics drew their sacred energy.

This doctrinal position had material consequences visible in the archaeological and manuscript record examined in preceding chapters. The distinction between two functions of manuscript interment in *stūpas*, established in Chapter 2, illustrated this. When manuscripts were deposited during a *stūpa*’s construction, they served as *dharma*-relics (*dharmakāya-dhātu*), the textual body of the Buddha installed as the consecrating presence within the reliquary structure, in place of, or alongside corporeal relics⁸⁷⁴. The *stūpa* required a relic to be constituted as a valid object of veneration, and the Prajñāpāramitā text could fulfil that requirement because the tradition understood the text as the source from which corporeal relics themselves derived power. When worn or damaged manuscripts were deposited within an already existing *stūpa*, the purpose was ritually appropriate disposal of sacred objects. The Senior manuscripts from Gandhāra, discussed in Chapter 2, exemplify the *dharma*-relic function: commissioned for ritual interment, their status rested on the principle that to encounter the *dharma* was to encounter the Buddha⁸⁷⁵.

Hartmann’s observation that even a textual fragment retains the capacity to represent the totality of the dharma is pertinent here. The *ye dharmā hetu* verse, the condensed formula of

⁸⁷² Gregory Schopen, "On the Buddha and His Bones: The Conception of a Relic in the Inscriptions from Nāgārjunikoṇḍā," in *Bones, Stones, and Buddhist Monks: Collected Papers on the Archaeology, Epigraphy, and Texts of Monastic Buddhism in India* (Honolulu: University of Hawai'i Press, 1997), 155. The passage is also discussed in Chapter 2 of this dissertation.

⁸⁷³ Schopen, "On the Buddha and His Bones," 155.

⁸⁷⁴ See the discussion in Chapter 2, section 2.1.b, of this dissertation; Gregory Schopen, "The Phrase 'sa pṛthivīpradeśaś caityabhūto bhavet' in the Vajracchedikā: Notes on the Cult of the Book in Mahāyāna," in *Figments and Fragments of Mahāyāna Buddhism in India: More Collected Papers* (Honolulu: University of Hawai'i Press, 2005), 25–62.

⁸⁷⁵ See Chapter 2, section 2.1.b, of this dissertation.

dependent arising inscribed on manuscripts, sculptures, and votive objects across the Buddhist world, could serve as a synecdoche for the *Nagaropamasūtra*, and by extension for the full body of the Buddha's teaching⁸⁷⁶. The manuscripts discussed in this dissertation, which contain not just this verse but the complete Prajñāpāramitā text, occupied the highest position within this hierarchy of textual relics.

What I wish to draw out from this well-established scholarly account of the *dharma*-relic is a consequence that has received comparatively lesser attention: its bearing on the ontological status of the manuscript as a material object. If the Prajñāpāramitā is the source of sanctity of the Buddha's relics and the foundation of his omniscience, then the manuscript is not a representation pointing towards a reality located elsewhere. It is an instantiation of that reality in material form. Its sacred status, arises dependently: through the convergence of textual content, iconographic programme, and the ritual practices that activate and sustain the manuscript's participation in *dharma*. The remainder of the chapter pursues the implications of this convergence: first through an examination of the ritual practices that activated the manuscript's *dharma*-relic status (section 3.3), and then through an extension of the same analysis to the *bodhi* tree and the *stūpa* (section 3.4).

The colophon evidence examined in Chapter 1 attests to the meritorious investment that manuscript production signified. Tejokā, a female householder and wife of a *kāyastha* official, commissioned the LACMA *AsP*; the lay woman Lāḍokā commissioned CUL Add. 1464; queen Uḍḍakā patronised the CUL *Pañcarakṣā*⁸⁷⁷. The Nepalese devotee Rāmajīva donated the LACMA *DnS*, inscribed by the scribe Svameśvara: a manuscript whose colophon attests to the networks of pilgrimage and cultural exchange connecting Nepal with eastern India⁸⁷⁸. As Kim demonstrated, the act of commissioning, copying, and donating a manuscript operated within the same ritual economy

⁸⁷⁶ Hartmann, "From words to books: Indian Buddhist manuscripts in the first millennium CE" in *Buddhist Manuscript Cultures*, 102-103.

⁸⁷⁷ See the colophon discussions in Chapter 1, sections 1.3.a (A, B, G) of this dissertation; Jinah Kim, *Receptacle of the Sacred: Illustrated Manuscripts and the Buddhist Book Cult in South Asia* (Berkeley: University of California Press, 2013), 225-228.

⁸⁷⁸ See Chapter 1, section 1.3.a (B) of this dissertation; Kim, *Receptacle of the Sacred*, 48, 51, 213-214.

as *stūpa* construction and image conation: it was a form of *dharma*-practice generating merit for the patron while simultaneously bringing into existence a new *dharma*-relic.

In his 1990 study on Tsongkhapa's imagery of bells, Victor Mansfield observed, drawing a very relevant corollary, that in classical Indian music the *śruti* note symbolises the sacred sound *Om*, which unifies all sound, whereas Madhyamaka Buddhism features an omnipresent philosophical denial of inherent or independent existence, an 'unsoundable note' that reveals *śūnyatā* as the ultimate truth⁸⁷⁹. Mansfield reviewed Prāsaṅgika-Madhyamaka⁸⁸⁰, defining emptiness as the negation of inherent existence, i.e., objects' supposed independence from perception and interrelations, leading to neither nihilism nor externalism but the middle-way of *pratītyasamutpāda*. The Prāsaṅgika-Madhyamaka interpretation of *śūnyatā*, while systematised most fully in the Tibetan scholastic tradition, was continuous with the philosophical frameworks operative at late Pāla institutions where many of the foundational Indian Madhyamaka texts were studied and transmitted. He observed that Einstein's separability mirrors this negation, originating in everyday thought; yet the bell experiment's violation resonates with the Madhyamaka emphasis on the relational constitution of phenomena. Mansfield argued that Madhyamaka dialectics, showing for example: objects' dependence on causes, unbindability in parts, and mental imputation, prove inherent existence contradictory, as non relational entities would be immutable and nonfunctional⁸⁸¹.

⁸⁷⁹ Mansfield also noted that Albert Einstein posited a similar foundational assumption for physics, the mutually independent existence of spatially distant objects, embodying locality and separability. To illustrate, Mansfield presented a nontechnical analogy using Tsongkhapa's bells, where paired resonators undergo mutually exclusive pass-fail tests for artistic style, bronze content, and construction strength in isolated rooms, ensuring no information exchange via locality. In Case 1 (identical tests), perfect correlations imply identical attributes; in Case 2 (different tests), assuming locality and independent existence yields Bell's Inequality, predicting same results at least one-third of the time for any attribute mix. However, experimental data showed same results only one-fourth of the time, violating the Inequality and falsifying independent existence, though not defeating complementarity. Mansfield emphasised that actual photon experiments confirm this violation, affirming quantum mechanics' predictions and necessitating experimental metaphysics. See: Victor Mansfield, "Tsongkhapa's Bell, Bell's Inequality, and Madhyamika Emptiness," *The Tibet Journal* 15, no. 1 (Spring 1990): 42-59.

⁸⁸⁰ Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 664.

⁸⁸¹ Mansfield, "Tsongkhapa's Bell," 59-64. Also see: V. N. Mansfield, "Mādhyamika Buddhism and Quantum Mechanics: Beginning a Dialogue," *International Philosophical Quarterly* 29 (1989): 371; J. Hopkins, *Meditation on Emptiness* (London: Wisdom Publications, 1983); R. Thurman, *Tsong Khapa's Speech of Gold in the Essence of True Eloquence* (Princeton, NJ: Princeton University Press, 1984).

Early Buddhist texts from the first five centuries ground their worldview in causality and impermanence, but Mahāyāna texts of the subsequent five centuries, under *śūnyavāda*⁸⁸², adopt subversive approaches. The *Prajñāpāramitāhṛdayasūtra* negates foundational doctrines like the Four Noble Truths, the six sense realms, and the *saṃsāra-nirvāṇa* distinction, while Nāgārjuna's *Mūlamadhyamakakārikā* (ca. 200 CE) employs the tetralemma to render core concepts like cause and effect or being and non being logically untenable⁸⁸³. The *Vajracchedikāprajñāpāramitāsūtra* similarly destabilises conceptual frameworks, particularly those deemed religious, through a linguistic strategy that D.T. Suzuki terms “*sokuhi*,” which asserts that “all dharmas are not all dharmas, hence they are called all dharmas” (T 8.235.751), revealing a *différance*-like disjunction between signifier and signified. Unlike Nāgārjuna's tetralemma⁸⁸⁴, which parallels Kantian antinomies⁸⁸⁵, the *Vajracchedikāprajñāpāramitāsūtra* advances a philosophy of language resonant with Derridean deconstruction⁸⁸⁶, which in effect allows a transformation of *śūnyatāvāda* from logical refutation of metaphysical concepts towards a critique of predication and significance. Vasubandhu⁸⁸⁷ (ca. 500 CE) and Chandrakīrti⁸⁸⁸ (600-650 CE) challenged *trīsvabhāva*⁸⁸⁹ by positing *triṇiḥsvabhāva*⁸⁹⁰, and texts like the *Dasheng qixinlun*⁸⁹¹ deconstruct *svabhāva*. Further subversive

⁸⁸² Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 872.

⁸⁸³ See: Claus Oetke, “Remarks on the Interpretation of Nāgārjuna's Philosophy,” *Journal of Indian Philosophy* 19, no. 3 (September 1991): 315–23; David Michael Levin, “Liberating Experience from the Vice of Structuralism: The Methods of Merleau-Ponty and Nāgārjuna,” *Journal of the British Society for Phenomenology* 28, no. 2 (1997): 116–41; A. K. Jayesh, “Nāgārjuna and the Concept of Time,” *Asian Philosophy* 31, no. 2 (2021): 121–42.

⁸⁸⁴ See: Robin Reames, “Becoming and Negation, Protagoras and Nāgārjuna,” *Comparative and Continental Philosophy* 14, no. 3 (2022): 217–35; Mark Siderits, “Does a Table Have Buddha-Nature?” *Philosophy East and West* 63, no. 3 (July 2013): 373–86.

⁸⁸⁵ Also see: Muller, Fabien. 2025. “The Catuskoṭi as Metaphysics. Cross-Reading Hegel and Nāgārjuna.” *Comparative and Continental Philosophy*, August, 1–13.

⁸⁸⁶ Also see: Robert Magliola, “Derridean Gaming and Buddhist Utpāda-Bhaṅga (Rising/Falling): How a Philosophical Stylistique Can De/Void Entitative Existence,” *Comparative and Continental Philosophy* 12, no. 1 (2020): 17–29.

⁸⁸⁷ Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 961-962.

⁸⁸⁸ Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 165.

⁸⁸⁹ Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 925.

⁸⁹⁰ Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 585, 924; See: Susan C. Stalker, *A Study of Dependent Origination: Vasubandhu, Buddhaghosa, and the Interpretation of 'Pratītyasamutpāda'* (PhD diss., University of Pennsylvania, 1987); Goran Kardas, “From Etymology to Ontology: Vasubandhu and Candrakīrti on Various Interpretations of Pratītyasamutpāda,” *Asian Philosophy* 25, no. 3 (2015): 293–317; Also see: Matthew MacKenzie, “Ontological Deflationism in Madhyamaka,” *Contemporary Buddhism* 9, no. 2 (2008): 197–207.

⁸⁹¹ Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 221-222.

interventions appear in the Zen canon: encounter dialogues, such as Linji Yixuan's⁸⁹² (- 866 CE) assertion that the Buddha-*dharma* is merely “the everyday and the ordinary” (T 1985.47.498)⁸⁹³, while Dōgen⁸⁹⁴ (1200–1253 CE), in his *Busshō*, offered a reinterpretation of buddha-nature as being, nonbeing, emptiness, and impermanence, emphasising its performative verification (*genjō*⁸⁹⁵) or expression (*dōtoku*), thus exposing the fragility of discursive boundaries⁸⁹⁶.

Texts employed for ritual and cosmological ends transcend their role as mere conduits of discursive content. The scriptural corpus they contain assumes the status of an ultimate embodiment of the Buddha's presence and his transcendent potencies. Such texts, as noted before, are sequestered, encased within sacred receptacles like amulets, reliquaries, *stūpas*, Buddha images, or altars. In their capacity to symbolise an ulterior reality, even a fragment thereof suffices to fulfil this function. The *Nagaropamasūtra*, a text which expounds the *pratītyasamutpāda*, metonymically encapsulates the entirety of the Buddha's doctrine. Similarly the *ye dharmā* verse may serve as a synecdoche for the *Nagaropamasūtra* itself. Fragments though incomplete, retain the capacity to represent the totality of the Dharma⁸⁹⁷.

The manuscript thus transcends its material constitution, with fragments such as the *ye dharmā*⁸⁹⁸ verse synecdochically embodying the totality of the Buddha's presence, activated through ritual to manifest a non-dual reality. Thus it can be said that the manuscript's ritual activation emerges from the practitioner's participatory engagement, which preconditions its ontological status as a sacred artefact. Thus, as a site of ritual activation, the manuscript constitutes a locus wherein Vajrayāna ritual practices: including the visualisation, mantra recitation, and consecration ceremonies

⁸⁹² Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 476.

⁸⁹³ Also see: Garth Mason, “Is Saṃsāra Actually the Same as Nirvāṇa?: A Critical Examination of Nāgārjuna's Provocative Understanding of Emptiness,” *Journal for the Study of Religion* 27, no. 2 (2014): 94–114.

⁸⁹⁴ Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 263.

⁸⁹⁵ Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 317–318.

⁸⁹⁶ Nathan Loewen and Gereon Kopf, “Deconstruction under Erasure in Derrida and Zen Buddhism,” in *Engaging Philosophies of Religion: Thinking Across Boundaries*, edited by Gereon Kopf, Purushottama Bilimoria, and Nathan R. B. Loewen (London; New York: Bloomsbury Academic, 2025), 178–79.

⁸⁹⁷ Hartmann, “From words to books: Indian Buddhist manuscripts in the first millennium CE” in *Buddhist Manuscript Cultures*, 102–103.

⁸⁹⁸ Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 1026.

that activated these manuscripts, were understood by their practitioners as enacting the Madhyamaka teaching that phenomena arise dependently and lack inherent existence. In the specific late Pāla context, this meant that the manuscript's transformation from inert object to ritually potent artefact was itself an instance of *pratītyasamutpāda*: its sacred status arose not from any inherent property of the materials but from the convergence of text, image, practitioner, and ritual act.

3.3 The manuscript as ritual instrument: *habitus* and Vajrayāna activation

The preceding section established the manuscript's doctrinal status as a *dharmā*-relic on the basis of claims internal to the Prajñāpāramitā tradition. That status, however, is not self-activating. A manuscript sitting unread in a monastic storeroom, whatever the doctrinal weight of its contents, did not function as a *dharmā*-relic in the same way as one opened for ceremonial recitation or installed on an altar for veneration. The transition from potential to actual sacred presence depended on a repertoire of embodied practices: production, consecration, recitation, visual engagement—that were socially structured, transmitted through monastic training, and enacted with the fluency of long habituation.

Bourdieu's concept of *habitus*: a system of durable, transposable dispositions acquired through sustained participation in a social field, through which agents perceive, evaluate, and act without necessarily bringing their principles of action to explicit consciousness, offers a productive framework for analysing these practices⁸⁹⁹. I employ the term not to impose an imported sociological grid on Buddhist ritual life but because it captures something that purely doctrinal analysis, tends to miss: the pre-reflective, bodily, and socially reproduced character of what practitioners did. A monk opening a manuscript for recitation did not pause to reflect on the Prajñāpāramitā's claim to be the source of power of the Buddha's relics. A painter executing an illumination of Mañjuśrī did not consciously enact the *Sādhanamālā* as a mere theoretical proposition. These were competencies

⁸⁹⁹ Pierre Bourdieu, *Outline of a Theory of Practice*, trans. Richard Nice (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 1977), 72-95; Pierre Bourdieu, *The Logic of Practice*, trans. Richard Nice (Stanford: Stanford University Press, 1990), 52-79.

acquired through immersion in social, artistic and monastic life and enacted with the practical fluency that Bourdieu's concept is designed to describe⁹⁰⁰.

3.3a Production as structured practice

The production of an illuminated manuscript engaged an ecology of skilled labour structured by the institutional setting in which it took place. The preparation of palm-leaves: selecting, curing, cutting, and ruling, required technical knowledge transmitted within monastic scriptoria, a process discussed in the Introduction⁹⁰¹. The scribes who inscribed the *Prajñāpāramitā* text were engaged in an activity that the *Prajñāpāramitā* literature itself commends as a source of merit. The text prescribes its own copying and dissemination as a devotional act, and the scribe performing this labour was therefore enacting a practice that the text's doctrinal content both describes and sanctions.

Similarly, the painters who executed the illuminated panels worked within the iconographic conventions codified in the *Sādhanamālā* and cognate liturgical texts. The painter worked within a system of prescriptions where deviation could compromise the image's capacity to serve as a basis for meditative visualisation. The distinction Pal noted between two registers of execution in the LACMA *DnS* (M.72.1.20 a-b), dated to approximately 1041 CE: the composition and figuration, which are "very suave and reflect artistic sophistication," and the striations of the Buddha's robes, which may have been rendered at a different stage⁹⁰², suggests that manuscript production involved a division of labour within the scriptorium, with different hands responsible for different aspects of the illumination programme. This is *habitus* at the level of the workshop: a collective competence distributed across multiple agents whose individual contributions converge in a finished object.

⁹⁰⁰ On the gap between doctrinal reconstruction and the study of what Buddhists actually did, see Gregory Schopen, "Archaeology and Protestant Presuppositions in the Study of Indian Buddhism," in *Bones, Stones, and Buddhist Monks* (Honolulu: University of Hawai'i Press, 1997), 1–22.

⁹⁰¹ See the Introduction of this dissertation; Jeremiah P. Losty, *The Art of the Book in India* (London: British Library, 1982), 6–8.

⁹⁰² Pratapaditya Pal, *Indian Painting: A Catalogue of the Los Angeles County Museum of Art Collection*, cat. no. 1 (Los Angeles: LACMA, 1993), 57.

The LACMA *DnS* is significant for another reason. The colophon records that it was donated by a Nepalese devotee named Rāmājīva and inscribed by the scribe Svameśvara. This is the only known instance of a Nepalese Buddhist commissioning an illuminated manuscript at Nalanda⁹⁰³. The manuscript therefore captures a moment at which two distinct production *habitus* intersected: that of the Nalanda scriptorium, which supplied the scribal and artistic labour, and that of a Nepalese patron whose devotional priorities shaped the commission.

3.3b Modes of ritual engagement with the completed manuscript

Once produced, the manuscript entered a cycle of ritual uses governed by a second dimension of *habitus*: the embodied dispositions structuring how practitioners related to the completed object. The evidence available from colophons, from the iconographic programmes themselves, and from the surviving Newari Buddhist practices documented in Chapter 2 and observed during fieldwork in Nepal in 2023, points to several distinct but overlapping modes of engagement.

The most fully attested is recitation (*pāṭha*). The Prajñāpāramitā text was read aloud in ceremonial settings, a practice documented in the living traditions of Newari Buddhism, where the recitation of the *AsP* remains a central liturgical event at monasteries such as the Golden Temple (Hiraṇyavarṇa Mahāvihāra) in Patan, as discussed in Chapter 2, drawing on Gellner’s account of Newari monastic ritual cycles⁹⁰⁴. Recitation essentially transforms the manuscript from a quiescent repository of text into an active vehicle of *dharma*-transmission: the teaching, once vocalised in the ritual space, enacts in auditory form the dependent arising it describes. The manuscript’s physical structure: its sequential folios, its divisions into *parivartas*, its colophon marking completion, constructed the temporal architecture of the recitation, pacing the ritual from opening invocation through the philosophical argument to the concluding dedication of merit. The CUL *Pañcarakṣā* (MS Add.1688), produced during Nayāpāla’s fourteenth regnal year for queen Uḍḍakā, is a case where

⁹⁰³ Pal, *Indian Painting*, cat. no. 1, 57.

⁹⁰⁴ David N. Gellner, *Monk, Householder, and Tantric Priest: Newar Buddhism and Its Hierarchy of Ritual* (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 1992), 189–230; see Chapter 2, section 2.3.

royal patronage specifically intended the manuscript for protective ritual use: the *Pañcarakṣā* being a collection of *dhāraṇī* texts whose efficacy depended on their vocalisation in the appropriate ritual setting. The manuscript's twelve illustrated folios, each with three painted panels strategically placed at the beginning of each *rakṣā* text and at the conclusion, were designed to structure the practitioner's passage through the protective recitation cycle: a liturgical architecture existing in the manuscript's physical form.

A second mode of engagement is visual. The manuscript's illuminated panels functioned as auspicious images within the broader South Asian practice of *darśana*. Eck's foundational study established the reciprocal character of the visual encounter between devotee and divine image in the Indian context⁹⁰⁵. The illuminated panels of Pāla period manuscripts actualised this encounter in a miniature, portable form. The V&A *AsP* (IS.5-1958–IS.10-1958), produced during Rāmapāla's thirty-sixth regnal year and donated by the minister Udaya Siṃha, is instructive here. Its iconographic programme: centred on Avalokiteśvara Lokanātha at Mount Potalaka, and incorporating the eight *bodhisattvas* of the Akṣobhya *maṇḍala* as identified by Kim⁹⁰⁶, constitutes not simple illustrations but an independent visual programme designed to structure the devotee's encounter with the divine presences inhabiting the manuscript. Whether the act of viewing these panels was understood to generate merit in the same formal sense as *darśana* of a consecrated temple image is difficult to establish with certainty from the available Pāla period sources; but what can be said is that the illuminations themselves served as independent loci of sacred presence within the manuscript.

Kim's analysis of the Buddhist book cult established a further mode: the veneration of the manuscript as a sacred object in its own right. Placed on an altar, surrounded by offerings, the manuscript could serve as a central object of a *pūjā* in much the same way as a Buddha image or a *stūpa*. Kim observed that within the South Asian Buddhist book cult, manuscripts were venerated as artefacts whose production and reverence mirrored the traditions surrounding *stūpas* and icons, and that a book's cultic potency could exceed that of other sacred objects, embodying what she described

⁹⁰⁵ Diana L. Eck, *Darśan: Seeing the Divine Image in India*, 3rd ed. (New York: Columbia University Press, 1998), 3–9.

⁹⁰⁶ Kim, *Receptacle of the Sacred*, 151, 153.

as a paradox of absent presence, in which the invisible (the *dharma*) is made present through the visible (the material manuscript)⁹⁰⁷.

3.3c The Kaiser Library manuscript: a case study in interrupted *habitus*

The Kaiser Library *AsP* (Acc. No. 9.102 / National Archives Kathmandu Acc. No. 18), discussed in Chapter 1, presents an unusually revealing case for the *habitus* argument because the normal production process was interrupted before completion. Kim assigned a late twelfth-century date to this manuscript, produced somewhere between Varendra and Magadha before being transmitted to Nepal. The text was completed, but the illumination process stopped at an early stage: across the eight illuminated panels, different stages of the painting process are preserved in what can be described as a frozen sequence. Further, the uneven distribution of the folios, suggests that the manuscript was originally intended as an ambitious commission whose scope was later curtailed⁹⁰⁸.

The critical observation, made by Kim, is that despite the abandonment of the illumination process, the eyes of every deity in all the panels were rendered⁹⁰⁹. The ‘opening of the eyes’ of a sculpted image is a well-attested South Asian consecration practice through which the image is ritually brought to life. The Kaiser Library manuscript suggests that an analogous principle governed manuscript illumination: the eyes, the locus of the visual encounter between deity and devotee, the point at which *darśana* becomes possible, were regarded as the minimum necessary condition for the manuscript’s ritual activation. Thus, when resources were insufficient to complete the illumination programme, priority was given not to finishing the most aesthetically prominent elements but to the one element that enabled the devotional encounter. The Kaiser Library manuscript is, in effect, a material diagram of the ritual priorities that governed the production *habitus*, priorities that remain invisible in completed manuscripts.

⁹⁰⁷ Kim, *Receptacle of the Sacred*, 35-40.

⁹⁰⁸ Kim, *Receptacle of the Sacred*, 259.

⁹⁰⁹ Kim, *Receptacle of the Sacred*, 258-259.

3.3d Transmission and the durability of *habitus*

The manuscripts discussed in Chapter 1 circulated through networks of monastic exchange, pilgrimage, and patronage that extended well beyond the Pāla heartland. The CUL Add. 1643, completed in 1015 CE in the Kathmandu Valley, is a case worth noticing in this regard: with its painted panels depicting pilgrimage sites across the known Buddhist world, constituting what Kim described as a portable virtual pilgrimage⁹¹⁰. The LACMA *DnS* (M.72.1.20 a-b), as discussed above, points to a reverse trajectory of a manuscript commissioned and inscribed at Nalanda by a Nepalese patron, carrying the production *habitus* of Magadha's scriptoria across to Nepal⁹¹¹.

The persistence of manuscript ritual practices in Newari Buddhism, where the recitation of the *AsP* continues: demonstrates the durability of the *habitus* that accompanied these manuscripts across centuries and across the Himalayas⁹¹². Gellner's observation that Prajñāpāramitā is "simultaneously identified" with Vajrayoginī, Ugrātārā, and Durgā within a unified liturgical structure at Sankhu⁹¹³ demonstrates both the continuity of the ritual *habitus* and its capacity for creative assimilation: the dispositions acquired in one doctrinal and institutional setting are proved to be "transposable," in Bourdieu's term, to altered circumstances.

3.3e A broader reflection on *habitus*

The analytical yield of *habitus* for this study lies in its capacity to connect the findings of the preceding chapters. The *polycentric* distribution of production styles across the *Magadha-Varendra-constellation* and the Samatāṭa-littoral, documented through the iconographic and stylistic analysis in Chapter 1, reflects the operation of regionally distinct production *habitus* at different monastic scriptoria. The trans-regional trajectory of Prajñāpāramitā's transformation from philosophical abstraction to deified devotional figure, traced in Chapter 2, describes the doctrinal and

⁹¹⁰ Jinah Kim, "An Ambitious Itinerary: Journey Across the Medieval Buddhist World in a Book, CUL Add.1643 (1015 CE)," *Religions* 16, no. 7 (2025): 900; Kim, *Receptacle of the Sacred*, 149-162.

⁹¹¹ Kim, *Receptacle of the Sacred*, 48, 51, 213-214; see Chapter 1, section 1.3.a (B).

⁹¹² See Chapter 2, section 2.3; Gellner, *Monk, Householder, and Tantric Priest*, 189–230.

⁹¹³ Gellner, *Monk, Householder, and Tantric Priest*, 256; see Chapter 2, section 2.3.

historical conditions within which this *habitus* operated and evolved. The ritual practices examined in this section: recitation, *darśana*, veneration, consecration, describe the means through which the manuscript's *dharma*-relic status, established doctrinally in section 3.2, is activated and sustained in the lived practice of the communities that produced and used these objects. Thus, this vocabulary helps us to see the Pāla period illuminated Buddhist manuscripts as a participants in the religious, intellectual, and material life of the communities that made, transported, and venerated them.

3.4 The *bodhi* tree and the *stūpa* as material embodiments of *pratītyasamutpāda*

Like the manuscripts examined in sections 3.2 and 3.3, the *bodhi* tree and the *stūpa* derived their sacred status not from inherent properties of their material constituents but from the conditions that constituted them as sacred objects: the doctrinal narratives linking them to the Buddha's awakening and *parinirvāṇa* respectively, the ritual practices of veneration that sustained their significance across centuries, and the monastic communities whose *habitus* of care, repair, and transmission ensured their persistence. The Bodhi tree, as a *paribhogika dhātu*, perpetuated the Buddha's presence at the site of his enlightenment through the lived continuity of a biological organism: a mode of persistence that is itself an instance of dependent arising, as the tree's survival depended on the human communities that protected, replanted, and venerated it across the destructions and restorations documented in the *Mahābodhivaṃsa*. The *stūpa*, consecrated through the interment of relics, whether corporeal or textual, had its efficacy continually reconstituted through the circumambulation, offerings, and devotional practices of the communities that maintained it.

The *bodhi* tree (Pāli: *bodhirukkha*; Sanskrit: *bodhivṛkṣa*; *Ficus religiosa*) possessed religious significance in South Asia long before the Buddha's enlightenment. According to Buddhist tradition, the Śākyamuni abandoned extreme asceticism, accepted food from Sujātā⁹¹⁴, and sat beneath the Bodhi tree at Bodh Gaya, vowing not to move until attaining enlightenment; this event established

⁹¹⁴ Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 866.

the tree as the *Samyak Sambodhi*⁹¹⁵ or “tree of knowledge.” The Bodhi tree’s leaves are regarded as imperishable: are said to fall only on the day of each Buddha’s nirvāṇa, symbolising both impermanence and renewal. The Bodhi tree has been repeatedly venerated and memorialised in Buddhist history. Aśoka annually honoured it with a festival in the month of Kārtika and his visit is depicted on a gateway at Sanchi. There are multiple parallel designations of the Bodhi tree, including: Sambodhi, Mahābodhi, Mahābodhi-taru, and Mahābodhi-druma, while Buddhist literature and inscriptions at Bhārhut refer to it as *bodhirukkha* and *bodhivṛkṣa*. Although the present tree is an *Asvattha* (pipal), Buddhist tradition asserts that each buddha has his own distinct *bodhi* tree, making the term relational rather than botanical⁹¹⁶. The *bodhi* tree constitutes the sacrosanct arboreal site of each buddha’s enlightenment, as delineated in normative hagiographic accounts. Integral to the narratological framework of a buddha’s awakening, each buddha is uniquely associated with a specific arboreal species. For Gautama, or Śākyamuni, the reigning buddha, enlightenment was achieved beneath a pipal tree (*Ficus religiosa*) at the “seat of enlightenment” (*Bodhimaṇḍal Vajrāsana*) in Bodh Gaya. Propagules from this original tree have been translocated across Buddhist Asia and globally. The Buddha is said to have authorised the planting of a seed at Jetavana. Despite iconoclastic interventions by Brahmanical sovereigns such as Saśānka in the seventh century CE, a seedling from a third-century BCE Sri Lankan cutting restored it. The Pāli *Mahābodhivaṃsa* (c. tenth–eleventh century CE) chronicles the tree’s history, its Sri Lankan transplantation, and the inception of its Sinhalese veneration as a Buddhist relic⁹¹⁷. Its large seeds frequently craft Buddhist rosaries

⁹¹⁵ Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 764.

⁹¹⁶ Arvind Kumar Singh, “Bodhi Tree,” in *Buddhism and Jainism*, ed. Jefferey D. Long, *Encyclopedia of Indian Religions* (Dordrecht: Springer, 2016), 249–252; Damien Keown, “Bodhi Tree,” in *A Dictionary of Buddhism*, Oxford University Press, accessed August 11, 2025, <http://www.encyclopedia.com/doc/1O108-BodhiTree.html>.

⁹¹⁷ Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 254; Singh also noted that texts such as the *Mahāvāṃsa* narrate the transplantation of Bodhi tree branches to Sri Lanka, notably the Sri Mahā Bodhi at Anurādhapura, brought by Saṅghamittā in 288 BCE, along with saplings subsequently planted across the island. The *Mahāvāṃsa* also lists *bodhi* trees of previous Buddhas, establishing a genealogy of sacred trees tied to enlightenment. The Ānandabodhi tree at Jetavana Monastery and other saplings likewise link living trees with the Buddha’s physical presence, suggesting a cult of relic and living plant combined. The Bodhi tree’s sacrality required physical protection and repeated restoration. Chronicles record Aśoka’s initial felling of the tree before his conversion and his later remorseful revival of it, as well as attempts at destruction by Queen Tissarakkhā, the Śuṅga king Puṣyamitra, and the seventh-century king Śaśānka. In each case, the tree or its saplings were replanted or ritually revived, often with branches from Anurādhapura. The present Bodhi tree at Bodh

(*mālā*). The *bodhi* tree possibly traces its origins to the *caitya* tree, which was a sacred locus associated with spirits or *yakṣas*, within a multi-religious context. Initially revered as a site of devotion, protection, and ritual offering, predating and subsequently integrated into Buddhist practice⁹¹⁸, the *caitya* tree is depicted in archaeological evidence from Bharhut, Bodh Gaya, Sanchi and related sites, where bas-reliefs show trees enclosed in *vedikās* (railed enclosures), often flanked by animals or worshippers and inscribed in early Brāhmī script. These inscriptions linked *caityas* to divine abodes and specific locations like Mount Nāḍoda or Mount Arbuda (Mount Abu). The *caitya* tree was originally worshipped as a living entity housing tree-spirits or *yakṣas*, which evolved into a formalised Buddhist symbol of the *bodhi* tree⁹¹⁹. Kinnard argued that the motif of the *bodhi* tree in early Buddhist art signified the centrality of *prajñā*⁹²⁰. Referring to Buddhaghosha's *Samantapāsādikā*⁹²¹, he noted that the Bodhi tree, under which the Buddha attained enlightenment, holds a direct connection to his spiritual awakening, making it a central object of veneration in Buddhism from its early history. Unlike the shrine ("*cetiya*m"), which contains the Buddha's physical relics and is linked to his presence, as Schopen argued, or the eldest member of the *saṅgha* ("*saṅghatthera*m"), the *bodhi* tree's sanctity is rooted in its soteriological and symbolic role⁹²². The place where a manuscript (*pustaka*) is located is also called a *caitya*, and as Schopen suggested, in the context of the term "*caityabhūta*," noting that it transcends the status of an ordinary *caitya*. Schopen demonstrated that, based on texts such as the *AsP*, *Vajracchedikā*, *Saddharmapuṇḍarīka*,

Gaya descends from a sapling planted in 1881 by Alexander Cunningham after the previous tree's demise. Throughout the Buddhist world, *bodhi* trees planted at monasteries and temples embody the living continuation of this sacred lineage (Singh, "Bodhi Tree," 249-252). Also see: B. M. Barua, *Gaya and Buddha Gaya* (Calcutta: Indian Research Institute, 1931/1934); "Mahāvamsa, Chapter 15," Lakdiva.org, accessed August 11, 2025, <http://lakdiva.org/mahavamsa/chap015.html>; *The Mahāvamsa*, trans. Wilhelm Geiger (London: Pali Text Society, 1908/1912).

⁹¹⁸ In this regard, Singh noted that iconographically, early Buddhist art eschewed anthropomorphic representations of the Buddha, using instead the Bodhi tree, along with the *dharmacakra*, empty throne, footprints, and begging bowl, to signify his enlightenment (Singh, "Bodhi Tree," 250-251).

⁹¹⁹ Ramaprasad Chanda, *The Beginnings of Art in Eastern India with Special Reference to Sculptures in the Indian Museum, Calcutta, Memoirs of the Archaeological Survey of India, no. 30* (Calcutta: Government of India, Central Publication Branch, 1927), 5-7.

⁹²⁰ Kinnard, *Imaging Wisdom*, 71-72.

⁹²¹ J. Takakusu and M. Nagai, eds., *Samantapāsādikā: Buddhaghosa's Commentary on the Vinaya Piṭaka, vol. 4* (London: Pali Text Society, 1924-38), 623. "Cetiyaṃ paṭimaṃ bodhiṃ saṅghattheraṃ vandathā ti ..."

⁹²² Kinnard, *Imaging Wisdom*, 54-55.

and other early Mahāyāna scriptures, “Our contexts... leave no doubt as to how the tradition understood the term *caityabhūta*: the *pṛthivīpradeśa* was not like a *caitya*, nor was it just a *caitya*...”⁹²³ Further, he equated the *pustaka* with the *Bodhimaṇḍa*⁹²⁴, the sacred seat under the Bodhi tree at Bodh Gaya where the Śākyamuni attained enlightenment, which embodies the essence of enlightenment itself⁹²⁵. This connection is reinforced by Lamotte, who described the *Bodhimaṇḍa* as the “*presence toute spirituelle de la Loi ou du dharmakāya des Bouddha*”⁹²⁶. The third chapter of the *AsP* also highlights the *Bodhimaṇḍa* at Bodh Gaya as those in its vicinity are protected from harm (except by their own past deeds), so too are those who venerate the *Prajñāpāramitā* book⁹²⁷.

Stūpas were first constructed after the death of the Buddha in order to preserve and worship his relics which were divided into eight portions between some of the main ruling clans of eastern India⁹²⁸. According to Mūlasarvāstivādin law, the Buddha legally possessed whatever was within the *stūpa* and the *gandhakuṭi* (the chamber dedicated to him in every monastery). Wealth attributed to the Buddha could only be used for their maintenance or for ritual purposes. The *Vinaya* stipulates that offerings of gold and other valuables must support the repair of the *gandhakuṭi* and the *stūpas* housing his hair and nail relics. Likewise, part of a deceased monk’s estate was allocated “for the Buddha,”

⁹²³ Gregory Schopen, “Notes on the Cult of the Book in Mahāyāna,” *Indo-Iranian Journal* 17 (1975): 177

⁹²⁴ The Bodhi tree’s symbolism marks its role as a mythic world tree and a signifier of the *Bodhimaṇḍa*, the last place to disappear at the end of a *kalpa* and the first to reappear with the promise of a future Buddha. The tree itself, springing up at the Buddha’s birth, thus became the *axis mundi* of the Śākyamuni’s life story (Singh, “Bodhi Tree,” 250). Also see: S. Dhammika, *Navel of the Earth* (Singapore: Buddhist Publication Society, 1996), accessed August 11, 2025, <http://trove.nla.gov.au/work/35346652>.

⁹²⁵ As Kinnard aptly observed, in the *Kalingabodhi Jātaka* the Buddha instructed Ānanda that among the three types of memorials (*ceṭiyāni*), a bodily memorial (*sarīrakam*) is unsuitable; an *uddesikam* memorial is also unfit as it relies on imagination (*uddesikam avatthukam manamakattena hoti*). However, a *bodhi* tree, likely representing a *pāribhogikam* shrine, is deemed appropriate for veneration. Consequently, the Buddha permitted Ānanda to have a *bodhi* tree planted (Kinnard, *Imaging Wisdom*, 65). Also see: D. C. Ahir, *Buddhist Shrines in India* (Delhi: BR Publishing Corporation, 1986).

⁹²⁶ Étienne Lamotte, *La Concentration de la Marche Héroïque (Śūraṅgamasamādhisūtra)*, *Mélanges Chinois et Bouddhiques*, vol. 13 (Bruxelles: Institut Belge des Hautes Études Chinoises, 1965), 221. Quoted in Kinnard, *Imaging Wisdom*.

⁹²⁷ P. L. Vaidya, ed., *Aṣṭasāhasrikā Prajñāpāramitā*, *Buddhist Sanskrit Texts*, no. 4 (Darbhanga: Mithila Institute, 1960), 28; Kinnard, *Imaging Wisdom*, 99.

⁹²⁸ J. F. Fleet, “The Tradition about the Corporeal Relics of Buddha,” *Journal of the Royal Asiatic Society of Great Britain and Ireland*, 1906, 881–913; Chanda, *The Beginnings of Art in Eastern India*, 7-8; Michael Willis, *Buddhist Reliquaries from Ancient India*, with contributions by Joe Cribb and Julia Shaw (London: British Museum Press, 2000); K. Werner, “The Place of Relic Worship in Buddhism: An Unresolved Controversy?” in *International Journal of Buddhist Thought & Culture* 12 (2009): 7–28. In the medieval eastern Indian context, see: Copplestone, *Monasteries, Mountains, and Maṇḍalas*, 163-166.

to be used for his worship, or for new works on the *stūpa*, suggesting that the *stūpa* functioned not merely as a reliquary, but as the Buddha's legal and ritual residence, and as the focal point of monastic devotion and community wealth⁹²⁹. Drawing on iconographical evidence, particularly reliefs depicting episodes from the Buddha's life, Giuseppe De Marco observed that Gandhāran artists consciously used the *stūpa* form to represent tombs and burial chambers⁹³⁰. He showed that certain reliefs depict sepulchral chambers surmounted by *stūpa*-like constructions, suggesting that in Buddhist practice and visual culture, the *stūpa* could function simultaneously as a relic-shrine, cosmological symbol, and funerary monument, challenging interpretations that restrict the *stūpa* to purely symbolic or commemorative meanings, demonstrating instead its heterogeneous role and its close connection with death, burial, and ritual memory⁹³¹. Beyond Gandhāra, De Marco noted parallels in Central Asia, particularly Kučā. A painting from Kučā reproduces the Sudāya story, where the mother is shown buried inside a tall quadrangular structure with an arched opening, cornices, and a cupola. Foucher identified this as reflecting the "characteristic form of Central Asian funerary monuments⁹³²." Other monuments in Kučā and Qizil, often called "*stūpas*" or "*stūpa* surmounting a *caitya*," share typological features with Gandhāran examples, including basements with arched openings and *aṇḍa* domes⁹³³. These analogies suggest that the "*stūpa*-tower" or *turmstūpa* form could combine the dual functions of a chamber tomb and a *stūpa*. Chinese sources further confirm the funerary role of *stūpas*: a second-century BCE text, the *Pi ni mu jing*, records: "*Sur les cadavres, on*

⁹²⁹ Schopen further noted that ordinary cremations of monks were prohibited near a *stūpa* because of their foul odour, which could defile the sanctity of the monument. The Buddha's cremation, however, was entirely different: his body was burned with fragrant woods, producing an overpowering aroma. This act transformed his body into two enduring forms central to Buddhist life: tangible relics and incorporeal fragrance, both situated at the heart of monastic practice, literally and symbolically anchored in the *stūpa*. See: Gregory Schopen, "The Fragrance of the Buddha, the Scent of Monuments, and the Odor of Images in Early India," *Bulletin de l'École française d'Extrême-Orient* 101 (2015): 15–16.

⁹³⁰ Alfred Foucher, *L'Art gréco-bouddhique du Gandhāra*, vol. 2 (Paris: Leroux, 1918), 391–95.

⁹³¹ On the *stūpa*'s symbolism, see: Adrian Snodgrass, *The Symbolism of the Stūpa* (Delhi: Motilal Banarsidass Publishing House, 1992).

⁹³² Foucher, *L'Art gréco-bouddhique du Gandhāra*, vol. 2, 392–393. Also see: Alfred Foucher, *The Beginnings of Buddhist Art and Other Essays in Indian and Central-Asian Archaeology* (Paris: Paul Geuthner, 1917), 167–169; John Marshall, *The Buddhist Art of Gandhāra: The Story of the Early School, Its Birth, Growth, and Decline* (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 1960).

⁹³³ Ernst Waldschmidt, *Die Legende vom Leben des Buddha*, vol. 3 (Berlin: Akademie Verlag, 1951), 151–53.

élève des stūpas” (“over corpses, *stūpas* are erected⁹³⁴”). Similarly, a Chinese translation of the *Mahābhisekadhāraṇīsūtra* (ca. 317–322 CE) cites the Buddha explaining that corpses may be treated “by water, by fire, or under a tomb in *stūpa*⁹³⁵.” The Chinese pilgrim and monk-scholar, Yi Jīng also attested to a related practice, describing a *kula*, “a thing like a *stūpa* for the dead, to contain his *śarīra*⁹³⁶ (relics).”⁹³⁷ Harry Falk argued that the wide distribution of relics of the Buddha across South Asia cannot be explained by the survival of a single, original set of remains but rather by the repeated division and redistribution of his ashes. The canonical narrative of the Buddha’s cremation, in which eight groups received relics, was only the starting point of an extended history of multiplication⁹³⁸. Archaeological finds: such as reliquaries from Sanchi⁹³⁹, Piprahwa⁹⁴⁰, Nepalese Terai⁹⁴¹, Sri Lanka,

⁹³⁴ Jean Przyluski, *La légende de l'empereur Açoka* (Paris: Paul Geuthner, 1923), 59 [translated to English by author]; Samuel Beal, *Texts from the Buddhist Canon Known as the Pi-ni-mu King* (London: Trübner, 1871), 12.

⁹³⁵ Étienne Lamotte, *Le Traité de la grande vertu de sagesse de Nāgārjuna (Mahāprajñāpāramitāśāstra)* vol. 2 (Louvain: Bureaux du Muséon, 1944), 695 [translated to English by author].

⁹³⁶ J. Takakusu, *A Record of the Buddhist Religion as Practised in India and the Malay Archipelago (A.D. 671–695) by I-Ching* (Oxford: Clarendon Press, 1896), 108.

⁹³⁷ Giuseppe De Marco, “The Stūpa as a Funerary Monument: New Iconographical Evidence,” *East and West* 37, no. 1/4 (December 1987): 191–246

⁹³⁸ T. W. Rhys Davids, *Dialogues of the Buddha*, vol. 2 (London: Pali Text Society, 1899), 164–70.

⁹³⁹ John Marshall, *The Monuments of Sanchi*, vol. 1 (Calcutta: Superintendent of Government Printing, 1940), 45–47.

⁹⁴⁰ Allen, Charles. “What Happened at Piprahwa: A Chronology of Events Relating to the Excavation in January 1898 of the Piprahwa Stūpa in Basti District, North-Western Provinces and Oude (Uttar Pradesh), India, and the Associated ‘Piprahwa Inscription’, Based on Newly Available Correspondence.” *Zeitschrift für Indologie und Südasiastudien* 29 (2012): 1–19; Herbert Härtel, “On the Dating of the Piprahwa Vases,” in *South Asian Archaeology 1997: Proceedings of the Fourteenth International Conference of the European Association of South Asian Archaeologists, Held in the Istituto Italiano per l’Africa e l’Oriente, Palazzo Brancaccio, Rome, 7–14 July 1997*, ed. Maurizio Taddei and Giuseppe de Marco, vol. 2, Serie Orientale Roma 90 (Rome: Istituto Italiano per l’Africa e l’Oriente, 2000), 1011–24; W. C. Peppé, “The Piprahwa Stūpa, Containing Relics of Buddha,” in *Journal of the Royal Asiatic Society* (1898): 573–78; W. C. Peppé, “The Piprahwa Stūpa: Discovered by Mr. W. C. Peppé of Birdpore Estate 1898,” [Birdpore], 1898; Vincent Smith, “The Piprahwa Stūpa,” in *Journal of the Royal Asiatic Society* (1898): 868–70; K. M. Srivastava, “Archaeological Excavations at Piprahwa and Ganwaria,” in *Journal of the International Association of Buddhist Studies* 3, no. 1 (1980): 103–10; V. Mishra, “Further Excavations (2012–13) at Piprahwa, Ganwaria and Tola Salargarh, District Siddharth Nagar, Uttar Pradesh,” in *Purāttatva* 43 (2013): 141–48, pls. 1–11. On the recent controversy around a Sotheby’s auction, and the eventual repatriation of the Piprahwa gems, see: Shreevatsa Nevatia, “We Cannot Sell the Body of the Buddha: The Planned Auction of the Piprahwa Relics Has Ignited a Global Debate — The Art Historian Weighs In on What Is Really at Stake,” *Frontline*, June 24, 2025, <https://frontline.thehindu.com/society/buddha-relics-piprahwa/article69731505.ece> (accessed August 13, 2025); Radhika Santhanam, “Art Historian Naman Ahuja on the Repatriation of the Piprahwa Buddha Relics,” *The Hindu*, August 17, 2025, <https://www.thehindu.com/society/history-and-culture/repatriation-piprahwa-buddha-sacred-relics-auction-interview-historian-naman-ahuja/article69919391.ece> (accessed August 13, 2025).

⁹⁴¹ P. C. Mukherji, *Report on a Tour of Exploration of the Antiquities in the Tarai, Nepal the Region of Kapilavastu; during February and March, 1899. With a Prefatory Note by Vincent Smith*, Archaeological Survey of India, 1901; D. R. Sahni, “Excavations at Rāmpurva,” in *Archaeological Survey of India, Annual Report (1907-08)*: 181–88, Calcutta, 1911; K. Werner, “The Place of Relic Worship in Buddhism: An Unresolved Controversy?” *International Journal of Buddhist Thought & Culture* 12 (2009): 7–28; Giovanni Verardi, *Excavations at Gotihawa and Pipri, Kapilbastu District, Nepal*

and Gandhāra⁹⁴²: show evidence of pulverisation and subdivision, suggesting a practice of creating multiple relics to meet devotional and political needs. Literary sources, including the *Mahāparinirvāṇasūtra* and the *Aśokāvadāna*, further attest to these redistributions, especially under Aśoka⁹⁴³, who is said to have opened existing *stūpas* to redistribute relics widely⁹⁴⁴. This multiplication enabled rulers and communities to anchor legitimacy and sacrality in possession of corporeal fragments of the Buddha⁹⁴⁵.

Buddhist epistemological traditions attribute the inception of pilgrimage to the Śākyamuni himself, who, before his *mahāparinirvāṇa*, called upon his devoted followers to journey to four locales in his absence: Lumbini, the site of Śākyamuni's birth; Bodh Gaya, where he realised enlightenment beneath the Bodhi tree; the Deer Park at Sarnath, venue of his inaugural discourse (*dharmacakrapravartana*); and Kushinagar, locus of his *mahāparinirvāṇa*. By the era of King Aśoka (ca. 268–232 BCE), four additional sites: Shravasti, Sāṅkāśyā, Rajgir, and Vaishali: renowned for their associations with the Buddha's miracles, augmented this itinerary, collectively constituting the Eight Great Places of Pilgrimage. Beyond these, Buddhist devotees traversed different other sites across the Gangetic plains tied to the Buddha's biography. Aśoka designated such peregrinations as *dharmayātrā*, undertaking his own in ca. 249 BCE, two decades post coronation. This imperial circuit proved transformative, as he erected *stūpas* and also erected towering, polished sandstone pillars surmounted by animal capitals at each halt.

Any discussion on pilgrimage in the Indian subcontinent, remains incomplete without a discussion on Gaya. Recent studies by Abhishek Singh Amar have substantially enriched our

(Rome: Istituto Italiano per l'Africa e l'Oriente, 2007); H. R. Joshi and I. Joshi, eds., *Antiquities of Buddha Sakyamuni's Birthplace in the Nepalese Tarai* by A. Führer, Including Correspondence of 1898 between Dr. A. Führer and General Khadga Shumsher Rana Along with an Article of Buddhist Archaeology in the Nepal Tarai, 1904, by General Khadga Shumsher Rana, Nepal Studies, Past and Present (Kathmandu: 1996).

⁹⁴² Harry Falk, "The Introduction of Stūpa-Worship in Bajaur," in *Afghanistan: Ancien Carrefour entre l'Est et l'Ouest*, ed. Osmund Boppearachchi and Marie-Françoise Boussac (Turnhout: Brepols, 2005), 93–104.

⁹⁴³ Harry Falk, *Aśokan Sites and Artefacts: A Source-Book with Bibliography*, Monographien zur indischen Archäologie, Kunst und Philologie 18 (Mainz: Verlag Philipp von Zabern, 2006).

⁹⁴⁴ Étienne Lamotte, *History of Indian Buddhism: From the Origins to the Śaka Era*, trans. Sara Webb-Boin (Louvain-la-Neuve: Université Catholique de Louvain, 1988), 207–8.

⁹⁴⁵ Falk, Harry. "The Ashes of the Buddha." *Bulletin of the School of Oriental and African Studies* 76, no. 1 (2013): 1–30.

understanding of the Gaya-Bodh Gaya complex by incorporating archaeological survey data, epigraphic analysis, and textual criticism into a unified framework. Through an extensive field study of the wider Bodh Gaya region, Amar documented the site's history within a settlement context extending from the Neolithic period onward, as attested by Taradih excavations adjacent to the Mahābodhi temple complex, and argued that the sacred landscape should be understood not as an isolated monument but as an interconnected Buddhakṣetra: including the Mahābodhi complex, the Sujātā stūpa, Mora hill, and Gayāśīrṣa, whose successive layers of monumentalisation from the third century BCE through the Pāla period were shaped by evolving conceptions of the Buddha's body, shifting ritual orientations from tree-shrine to temple-image, and the *saṅgha's* active strategies of "hierarchical-inclusion" in response to competing Vaiṣṇava and Śaiva orders⁹⁴⁶. The Gaya region, which includes Bodh Gaya, is a pivotal 'sacred centre' across Indian religious traditions, particularly Hinduism and Buddhism, attributed to its deep connections with spirit deities and the deceased, a significance suggested by the juxtaposition of Sujāt'ās offering of rice-milk⁹⁴⁷ to the meditating Śākyamuni, drawn from the *Buddhacarita*, *Lalitavistāra*, and *Nidānakathā* (spanning the first to fifth centuries CE), with the funerary practice of *śrāddha*, perhaps implying that the Buddha's visit to what is now Bodh Gaya may have been influenced by its association with ancestor and spirit worship⁹⁴⁸.

⁹⁴⁶ Abhishek Singh Amar, "Sacred Bodh Gaya: The Buddhakṣetra of Gotama Buddha," in *Cross-disciplinary Perspectives on a Contested Buddhist Site: Bodh Gaya Jataka*, ed. David Geary, Matthew R. Sayers, and Abhishek Singh Amar (London: Routledge, 2012), 29–42; Amar, "Buddhist Responses to Brāhmaṇa Challenges in Medieval India: Bodhgayā and Gayā," *Journal of the Royal Asiatic Society*, ser. 3, 22, no. 1 (2012): 155–85; Amar, "The Buddhakṣetra of Bodhgaya: Saṅgha, Exchanges and Trade Networks," in *Revisiting Early India through Epigraphy and Other Texts: Essays in Honour of D.C. Sircar*, ed. Suchandra Ghosh et al. (Calcutta: R.N. Bhattacharya, 2014), 117–38; Amar, "Contextualising Bodhgaya: A Study of Settlements and Monastic Sites in the Bodhgaya Region," in *South Asian Archaeology 2007*, vol. 2, ed. Pierfrancesco Callieri and Luca Colliva (Oxford: Archaeopress, 2010), 1–13; Amar, "An Archaeological Study of Pilgrimage and Ritual at Sacred Bodhgaya," *Prāgdhārā* 19 (2008): 38–45.

⁹⁴⁷ 'Sujāt'ās stūpa', in Gaya, located on the eastern bank of the Niranjana River, merits attention in this discussion. Archaeological findings at the site include fragments of dark grey polished ware and a punch-marked coin dating to the second century BCE., while Pāli and Sanskrit textual biographies indicate that the *stūpa* was erected to commemorate Sujāt'ās offering of rice-milk to Śākyamuni. Richard Salomon notes that the earliest surviving reference to 'Sujāt'ās stūpa' appears in manuscripts written in the Kharoṣṭhī script, unearthed from a *stūpa* in Hadda near Jalalabad, eastern Afghanistan, buried circa 140 CE., suggesting that narratives of the Buddha's life, including Sujāt'ās donation and the *stūpa's* presence in eastern India, were widely circulated and revered in distant northwestern regions beyond Bodh Gaya.

⁹⁴⁸ Robert DeCaroli, *Haunting the Buddha: Indian Popular Religions and the Formation of Buddhism* (New York: Oxford University Press, 2004).

Conversely, Matthew Sayers contested this, asserting a lack of conclusive evidence that Gaya was an established centre for ancestor worship or *śrāddha* rituals during Śākyamuni's lifetime, proposing instead that its prominence as a site for such practices emerged in the early centuries of the Common Era, though he acknowledges its status as a 'sacred site' favoured by ascetics, evidenced by over eleven mentions in *sūtra* literature and several in the *Vinaya*, including the Mahāvagga's account of the Buddha's encounter with the fire-worshipping Kaśapa brothers: Uruvilvākāśyapa, Nadīkāśyapa, and Gayākāśyapa: in the Gaya region⁹⁴⁹. Additionally, Tibetan sources recount Padmasambhava's encounter with the goddess Kurukullā: akin to the Brahmanical Kāmadeva but significant to *siddhas*, linked to the Kurukulla mountains or Laṭadeśa: near a Gaya funerary ground during his *sādhana*, influencing her iconography in Tibetan art, where she is depicted rising from a corpse amidst fire, red-hued with one leg pendant; collectively, these accounts indicate that while a direct link between Sujāt'ās offering and *śrāddha* rituals at Gaya remains tenuous and potentially contentious, the region's role extends beyond a mere ascetic retreat to a key locus for funerary rituals and pilgrimage.

Buddhist *stūpas* embody evolving layers of religious, philosophical, and cosmological meaning. While plausibly rooted in early fertility cults, the *stūpa* was gradually transformed into a distinctly Buddhist monument serving as reliquary, memorial, and cosmogram. Its architectural features such as the dome, *harmikā*, and *āyaka* pillars, were interpreted through Buddhist doctrine, mapping theological concepts like the Four Noble Truths, the Eightfold Path, and the Wheel of Dharma onto physical structures. Excavated examples from sites such as Nāgārjunikoṇḍa reveal *stūpas* constructed in wheel and *svastika* forms, each integrating symbolic references to Buddhist ethics, cosmology, and soteriology. *Stūpas* are not merely architectural forms but material expressions of Buddhist ideology, transmuting abstract doctrine into tangible, aesthetic, and ritualised structures that bridged cosmic, religious, and social dimensions⁹⁵⁰. Yael Bentor noted in her 2003 study that

⁹⁴⁹ Matthew Sayers, *Feeding the Dead: Ancestor Worship in Ancient India* (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2013).

⁹⁵⁰ K. Krishna Murthy, "Buddhist Ideologies Transmuted in Stūpas," *The Tibet Journal* 18, no. 4 (Winter 1993): 49–55.

Tibetan *stūpas* and images distinctly embody Tibetan conceptions of relics, evolving from the physical remains of the Buddha into a multifaceted term shaped by both customary practices and emerging theoretical frameworks, with significant developments originating in India. Initially, certain relic concepts were probably related to specific doctrines, though these associations largely faded over time, and by the period of doctrinal consolidation in mainland India, these practices were similarly harmonised; within Tibetan *stūpas* and images, different relic types, rooted in Indian precedents, were enshrined, though the practice achieved a level of elaboration in Tibet which is unparalleled elsewhere. Bentor also observed, that despite extensive scholarly attention to the contents of these Tibetan structures, there has been a general oversight in recognising them as integral to the established Buddhist tradition of relic veneration; the exuberant complexity of Tibetan practices, which might initially obscure their original intent, upon closer examination, serves to enhance and magnify those purposes⁹⁵¹. In his 2012 study, using materiality and semiotics⁹⁵² to understand the shift of Buddhist “ritual foci” from ca. 500 BCE to 500 CE, from earthen *stūpas* to Western Ghats *vihāra* images⁹⁵³, Lars Fogelin observed, that Mahāyāna Buddha images are not the culmination of earlier monks’ efforts, given alternative possibilities; he highlighted that, similar to the agency earlier monks exercised in building *stūpas*, later monks shaped Mahāyāna Buddhism and

⁹⁵¹ Yael Bentor, “The Content of Stūpas and Images and the Indo-Tibetan Concept of Relics,” *The Tibet Journal* 28, no. 1/2 (Spring & Summer 2003): 21–48.

⁹⁵² Fogelin’s comments are apposite here: “Without semiotics, the specific manipulations of stūpas and creation of images have no significance. People are actors and interpretants, objects are of the world and of the mind, and signs have real impacts on people’s actions. A full accounting of archaeological pasts must employ multiple theories that together can account for the dialectic between signs inherited from the past and the actions of agents that alter those signs for the future.” See: Lars Fogelin, “Material Practice and the Metamorphosis of a Sign: Early Buddhist Stūpas and the Origin of Mahayana Buddhism,” *Asian Perspectives* 51, no. 2 (Fall 2012): 305-306.

⁹⁵³ For a study on the spread of Buddhism during this period, also see: Dilip K. Chakrabarti, “Buddhist Sites across South Asia as Influenced by Political and Economic Forces,” *World Archaeology* 27, no. 2 (October 1995): 185–202. Chakrabarti argued that the proliferation and spatial distribution of Buddhist sites across South Asia were fundamentally shaped by evolving political and economic forces. He identified three key phases of expansion: around the sixth century BCE, the second century BCE, and the first to third centuries CE, each correlating with successive expansions of urban centres in India, facilitated by trade networks that sustained monastic institutions. Early Buddhism thrived in urban centres through lay and royal patronage, and under Aśoka, it gained pan-Indian visibility through monumental and inscriptional projects. Subsequent centuries saw regional diversification, with *stūpas*, monasteries, and rock-cut cave complexes flourishing along trade routes and coastal hubs, supported by guilds, merchants, and rulers. In the later period (sixth to thirteenth centuries CE), Buddhism became concentrated in certain regions (e.g., Bengal, Orissa, Gujarat, Tamil Nadu) under dynasties such as the Pālas and Bhauma-Kāras, before its decline as a dominant religious force. Chakrabarti noted that Buddhist sites should be studied not only as monuments but as archaeological reflections of the socio-political and economic conditions that enabled their creation and transformation.

its imagery, with fifth-century CE monks potentially leaving monasteries for pilgrimage sites like Sanchi⁹⁵⁴ or preserving *stūpas* with relics. Fogelin noted that early Buddhists enlarged *stūpas* with stone and stucco to highlight relics, and later monks built attenuated *stūpas* for lay control, then adopting *vihāras* for seclusion, and observed that attenuated *stūpas* connected to ancestral forms and prior *stūpas* 'intellectual backdrop'.⁹⁵⁵ Julia Shaw noted in 2013 that the decline of Indian Buddhism stemmed from internal disputes, reduced patronage after the Gupta period, and external Brahmanical pressures. Unlike Buddhism, Jainism survived by adopting Brahmanical practices and fostering a strong ritual identity for lay followers. Buddhism, by failing to do the same and losing many of its social functions to rival traditions, often became confined to small monastic groups with little societal influence. The decline of institutional Buddhism in the eastern Indian subcontinent following the destruction of the great monastic centres in the late twelfth and early thirteenth centuries CE resulted in a significant diminution of Buddhist societal influence in the region, in contrast to the more sustained institutional presence of Brahmanical traditions in the subcontinent. This observation, however, has to be qualified: as it applies specifically to the Pāla heartland of Bihar and Bengal after the twelfth century CE and cannot be generalised to Buddhism's societal influence across South Asia as a whole. The survival of Newar Buddhism in the Kathmandu Valley represents a prominent counterexample: as Gellner has demonstrated, Newar Buddhist institutions, organised through the *guthī* system of socioreligious corporations, maintained unbroken ritual traditions, community religious functions, and manuscript copying practices from the medieval period to the present, representing precisely the kind of sustained societal integration and institutional continuity whose absence in eastern India this chapter observes. The Pāla manuscript traditions examined throughout this dissertation were preserved, translated and copied precisely within this Newar institutional context, as the living manuscript cultures observed during fieldwork in Nepal in 2023 attest. The decline of Buddhism in eastern India is therefore better understood as a regionally specific

⁹⁵⁴ John Marshall and Alfred Foucher, *The Monuments of Sanchi*, 3 vols. (Delhi: Swati Publication, 1983).

⁹⁵⁵ Fogelin, "Material Practice and the Metamorphosis of a Sign": 304–306.

phenomenon shaped by the particular political and economic conditions of the post-Pāla subcontinent, rather than as evidence of a general failure of Buddhist institutions to achieve societal influence.

Archaeological evidence shows that by the second century BCE, Buddhist monasteries were deeply embedded in local economies, providing services like water management, agriculture, and social welfare alongside their spiritual functions. These practical roles attracted lay patronage and helped integrate monasteries into community life. While the timeline of these activities is debated, they illustrate how Buddhism adapted to complement existing traditions, with monks often playing selective, practical roles in local society. This integration was crucial to the endurance and spread of Buddhism⁹⁵⁶.

3.5 End remarks

This chapter has examined the Pāla period illuminated manuscripts discussed in Chapter 1 through three aspects of their significance within the Buddhist communities that produced and used them. Section 3.2 established their doctrinal status as *dharma*-relics, drawing on Schopen's analysis of the *Prajñāpāramitā* literature's claim that the text is the generative source of the Buddha's relics, and tracing the material consequences of that claim in the practices of manuscript interment, consecration and veneration documented in Chapter 2 and in colophon evidence from Chapter 1. Section 3.3 examined the ritual practices through which the manuscript's *dharma*-relic status was activated and sustained: production, recitation, visual engagement, veneration, analysing these practices as expressions of a *habitus* transmitted within and across monastic institutions. Section 3.3 also argued that the regional variations in manuscript production documented in Chapter 1 can be understood as visible traces of regionally differentiated *habitus*, connecting the art historical findings of the *polycentric semiosis* framework with the ritual analysis developed here. Section 3.4 extended the analysis to the *bodhi* tree and the *stūpa*, which share with the manuscripts the characteristic that

⁹⁵⁶ Julia Shaw, "Archaeologies of Buddhist Propagation in Ancient India: 'Ritual' and 'Practical' Models of Religious Change," *World Archaeology* 45, no. 1 (March 2013): 83–108.

their sacred status arises not from inherent material properties but from the convergence of doctrinal narrative, material form, and the ritual practices of the communities that maintain them. *Pratītyasamutpāda*, the teaching of dependent co-arising that forms the doctrinal core of *Prajñāpāramitā* is also the condition of the existence of these manuscripts as the kind of objects they are. The argument that runs through these sections is a simple one, though its implications are not. The concept of *habitus*, drawn from Bourdieu, has served to describe the embodied, socially structured, and largely pre-reflective character of the practices through which this philosophical reality was performed and enacted in the daily life of the monasteries, households, and pilgrimage routes where these manuscripts were made, used, and transmitted.

To conclude this chapter, I cite a verse from the *Mūlamadhyamakakārikā*, which aptly reflects the principal philosophical underpinning of the above discussion:

Prapañcayanti ye Buddha prapañcātītā avyayam

Te prapañcahatāḥ serve na paśyanti Tathāgatham

[tr.] Those who describe the Buddha who is transcendent to thought and world and is not subject to birth and death in terms of conceptual categories are all victims of *prapañca* (the verbalising mind) and are thus unable to see the Tathāgata in his real nature⁹⁵⁷.

⁹⁵⁷ J. W. de Jong, ed., *Mūlamadhyamakakārikā*, *Adyar Library Series 109* (Madras: The Adyar Library and Research Centre, 1977), 22:15.

Chapter 4: Time's own other: Crafting locality in South Asian Buddhist heritage within the Anthropocene

The main purpose of this chapter is to offer a reflection on the disjunctures in historiographical and anthropological frameworks, and epistemic constructs, from the emic issues on the ground in the context of Buddhist cultural and material heritage in South Asia. In other words, we closely look at what causes the *denial of coevalness*⁹⁵⁸ in archaeological and anthropological research surrounding Buddhist heritage in the region. Building on existing scholarship that has examined the layered temporalities of specific Buddhist heritage sites in the Himalayan region and eastern India, this chapter extends these inquiries by examining how allochronic frameworks and their enduring legacies continue to shape the conditions under which such heritage is managed, accessed, and understood: particularly at sites that have received less sustained scholarly attention. Rather than claiming that layered temporalities have gone entirely unrecognised, the chapter argues that the integration of these insights into heritage management practice and policy remains incomplete, and that infrastructural and bureaucratic conditions on the ground often reproduce the very temporal disjunctures that scholarship has identified. Scholarship on Buddhist heritage sites in the Himalayan region and eastern India has made significant advances in investigating layered temporalities at specific sites. In the eastern Indian context, Abhishek Singh Amar's archaeological survey and epigraphic analysis at Bodh Gaya and across the wider south Bihar region traced the multi-phased development of the buddhakṣetra from its Neolithic settlement origins through Mauryan monumentalisation, Gupta-period sculptural elaboration, early medieval inter-religious competition,

⁹⁵⁸ Johannes Fabian, *Time and the other : how anthropology makes its object*, reprint, (New York: Columbia University Press, 2014).

and Pāla period ritual elaboration⁹⁵⁹. Janice Leoshko, working at the same site, showed how Bodh Gaya's present structures are incomplete, reconfigured, or composed of fragments from different periods⁹⁶⁰. Luczanits's studies of the early Buddhist heritage of Ladakh, particularly his reassessment of the chronological and stylistic layers at Alchi and related western Himalayan sites, demonstrated how successive phases of artistic production coexist within single monument complexes⁹⁶¹, requiring analytical frameworks that can hold multiple temporalities simultaneously. Klimburg-Salter's extensive work on the mural programmes at Tabo similarly revealed how later interventions: restorations, overpainting, architectural modifications, do not simply obscure earlier phases but constitute distinct temporal layers in their own right⁹⁶². What remains less explored, however, and what this chapter seeks to address, is the gap between these scholarly insights and the conditions under which Buddhist heritage is actually managed, accessed, and experienced on the ground. The infrastructural politics, bureaucratic structures, and resource inequities that determine custodianship of these sites in twenty-first century South Asia often reproduce the very temporal disjunctures that scholarship has identified. It is this gap between scholarly recognition and practical stewardship, examined through fieldwork conducted between 2016 and 2023 across eastern India, northern Bengal, Nepal, and Ladakh that this chapter addresses.

The chapter begins by presenting an enquiry into the questions and conditions concerning infrastructure, and the politics of infrastructure, that govern the custodianship, management and accessibility of Buddhist heritage, archaeological and pilgrimage sites in the twenty-first century, in

⁹⁵⁹ Abhishek Singh Amar, "Sacred Bodh Gaya: The Buddhakṣetra of Gotama Buddha," in *Cross-disciplinary Perspectives on a Contested Buddhist Site: Bodh Gaya Jataka*, ed. David Geary, Matthew R. Sayers, and Abhishek Singh Amar (London: Routledge, 2012), 29–42; Amar, "Buddhist Responses to Brāhmaṇa Challenges in Medieval India: Bodhgayā and Gayā," *Journal of the Royal Asiatic Society*, ser. 3, 22, no. 1 (2012): 155–85; Amar, "Contextualising Bodhgaya: A Study of Settlements and Monastic Sites in the Bodhgaya Region," in *South Asian Archaeology 2007*, vol. 2, ed. Pierfrancesco Callieri and Luca Colliva (Oxford: Archaeopress, 2010), 1–13.

⁹⁶⁰ Janice Leoshko, "The Changing Landscape at Bodh Gaya," in *Cross-disciplinary Perspectives on a Contested Buddhist Site: Bodh Gaya Jataka*, ed. David Geary, Matthew R. Sayers, and Abhishek Singh Amar (London: Routledge, 2012), 43–59.

⁹⁶¹ Christian Luczanits, "The Early Buddhist Heritage of Ladakh Reconsidered," in *Ladakhi Histories: Local and Regional Perspectives*, ed. John Bray (Leiden: Brill, 2005); Christian Luczanits, *Buddhist Sculpture in Clay: Early Western Himalayan Art, Late 10th to Early 13th Centuries* (Chicago: Serindia Publications, 2004).

⁹⁶² Deborah Klimburg-Salter and Christian Luczanits, eds., *Tabo: A Lamp for the Kingdom: Early Indo-Tibetan Buddhist Art in the Western Himalaya* (Milan: Skira, 1997)

eastern India: in the heartland of Buddhism, a region where the Pāla empire proliferated, once dotted with many active Buddhist places of worship as well as academic and scholastic institutions of immense repute like Bodh Gaya and Nalanda, and also the region where many of the medieval manuscripts discussed in this dissertation were physically produced. The next section discusses issues related to archaeological sites in northern Bengal, focussing on Bangarh in South Dinajpur district of northern West Bengal, an important archaeological site of Pāla-period settlement, one of the principal centres of Puṇḍravardhana, and considered second in importance only to the more well-known Mahasthangarh in the Bogra district of northern Bangladesh. It then briefly ponders on the material and lived histories of manuscript cultures in Nepal, a region prominently associated with the history and historiography of illuminated Buddhist manuscripts from eastern India, putting together observations from field work in Nepal conducted in 2023, before addressing issues pertinent to the cultural heritage of Ladakh, a region not directly relevant to illuminated Buddhist manuscripts from eastern India, but like Nepal, *mutatis mutandis*, has historically functioned as an important intermediary/ conduit for the transmission of Buddhist art and philosophy, harbouring the confluence of different artistic styles and artists from different regions, like northern India and Kashmir. For this chapter, Ladakh also serves as an important case for: studying cultural heritage in the context of emic knowledge of the local population: and the limitations of such an approach, active military infrastructure in frontier regions and fragile ecology, on which I reflect based on observations from field work conducted in 2022. The chapter concludes by discussing tentative solutions to the problems discussed.

In framing this chapter's exploration of the politics of infrastructure and its impact on cultural heritage preservation in India, my adoption of the first-person perspective is a methodologically deliberate act, grounded in contemporary anthropological scholarship that demands reflexive engagement with my socio-historical positionality, as primarily inspired by Johannes Fabian's critique⁹⁶³ of anthropology's temporal distancing. As a native of northern Bengal, my

⁹⁶³ Fabian, *Time and the other*.

scholarship is shaped by an intimate connection to a region marked by complex historical trajectories: from its partial subsumption under Bhutanese suzerainty until the 1864-65 Anglo-Bhutan War, to its economic dependence on colonial-era tea plantations, and its post-1947 Partition status as a frontier zone. As a descendant of conflict migrants who relocated from southeastern Bengal (now Bangladesh) in the 1940s, I am very much attuned to the enduring legacies of Partition from a frontier perspective: economic precarity, cultural dislocation, and infrastructural neglect, that echo Fabian's notion of the "other" as a construct of temporal *alterity* imposed by hegemonic discourses, and continue to define borderland regions.

My positionality is a critical epistemological stance that aligns with anthropological calls for emic-etic integration. My embeddedness in the region, through lived experiences and prolonged field work in district-level museums, archaeological sites, and state-managed collections in eastern India since the last eight years, affords an intimate understanding of the local idioms, practices, and challenges that shape heritage. While acknowledging the partiality of all ethnographic accounts, my methodology in this chapter is informed by Arindam Dutta's notion of *developmental time*⁹⁶⁴, and the production of culture⁹⁶⁵, and Akhil Gupta's theorisation⁹⁶⁶ of postcolonial bureaucracy, in order to interrogate how systemic inequities in different resources undermine heritage stewardship. Drawing on Sara Ahmed's concept of "affective economies"⁹⁶⁷, I also position my regional rootedness as a form of embodied knowledge that informs my critique. This method further is complemented by Arjun Appadurai's notion of the "production of locality"⁹⁶⁸, therefore positioning my lived experience as a critical lens to interrogate the asynchronous temporalities of South Asian Buddhist heritage, and

⁹⁶⁴ Arindam Dutta, "Incompletion: on more than a certain tendency in postwar architecture and planning," in *Architecture in Development: Systems and the Emergence of the Global South*, ed. Aggregate Architectural History Collaborative (Oxon and New York: Routledge, 2022), 25-46.

⁹⁶⁵ Arindam Dutta, "Designing the Present; The Cole Circle and the Architecture of (an) Imperial Bureaucracy, 1851- 1901" (PhD thesis, Princeton University, 2001); Arindam Dutta, *The Bureaucracy of Beauty: Design in the Age of its Global Reproducibility*, (New York: Routledge, 2007)

⁹⁶⁶ Akhil Gupta, *Red Tape: Bureaucracy, Structural Violence and Poverty in India*, (Durham and London: Duke University Press, 2012).

⁹⁶⁷ Sara Ahmed, *The Cultural Politics of Emotion*, reprint, (Edinburgh: Edinburgh University Press, 2014); Sara Ahmed, "Affective Economies," *Social Text* 79 22, no. 2 (2004): 117-139.

⁹⁶⁸ Arjun Appadurai, "The Production of Locality" in Appadurai, A. *Modernity at Large: Cultural Dimensions of Globalization*. (Minneapolis: University of Minnesota Press, 1996), 178-199.

analyse how the interaction of global discourses of development and heritage converge with regional realities, to shape the preservation and accessibility of South Asia's cultural 'patrimony'.

4.1 Beyond 'othering': Buddhist heritage and infrastructural present in eastern India

Remarking on the limitations that could be posed by the incorrect application of the laws of Great Britain in the eighteenth century, and how law itself can become an obstruction, Adam Smith noted in his *Wealth of Nations*: "The natural effort of every individual to better his own condition... is so powerful a principle", which is:

not only capable of carrying on the society to wealth and prosperity, but of surmounting a hundred impertinent obstructions with which the folly of human laws too often encumbers its operations; though the effect of these obstructions is always more or less either to encroach upon its freedom, or to diminish its security⁹⁶⁹.

Smith's 'impertinent obstructions', has in today's bureaucratic maze of administrators and lawmakers in a 'developing economy' like India transformed into a myriad of implementation, administration and infrastructure issues: the latter being important in our thread of discussion in this chapter. While it may be tempting, and may even seem wise at first to look away stereotyping⁹⁷⁰ such circumstances within the generalised category of 'developing' or the 'third world':

When notions of corrupt so-called underdeveloped countries are combined with a developmentalist perspective, in which state-society relations in the Third World are seen as reflecting a prior position in the development of the advanced industrial nations, the temptation to compare "them" to "our own past" proves irresistible to many Western scholars. Instead, one needs to ask how one can use the comparative study of Third World

⁹⁶⁹ Adam Smith, *An Inquiry into the Nature and Causes of the Wealth of Nations*, reprint, (New York: Random House, 1937), 508.

⁹⁷⁰ Steven Pierce, "Looking Like a State: Colonialism and the Discourse of Corruption in Northern Nigeria," *Comparative Study of Society and History* 48, no. 4 (2006): 888.; Haller Dieter and Cris Shore, "Introduction—Sharp Practice: Anthropology and the Study of Corruption" in Haller, D. And Shore, Cris (eds.). *Corruption: Anthropological Perspectives*. (London: Pluto Press, 2005), 3.; Daniel Jordan Smith, *A Culture of Corruption: Everyday Deception and Popular Discontent in Nigeria*, (Princeton: Princeton University Press, 2007).

political formations to confront the naturalness of concepts that have arisen from the historical experience and cultural context of the West⁹⁷¹.

but it becomes necessary after a point to pose the question that whether indeed this is purely macro-economic, to which even a non-specialist, with a minimum experience of living in the Indian small towns and villages, will retort at the first instant that it isn't. So what are the broader issues in administration of cultural heritage in the country which fail to make it effective in being a responsible custodian?

My first brush with the significance of politics of infrastructure and the important role that it plays in dictating preservation and accessibility of heritage began after following the works done at the Infrastructure Architecture Lab. at MIT Architecture by Professor Arindam Dutta, which:

... conducts research on the relationships between broad, macroeconomic factors driving built infrastructure and the specificities of architectural and urban form ... to study the real-world complexities that go into the making of infrastructure and its effects on built form' with particular focus on 'situations in emerging economies and the developing world'⁹⁷².

One of the primary reasons why it resonated with me is because, throughout my field works at various district-level museums, collections and archaeological sites in eastern India over the years, I have encountered the dismal state of infrastructure at, and connecting most heritage and archaeological sites, museums and state-owned collections in eastern India. The issues of politics of infrastructure, bureaucracy and red-tapism associated with the Buddhism pilgrimage circuit in eastern India, encompass not just accessibility, but heritage reception in general. The problem of infrastructure visibly impact a huge number of visitors, both pilgrims and tourists, alongside presenting an obstruction to the environmental and socio-economic interests of the region and its population. The

⁹⁷¹ Gupta, 79.

⁹⁷²“ Infrastructure Architecture Lab,” MIT Architecture, accessed July 9, 2025, <https://architecture.mit.edu/infrastructure-architecture-lab>.

situation is more amplified at the Nalanda-Bodh Gaya circuit, which also coincides with different holy-sites in the Brahmanical, Jain and Islamic traditions.

(A) Bihar

At the IAL, MIT Dutta posited⁹⁷³ the fundamental importance of the issue of river-bridging, as a leading example of the politics of infrastructure that is explicit in the Buddhist heartland: the eastern Indian state of Bihar. Just north of the Buddhist sites of Gaya and Nalanda, and a stone's throw away from the Sikh pilgrimage site of Takht Sri Patna Sahib⁹⁷⁴, there are two parallel bridges, few kilometres apart, both connect Patna with Hajipur. The older one is known as the Mahatma Gandhi Setu (Plate 67), which was one of the first bridges over the Ganga in eastern India, post-Independence: built by Gammon India Ltd., over a period of ten years from 1972 to 1982⁹⁷⁵. *Ab initio*, bridges in eastern India are conceptually different to begin with, from bridges elsewhere in the country, like the western Indian state of Gujarat: an example that Dutta uses. Unlike western India, the span of the rivers in eastern India, especially like that of the Ganga, often span more than just a few kilometres, with the other end of the bridge remaining invisible and fades away into perspective: implying a mammoth construction project funded by huge capital investments. The construction has been so poor, that often chunks of the bridge fall off into the river below, rendering portions of the bridge useless, and causing huge traffic bottlenecks lasting between six to twelve hours on either side of the bridge. What would seem quite surprising to anyone not familiar with on-the-ground infrastructure in the region, is the fact that the second bridge over the Ganga which is 'being constructed', unlike any conventional bridge, doesn't taper off to ramps on both ends, instead they just finish abruptly, often creating a height of more than six feet from the ground. This kind of infrastructural aberration, when looked into, turns out to be caused by the effects of division of

⁹⁷³“KVDF 2020 Day 3: De-Talk by Arindam Dutta & Gurmeet Rai,” KVD Forum, August 17, 2020, video, 2:35:53, <https://www.youtube.com/live/pFQO9wY6GNU?si=GRIUwglJuS33-QTq>.

⁹⁷⁴ Birthplace of Guru Gobind Singh, the tenth Guru of the Sikhs. Also known in popular parlance as Takht Sri Harimandir Ji.

⁹⁷⁵ Dutta and Rai, “KVDF 2020 Day 3: De-Talk by Arindam Dutta & Gurmeet Rai.”

jurisdiction and politicisation of jurisdictions. The bridge and the land on which it stands happens to belong to the central government while the lands adjacent to it, are owned by rival political factions after having lobbied successfully to disrupt the infrastructural project⁹⁷⁶. Both the bridges are pivotal in connecting domestic and international tourists and pilgrims to the Buddhist sites in Bihar. The macro-economic concept of ‘rent-seeking⁹⁷⁷’, can be observed⁹⁷⁸ in action in infrastructural projects across eastern India. The idea of obstructing an infrastructural project and rent-seeking are activities which define the popular word ‘corruption’. Corruption can also serve a significant theoretical lens:

Instead of treating corruption as a dysfunctional aspect of state organizations ... as a mechanism through which the state itself is discursively constituted. Corruption is an essential lens for understanding the meaning of the state in the Indian context. For example, it helps one comprehend how state violence enacted on the poor is constitutive of its developmental mission⁹⁷⁹.

To expand upon Dutta’s study, which attributed the high levels of politicisation of infrastructure to the abysmally low levels of economic activity on the north of the Indian state of Bihar, a region where even road networks are sporadic, as are the number of motor vehicles, the latter almost non-existent⁹⁸⁰, throughout important Buddhist pilgrimage sites, a majority of them located to the north of the river Ganga in Uttar Pradesh, Bihar, West Bengal and Bangladesh, we find a disjunct between the reputation of these sites as world heritage sites and the economic reality which surround them. The erstwhile National Highway 83 (now National Highway 22), which connects Patna to Bodh Gaya, and which is in the *process* of redevelopment, to accommodate the rising number of pilgrims to the region, and reduce the travel time between Patna and Gaya to less than four hours⁹⁸¹, has been

⁹⁷⁶ Dutta and Rai, “KVDF 2020 Day 3: De-Talk by Arindam Dutta & Gurmeet Rai.”

⁹⁷⁷ Gordon Tullock, “The Welfare Costs of Tariffs, Monopolies and Theft,” *Economic Inquiry* 5, no. 3 (1967): 224-232.; Anne Kreuger, “The Political Economy of the Rent-Seeking Society,” *American Economic Review* 64, no. 3 (1974): 291-303.

⁹⁷⁸ Dutta and Rai, “KVDF 2020 Day 3: De-Talk by Arindam Dutta & Gurmeet Rai,” 1:05:37.

⁹⁷⁹ Gupta, 78.

⁹⁸⁰ Dutta and Rai, “KVDF 2020 Day 3: De-Talk by Arindam Dutta & Gurmeet Rai,” 1:06:32 - 1:07:32.

⁹⁸¹ “Patna to Gaya in 2 hours as 4-lane road nears completion,” *Business Today*, Mar. 16, 2025.

marred in controversy⁹⁸² since the project took off. The disproportionate levels of income, politics of infrastructure, and severe unemployment which today mark Bihar, culminated and found violent expression through the ‘Agnipath protests’ in June 2022, against the Indian Army’s new recruitment scheme, when large scale arson and vandalism were reported⁹⁸³ along the National Highway 82, which connects Gaya to Bihar Sharif, passing through Rajgir, and the National Highway 22 (in old numbering National Highway 83) which connects Patna to Dobhi, passing through Jehanabad, Gaya and Bodh Gaya. The Vikramshila Setu on the Ganga, named after the famous monastic institution, whose archaeological site lies in its vicinity, in the Bhagalpur district of northern Bihar, was opened in 2001. It serves to connect National Highway 33 (which served as a vital link between Bihar and West Bengal through Jharkhand, connecting cities in northern Bihar like Munger and Bhagalpur with the capital Patna) and National Highway 31 (which connects Unnao in Uttar Pradesh with Gajole in Malda). The bridge itself is around 4.4 kms long and is one of the longest river bridges in India. Presently it faces intense traffic congestion. To remediate the situation, construction work for another four-lane road bridge parallel to the Vikramshila Setu was started in 2020. The region in which the bridge is located is marked by a very vast expanse of the Ganga, with the cities of Bhagalpur and Naugachia on the southern and northern banks, respectively. Before the construction of this bridge, local people used small boats to cross this expanse, which some still do. I had my first reckoning with the vastness of the Ganga here, during my train journeys from Jalpaiguri to Delhi as a college student in Delhi University. This entire region is well-known for being devastated every year by significant flooding, caused by a lack of river-management infrastructure and policies.

In post-Independence India, in contrast to British India, generally road networks were prioritised for infrastructural development. While the British did build roads, famously the Grand Trunk Road, their focus was often on facilitating trade, military movement and resource extraction based on an idea of the subcontinent as an “... untapped hermetic reservoir waiting to be aerated by

⁹⁸²“ Bihar’s NH-22 Goes Viral: Full-Grown Trees Left In Middle Of 4-Lane Highway!,” *Business Today*, Jul. 2, 2025.

⁹⁸³“ Train Set on Fire as Agnipath Protests Rage in Bihar for Second Day,” *The Wire*, Jun. 16, 2022.

the introduction of roadways and railways⁹⁸⁴.” Starting from the 1950s to the mid-1980s, although road networks increased throughout India, Bihar was often ranked at the bottom in terms of new development of road infrastructure⁹⁸⁵. There has also been a recent push in India, through its nodal federal government body, the National Highways Authority of India, for the development of road infrastructure, both highways and rural roads⁹⁸⁶, and large amount of capital⁹⁸⁷ have been invested on different road infrastructure projects. The project of *aeration*, which was started by British imperialism, is now continued through policies which often promote infrastructure development, often to give multinational corporations access to mineral resources⁹⁸⁸, as well as access to neoliberal market forces⁹⁸⁹. Focussing on Bihar, beyond practices of corruption⁹⁹⁰ plaguing these infrastructure projects, often such policy fails to make qualitative changes in terms of *mobility*, on the ground, as the region continues to remain affected by abject socio-economic conditions. This brings us back to Dutta’s observation that the economic conditions are so dire, that very few people in the region have any need to move at all⁹⁹¹, unless for migrating to work in other Indian cities. The push for the development of road infrastructure has been consistent over several decades of Indian policy-making, which has its own serious repercussions:

Obviously, the Indian road establishment likes the lateral growth of roads as in the US where land is available aplenty ... The social cost is ignored, and the consequent huge economic cost too is taken lightly in these administrative directives⁹⁹².

⁹⁸⁴ Arindam Dutta, “Designing the Present; The Cole Circle and the Architecture of (an) Imperial Bureaucracy, 1851- 1901” (PhD thesis, Princeton University, 2001), 400.

⁹⁸⁵ Samrat Bose, “Road Density, Resource Intensity and Efficiency in National Highways of India: 1958-1997,” *Economic and Political Weekly* 38, no. 6 (2003): 561–71.

⁹⁸⁶ “India’s other, little-known infrastructure revolution,” *The Economist*, Feb. 20, 2025.

⁹⁸⁷ “India’s US\$268.4 billion transport infrastructure plan,” *Global Highways*, Jul. 3, 2024.; “India will have better road infrastructure than the U.S., says Nitin Gadkari,” *The Hindu*, Oct. 20, 2024.

⁹⁸⁸ Roshan Varughese and Soumen Mukherjee, “Development-induced dispossession: Adivasi existence in the milieu of contemporary Indian texts in translation,” *Humanities and Social Sciences Communications* 11, 659 (2024): 561–71.; “Contradictions of ‘development ’in contemporary India,” *openDemocracy*, Feb. 7, 2011.; “Dongria Kondh tribe of India resist powerful mining company,” *The Economist*, Nov. 20, 2013.

⁹⁸⁹ Annapurna Devi Pandey, “The Challenges of Neoliberal Policies and the Indigenous People’s Resistance Movement in Odisha, India,” *e-cadernos CES*, 28 (2017).

⁹⁹⁰ “CBI arrests four, including NHAI official, for bribery to process private company bills related to contracts,” *The Hindu*, Mar. 24, 2025.

⁹⁹¹ Dutta and Rai, “KVDF 2020 Day 3: De-Talk by Arindam Dutta & Gurmeet Rai,” 1:07:39.

⁹⁹² Biswanath Debnath, “Land Acquisition and National Highways,” *Economic and Political Weekly* 43, no. 31 (2008): 4.

Effective branding, advertisement and promotion, incorporating different government and non-government sectors, for example the introduction of the Mahaparinirvana Express by the Indian Railways, as well as events of international reputation, like visits by the Dalai Lama, the Prime minister and other dignitaries of the government, have been the main impetus behind the rising inflow of domestic and global tourists. With the advent of globalisation, many heritage sites in Bihar serve as a point of cut-throat competition for the regional economy and tourism market. A situation thus results from a combination of the already poor levels of public infrastructure, and the burden of twenty-first century tourism, whereby heritage sites, which sustained pilgrimage activities for thousands of years, falter. During the 2020 Covid-19 pandemic, although the lessening of tourist flows seemed like a fair change from an environmental perspective, the impact on the already deprived economy of the region, was undoubtedly catastrophic. Given the proximity of the heritage sites in Bihar, to the Ganga and its different tributaries and distributaries, they are significantly prone to environmental hazards and erratic weather patterns caused due to climate change: which is marked by extreme levels of heat that often destroys the top layer of the soil in the summers, punctuated by turbulent monsoons.

The Nalanda archaeological site comes under the supervision of the Archaeological Survey of India (henceforth ASI), with numerous international institutions in its vicinity, and parts of the site itself home to the re-conceptualised Nalanda University. With the entire site itself coming under the ambits of different authorities, the problematic of jurisprudence is bound to arise. Unlike the Buddhist murals in the caves of western India which have been fairly well-documented and copiously written about, the medieval wall-paintings of eastern India, very few of which actually exist: owing perhaps to the unfavourable humid climatic conditions, have almost escaped scholarly notice: which is surprising, since such a large number of paintings from eastern India have survived on palm-leaf manuscripts, it is reasonable to infer that mural-making activities took place, given the tradition of murals within Buddhism. As of 2022, Bodh Gaya and Nalanda from eastern India, Sanchi

from central India, and Ajanta and Ellora caves of western India are the only ones amongst the numerous sites associated with the Buddhist pilgrimage circuit in India, to be marked as World Heritage Sites by the UNESCO.

In Nalanda, measuring 31.7m x 22.7m, a Buddhist temple was discovered during the 1975-76 excavations of the Mid-eastern/ Patna circle of the ASI, which originally started during 1973-1974. It is locally known as the ‘shrine mound’, and officially the ‘Sarai mound’. It exists outside the main perimeter of the Nalanda archaeological site, but inside the ASI boundary wall. The ASI had earlier run conservation efforts, which have significantly modified the structure itself; and also conducted excavation exercises around the main *caitya*, and recovered some artefacts and sculptures which are kept in the adjacent site-museum. Although the earlier excavations at Nalanda starting from around 1915/16 to 1953, are well known to scholars, the post-1975/1976 discoveries have come under considerably lesser limelight. It was brought into scholarly attention through Gouriswar Bhattacharya’s 1983 presentation at the South Asian Archaeology conference at Brussels, which was later published in 1985. When Bhattacharya visited the aforementioned Buddhist temple, he encountered:

Above a huge pedestal, measuring 8m in length (Nath 1983), inside the sanctum, on a large stucco double-petaled lotus of light red colour the damaged figure of a huge standing figure, no doubt of the Buddha ... The lotus is badly damaged and the feet are unto the ankles of the legs, there being no trace of the rest of the figure⁹⁹³.

The stucco image itself, as Bhattacharya conjectured, could have been as high as seven meters, which according to him, would have been an example of one of the largest sculptural examples of the Buddha image, with no rival from any part of India⁹⁹⁴. He drew specific attention to the paintings,

⁹⁹³ Gouriswar Bhattacharya, “The Newly Discovered Buddhist temple at Nālandā” in Schotsmans, J. and Maurizio T. (eds.) *South Asian Archaeology 1983. Papers from the Seventh International Conference of the Association of South Asian Archaeologists in Western Europe, held in Musées Royaux d’Art et d’Histoire, Brussels*. (Naples: Instituto Universitario Orientale, Dipartimento di Studi Asiatici, 1985), 722.

⁹⁹⁴ Bhattacharya, 722.

which were mostly obscure outlines: "... in blue lines, over white-washed lime plaster, of continuous scrolls and a series of rosettes" on the northern, southern and western walls inside the sanctum, and the paintings in front of the pedestal in two panels⁹⁹⁵. The painted panels were published by B. Nath in 1977⁹⁹⁶ and 1983⁹⁹⁷. The noted Bengali art historian Sarasi Kumar Saraswati also heard about the the 1975-76 discoveries at Nalanda, but did not have the opportunity to visit, but argued in his book on paintings from the Pāla-period, that the style of these mural paintings should surely correspond to the palm leaf miniature illustrations from medieval eastern India⁹⁹⁸. A. Ghosh, mentioned similar mural paintings at Monastery No. 14, but which Bhattacharya couldn't trace during his visit⁹⁹⁹. Niharranjan Ray, observed in 1957: "these miniatures ... do not represent a separate style of book-illustration, they are, in fact, mural painting in reduced dimension"¹⁰⁰⁰. I had the first opportunity to visit the site of Nalanda in 2016, when I could view the feet of the main stucco image of the Buddha. To the naked eye, the paintings were almost non-existent by then, that they were hardly recognisable. Presently, the main stucco image of the Buddha is also almost non-existent, and only an outline of the feet of the Buddha Śākyamuni is visible. The colours were still determinable during Bhattacharya's visit (Plates 68a-b & 69a-b). In the upper panel, a seated two-armed figure, likely Avalokiteśvara, exhibits *varadamudrā* with his right hand, and holds a lotus stalk in his left, within a two-pillared niche, flanked by unidentified figures. The lower panel features a rotund seated male figure holding a fruit-like object and an animal-shaped money-bag, accompanied by a seated male with unclear attributes and a trotting horse to his right, and a seated female with a mirror-like object to his left, beside an elephant and a possible circular object, perhaps representing the Seven Jewels (*saptaratna*)¹⁰⁰¹. The colours are now completely obliterated, due to unchecked weather conditions

⁹⁹⁵ Bhattacharya, 722.

⁹⁹⁶ B. Nath, "The Nalanda Murals," *The Journal of the Bihar Purāvid Parishad* 1 (1977): 269–271.

⁹⁹⁷ B. Nath, *Nalanda Murals*, (New Delhi, 1983).; Bhattacharya, 723.

⁹⁹⁸ Sarasi Kumar Saraswati, *Pāl Juger Chitrokola*, (Calcutta: Ananda Publishers, 1978), 181.; Bhattacharya, 732.

⁹⁹⁹ Bhattacharya, 731.; A. Ghosh, *Nālandā*, (New Delhi, 1971).

¹⁰⁰⁰ Niharranjan Ray, "Painting" in Majumdar, R.C. and A.D. Pusalker (eds.), *The Struggle for Empire, Bharat Vidya Bhavan's The History and Culture of the Indian People, Vol. V.*, reprint, (Mumbai: Bharatiya Vidya Bhavan, 2001), 690.; Bhattacharya, 732.

¹⁰⁰¹ Bhattacharya, 723-724.

and poor or none conservation efforts. The painted panels are also accompanied by inscriptions, one of which from the eighth century CE in the Siddhamātrkā script, contains three names of individuals: while the first name is illegible, the second and third read *śrī-Prachanḍa-hasti* and *Pr̥thvicanḍa* respectively, who Bhattacharya suggested¹⁰⁰² to be names of pilgrims who visited the temple.

En passant, in nearby eastern Uttar Pradesh there are several popular Buddhist heritage sites. In Kushinagar, the place considered by Buddhists as the site of the Buddha's *mahāparinirvāna*, the socio-economic conditions are at similar abysmally low levels as in northern Bihar. Alongside Kushinagar, numerous other important Buddhist pilgrimage sites in the region can be described within the same category; these include: Sarnath and Kausambhi in Uttar Pradesh, Vaishali, Antichak, Rajgir, Bihar Sharif, Nalanda and Bodh Gaya in Bihar, and in nearby Madhya Pradesh, sites such as: Sanchi, Murel Khurd, Satdhara, Bharhut and Deur Kothar¹⁰⁰³. The site of Deur Kothar was discovered as late as 1982 by P.K. Mishra of the ASI along with the village *sarpanch* of the Barhat village where the site is located. Alongside two *stūpas* thought to have been built by Aśoka, the entire perimeter of the site, which is not very distinctly marked, are rich in rock-paintings and inscriptions in the Brāhmī script. The site was taken up for excavation briefly by the ASI during 1999-2000, but was stopped abruptly for unknown reasons¹⁰⁰⁴.

(B) Northern Bengal and the Terai-Duars

Moving from north Bihar along the Ganga to northern West Bengal and northern Bangladesh, the trend in very low economic activity and infrastructural development continues, forming a kind of regional distinction of itself as an area of low-infrastructure. In northern Bengal, Bangarh in the South Dinajpur district is an important site that will be taken up for discussion in this section. In Bangladesh, this extends to the districts of Bogra and Rajshahi, home to Mahasthangarh,

¹⁰⁰² Bhattacharya, 731.

¹⁰⁰⁴ P. K. Mishra, "Excavations at the Buddhist site of Deorkothar (Barhat), District Rewa, Madhya Pradesh, India 1999-2001," *SOAS Circle of Inner Asian Art Newsletter* 13, (June 2001): 3-14.

the Somapura and Jagaddal Mahāvihāras. The continuity in the trend of very low levels of economic activity across this geographical region, keeping to the north of the Ganga, is astounding.

My engagement through field work in 2017 at the archaeological site of Bangarh and in the districts of North Dinajpur, South Dinajpur, and Malda in northern Bengal particularly resonates with Arjun Appadurai's critique of anthropology's historical reliance on the spatially and epistemically distant "somewhere" as a constitutive site of knowledge production:

At least since the latter part of the nineteenth century, anthropological theory has always been based on the practice of going *somewhere*, preferably somewhere geographically, morally, and socially distant from the theoretical and cultural metropolis of the anthropologist. The science of the other has inescapably been tied to the journey elsewhere. But the question of what kind of elsewhere is tied in complicated ways to the history of European expansion, the vagaries of colonial and postcolonial pragmatics, the shifting tastes of Western men of letters¹⁰⁰⁵.

Noting on an encounter with a nineteenth Nepalese copper-alloy standing Māyā image at the American Museum of Natural History in New York¹⁰⁰⁶, and its corresponding label, and contrasting it with the nuanced display offered at the Metropolitan Museum, Mieke Bal once noted:

The verbal presentation is consistently anthropological. Keeping its purpose and status distinct from the museum of high art on the other side of the park, this display has an artifact from a "low" moment of the history of Buddhist art, low because the moment of making coincides with the moment of acquisition: the nineteenth century. This temporal coincidence deprives the artifact of historical patina and scarcity, a requirement for high-art status. Typically, nothing is noted about its style, as it would be in the Met. It is, moreover, thoughtfully presented as anchored in "popular tradition," the nameless other of

¹⁰⁰⁵ Arjun Appadurai, "Theory in Anthropology: Center and Periphery," *Comparative Studies in Society and History* 28, no. 2 (1986): 356-357.

¹⁰⁰⁶ Mieke Bal, *A Mieke Bal Reader* (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2006), 175-180; Fig. 6.2.

individual elite art. From art it thus becomes anthropological evidence of a timeless culture¹⁰⁰⁷.

This encounter may be framed as an experience of *alterity*. As a scholar native to Jalpaiguri, within the same region, I initially encountered northern Bengal not with the minutest of *alterity*: temporal or spatial, but as an extension of my socio-cultural and epistemic milieu. Yet, situating my analysis of the medieval artistic corpus of this region within the existing historiographical frameworks, necessitated an interrogation of my positionality vis-à-vis the metropolitan scholarly traditions that shape my disciplinary training. This exercise is further informed by Sara Ahmed's theorisation of emotions as a deconstructive force, both marginalised and central to intellectual history:

... even if emotions have been subordinated to other faculties, they have still remained at the centre of intellectual history. As a reader of this history, I have been overwhelmed by how much 'emotions' have been a 'sticking point' for philosophers, cultural theorists, psychologists, sociologists, as well as scholars from a range of other disciplines. This is not surprising: what is relegated to the margins is often, as we know from deconstruction, right at the centre of thought itself¹⁰⁰⁸.

This allows me to reflexively contend with the affective dimensions of my embeddedness, such as cultural affinity and sensory engagement with material heritage. These emotions operate within what Ahmed termed "affective economies¹⁰⁰⁹".

As a child I remember my maternal granduncles discussing about the arduous journey from Calcutta to northern Bengal before the construction of the Farakka Barrage over the Ganga in Murshidabad district of West Bengal. The Farakka Barrage was opened in 1972, with construction having started almost a decade earlier. The barrage, alongside the Gajoldoba Barrage in Jalpaiguri district on the Teesta river, lies at the heart of diplomatic tensions over water-sharing issues between

¹⁰⁰⁷ Bal, *A Mieke Bal Reader*, 177.

¹⁰⁰⁸ Sara Ahmed, *The Cultural Politics of Emotion*, reprint, (Edinburgh: Edinburgh University Press, 2014), 4.

¹⁰⁰⁹ Sara Ahmed, "Affective Economies," *Social Text* 79 22, no. 2 (2004): 117-139.

India and Bangladesh. My recollection of the Farakka Barrage, informed by childhood train journeys, is marked by the visceral sensory experience of traversing this vast infrastructural threshold. At midnight, the resonant clatter of the train crossing the bridge, a protracted auditory event spanning several minutes, coincided with fleeting glimpses through the carriage window of the Ganga's expansive flow, illuminated momentarily by water surging through the barrage gates. The stark contrast between the barrage's immediate environs, animated by human activity and artificial illumination, and the enveloping darkness into which the train plunged as it progressed, evoked for me a phenomenological shift from *presence* to *absence*.

The Farakka barrage, as a material and symbolic conduit, emerged in my lived experience as an interstice bridging the metropolitan centre of Kolkata, where I frequently travelled to as a high school student to acquire scholarly and leisurely texts, and the 'peripheral', frontier region, the tea-garden town of Jalpaiguri, my hometown. As an individual shaped by an English-medium education and access to cosmopolitan cultural resources and social mobility, yet spatially situated in a marginalised region, I realised that I occupy a dual positionality that complicates the binary of 'centre' and 'periphery', which I conceptualise as a site of hybridity, where the toponym of Kolkata did not manifest as an antagonistic counterpoint to the hinterland but as a dialogic space of negotiation. This overlaps with the experiences of peers from northern Bengal's urban centres, such as Siliguri and Jalpaiguri, who, like myself, migrated to Delhi for advanced study: inhabiting an ontologically precarious yet fertile space, which enables the oscillation between insider and outsider positionalities. This liminality perhaps affords us the agency to maintain a reflexive distance from metropolitan hegemonies while simultaneously engaging with, and reshaping their epistemic and cultural frameworks, thereby attempting to enact a kind of transformative intervention from the periphery.

Historically, the Farakka Barrage's primary infrastructural role has been to facilitate connectivity between the metropolitan hub of Kolkata and the 'peripheral' region of northern Bengal, addressing the absence of a bridge spanning the Ganga in eastern India following the 1947 Partition. The bridge, or rather its *absence*, which significantly redefined and reconfigured regional mobilities,

is reminiscent in my granduncle's accounts of arduous train journeys to Rajmahal, the hypothesised medieval locus of the Pāla black stone¹⁰¹⁰, and the contemporary geopolitical boundary between West Bengal and Bihar: where passengers transferred to ferries to reach Manihari Ghat, resuming train travel via Katihar to Kishanganj. A parallel historical precedent is evident in the pre-1915 era, before the Hardinge Bridge's construction over the Padma river, which served as a vital artery linking the northern and southern territories of the Bengal Presidency till the mid-twentieth century, when it was disrupted by Partition. Prior to its establishment, passengers on the Darjeeling Mail, the principal rail service connecting Calcutta with northern Bengal and Darjeeling, disembarked at Damukdiya, crossed the Padma by ferry, and rebounded at Saraghat to continue to Siliguri. The Hardinge Bridge's partial destruction during the 1971 Bangladesh Liberation War also highlighted the precocity of such infrastructure, in the face of geopolitical uncertainty. The Darjeeling mail, traversing my hometown of Jalpaiguri, has symbolically come to embody the enduring geo-cultural implications of the Partition, evidenced by its multiple historic reroutings. Recent efforts to reinstate connectivity through the historic Darjeeling Mail route via Bangladesh, marked by the introduction of the Mitali Express, on which I once intended to travel to Bangladesh for field work, were disrupted¹⁰¹¹ by recent political shifts in Bangladesh. These infrastructural and historical subjectivities and shifts perhaps reveal how emotions: nostalgia, disruption, and aspiration circulate through 'lifeless' material networks.

Coming back to Bangarh, although it was around seven years ago, but I still vividly remember the night I reached Gangarampur, an administrative subdivision of South Dinajpur district where the Bangarh archaeological site is located. After a few hours of coach travel from Siliguri, I reached Gangarampur in the middle of the night. I spent the night outside the archaeological site, as there was no place to put up nearby. Next morning, I checked into a Jain¹⁰¹² *dharamśālā*. The region

¹⁰¹⁰ Frederick M. Asher, "Stone and the Production of Images," *East and West* 48, no. 3/4 (1998): 313–28.

¹⁰¹¹ "Mitali Express returns to India after five months," *Dhaka Tribune*, Dec. 11, 2024.

¹⁰¹² The Jain community who migrated here from far off regions of northern and western India, mainly known for their reputation as traders, have contributed immensely to the infrastructure of the region, with establishing schools for girls, hospitals, *dharamśālās* etc. Following the 1947 Partition, which reconfigured northern Bengal

of undivided Dinajpur had several major settlement centres during the Pāla-period: taking into consideration the sheer number of sculptures and architectural fragments discovered from this region and scattered even now over a large number of villages. My first encounter with medieval ruins and landscape of this region, was actually even before I started studying the artefacts. During my stay in Gangarampur, one evening I had the opportunity to visit the large tanks, Kal Dighi and Dhal Dighi in vicinity, known by these names for their distinct dark and light colours respectively. While both have significantly reduced from their original dimensions, the Kal Dighi is better preserved as it was bought by the South Dinajpur Zilla Parishad for renovation. A short walk from the city centre of Gangarampur, and situated along the Hili-Balurghat highway (National Highway 512 connecting Gajole to Hili, an important land port on the international Indo-Bangladesh border) are these two huge man-made waterbodies, possibly from the medieval period, believed to be ancient paleo-channels of the Punarbhaba river¹⁰¹³, the river on whose southern bank the site of Bangarh is located. Similarly in nearby Tapan, there is the huge Tarpan Dighi: a corruption of whose name has lent the settlement its name. In 1998, Dilip K. Chakrabarti noted:

No reference to the archaeology of this region can be complete without mentioning the Pāla period tanks and associated religious buildings. I have else-where cited Francis Buchanan's evocative description of Tarpan Dighi which still measures more than 100 acres in extent ... In Buchanan's measurement it was 4700 ft north-south and 1700 ft east-west including 300 ft wide banks¹⁰¹⁴.

The river Punarbhaba which flows north of the Bangarh mound might have had various old channels, and it may be presumed that the present channel between Bangarh and the nearby site

as frontier zone severed from the road and rail networks linking to eastern Bengal, many Jian families undertook further migrations, dispersing from the region. The Jain merchants, alongside their Marwari counterparts could once be seen in every district of undivided northern Bengal: playing an important role in trade and infrastructure development, marking a convergence of mobility, mercantilism, and community-building in a region marked by geopolitical rupture.

¹⁰¹³ Gautam Kumar Das. "River Systems of West Bengal -A Review," in *Indian Science Cruise*, 37, no. 2 (2023): 11–34.

¹⁰¹⁴ Dilip K. Chakrabarti, *The Issues in East Indian Archaeology*, (Delhi: Munshiram Manoharlal, 1998), 75.

of Ushagarh hasn't changed for quite some time: as local testimony goes, and which K.G. Goswami also noted in his excavation reports of Bangarh¹⁰¹⁵.

As one of the principal centres of Puṇḍravardhana or Varendra, Bangarh has several mentions in ancient literature. The Mahasthan inscriptions in Brahmī script of the third century BCE record that Bangarh was part of the Mauryan empire. Other documents like *Vayupurāṇa* and *Bṛhat Samhita* mention that Kotivarsha or Bangarh was once the seat of the provincial governors of the Gupta kings. Numerous historical sites with evidences of human settlement and habitation had been reported from this region. Archaeological activities during the last sixty-five, seventy odd years diversified our knowledge of this region in manifold ways. The discovery of the Jagajivanpur plate alone added nine more inscriptions, earlier thought to have belonged to the Pratihāra ruler Mahendrapāla (885-908 CE.), to the existing Pāla repertoire of epigraphy. Besides this very important finding, in the last forty-fifty odd years, several copper plates came to light. We may refer here to the Bangarh inscription of Nayapāla, *Prasasti* of Pāhila, two Rajibpur copper plates, and two copper-plates of Gopāla II. The eleventh century *Rāmacaritam* by Sandhyākaranandī affirms that Bangarh or Sonitpur was rich and glorious during the reign of the Pālas¹⁰¹⁶. Bangarh is also known to have been an important centre of Śaivism in eastern India, and a study of the history of the Bangarh, especially sculptural and epigraphical records, sheds light on the Pāla associations with Śaivism¹⁰¹⁷. Noting on connections between Bangarh and Mahasthangarh, Chakrabarti observed:

¹⁰¹⁵ Kunja Gobinda Goswami, *Excavations at Bangarh (1938-41)* (Calcutta: University of Calcutta, 1948).

¹⁰¹⁶ Ranjusri Ghosh, "Pundravardhana/ Varendra: a socio - economic and cultural profile of a sub - region in early Bengal (cir. BC 300 to mid -12th century)" (PhD thesis, Jawaharlal Nehru University, 2003); Ranjusri Ghosh, *Early North Bengal: From Puṇḍravardhana to Varendra, c.400 BCE-1150 CE* (Delhi: Primus Books, 2023).

¹⁰¹⁷ Ranjusri Ghosh, "A few fierce images of Śiva and four image inscriptions from northern Bengal," in *South Asian Religions and Visual Forms in their Archaeological Context*, ed. Vincent Lefèvre, Aurore Didier and Benjamin Mutin (Turnhout: Brepols, 2016), 493-516; Ranjusri Ghosh, "Śaiva cult and some images at Bāṅgaḍ: Dakṣiṇ Dinājpur," in *Journal of the Asiatic Society*, XLVIII, no. 4 (2007): 44-64; Ranjusri Ghosh, "Image of a Śaiva teacher and an inscription on pedestal: New evidence for Bangarh Śaivism," in *Pratna Samiksha*, Vol. 1 (2010): 135-139; Gouriswar Bhattacharya, "Inscribed Image of a śaivacārya from Bengal," in *South Asian Archaeology: Proceedings of the Twelfth International Conference of the European Association of South Asian Archaeologists Held in Helsinki University 5-9 July 1993, Vol. 1*, ed. Akso Parpola and Petteri Koskikallio (Helsinki: Suomalainen Tiedeakatemia, 1994), 93-99; Gouriswar Bhattacharya, "A new śaivacārya with disciple," *Kalyan Bharati: Journal of Indian history and culture VI* (2002): 5-14.

The old route from Kandaran to Bangarh perhaps laid through Bansihari, and from Bangarh to Mahasthangarh the road passed through Panchbibi on the Bangladesh side. Kandaran was linked to the route following the northern bank of the Ganga in Bihar ... Bangarh must also have had links with the Bhagirathi delta¹⁰¹⁸.

Excavation in Bangarh started in 1938, conducted by the Ashutosh Museum of the Calcutta University, it continued until 1941, and halted during the Second World War just before the Partition. The Partition also significantly hampered our understanding of this region, and shaped¹⁰¹⁹ historiographical studies of the region, as institutional activities like archaeological excavations halted indefinitely, and cultural and geographical access became severely limited. Here, all over the modern village, there is a clear deposit of ashy, blackish-grey soil, but only two mounds stand out: the one at the southern extremity of the village, and the one at some distance to the north of the village. The well spread out circular shape of the of the northern mound stands probably for a *stūpa* site outside the northern limits of the ordinary residential settlement, whereas the southern mound, because of its narrow-based tower-like shape may be that of a temple compound.

The Bangarh archaeological site is also a rich ethnographic palimpsest, shaped by historical migrations and colonial labour regimes. Positioned along the main highway, Gangarampur serves as the primary urban node, its demographic composition reflecting a confluence of Bengali refugee descendants from post-Partition eastern Bengal, and Adivasi communities, the latter forcibly relocated by British colonial authorities from central India to labour in the tea estates northern Bengal, many of which were situated in undivided Dinajpur. Adjacent to the Bangarh site, lies an Adivasi village, often subsumed within the broader archaeological landscape, where mud-walled dwellings could be located adorned with intricate clay-based wall paintings. This aesthetic richness offers a

¹⁰¹⁸ Dilip K. Chakrabarti, *Archaeological Geography of the Ganga Plain: The Lower and the Middle Ganga* (Delhi: Permanent Black, 2001), n.p.

¹⁰¹⁹ Sarker, "Hermeneutics of Subcontinental Art Historiography," 13-14, 31-48, 58-59, 83, 151-152, 172.

stark contrast against pervasive structural marginalisation, marked by poverty, unemployment, and overtly deficient access to basic resources.

My fieldwork here, conducted on Christmas Day, coincided with the village's predominantly Catholic Christian community engaging in syncretic religious practices, blending Adivasi cosmological frameworks with Catholic ritualism, enacting a specific localised vernacularisation. The village itself is interspersed with archaeological vestiges, most notably four pillars and the plinth of a Gupta-period Viṣṇu temple, which local narratives, often detached from the historical exegesis provided by an informational plaque, ascribe apotropaic significance, believing that passing through the pillar's surface with one's body confers good fortune. These ritualised interactions with the pillars suggest a collective re-appropriation of archaeological materiality, transforming state-sanctioned heritage into a site of vernacular meaning-making. Conversations with residents further disclosed instances of livestock falling into trenches excavated by the ASI, prompting the cessation of digging, and infilling of deeper excavations. From the anthropological framework of "dwelling¹⁰²⁰", Bangarh can be posited as a lived landscape, continuous shaped by historical memory, colonial legacies, and contemporary socio-economic precarity:

A place owes its character to the experiences it affords to those who spend time there – to the sights, sounds and indeed smells that constitute its specific ambience. And these, in turn, depend on the kinds of activities in which its inhabitants engage. It is from this relational context of people's engagement with the world, in the business of dwelling, that each place draws its unique significance. Thus whereas with space, meanings are *attached* to the world, with the landscape they are *gathered from* it¹⁰²¹.

After visiting Bangarh, Kushmandi and Tapan, I headed to Balurghat, which is the divisional headquarters of the South Dinajpur district and had some important institutions like the

¹⁰²⁰ Tim Ingold, "Building, Dwelling, Living: How Animals and People Make Themselves at Home in the World," in *The Perception of the Environment: Essays on livelihood, dwelling and skill* (London and New York: Routledge, 2000), 172-188.

¹⁰²¹ Ingold, "The temporality of the landscape", 192.

South Dinajpur District Museum and the Balurghat College Museum. The South Dinajpur District Museum, housed in a colonial prison, is a treasure-trove of Pāla art, mostly sculptures. There were no significant bureaucratic challenges in accessing the museum, and a visit to the district collector and an approved permission, enabled me to take photographs. At the Balurghat College Museum, which is an academic institution and there was no involvement of bureaucracy, the museum was specifically opened for me, as it otherwise remains locked, and there were no challenges as such. Both these institutions contain a large number of artefacts from across the Dinajpur region: which include Buddhist and Brahmanical objects. Antiquities from both these institutions and the region were discussed extensively in the light of the institutional histories, and the historiography of Pāla art, in my MPhil dissertation¹⁰²². Another significant site almost similar to Bangarh but smaller in proportions is that of Potiram, close to Bairhatta. During my work at the South Dinajpur District Museum, a sculpture, found in waterbody, was brought in freshly to the museum.

Moving south, but north of the Ganga, there are some important sites in Malda district: Gajole, Pichhli Gangarampur, Kandaran and Amati. A number of sculptures from the medieval period were found from Pichhli Gangarampur, now housed in the Malda Museum¹⁰²³, which suggest that the place was of considerable importance historically. There were also some comparatively isolated religious settlements, such as Jagjivanpur and Nazirpur; the archaeological finds from both the sites, alongside those from sites like Gajole, are presently kept at the Malda Museum¹⁰²⁴, and the State Archaeological Museum in Kolkata. The latter was a *stūpa* site with a tank and a village nearby, while Jagjivanpur was on a much larger scale than Nazirpur.

¹⁰²² Archishman Sarker, "Hermeneutics of subcontinental art historiography: The Varendrī region of Bengal" (MPhil thesis, Jawaharlal Nehru University, 2019).

¹⁰²³ Gouriswar Bhattacharya, "Malda Museum of Antiquities," in *Baha VII (2013-2014)*, ed. Debashish Banerji and Biswadeb Chatterjee (Kolkata: Satyabrata Bhattacharya, 2014), 51-55.

¹⁰²⁴ Gerd J.R. Mevissen, "A Group of Strange Sūrya Images from Gajole in the Malda Museum: Some Remarks on the Bare Feet of Sūrya and his Attendants," *Journal of Bengal Art* 13 & 14 (2008-2009): 89-108; Malaysankar Bhattacharya, *Art in Stone: A Catalogue of Sculptures in Malda Museum*, (Malda: Malda Museum, 1982).

Travelling further north brings one to the Siliguri corridor, and the Bengal Duars¹⁰²⁵ region, part of the *Kāmārūpa-interstice*. Historically, this region has acted as one of the important conduits between the larger cultural landscape of Himalayas and Tibet, and the plains of northern and eastern India. The role of this region, in the preservation and proliferation of Buddhist thought, literature and philosophy across the Himalayas is well-attested. However the connections that these sites in the Terai-Duars might have had with the wider Buddhist world, especially Southeast Asia, through riverine ports connecting them to the maritime networks of Bay of Bengal, is under-researched. In an important 2016 study, observing on the geo-cultural coordinates of two major capitals from the Bengal Terai-Duars sub-Himalayan region: Bhitargarh and Nal Rājar Garh. Radhika Seshan noted in 2016:

Both Bhitargarh and Garh Mendabari were hubs or junction points on strategic routes, with their radials spanning many directions: To the Middle Ganga Valley, to the Middle Brahmaputra Valley, to the Trans-Himalayan region, to peninsular India, to Southwestern China and toward Laos/Cambodia (Champa or Cochin China). Because Bhitargarh was situated on the main channel of Karatoya - the Talma - people could access Tibet through the Tista in Sikkim, by way of its riverine port of Dhumgarh¹⁰²⁶. (Seshan 2016)

¹⁰²⁵ The Duars region (from Sanskrit *dvāra* 'gate, door; entry') encompasses the eastern and northeastern Himalayan Terai belt, extending across northern West Bengal and Assam in India, and abutting Bangladesh and Nepal. The name denotes 'the doors 'to and from the eastern Himalayas, including the kingdoms of Sikkim, Bhutan, the Chumbi Valley, and Tibet beyond. In modern history, following the Anglo-Bhutan War (1864–65) and the annexation of much of the area, British colonial authorities delineated it into the 'eastern Duars '(now mainly in Assam) and the 'western Duars '(now mainly in northern Bengal), the latter historically affiliated with the Kāmārūpa, Kāmatā, and subsequent Afghan Hussain Shahi and Koch kingdoms. Geographically, the region is delineated by its eighteen passageways, best understood through contemporary riverine features: the eleven Duars of West Bengal (Dalimkot, Chamurchi, Zumerkot/Maynaguri, Luckee/Lakshmi, Buxa/Baxa, Bhalka/Bhulka, Gommar, Reepoo, Bagh, and Sidli) span the Manas River (west) to the Teesta River (east), while Assam's seven (Boree Goomah, Kalling, Shurkolla, Chappaguri, Banska, Chapkahama, and Bijni) extend from the Manas (east) to the Dhansiri (west). Historically, the Bengal Duars encompassed territory west of the Teesta to the Mechi River, termed the Morang/Morung (Morāṅga) region. The Duars 'landscape is interwoven with rivers that descend from the mountains into the plains, laden with alluvium; these waterways: often turbulent, prone to course shifts, mergers, braiding, and interlockings, include major rivers alongside tributaries, distributaries, channels, subterranean streams, and *jheel* lakes. Such fluvial changes, compounded by the 1947 Partition's Radcliffe Line bisecting Duars districts and relegating them to 'frontier 'zones in India and (implicitly) Bangladesh, has obscured historical geography, confounding interpretations of primary sources more profoundly here than elsewhere in eastern India's archaeological terrain and often curtailing scholarly access. A precise geographical framing is thus essential to apprehending the Duars 'anomalous status among South Asian historians: straddling Bengal and Assam, it remains quite an exceptional frontier eluding systematic taxonomic or quantitative scrutiny.

¹⁰²⁶ Radhika Seshan, *Narratives, Routes and Intersections in Pre-Modern Asia*, (New York: Routledge, 2016).

Seshan's study importantly acknowledged these sites situated the Terai-Duars region of northern Bengal: Dhumgarh, Bhitargarh and Garh Mendabari, as important port-cities cum sites of economic activity whose reach seemed to have crossed the Bay of Bengal into further Southeast Asia into Cambodia and Vietnam, and played a vital role in the transference and adaptation of Mahāyānist Buddhist religion, ritualisms, art and culture in Southeast Asia. As a matter of fact, no other historic port-city is known to us, within the upper reaches of the Bengal deltaic region with proximity to the northeastern region and Kāmrūp. Some other ancient port cities of Bengal like Talmuk in the south, has had a rich and complex history of trade, commerce and cultural proliferation.

There are two main museums in the Bengal Duars: The Akshaya Kumar Maitreya Heritage Museum, at the North Bengal University, and the Coochbehar Palace Museum in Coochbehar. Both these institutions, alongside some regional antiquities, mostly contain Pāla-period artefacts, some female divinities amongst which I had elsewhere discussed¹⁰²⁷. Amongst the excavated sites in the region, the most prominent is Gosanimari in the Dinhata subdivision of Coochbehar district. I have elsewhere discussed the antiquities from Gosanimari, and some artefacts from the medieval Bengal Duars region¹⁰²⁸. The region, however, is not as archaeologically rich as Dinajpur. Remarking on the slight number of artefacts recovered from the Jalpaiguri - Coochbehar region it has been noted:

However, in view of the existence of two trade routes through the terai region to Tibet and also in view of the copper resources of Buxa and Sikkim, the Jalpaiguri-Coochbehar belt must have some significance at least from the 8th century onwards when the textual references to the travels of monks from Bengal to Tibet become explicit¹⁰²⁹.

¹⁰²⁷ Archishman Sarker, "Popular Religion in the Pāla Period: Evidence from Iconographic Study of Four Female Deities from Northern Bengal," *Religions of South Asia* 13, no. 1 (2019): 51-75; Sarker, "Hermeneutics of Subcontinental Art Historiography," 64-137.

¹⁰²⁸ Archishman Sarker, "New Discoveries in Smaller Antiquities and a Unique Portrait Sculpture from Medieval Bengal Duars," *Religions of South Asia* 16, no. 1 (2022): 3-41.

¹⁰²⁹ Dilip K. Chakrabarti, *The Issues in East Indian Archaeology* (Delhi: Munshiram Manoharlal, 1998), 73.

The period from eighth century CE onwards also witnessed the rise of the tradition of making images in bronze (copper-alloy) in Bengal so the region must have had some prominence in this newly emerging art¹⁰³⁰. Chakrabarti further observed, that in most parts of northern Bengal the production sites of copper-alloy materials haven't undergone much change since historical times and the same ores and production sites which have been historically in existence, still produce copper-alloy materials, and often in a manufacturing process that has undergone little change¹⁰³¹.

During the course of my travels in this region, the expansion of the National Highway 27-cum-State Highway 12A, which is one of the two main routes connecting mainland India to the northeast: and thus geo-strategically important for India, (which was, before the construction of the Teesta railway and motor bridges in Jalpaiguri in the 1970s, connected in post-Independence India only through the Coronation bridge at Sevoke further north), has heavily impacted the ecosystem surrounding the major riverine channels of the Teesta: Karatoya and the Talma. These channels were already been reduced even before the highway construction activities began, owing to the several hydroelectric engineering projects and barrages over the river Teesta in the hills, as well as in the plains. The riverine geography has played an important role in the construction of the material history of the region, as the rivers are marked by historical changes of courses, including the well-known 1787 course-change of the Teesta documented by James Rennell¹⁰³². These issues, specifically in the context of the riverine geography of northern Bengal, were again discussed elaborately in my MPhil dissertation¹⁰³³. The banks of the Karatoya which were once lined by small brick-made Śaivite shrines of unknown antiquity, have been completely obliterated, alongside numerous old trees and homes. Similar small structures were also been reported¹⁰³⁴ on the banks of Karatoya on way to Mahasthangarh, on the Bangladesh side. In the present day, there are numerous 'Karatoyas', and these

¹⁰³⁰ Sarker, "Hermeneutics of Subcontinental Art Historiography," 63.

¹⁰³¹ Chakrabarti, 73.

¹⁰³² James Rennell, *Bengal Atlas* (London: East India Company, 1781); Sarker, "Hermeneutics of Subcontinental Art Historiography," 23-24.

¹⁰³³ Sarker, "Hermeneutics of Subcontinental Art Historiography," 8-11.

¹⁰³⁴ Gouriswar Bhattacharya, "A new śaivacārya with disciple," *Kalyan Bharati: Journal of Indian history and culture* VI (2002): 14.

are known by their distinctive names like the ‘Rangpur Karatoya’, ‘Dinajpur Karatoya’, ‘Bogra Karatoya’, ‘Pabna Karatoya’ etc. The Karatoya river has ample mentions in Brahmanical literature, specifically the twelfth-thirteenth century text *Karatoyāmāhātmya*. Being a river of Śaivite significance, it is very much possible that the initiated visits the river valley even today. I cross the Karatoya river quite often on my way to Jalpaiguri from the airport in Bagdogra, and over the years the expansion of the National Highway 27, especially through its integration with the Asian Highway project (Asian Highway 2) has noticeably impacted life and livelihood in the region: the serene beauty of the green fields replaced by dust and pollution offered by a myriad of vehicles mostly delivering goods and services from mainland India to the northeast, or vice versa. A recent study¹⁰³⁵ has collated data on the construction and reconstruction efforts conducted in post-Independence Bangladesh at archaeological and heritage sites along the Teesta, including Dhumgarh.

4.2 Allochronic scripts: Manuscripts, monasteries & microfilms

This section contends that colonial influence on modern historiographical models obscure the intricate processes of cultural association, dissociation, and appropriation that have historically shaped Himalayan manuscript cultures, where manuscripts often play the role of ‘living agents’ in the construction of ‘social time’. Situating these manuscripts within the localised and interconnected contexts of Buddhist communities in Nepal and adjacent Himalayan regions, where manuscripts produced in eastern India during the Pālas, were actively translated, preserved, and disseminated. It is argued that manuscript cultures in contemporary Nepal are not static repositories of historical knowledge, but participants in the production of historical and cultural continuity. By integrating the materiality of textual traditions with their embedded socio-cultural networks, the limitations of allochronic historiographical models in the study of manuscripts and societies in South Asia is

¹⁰³⁵ Swadhin Sen and A. K. M. Khorshed Alam, “Chronicles of perpetually reconfiguring entanglements: A precursory understanding of the landscape archaeology of Teesta Megafan of Bangladesh” in Sen, S., Varma, S. and Sahu, B. P. (eds.), *The Archaeology of Early Medieval and Medieval South Asia: Contesting Narratives from the Eastern Ganga-Brahmaputra Basin*, (London: Routledge, 2022).

discussed, advocating for a nuanced, contextually grounded approach to understanding the interplay between Buddhist textual traditions, the hermeneutics of colonial historiography, and the lived experiences of Buddhist communities. Focusing on the *AsP* manuscripts, the analysis examines their reception, dissemination, and preservation in Nepal.

In Nepal, the mid-eighteenth century witnessed significant political tensions among the Mallas, Tibetans, and Gurkhas, driven by disputes over the adulteration of Tibetan currency produced in Nepal: a measure the Mallas employed to finance their defence against Gurkha aggression¹⁰³⁶. The Tibetans, bolstered by Qing military support, ultimately precipitated the collapse of the Malla kingdoms. Yet, the disruption to the region's religious and social manuscript traditions remained relatively contained. Following the 1775 treaty between the Gurkhas and the Tibetans, and the Gurkha annexation of Darjeeling and the Chumbi valley: undermining Tibet's trade with British India via Calcutta- Kathmandu, Kyiorong, and Kuti emerged as key trade routes¹⁰³⁷. The closure of the Chumbi valley route, central to trade between Tibet and British Bengal, following the Gurkha conquest of Kathmandu, redirected focus to alternative routes. In 1848, Joseph Dalton Hooker attempted to access Tibet via Nepal¹⁰³⁸, but it was Sarat Chandra Das¹⁰³⁹, as recounted in the Introduction, the British Indian agent, who first successfully transported manuscripts from Tibet to British India. Initially planning to travel through Walung, Das altered his route to the neighbouring Yangma valley to avoid scrutiny¹⁰⁴⁰, returning with manuscripts that unveiled an extensive repository of Indian Buddhist texts in Nepal. However, this status persisted until British control over Chumbi valley, resulting from conflicts among the Bhutanese, Gurkhas, and British: restored access through the corridor¹⁰⁴¹. Internationally, the nineteenth century's geopolitical upheavals, particularly the colonial 'Great Game,' profoundly disrupted Nepal's cultural landscape, restricting access to material culture: that

¹⁰³⁶ Martin Saxer, "Moving In, Moving Up, Moving Out", in *Places in Knots: Remoteness and Connectivity in the Himalayas and Beyond* (Ithaca: Cornell University Press, 2022), 38.

¹⁰³⁷ Saxer, 38.

¹⁰³⁸ Saxer, 40.

¹⁰³⁹ Saxer, 41.

¹⁰⁴⁰ Saxer, 41.

¹⁰⁴¹ Saxer, 38.

which has the potential to act as a “... a stimulus for a re-memory of memories which is part of the process of retrieving and reconceptualising memories in a new time and space,¹⁰⁴²” alienating religious practices from historical continuities, and fragmenting socio-historical memory. This era saw a fragmentation of Nepal’s socio-historical memory, as the alienation of religious and social life from its material past, due to prevalent geopolitics, disrupted long established practices of textual transmission, veneration and *continuity*. In 1954, trade through Chumbi valley again came to a halt following Tibet’s annexation by the People's Republic of China, and US restrictions on trade with China. *Ex se intellegitur*, Tibet’s political and cultural annexation by China had far-reaching consequences on the material culture, socio-economy, and social memory of the entire Himalayan region and its adjacent areas.

Fig. 1. Map illustrating trade routes connecting Tibet with northern and eastern India in the nineteenth and early twentieth centuries.

As it has been stated at the beginning of this dissertation, and is a well-known fact that a reconstruction of the Pāla-period, art, history and culture starting from the early twentieth century

¹⁰⁴² Dagmar Freist, “Lost In Time And Space? Glocal Memoryscapes In The Early Modern World”, in *Memory before Modernity: Practices of Memory in Early Modern Europe* (Leiden: Brill, 2013), 217.

relied heavily upon manuscripts produced in Nepal. I primarily visited Nepal in order to view these manuscripts now kept at the Kaiser Library and the National Archives in Kathmandu. In the 1990s, the Nepal-German Manuscript Preservation Project¹⁰⁴³ (henceforth NGMPP), a joint collaboration between the Department of Archaeology, HMG Ministry of Education and Culture and the German Oriental Society, undertook a large-scale effort to microfilm manuscripts from monasteries, public repositories, and private collections across Nepal with the objective to: "... preserve the literary, historical, religious and cultural heritage of Nepal through the microfilming of manuscripts, block prints and historical documents. Any manuscript that has a bearing on this objective can be included for microfilming if its owner do desires. No language or subject area is excluded". A vast majority of these texts were in Sanskrit and had an Indian provenance. It was largely focussed on the collections of the Kaiser Library, named after its founder, Keśar (Kaiser) Śamśer Rāṇā (1892–1964)¹⁰⁴⁴, member of Nepalese royalty and collector of literary materials, while manuscripts from several other regions of Nepal were also brought to Kathmandu. The team also often travelled long distances on horseback to get access to manuscripts in remote locations across Nepal. The Kaiser Library's collections consists of manuscripts procured from throughout Nepal, many of which were imported from northern India in the past, or produced locally. However, after becoming part of the Kaiser Library's collections in the early twentieth century, these manuscripts as 'physical objects' were already cut off from the geographical connections they have been historically part of¹⁰⁴⁵. The Nepal-German Manuscript Preservation Project, while pioneering, had both advantages and limitations. On the one hand, it preserved manuscripts that might have otherwise been lost, established an early archival

¹⁰⁴³ Franz-Karl Ehrhard, "The Nepal German Manuscript Preservation Project," in *European Bulletin of Himalayan Research* 2 (1991): 20; Vincenzo Vergiani, "A Tentative History of the Sanskrit Grammatical Traditions in Nepal through the Manuscript Collections: Material, Textual, and Historical Investigations" in Vergiani, V., Cuneo D. and Formigatti, C.A. (eds.). *Indic Manuscript Cultures through the Ages*. (Berlin and Boston: De Gruyter, 2017), 80.

¹⁰⁴⁴ Dragomir Dimitrov and Kashinath Tamot. "Kaiser Shamsheer, his Library and his Manuscript Collection," in *Newsletter of the NGMCP*, 3 (2007): 26–36.

¹⁰⁴⁵ Olli-Pekka Antero Littunen, "The Social Life of a Manuscript," *Textual Cultures* 17, no. 2, Special Issue: Material Texts: Religion, Mobility, and Responsibility (Fall 2024): 120.

framework, and culminated in the Nepal German Manuscript Cataloguing Project¹⁰⁴⁶ (2002), providing scholars with accessible catalogues, and the catalogues themselves often throw light¹⁰⁴⁷ on networks and processes of assimilation that determined their present spatiality and temporality. On the other hand, the timing of the project coincided with the rise of digital archiving, which, unlike microfilms, enables high-definition, colour reproductions of manuscripts, as seen in collections in the UK and US today, therefore impacting the relevance of the exercise over time. In another turn of events, in 2009, the British Library sponsored a project “Preservation of historic ephemera and manuscripts from Nepal¹⁰⁴⁸”, whose main objective was “... to digitise and preserve approximately 1,450 ephemera from the period 1900-1960 and 215 manuscripts ranging from the early 19th to early 20th century¹⁰⁴⁹”, however presently if one wishes to access these materials, the website states: “Due to the cyber-attack on the British Library in October 2023, the archives and manuscripts database is currently inaccessible ... ”¹⁰⁵⁰. This incident draws attention towards the limitations of a hyper-connected global virtual world, where material culture becomes an embodiment of ‘ephemerality’. Back in Nepal, the reliance on microfilms has created barriers to accessing original manuscripts. However, I could view the manuscripts at the Kaiser Library on black and white microfilm (Plate 70a-b), co-incidentally reminiscent of old East German films, at the National Archives. During my visit to the National Archives in Kathmandu, I was denied access to the physical manuscripts and was instead directed to their corresponding microfilm records: an experience common to several contemporary scholars¹⁰⁵¹. These microfilms themselves start degenerating after twenty-thirty odd years¹⁰⁵², rendering a life-span even shorter than high-quality palm leaf manuscripts, which have survived for centuries. Following Nepal's transition from a monarchy to a democratic nation-state,

¹⁰⁴⁶“ The Nepalese-German Manuscript Cataloguing Project,” Universität Hamburg, accessed July 9, 2025, <https://www.aai.uni-hamburg.de/en/forschung/ngmcp>.

¹⁰⁴⁷ Kenneth G. Zysk, “The Use of Manuscript Catalogues as Sources of Regional Intellectual History in India’s Early Modern Period” in Rath, S. (ed.). *Aspects of Manuscript Culture in South India*. (Leiden: Brill, 2012).

¹⁰⁴⁸“ Endangered Archives Programme: Preservation of historic ephemera and manuscripts from Nepal (EAP272),” British Library, accessed July 9, 2025, <https://eap.bl.uk/project/EAP272>.

¹⁰⁴⁹ *ibid.*

¹⁰⁵⁰ *ibid.*

¹⁰⁵¹ Littunen, 123.

¹⁰⁵² Littunen, 123.

factors such as political instability and socio-economic challenges have significantly influenced the engagement with its manuscript heritage, both at the local and international levels. In March 2024, a digitised version of a certain batch of manuscripts from the cataloguing programme, termed the ‘X-Series’ which was the only batch from all microfilmed manuscripts to be previously not available at the National Archives, and was at the Berlin State Library in microfilmed version: digitised by the Centre for the Study of Manuscript Cultures, University of Hamburg in cooperation with the Berlin State Library and the DFG (German Research Foundation), was handed over to the National Archives¹⁰⁵³. I had the opportunity to visit the Centre for the Study of Manuscript Cultures in Hamburg later in March 2025, when I was able to look at their state-of-the-art laboratories and equipments, and the different advanced technologically-equipped processes for studying historical manuscripts.

At the Kaiser Library, which was housed inside a makeshift shanty adjacent to the main building that was being renovated during my visit, after three days of waiting, I could only view one original manuscript, from a pile wrapped in red cloth and stacked inside a shelf adjacent to a damp wall (Plate 71a-b), with a vast amount of dust accumulated on it. Turning by hand each folio was an arduous task in itself, as they have turned so brittle that every moment, I had to be careful not to incur damage. Even after a three hour long task of browsing through all the folios in order to locate and photograph the illustrated ones, I wasn’t able to locate those illuminated folios in this manuscript. While viewing these manuscripts at the National Archives and the Kaiser Library came with no cost, in order to obtain images, I was charged an under-the-table-charge per image at both institutions: a complicated issue in the absence of an official policy on the disbursal of images in the public domain. At the Kaiser Library, when I asked the Chief Librarian about methods for preserving these manuscripts inside the library, I was informed there was no such active preservation exercise, and he was curious to know more about the preservation techniques opted elsewhere in the world. Even at Nepal’s grandly housed National Museum in Chhauni, without proper climate control, and with

¹⁰⁵³“ Nepal Project Hands Over Digitised Documents to the National Archives,” Universität Hamburg, accessed July 9, 2025, <https://www.csmc.uni-hamburg.de/news/2024-03-19-x-series.html>.

anodyne labelling, the prospect of preserving and displaying these manuscripts according to international standards, seems very far for now. Plate 72 is an image of a 13th-14th CE Tibetan *AsP* manuscript at the National Museum, Chhauni, Kathmandu; Plate 73 is an example of a Newari *AsP* manuscript, from around the same time period, or even earlier (it hasn't been dated by the museum), also at the National Museum in Chhauni, whose label informs that it was recently returned/ 'repatriated' from the United Kingdom. While the issue of repatriation is a widely discussed and politically charged topic domestically within Nepal, the broader implications of these exercises are rarely discussed.

During my fieldwork in Nepal in June 2023, in Patan (also known as Lalitpur), it was at the Kvābāhāḥ, or the Hiraṇyavarṇa Mahāvihāra that I witnessed the ritual recitation and worship of an *AsP* manuscript, which offered profound insights into the cultic significance and enduring popularity of manuscript veneration in Nepal's Vajrayāna Buddhist tradition. Far from being a monolithic practice, these rituals demonstrate the relationship between textual materiality, religious devotion, and social memory. The Hiraṇyavarṇa Mahāvihāra, which dates back to approximately the twelfth century CE, serves as a site of remarkable *continuity*, where the *AsP* is ritually preserved, worshipped, and recited. The manuscript remains central to the monastery's ritual life, with recitations performed upon request by lay Buddhist devotees, a practice that illustrates the active participation of manuscripts in the religious and social lives of communities. Plate 96 illustrates the monastery's courtyard, dominated by an intricately adorned *svayambhū caitya*. Plate 97 depicts the main Śākyamuni temple on the ground floor, where the *AsP* is ritually enshrined. This spatial positioning highlights the manuscript's elevated status within the monastery's religious hierarchy. The Avalokiteśvara temple is on the first floor (Plate 98). Plate 99 depicts the interior of the Prajñāpāramitā temple on the ground floor, where the *AsP* recitation ceremony is performed. The recitation ceremony itself, as shown in Plate 100, involves a performative engagement with the text, while Plate 101 captures a moment of individual devotion in front of the Śākyamuni shrine, illustrating the monastery's primary role in mediating the spiritual aspirations of the lay community.

Although I was unable to witness the *jīrṇoddhāra* process during my visit, as it occurs only during specific Tibetan calendrical months, my conversations with a Vajrayāna priest involving several aspects of these rituals provided insights into the symbolic and material dimensions of restoration practices. The *jīrṇoddhāra* of the *AsP* exemplifies the intersection of social memory, material preservation, and ritual renewal, ensuring the manuscript's continued vitality as both a physical object, and a locus of religious meaning. These practices essentially help us imagine an *AsP* manuscript as a living entity, embedded within the ritual and social fabric of Vajrayāna Buddhism. The colonial period profoundly transformed the material culture surrounding Nepalese manuscripts, reshaping practices of circulation, preservation, and veneration: a legacy that continues to influence contemporary rituals.

Although the temporality of the ritual veneration itself is *sub specie aeternitatis* from a Vajrayāna frame of praxis, the ritual veneration of the *AsP* at the Hiraṇyavarṇa Mahāvihāra also offers different understandings of the intersections of manuscript materiality, ritual performance¹⁰⁵⁴, and socio-religious life. Kathmandu, with its renowned Boudha *stūpa* and a network of smaller *stūpas* and monasteries, has long served as a pivotal site for Buddhist pilgrimage within the greater Tibetan cultural sphere, encompassing regions such as Ladakh, Arunachal Pradesh, Sikkim, and Bhutan. The historical presence of pilgrims from these areas has been integral to shaping Kathmandu's identity as a Buddhist pilgrimage centre. Ritual practices exemplify the intersection of religious performance, material culture, and economic networks. The materials employed in these ceremonies, their sourcing, and their circulation are deeply embedded within broader trade systems and the collective memory of Himalayan Buddhist communities. These practices highlight the active role of manuscripts in mediating religious, cultural, and economic transformations, offering a lens through which to interrogate the temporal and spatial negotiations of Nepal's Buddhist manuscript traditions. In this context, the permeability of the Himalayan Buddhist landscape, which encompasses diverse

¹⁰⁵⁴ Richard Widdess, "Text, Orality, and Performance in Newar Devotional Music", in *Tellings and Texts: Music, Literature and Performance in North India*, edited by Francesca Orsini and Katherine Butler Schofield (Cambridge: Open Book Publishers, 2015), 231.

elements: natural, social, material, and emotional, while remaining holistic, “mutable”, and simultaneously “... in the process of being and becoming...”¹⁰⁵⁵ emerges as contingent upon shifting socio-political conditions, suggesting the intricate entanglements between material culture and the sophistications of power, memory, and religious practices. Furthermore, the *AsP* exemplifies the potential of manuscripts to function not merely as repositories of textual knowledge, but as active agents in the mediation of memory, identity, and historical consciousness¹⁰⁵⁶.

During a conversation with a priest at the monastery, I learnt that some materials central to the ritual conservation of the *AsP* manuscript at the Golden Temple have historically depended on access to specific trade routes and regions across the Himalayas and Tibet. For instance, the polishing stones once sourced from Tibet were replaced by stones from Rajasthan following the closure of Tibetan trade routes. Similarly, the arrival of cello-tape in Nepal introduced its use in manuscript repairs. These shifts suggest the nuanced relationship between material culture, trade networks, and the historical contingencies shaping manuscript traditions. To address such intricacies, the “network approach¹⁰⁵⁷”, largely developed as a historiographic and socio-anthropological framework in the twenty-first century in the Netherlands and Germany to study Central Asian and Trans-Himalayan Buddhist networks of knowledge and material culture, might perhaps offer a non-linear but non-fragmented and ‘lived’ perspective of temporality. It scrutinises both at the “... macro-level of interregional and intercultural exchanges as well as the micro-level of local interactions and contacts”: taking into account the lived experiences of Buddhist communities, through the perspective of “relational religion”, a concept developed at the Center for Religious Studies (CERES) at Ruhr University Bochum, and is defined as:

¹⁰⁵⁵ Christopher Tilley and Kate Cameron-Daum, “The anthropology of landscape: materiality, embodiment, contestation and emotion”, in *Anthropology of Landscape: The Extraordinary in the Ordinary* (London: UCL Press, 2017), 20.

¹⁰⁵⁶ See: Christoph Emmrich, “Emending Perfection: Prescript, Postscript, and Practice in Newar Buddhist Manuscript Culture,” in *Buddhist Manuscript Cultures: Knowledge, Ritual, and Art*, ed. Stephen C. Berkwitz, Juliane Schober, and Claudia Brown (London and New York: Routledge, 2009), 140-155.

¹⁰⁵⁷ Carmen Meinert, “Introduction—Dynamics of Buddhist Transfer in Central Asia”, in *Transfer of Buddhism Across Central Asian Networks (7th to 13th Centuries)* (Leiden, The Netherlands: Brill, 2015), 7.

... the theoretical framework for a perception according to which the characteristics of single components within the religious field are defined not only by the point of view of the observer, but also in relation to other religious constituents as well as to other past and present social and cultural facts¹⁰⁵⁸.

Walking through the streets of Patan, leading from the Golden Temple to the Patan Durbar square is an experience in itself. These streets are lined with shops selling modern as well as antique objects, with the line between the two heavily blurred. The subject of the involvement of Patan-based Nepalese art dealers in global illegal antiquities trade has been a subject of much discussion in popular press, as well as in academia, since at least the 1940s, and is a topic outside the scope of this dissertation. At the newly renovated Patan Museum at the Durbar square with its immense number of antiquities, which are comparatively better displayed than their counterparts at the National Museum at Chhauni or at the Kathmandu Durbar Square, in its museum store, tucked among contemporary pieces, I could see a small oct-alloy *yakṣiṇī* piece, which I suspected to be an antiquity, based on the nature of the mould, the appearance of the metal, and some other stylistic considerations. However, like any other object at the museum shop, this too was for sale, albeit at quite an exorbitant price. Another important collection, which is again an important monastery with a huge collection of manuscripts, is the Macchindranāth *stūpa* in the heart of Kathmandu. During my visit, it was undergoing renovation under the Indian non-profit heritage preservation organisation: Indian National Trust for Art and Cultural Heritage (INTACH). Alongside those in monasteries such as the Macchindranāth *stūpa* and the Hiraṇyavarṇa Mahāvihāra, the manuscripts in different private collections across the Kathmandu valley also remain inaccessible to scholars in their original form, with their microfilm versions however, often available at the National Archives.

4.3 Ladakh's Buddhist heritage and 'ecological locality'

¹⁰⁵⁸ <http://khk.ceres.rub.de/en/research/>, last accessed February 10th, 2025

Ladakh is included in this chapter not as a site directly relevant to the illuminated manuscripts from eastern India that form this dissertation's primary object, but as a comparative case whose differences from the Bihar-Bengal-Nepal axis are as significant as its similarities. While the eastern Indian sites examined above suffer from infrastructural neglect rooted in postcolonial bureaucratic dysfunction and economic precarity, Ladakh's Buddhist heritage confronts a qualitatively different set of pressures: active military infrastructure in a frontier zone, fragile high-altitude ecology, and the particular limitations of emic knowledge in a community whose relationship to its own Buddhist heritage has been mediated by centuries of geographical isolation and recent political transformation. Reading these two together: the neglected heartland and the militarised frontier, reveals that the allochronic denial of coevalness to Buddhist heritage in South Asia is not a single uniform phenomenon but takes regionally specific forms shaped by distinct postcolonial histories. This perspective is primarily used here to reinforce the argument that any adequate narrative of Buddhist cultural heritage in the region must take into account the layered and asynchronous temporalities that different sites inhabit simultaneously.

The Little Ice Age (ca. 1300-1850 CE), a protracted epoch of climactic cooling marked by heterogeneous regional expressions, perhaps offers a heuristic for understanding the relationship between 'ecological locality' and cultural heritage within the Anthropocene, and its precarity, particularly in the waterscape of Ladakh's Upper Indus Basin. In pre-Enlightenment Europe, alpine glaciers were imbued with menacing attributes, as high altitude landscapes often evoked anxieties of backwardness and *alterity*:

In pre-Enlightenment Europe, most glacier narratives emphasized menacing characteristics. This was an era when, to most Europeans, high elevation provoked anxiety because, as one went up, the people, the settlements, and the landscape became more backward. Mountains-and alpine glaciers in particular-inspired fear of the cold, snow, and wild inhabitant¹⁰⁵⁹.

¹⁰⁵⁹ Mark Carey, "The History of Ice: How Glaciers Became an Endangered Species," in *Environmental History* 12, no. 3, (2007): 502.

Contemporary scholarship has however proven¹⁰⁶⁰ that the Little Ice Age's identification transcends glacial metrics alone. In 1933, Giotto Dainelli, a Florentine traveller and palaeontologist, and a known supporter of Italian Fascism, noted in his book based on his travels to the Siachen glacier of Ladakh:

My Base Camp is on a small flat space on the slope which descends to the lake, between the two glaciers, in the midst of a world of ice which, in immensity, has no equal on earth, except possibly in the ice-caps round the Poles¹⁰⁶¹.

This description of Ladakh as an unparalleled “world of ice” offers a snapshot in history of a high altitude cryospheric landscape. The Siachen glacier, also known as the world's largest non-polar glacier, is an important component of the Himalayan cryosphere, which serves as the water tower for major river systems like the Indus. During the Little Ice Age, in the Karakoram, evidence suggests that glaciers like Siachen experienced significant advances during this period, with moraine deposits etc¹⁰⁶². Danielli's 1933 observation likely captured Siachen at a time when it was still influenced by the Little Ice Age's legacy, with relatively stable or slowly retreating ice masses. Recent studies have indicated that Himalayan glaciers have lost significant mass since the mid-twentieth century due to rising temperatures, with Siachen itself showing signs of retreat and thinning. Glaciers have thus been positioned as “sentinels of climate change¹⁰⁶³”.

In the light of Appadurai's construct of locality as a relational practice of place-making amidst “... conditions of anxiety and entropy, social wear and flux, ecological uncertainty and cosmic volatility¹⁰⁶⁴”, this section positions Ladakh's medieval murals as material nodes that articulate and

¹⁰⁶⁰ Sam White, “The Real Little Ice Age,” in *The Journal of Interdisciplinary History* 44, no. 3, (2014): 343.

¹⁰⁶¹ Giotto Dainelli, *Buddhists and glaciers of Western Tibet* (London: Kegan Paul, Trench, Turner & Co. Ltd., 1933), 156.

¹⁰⁶² Bolch, Tobias, et al. “The State and Fate of Himalayan Glaciers.” *Science* 336, no. 6079 (2012): 310–314; Kääb, Andreas, et al. “Contrasting Patterns of Early Twenty-First-Century Glacier Mass Change in the Himalayas.” *Nature* 488, no. 7412 (2012): 495–498.

¹⁰⁶³ Carvalho Resende and Stepanov Tales et al, *World Heritage glaciers : Sentinels of climate change* (Gland: International Union for Conservation of Nature and Natural Resources, 2022); Steven Mithen, *After the Ice: A Global Human History, 20,000–5000 BC* (Cambridge, MA: Harvard University Press, 2006).

¹⁰⁶⁴ Arjun Appadurai, “The Production of Locality” in Appadurai, A. *Modernity at Large: Cultural Dimensions of Globalization*. (Minneapolis: University of Minnesota Press, 1996), 181.

diagnose the region's 'ecological locality'. In doing this, I also use the frame of problematisation¹⁰⁶⁵ of the notion that endogenous communities' have inherent capacity and "timeless knowledge" for environmental conservation in the light of climate change. Another study examined how Ladakhi Buddhist communities integrate cosmological beliefs, like rituals invoking water spirit or *lu*, with modern development interventions, such as flood prevention schemes, in the context of environmental flux¹⁰⁶⁶. These rituals which often include the elements like fire and water, are also a means of social cohesion and connection, as demonstrated in a study in the context of the Ladakhi village of Achinathang, where:

Ideally, to be considered a fellow villager (*yul-pa*), a person must be able to undertake the exchange of fire (symbolic of hospitality around the hearth) and water (symbolic of labor reciprocity outside the house), participate in ritual celebrations, and claim a shared history¹⁰⁶⁷.

The indigenous community's changing historical environmental interactions with heritage has also been studied in an art historical context focussing on the murals and *stūpas* at the Alchi monastery¹⁰⁶⁸.

Ladakh's cultural imagery has also been profoundly shaped in the twentieth century by its discursive construction as a 'Shangri-La,' rooted in an Eurocentric fascination with Tibetan Buddhism and romanticised notions of ecological harmony¹⁰⁶⁹ perpetuated till as late as the 1980s and 1990s. Ladakh's idealised vision has also been juxtaposed with the proliferation of military infrastructure in the region's landscape, which suggest both the geopolitical strategic location of the region, and the ecological disruption caused by it¹⁰⁷⁰.

¹⁰⁶⁵ Karine Gagné, "Cultivating Ice over Time: On the Idea of Timeless Knowledge and Places in the Himalayas," in *Anthropologica* 58, no. 2, (2016): 194.

¹⁰⁶⁶ Andrea Butcher, "Keeping the Faith: Divine Protection and Flood Prevention in Modern Buddhist Ladakh," *Worldviews: Global Religions, Culture, and Ecology* 17, no. 2 (2013): 103–14.

¹⁰⁶⁷ Ravina Aggarwal, "At the Margins of Death: Ritual Space and the Politics of Location in an Indo-Himalayan Border Village." *American Ethnologist* 28, no. 3 (2001): 552.

¹⁰⁶⁸ Monisha Ahmed, "Materiality and Memory: The Stūpas and Murals of Alchi," in *Art and Architecture in Ladakh: Cross-cultural Transmissions in the Himalayas and Karakoram*, ed. Erberto Lo Bue and John Bray (Leiden: Brill, 2014), 185–204.

¹⁰⁶⁹ H. Norberg-Hodge, *Ancient futures: Learning from Ladakh* (Delhi: Oxford University Press, 1992).

¹⁰⁷⁰ Gagné, 197.

Geographically and culturally congruous with the Tibetan plateau, Ladakh and the region of Lahaul and Spiti in Himachal Pradesh are often seen as cultural extensions of Tibet, so much so, that it has been variously known in modern history as western Tibet, ‘little Tibet’ or ‘Indian Tibet’; as the 14th Dalai Lama suggested:

Ladakhi Buddhists, like Tibetans, follow the Nalanda tradition, studying masters such as Nagarjuna, Dignaga and Dharmakirti, who explained Buddhist philosophy through reasoning¹⁰⁷¹.

However this categorisation which has been critiqued in the light of recent archaeological data which has proved that the region “... includes a much richer set of material, cultural and religious influences¹⁰⁷²”. Situated in a geographically secluded location which has been at the crossroads of empires and important trade routes¹⁰⁷³ since the ancient period:

Ladakh occupies a special place in the study of the wider Himalayan region because of its geographical location bordering on Western Tibet, Xinjiang, and the Gilgit-Baltistan region of what is now Pakistan, as well as Kashmir and the Indian state of Himachal Pradesh. Lying on one of the main historic trading routes from South Asia across the Karakoram to Central Asia, the region has long been a meeting place of different cultures, languages and religions: not only Tibetan Buddhism but also Shia and Sunni Islam and— since the mid-19th century—Christianity¹⁰⁷⁴.

It was not just important trade routes, but also capillary routes that crisscrossed the region, often following the course of a river, which existed alongside the main arterial roads, connecting it to

¹⁰⁷¹“ Pilgrimage to Leh Jokhang,” *His Holiness The 14th Dalai Lama of Tibet*, July 5, 2017, <https://www.dalailama.com/news/2017/pilgrimage-to-leh-jokhang>.

¹⁰⁷² Quentin Devers, “Archaeological Ladakh: Recent Discoveries Redefining the History of a Key Region between the Pamirs and the Himalayas,” *Central Asiatic Journal* 61, no. 1 (2018): 103.

¹⁰⁷³ Sonam Joldan, “Relationship between Ladakh and Buddhist Tibet: Pilgrimage and trade,” *The Tibet Journal* 31, no. 3 (2016): 43–76.

¹⁰⁷⁴ John Bray, Petra Maurer and Andrea Butcher, “Introduction,” *The Tibet Journal* 40, no. 2 (2015): 3.

important centres in South and Central Asia¹⁰⁷⁵. Petroglyph sites, like the one in Alchi, attest to this fact. Plate 74a-b shows images of a site along the Indus filled with petroglyphs from different periods, on way to Alchi.

The relationship between Ladakh and Tibet, and the evolution of Ladakh's cultural identity in the medieval period is complex and multilayered, and spans several centuries of cultural and religious exchanges:

The cultural Tibetanization of Ladakh grew to full maturity later, during the establishment of the first dynasty by descendants of Glang-dar-ma ... Rinchen bzang-po (958-1055), a great translator and builder of temples, worked for the so-called 'second propagation of the Buddhist law' under the royal dynasty established in Western Tibet ... This process of propagation of Buddhist culture was in a sense a continuation of the first phase of Tibetan Buddhism ... It included, as well, Indian Buddhist traditions mediated from India and Central Asia in which many external influences converged through the caravan routes from Persia and Byzantium eastward and from China westward. This confluence of traditions can be remarked in the subsequent Ladakhi Buddhist art¹⁰⁷⁶.

However, Tibet has historically been the main cultural influence on Ladakh¹⁰⁷⁷. The trade routes between western Tibet and Ladakh have also historically faced disruptions, which culminated into different landscape and waterscape implications:

At some point during the thirteenth century, the influence of Western Tibet seems to have completely collapsed. Examples of this decay are the numerous raids carried out in Ladakh by armies coming from Kashmir and from Central Asia ... In this climate of insecurity, new rulers unrelated to Western Tibet were able to rise and to create ephemeral kingdoms within the territories previously controlled by Ngari. Since the protohistoric period,

¹⁰⁷⁵ Jason Neelis, "Capillary Routes of the Upper Indus," in *Early Buddhist Transmission and Trade Networks: Mobility and Exchange within and beyond the Northwestern Borderlands of South Asia* (Leiden: Brill, 2010), 257-287.

¹⁰⁷⁶ Giacomella Orofino, "A Note on Some Tibetan Petroglyphs of the Ladakh Area," *East and West* 40, no. 1/4 (1990): 177.

¹⁰⁷⁷ Tsering Jolden and Rinchen Tundup, "Cultural Relationship between the People of Ladakh and Tibet," *The Tibet Journal* 43, no. 2 (2018): 69.

fortifications underwent great development, providing systematic access to water, multiple levels of ramparts, outpost defence towers, etc¹⁰⁷⁸.

Alongside being an important trade and cultural conduit, Ladakh, like Nepal, has historically acted as an important repository of material culture, further facilitated by its dry arid climate, low temperature, combined with very low precipitation which significantly supports material preservation without human intervention. The monasteries in Ladakh, like their counterparts in Nepal, Himachal Pradesh across the Himalayan Buddhist belt, occupy a unique position in the study of Buddhist heritage and history because they are still active places of worship, alongside being repositories.

In around 1873, already facing friction in Nepal from the Gurkhas, Ladakh became one of the main trade routes between India and Tibet, which the British colonial administrators preferred to the routes in Nepal:

The Ladakh route was taken for a number of reasons. The foremost was the long standing relations of the people of Ladakh with Tibet. Besides, Ladakh was directly under Kashmir which was in turn the feudatory of the British. The Maharaja of Kashmir had declared transit trade with Tibet, duty free. In 1873 he passed an order that all merchandise through Ladakh would be remitted for the future. In comparison on the Nepal route the Nepalese government levied a transit duty of 12 1/2 percent *ad valorem*. The problem was further simplified when the Tibetan Government too levied no duty on Leh-Lhasa trade¹⁰⁷⁹.

Between 1947 and 1974, Ladakh was inaccessible to international visitors, which resulted in cultural studies being scarce, and research having progressed only very slowly. However, after these restrictions were lifted, "... cultural research, particularly in Buddhism, iconography and

¹⁰⁷⁸ Devers, 116.

¹⁰⁷⁹ Bir Good Gill, "India's Trade With Tibet: Early British Attempts," *The Tibet Journal* 25, no. 4 (2000): 79.

ethnology, has made systemic progress¹⁰⁸⁰”. However, over-accessibility has also posed its own problems, which when combined with natural ones, accelerate the process of heritage loss:

With Ladakh more and more taking on the excessive speed of the so-called 'First World', its cultural heritage is increasingly coming under pressure. Year by year, evidence of the early history of Ladakh gets further distorted or lost due to repair, reconstruction, negligence and or natural damage¹⁰⁸¹.

Traditional Buddhist monastic institutions lie at the centre of social life in Ladakh. The co-existence of these institutions with modernity has led to a unique mode of cultural exchange that has enabled temporal and spatial connections to emerge, dislocating earlier ones, or perpetuating and complementing them¹⁰⁸². There has also been a direct relationship between the evolution of these monastic institutions and their material and socio-cultural context:

Given the finite resource base, traditional Buddhist institutions evolved in consonance with the limited production possibilities and were characterized by customs such as primogeniture, polyandry, and the monastic way of life¹⁰⁸³.

This relationship has also been studied in terms of “economy of merit¹⁰⁸⁴”, a framework that interpreted modern Buddhist societies based on the concept of earning merit in Buddhism, which often translate into socio-cultural and material implications, beyond religion.

The well-known Buddhist temple-complex at Alchi in Ladakh (Plate 75a-b), which was established in the third quarter of the twelfth century CE, is situated around 60 kilometres west of

¹⁰⁸⁰ Skalzang Dorjey, “Ladakh Monastic Art and Architecture:: A Case Study of Its Developmental Perspective in Relation with Tibet,” *The Tibet Journal* 41, no. 2 (2016): 22.

¹⁰⁸¹ Christian Luczanits, “The early Buddhist heritage of Ladakh reconsidered”. In John Bray ed. *Ladakhi Histories: Local and Regional Perspectives* (Lieden and Boston: Brill, 2005), 91.

¹⁰⁸² Sonam Joldan, “Traditional ties between Ladakh and Buddhist Tibet: Monastic organization and monastic education as a sustaining factor,” *The Tibet Journal* 31, no. 2 (2006): 69-88.

¹⁰⁸³ Sandhya Chatterji, “Development Prospects in Ladakh,” *Mountain Research and Development* 7, no. 3 (1987): 218.

¹⁰⁸⁴ Andrea Butcher. “Ceremonial Activities in Development: The Spiritual ‘Problems’ for Ladakh’s Secular Encounter,” *The Tibet Journal* 40, no. 2 (2015): 202; Andrea S. Wiley, “A Role for Biology in the Cultural Ecology of Ladakh,” *Human Ecology* 25, no. 2 (1997): 274-282.

Leh, nestled on an alluvial platform above the Indus river basin. The architecture and mural works at Alchi, demonstrate its accumulated influences over the years: that of the Indian subcontinent including nearby Kashmir valley, Tibet, Trans-Himalaya, Central Asia and even ancient Greece. Alongside its profuse mural works, the temple-complex also houses thousands of rare sculptures, bronzes, manuscripts, paintings and other Buddhist masterpieces from Ladakh dating from at least the eleventh century. Alchi was nominated as a UNESCO World Heritage Site in 1998¹⁰⁸⁵, a prospect yet unrealised. At the nearby Buddhist monastery at Tabo, in the Lahaul and Spiti district of Himachal Pradesh, often considered geographically and culturally congruous with Ladakh, specific conservation efforts were made, led by the Centre de recherche sur les civilisations de l'Asie orientale (CRCAO), Paris: after the abbot and the head administrator of Tabo monastery requested the institution technical assistance in documenting the present status of its mural paintings “in view of long term conservation”: which was attempted to be fulfilled, alongside also documenting in detail the ‘Maṇḍala Temple’ at Tabo¹⁰⁸⁶, which previously escaped detailed documentation in 1997¹⁰⁸⁷. Basgo is another well-known settlement on the Indus which once functioned as the capital of Ladakh and has three ancient Buddhist temples and a fort¹⁰⁸⁸ (Plate 76a-b). It is an exception in conservation status amongst the monasteries in Ladakh¹⁰⁸⁹. In 2006, the UNESCO presented the Basgo Welfare Committee of the Basgo Gömpa at Basgo an award of excellence for cultural-heritage conservation in Asia for the work done by the monastery in preserving its heritage in collaboration with the Hemis

¹⁰⁸⁵ Jeremy Kahn, “Glimpses of the lost world of Alchi,” last modified April, 2010, <https://www.smithsonianmag.com/arts-culture/glimpses-of-the-lost-world-of-alchi-9293135/>.

¹⁰⁸⁶ Amy Heller, “The Maṇḍala Temple of Tabo: A Reassessment of the Chronology based on Tibetan Historic Inscriptions and the Iconography of the Mural Paintings,” *Revue d’Etudes Tibétaines*, 41 (September 2017): 202-225.

¹⁰⁸⁷ Which culminated into the multi-disciplinary publication: Deborah E. Klimburg-Salter, Christian Luczanits, eds., *Tabo a Lamp for the Kingdom: Early Indo-Tibetan Buddhist Art in the Western Himalaya* (Milan: Skira, 1997).

¹⁰⁸⁸ Georgios T. Halkias, “A History Worth Remembering: An Expedition to the Fortress of Basgo,” *Orientalis*, 48, no. 2 (2017): 2-7; Sanjay Dhar, “Basgo: The Remains of a Royal Precinct,” <https://www.sahapedia.org/basgo-the-remains-of-royal-precinct>; Jamspal, Lobzang. “The Five Royal Patrons and Three Maitreya Images in Basgo.” In *Recent Research on Ladakh 6: Proceedings of the Sixth International Colloquium on Ladakh, Leh 1996*, ed. Henry Osmaston and Nawang Tsering, 139–56. New Delhi: Motilal Banarsi Das Publisher Pvt. Ltd., 1997.

¹⁰⁸⁹ Sanjay Dhar, “Basgo: The Conservation Story,” <https://www.sahapedia.org/basgo-the-conservation-story>.

monastery, the ASI and international partners like the New York-based World Monuments Funds and other global art foundations. However, the then spokesperson of Likir monastery (who also represents Alchi) was reportedly not perturbed by the conservation status at Alchi and Likir¹⁰⁹⁰.

The development of modern infrastructure itself poses significant challenges in the preservation of Ladakh's cultural heritage, for example rock engravings were lost at a historic site near Kargil, during bridge construction over the river Indus¹⁰⁹¹. During field work in Ladakh, the main concerns that I observed, related to heritage in the context of infrastructure, include: a) at some high altitude monasteries like Wanla and Mangyu, the road infrastructure is extremely poor: where, similar to most Indian frontier regions, the highways facilitating military movement is often prioritised over endogenous needs of the community. Even if road networks are extant, they are often in a very poor condition, even for the few summer months in a year that they remain open for; road networks are also contingent upon whether the local-level administrator is favoured by the ruling dispensation; b) there is also the issue of unplanned infrastructural development, in the form of dams in the Upper Indus Valley and construction of military infrastructure often without a cognisance of their ecological impacts; and c) lack of heritage-awareness amongst local-level administrators, where often newly produced murals are more guarded, than the antique ones, which are left to decay, for example at the monastery in Lamayuru (Plate 77a-b), where I had full access to the murals for photographing at the Avalokiteśvara temple (Plate 78a), which had old murals (Plate 78b), however the newer ones at other temples were rendered inaccessible. Plate 78-b shows the murals painted on the eastern wall in the interior of the Avalokiteśvara temple, with a visible crack which starts from the roof and extends downwards on the wall. The wooden frame supporting this section of the roof has been freshly inserted to arrest further collapse of the roof. While the colours are not very badly damaged, the painted boundary on the top in shades of ochre, appears to be newly painted. The painting is divided into sections, with each section telling an individual story and also being part of a

¹⁰⁹⁰ Kahn, "Glimpses of Alchi."

¹⁰⁹¹ Christian Luczanits, "The early Buddhist heritage of Ladakh reconsidered". In John Bray ed. *Ladakhi Histories: Local and Regional Perspectives* (Liedien and Boston: Brill, 2005), 92.

larger visual narrative. The image of the Buddha in the *bhūmisparśamudrā* can be noted at the centre of some of these sections, surrounded by monks and devotees. The landscape is very carefully portrayed, with hills, clouds, flowing rivers, flying *siddhas* and *lāmās* etc. The portrayal of the clouds suggest a distinct Chinese influence. Horse riders, traders, soldiers and monks engrossed in monastic activities, are also depicted. At Wanla, which is only accessible through a dirt track (Plate 79a) beside a tributary of the Indus, the main temple (Plate 79b) was locked in the absence of the temple priest. Mangyu is also accessible through a dirt track (Plate 80a-b), with centuries old wooden architecture and images, across the Indus, off the National Highway 1 (also known as the Srinagar-Leh highway), which goes towards Alchi. Here conservation is in a very dilapidated state. The entire temple is cloistered by an overgrowing Mangyu village and its modern constructions. It is often only the rituals and worship that the villagers are able to pay particular attention to, and not the preservation of the site and its artefacts: as evident from the leaking roofs, from where snow melts and turns into water to drip over these wooden images every year, slowly eating into the frame. Plate 81a-b shows the inside of the Avalokiteśvara temple. The large standing Avalokiteśvara image is depicted in the *varadamudrā*. Here the colours of the main image have mostly faded. The murals on all the walls show different degree of *decay*. The murals on the side walls appear newer than the ones at the back of the deity. Plate 81-b shows the murals at the back of the deity. The central image is of an eight-armed Avalokiteśvara. At the top of the Avalokiteśvara image, is an image of Vajrapāṇi, identifiable from the colour blue. Below it, are two roundels depicting two forms of Tārā. This temple is the most damaged amongst the three. Plate 82-a shows the inside of the Mañjuśrī temple, with a stack of manuscripts in the background behind the main deity. Plate 82-b shows the murals on the eastern wall of the temple. This is comparatively better preserved than those at the other temples. Plate 83a-c shows the interiors of the Vairocana temple. Plate 83-a shows the main large sculpture of Vairocana, with recently repainted colours. Here, the murals on the wall behind the deity are almost obliterated. Plate 83-b and 83-c shows a section of the murals from the eastern and western walls of the temples, which are comparatively better preserved, and represent *maṇḍalas* in different cosmological

formations. The Saspol caves in vicinity, with Buddhist murals, also suffers from lack of conservation. The Indian National Trust for Art and Cultural Heritage (INTACH) was recently involved in a renovation project at the Saspol caves (Plates 84 a-b, 85 a-b, 86 a-b & 87 a-b) in Ladakh. Plate 87-a shows a mural depicting Amitābha in Sukhāvātī paradise, while the mural in Plate 87-b depicts clockwise: Vajravārāhī, possibly Lāmā Atiśa, a *lāmā* with an inscription, and a two-armed Kālacakra.

Coming back to glaciers, and the waterscape of Ladakh, precipitation data from the last two centuries in Ladakh, clearly denote a gradual increase¹⁰⁹². The murals at the monasteries in Ladakh have mostly survived centuries, without any human intervention, owing to the unique climate of this region. The state of decay in which some of these murals presently are, is symbolic of the changing climate and its impact on heritage. The case of artificial glacier conservation in Ladakh, especially through the example of Chewang Norphel, has been talked about as an exemplar of implementing endogenous knowledge for modern ecological conservation. But it has also been shown that the idea of endogenous knowledge as “timeless” knowledge has serious limitations as they “... risk obscuring the fact that climate change adaptation is a critical issue with no easy solution, and for which local communities do not necessary have all of the answers¹⁰⁹³.” The village communities themselves are entities in flux as “ ... changes in village dynamics, the dismantling of community arrangements, and the discontinuity in local practices may also function as exacerbating factors¹⁰⁹⁴” : as we observed, in the case of conservation of mural works in the Buddhist temples and monasteries of Ladakh, the local population, through both institutionalised and community gestures, has played a limited role in heritage conservation in recent times. While the Little Ice Age posited advancing glaciers a threat, it is repleting glaciers and increased precipitation leading to macro-level changes,

¹⁰⁹² Shafiq MU, Bhat MS, Rasool R, Ahmed P*, Singh H and Hassan H, “Variability of Precipitation regime in Ladakh region of India from 1901-2000,” *Journal of Climatology & Weather Forecasting* 4, no. 2 (2016): 165–169.; Binita Phartiyal, Debarati Nag and Priyanka Joshi, “Holocene climatic record of Ladakh, Trans-Himalaya,” in *Holocene Climate Change and Environment*, eds. Navnith Kumaran and Padmalal Damodara (Amsterdam: Elsevier, 2022), 61-89,

¹⁰⁹³ Karine Gagné, “Cultivating Ice over Time: On the Idea of Timeless Knowledge and Places in the Himalayas,” in *Anthropologica* 58, no. 2, (2016): 203.

¹⁰⁹⁴ Gagné, 201.

which is a threat now. From the framework of “amphibious anthropology¹⁰⁹⁵,” in the context of the Upper Indus Valley, it can also be argued that:

... time is a salient feature of place, whereas movement is a defining quality of water. At the concrete and abstract levels, land, as it becomes submerged in water, becomes movement and gets unsettled, whereas the temporal dimension of water crystallises as its flow demarcates space¹⁰⁹⁶.

The ‘ecological locality’ of Ladakh and its heritage has to be situated at the intersection of endogenous temporalities, deconstruction of constructed temporalities that deny *coeval* understanding, and hence limit scientific approaches, and a rigorous study of climate change and its impact in the Upper Indus: in the context of the environment, community, culture, and knowledge production.

While Bihar and northern bengal’s heritage sites suffer from the slow violence of infrastructural neglect and bureaucratic indifference, Ladakh’s Buddhist monuments face the more acute pressures of militarisation and ecological fragility: pressures that produce their own form of allochronic displacement, rendering these sites simultaneously hyper-visible as national security assets and invisible as living Buddhist heritage. This contrast demonstrates perfectly what is at stake in the eastern Indian case: the manuscripts produced at Nalanda and Vikramaśilā, now scattered across global collections, represent a heritage whose allochronic displacement has been so complete that even its geographical origins are contested. Ladakh, by contrast, still possesses its heritage in situ but under conditions that threaten its integrity in different but equally urgent ways.

4.4 The way forward

¹⁰⁹⁵ René ten Bos, (2009). “Towards an Amphibious Anthropology: Water and Peter Sloterdijk.” *Environment and Planning D: Society and Space*, 27, no. 1 (2009): 73-86.

¹⁰⁹⁶ Karine Gagné and Mattias Borg Rasmussen, “Introduction – An Amphibious Anthropology: The Production of Place at the Confluence of Land and Water,” in *Anthropologica* 58, no. 2, (2016): 139.

The World Heritage Convention (henceforth WHC) adopted by the General Conference of the UNESCO on 16th November 1972, to which India is a signatory, mentioned and acknowledged the previously unacknowledged and often overlooked role of heritage and heritage conservation for achieving sustainable development aims:

Heritage was long absent from the mainstream sustainable development debate despite its crucial importance to societies and the wide acknowledgment of its great potential to contribute to social, economic and environmental goals¹⁰⁹⁷.

From its inception in 1972, the WHC has been putting together efforts towards promoting sustainable development in the context of heritage sites. Although ‘sustainability’ as a concept in environmental conservation has a history going back to the eighteenth century, it is only in the 1970s and 80s that it was applied across various fields, often at the global level, through institutions like the WHC, including in the context of heritage sites:

During the 1980s, sustainability became a key concept in nature protection. The concept has always connoted a strong connection between economy and ecology, stemming from ‘sustained yield’ in German forestry (dating back to 18th century) ...¹⁰⁹⁸

It has also been argued that: “... that sustainable development is essentially a profit-driven model only nominally focused on environmental concerns¹⁰⁹⁹.” So far, my observations affirm that the WHC has failed to translate into noticeable qualitative differences across relevant heritage sites in different regions in India.

The disciplines of field-archaeology in the Indian subcontinent is intricately linked to its epistemic origins in the European Enlightenment, and the colonial period surveys and mapping

¹⁰⁹⁷“ World Heritage and Sustainable Development,” *UNESCO World Heritage Convention*, November 19, 2015, <https://whc.unesco.org/en/sustainabledevelopment/>.

¹⁰⁹⁸ Gro Birgit Ween and Lars Christian Risan, “Exploring Heritage Lives: Indigenous peoples in World Heritage sites,” *Primitive Tider* 2, 2014 special edition (2014): 68.

¹⁰⁹⁹ Gagné, 196.; Wolfgang Sachs (ed.), *The Development Dictionary: A Guide to Knowledge as Power* (London: Zed Books, 1992); Arturo Escobar, *Encountering Development: The Making and Unmaking of the Third World* (Princeton, NJ: Princeton University Press, 1995.)

activities of the modern imperialist powers, which had fostered a politics of infrastructure, based on privilege and political power. The definition of heritage itself signified then a barrier in knowledge which was inaccessible and also had no historical relevance for the life and education of the ‘natives’. Perhaps the dissonance in the approach between modern scholarship and endogenous means of knowing, and the proliferation of knowledge, is the root behind the modern misbalances at heritage sites, which gets highlighted as the Anthropocene touches its peak. It was often the forest-dwellers and lower castes, the ones who actually lived in proximity to these sites, who were denied access or prosecuted at times. With the advent of modern archaeological exercises in the Indian subcontinent through the hands of British imperialism and the foundation of the ASI, the indigenous population was often employed as bearers and labourers by the colonial administrators. It is this lowest class, who were either pastoralists or forest-dwellers staying beside heritage sites, who were the most exploited, carried out the most toilsome of tasks, gross-insufficiently rewarded and obliterated from historical records: which today costs the twenty-first century field-archaeologist in South Asia, his/her dissonance or disconnect from endogenous methods of heritage-management which have been suppressed and obliterated from knowledge. From the later half of the eighteenth century, the ‘native surveyor’ or the ‘native draftsmen’: educated in modern Western education and also often scholars in a particular Indian languages, emerged, who were instrumental in laying the foundations of modern historiographical studies on the eastern Indian subcontinent¹¹⁰⁰.

A 2014 article offered an anthropological study¹¹⁰¹ of indigenous people in world heritage sites in New Zealand. Arguing for an emic-etic integration, it suggested that while it may be uneasy to try and find a way out of this modernist trap of the conception of heritage within the limitations of objective knowledge and scientific history, it becomes important to dissect these constructions as the primary constitutive elements of our understanding of heritage as such. Emic-etic integration would

¹¹⁰⁰ Tapati Guha-Thakurta, ““Interlocuting Texts and Monuments: The coming of age of the “native” scholar” in *Monuments, objects, histories: Institutions of art in colonial and postcolonial India* (New York: Columbia University Press, 2004), 85-112; Sarker, “Hermeneutics of Subcontinental Art Historiography,” 32-47.

¹¹⁰¹ Gro Birgit Ween and Lars Christian Risan, “Exploring Heritage Lives: Indigenous peoples in World Heritage sites,” *Primitive Tider* 2, 2014 special edition (2014): 61-72.

allow one to recognise how heritage construes us, as much as the socio-political ripples of our cultural discourse construe the idea of heritage: which is always in a state of continuous formation through constant inputs from different ontological sources. Therefore, constructing a socially relevant and sustainable model of heritage management and accessibility, may lie in our ability to see beyond the ‘modernist trap’ of heritage in concrete contextualisations which are often subject to the same limitations as objective knowledge itself¹¹⁰².

Heritage can be posited as a non-renewable resource, and thus a scarce commodity¹¹⁰³, which is an essential framework for understanding the role of heritage in the production and construction of culture, across temporal frames. A teleological frame with concrete definitions and set patterns of experiences of time, imposed through institutional frameworks, fundamentally limits a heritage site’s role in the production of its own locality:

All locality building has a moment of colonization, a moment both historical and chronotypic, when there is a formal recognition that the production of a neighborhood requires deliberate, risky, even violent action in respect to the soil, forests, animals, and other human beings¹¹⁰⁴.

Without a possibility for *Gleichzeitigkeit*¹¹⁰⁵, with globalisation, the ‘regional’ existence of a heritage site, becomes in Dutta’s terminology an “ontological ablative.¹¹⁰⁶” Along the lines of Dutta’s hypothesis regarding the role played in the nineteenth century by modern Eurocentric imperialism in the construction and imagination of South Asian culture that: “Imperialism is not a variegated experience whose vicissitudes can be confined within the critical matrix of disciplinarity; *it is rather the very opening into variegation itself*¹¹⁰⁷”, it can also be argued that: since disciplinarity itself, being

¹¹⁰² Weeen and Risan, 62.

¹¹⁰³ Lynn Meskell, “Negative Heritage and Past Mastering in Archaeology,” *Anthropological Quarterly* 75, no. 3 (2002): 557-574.

¹¹⁰⁴ Arjun Appadurai, “The Production of Locality” in Appadurai, A. *Modernity at Large: Cultural Dimensions of Globalization*. (Minneapolis: University of Minnesota Press, 1996), 183.

¹¹⁰⁵ A phenomenological category that denotes both ‘contemporaneity’ and ‘synchronicity’/ ‘simultaneity’.

¹¹⁰⁶ Arindam Dutta, “Designing the Present; The Cole Circle and the Architecture of (an) Imperial Bureaucracy, 1851- 1901” (PhD thesis, Princeton University, 2001), 88-110; 219.

¹¹⁰⁷ Dutta, 48.

rooted in Eurocentrism, is defined by temporal frames that advance teleological understanding of the past, the experience of production of culture, which “... in modernity ... (is) used to describe an entity the name for which is also culture¹¹⁰⁸”, and its reception, in postcolonial nation states: also come as an unique opportunity to study the variegations and vicissitudes associated with it. Thus personal and as well as public reaction to the ideological constructions of heritage have often been that of identifying the fundamental nature of the ephemerality of ‘heritage,’ and thus proceeding to engage with heritage and the experience of heritage with an acute awareness of its artificiality and formal incapacities.

From the European ‘regime of protection and map-making’ to the advent of platforms like Google Earth and Google Maps, from the computer screen to the tiny android devices, we have today traversed a full circle: from the power structures of the modern imperial empires to the complex tentacles of global multi-national companies and their quantifying and capitalising activities on natural space and time. Today, with the proliferation of internet connectivity to the remotest of villages, albeit demonstrating other forms of inequality and misbalance, the world heritage sites, at least in the context of South Asia, are in a very unique position. The advent of technocracy in the twenty-first century in the context of cultural and heritage infrastructure in an emerging economy like India, has been unique because of the fact that technology comes under the garb of being impactful in democratisation of knowledge and making qualitative as well quantitative improvement in terms of access and mobility; while simultaneously it is also one of the main forces behind monopolisation of knowledge. The cartographic model of the proliferation of Eurocentric interests following the Enlightenment and the Cartesian rooting in the superiority of the dominance of man over nature, has metamorphosed into the algorithmic manipulation and control over natural and man-made space in the twenty-first century.

¹¹⁰⁸ Dutta, xii.

In 2021 the term “emotional heritage¹¹⁰⁹” was coined¹¹¹⁰, a term laden with semantic value which conveys, and provides a valuable theoretical framework of, how heritage becomes an important and inalienable aspect of the personal self. The idea to assimilate visitor experiences in the curation of a cultural space has already been a tried and tested method. At the receptive level, although absolute political power in itself may be denied to a heritage site, it still maintains an agency of its own through a direct participation with an individual’s subjective experience.

Infrastructure plays a vital role in making the heritage physically as well as emotionally accessible. Heritage can be located in cultural discourse in a discursive context and as a mode of social practice that is more of a process, practice, or performative activity¹¹¹¹, and not a thing; and that these practices and performances are framed by particular heritage discourses, some of which were more politically powerful than others¹¹¹². Within the South Asian heritage management scene, there are often a diverse group of invested parties, who play a role in the prioritisation of a certain thread of a cultural discourse, often with political objectives: in such instances, it is heritage which is ‘performed’ in the theatrical sense of the term, and also becomes the site of performance over the fight for political control over cultural discourse. In South Asia, artefacts and heritage *per se*, have in modern history, played a central role, in cultural and political discourse. In post-Independence India, the public perception and assimilation of heritage through nationalist incorporations have often rendered reception within the domestic turf marked by an imposition of ideological symbolism and narrative homogeneity.

Heritage sites in South Asia, especially the popular tourist and pilgrimage destinations, have been largely unable to keep up with the pace of developments required in accommodating the needs of burgeoning tourism and urban-expansion, combined with a poor socio-economy on the ground, as well as a lack in creativity in applying technological innovations and advancements in

¹¹⁰⁹ Laurajane Smith, *Emotional Heritage: Visitor Engagement at Museums and Heritage Sites* (New York: Routledge, 2021).

¹¹¹⁰ By relying on a methodology derived from critical realism, the study investigates the “affective and political consequences of heritage-making.” (Smith, 90)

¹¹¹¹ Laurajane Smith, *Uses of Heritage* (New York: Routledge, 2006), 66.

¹¹¹² Smith, 35.

infrastructural design. Academia, which is often accused of being involved in the same tentacles of capital-driven profit making machinery of global capitalistic interests, because of it being one of the many constituent elements of the structure that filters power and actively plays a role in the distribution of power, just like the bureaucracy and the administration, through the control, manipulation and branding of knowledge; is but at the same time, being bestowed with the power of control over the knowledge, can be used for a rather different purpose: of actually doing on the ground work to make new contributions to holistic knowledge, broaden the ambit of accessibility and reach, and contribute to making substantial qualitative changes on the ground.

Afterword

Chapter 1 examined illuminated Buddhist manuscripts and stone sculptures through a *polycentric semiosis* framework, arguing that Pāla period artistic production was not centered on a few dominant monasteries but distributed across a network of regionally distinct production sites: described through the nomenclature of *Magadha-Varendra-constellation*, *Varendra-confluens*, and *Samatāṭa-littoral*. Chapter 2 traced the transformation of Prajñāpāramitā from an abstract philosophical concept to a deified devotional figure, framing this as an extended historical process shaped by the trans-regional circulation of Mahāyana Buddhism across South, Central and Southeast Asia. Chapter 3 examined the manuscripts as *dharma*-relics, ritual instruments, and material embodiments of *pratītyasamutpāda*. It also drew on Bourdieu's concept of *habitus* to analyse the embodied practices: production, consecration, recitation, and *darśana*, through which the manuscripts' sacred status was activated and sustained. Chapter 4 offered a reflexive critique of how historiographical and heritage management frameworks have tended to deny coevalness to Buddhist heritage in South Asia, drawing on fieldwork conducted between 2016 and 2023 across eastern India, northern Bengal, Nepal and Ladakh.

This dissertation has attempted to reframe the study of Pāla period illuminated Buddhist manuscripts, stone sculptures, and their living heritage through an interdisciplinary approach that combined art historical analysis with theoretical inquiry and reflexive anthropological critique. Its central argument is that these artefacts are best understood not as static aesthetic objects but as active participants in networks of ritual practice, monastic patronage, regional production, and trans-regional exchange. Chapter 1's principal contribution was the *polycentric semiosis* framework and its accompanying regional nomenclature, which demonstrated through close iconographic and stylistic analysis that Pāla period artistic production was distributed across multiple, regionally distinct centres rather than radiating outward from a few dominant monasteries. The *Magadha-Varendra-constellation*, *Varendra-confluens*, and *Samatāṭa-littoral* nomenclature offered an alternative to the

anachronistic Bihar-Bengal binary and the persistent tendency to privilege Magadha as the normative centre of Pāla art. By applying this framework to both manuscripts and stone sculptures, the chapter demonstrated that so-called peripheral regions: particularly the *Samataṣa-littoral*, produced iconographic innovations that cannot be explained by a diffusionist model radiating from Magadha. Chapter 2 traced Prajñāpāramitā's transformation from textual abstraction to iconic deity as an extended historical process, shaped by monastic networks, lay patronage, and the interaction of Buddhist and Brahmanical traditions, that unfolded unevenly across South, Central, and Southeast Asia before culminating in the distinctive Pāla period formations. This chapter demonstrated how the material production of manuscripts and images both reflected and constituted the devotional significance of the goddess. By tracing the Prajñāpāramitā tradition's textual and visual transmission: from the Gilgit manuscripts and Kashmiri Mahāyāna centres, through Central Asian conduits like Khotan, to interactions with Brahmanical *mātrkā* and goddess traditions in eastern India, the chapter situated the Pāla period iconographic innovations within a broader trans-regional history, extending briefly to the living ritual traditions of Newari Buddhism in the Kathmandu Valley. Chapter 3 examined the manuscripts through three dimensions of their significance within the Buddhist communities that produced and used them. It established their doctrinal status as *dharma*-relics: material instantiations of the Prajñāpāramitā whose theological authority rests on the text's own claim to be the generative source of the Buddha's relics, as analysed by Schopen. It then introduced Bourdieu's concept of *habitus* to examine the embodied practices through which this doctrinal status was activated: the structured labour of scribes and painters, the ritual practices of recitation, *darśana*, and veneration that sustained the manuscript's sacred presence, and the trans-Himalayan networks of exchange through which manuscripts and their accompanying ritual *habitus* circulated between eastern India and Nepal. Through an analysis of individual manuscripts, particularly the LACMA *DnS* (M.72.1.20 a-b) and the Kaiser Library *AsP* (Acc. No. 9.102), the chapter argued that the manuscript's sacred reality arose through the interdependence of its material, textual, iconographic, and ritual dimensions. The analysis was extended to the *stūpa* and the *bodhi* tree, which share with

the manuscripts the characteristic that their sacred status arises dependently from the coming together of material form, doctrinal narrative, and ritual practice. Chapter 4 offered a reflexive critique of how historiographical and heritage management frameworks have tended to consign Buddhist heritage in South Asia to a sealed-off past, drawing on Fabian's concept of allochronism and grounded in my own positionality as a native of northern Bengal and descendent of Partition-displaced communities. Through fieldwork conducted across eight years at sites in eastern India, northern Bengal (particularly Bangarh), Nepal, Ladakh, the chapter examined how resource inequities, bureaucratic structures, and infrastructural neglect undermine the stewardship of Buddhist heritage in these regions, and proposed approaches that recognise the continuing temporal presence of this heritage rather than treating it as a relic of a concluded past.

While this dissertation attempted to provide a synthesised interdisciplinary framework for analysing Pāla-period illuminated Buddhist manuscripts, stone images, and their heritage, its scope is necessarily constrained by the vastness of the Pāla cultural corpus, and the complexity of its regional and temporal contexts: limiting the depth of exploration into certain areas such as the full spectrum of manuscript and images production sites, lesser-known regional ateliers, or the socio-economic intricacies of patronage networks. The study leaves room for more detailed investigations of lesser-known regional production sites, under-explored artefacts such as the large corpus of Pāla copper-alloy images, and comparative analyses with contemporaneous Southeast Asian Buddhist traditions. The *polycentric semiosis* framework, the *dharma*-relic analysis, and the *habitus*-based approach to manuscript culture developed in Chapters 1 and 3 are offered as starting points that future research might extend, refine, or challenge: including through digital humanities methods that could map the distribution of iconographic features across the full range of known manuscripts and sculptures, and through ethnographic fieldwork in the Kathmandu Valley that could further document the surviving ritual *habitus* of Newari manuscript culture. The reflexive anthropological approach in Chapter 4 opens avenues for longitudinal studies of heritage management and community-driven preservation in South Asia. It is my hope that the frameworks developed in this dissertation: the

polycentric regional nomenclature, the analysis of Prajñāpāramitā's transformation as an extended historical process, the theoretical engagement with manuscript materiality and ritual function, and the emic perspective on heritage stewardship, may prove useful to future scholars working on Buddhist cultural production and its enduring legacies across South Asia and beyond.

APPENDIX 1: TABLE OF GENEALOGY OF PĀLA RULERS

	RC Majumdar (1971)	B.P. Sinha (1977)	DC Sircar (1975–76)	D. K. Ganguly (1994)	Shin'ichiro Hori (2019)	Ryosuke Furui	Rajat Sanyal (2014)
Gopāla I	750–770	755–783	750–775	750–774		750 (accession)	741 (accession)
Dharmapāla	770–810	783–820	775–812	774–806			766–798
Devapāla	810–c. 850	820–860	812–850	806–845		810–850	
Mahendrapāla	N/A (Mahendrapāla's existence was conclusively established through a copper-plate charter discovered later.)			845–860		850–865	
Śurapāla I	850–853	860–865	850–858	860–872			
Vigrahapāla I			858–60	872–873			
Nārāyana pāla	854–908	865–920	860–917	873–927			
Rajyapāla	908–940	920–952	917–952	927–959			
Gopāla II	940–957	952–967	952–972	959–976		Late 9th CE/ ca. 866–870	
Vigrahapāla II	960–c. 986	967–980	972–977	976–977			
Mahipāla I	988–c. 1036	980–1035	977–1027	977–1027			
Nayapāla	1038–1053	1035–1050	1027–1043	1027–1043			
Vigrahapāla III	1054–1072	1050–1076	1043–1070	1043–1070			
Mahipāla II	1072–1075	1076–1078/9	1070–1071	1070–1071			1067–1075
Śurapāla II	1075–1077		1071–1072	1071–1072			
Rāmapāla	1077–1130	1078/9–1132	1072–1126	1072–1126	1078/1079 - 1131		
Kumārapāla	1130–1125	1132–1136	1126–1128	1126–1128			
Gopāla III	1140–1144	1136–1144	1128–1143	1128–1143			
Madanapāla	1144–1162	1144–1161/62	1143–1161	1143–1161		1143–1165	1143 (accession)
Govindapāla	1155–1159	1162–1176 or 1158–1162	1161–1165	1161–1165			
Pālapāla	N/A	N/A	1165–1199	1165–1200			

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APPENDIX 2: LIST OF SOME IMPORTANT KNOWN BUDDHIST MONK-SCHOLARS

2.a From Eastern India and Bengal

1. Śīlabhadra (born. Samatāṭa, Bengal. 529-645 CE¹¹¹³): Born into a Brahmanical family. Abbott at Nalanda; trained by the renowned Dharmapāla; considered an important philosopher in the Yogācāra tradition. Author of *Buddhabhūmiviyākhyāna*.
2. Kāṇha or Kṛṣṇācārya¹¹¹⁴ (c. 8th CE Born: eastern India). Literally, 'the dark one'. One of the most well known of the 84 Indian *mahasiddhas*; disciple of Virūpa; and one of the composers in *cāryapada*, the *Kāṇhapada*. One of the most important *siddhacāryas*¹¹¹⁵.
3. Tilopā¹¹¹⁶ (born. Bengal 988-1069 CE¹¹¹⁷): Also known as Tilopadā; practised *Anuttarayogatantra*. Born into a Brahmanical household, and inspired to take up monastic life by a *dākinī*. Also considered a tantric adept and an authority in Mahāmudrā¹¹¹⁸.
4. Atiśa Dīpankara Śrījñāna (Born. Bikrampur, Bengal; 982-1054 CE¹¹¹⁹): Well-known as one of the most influential Buddhist monk to introduce Buddhism in Tibet¹¹²⁰.
5. Maitrīpadā (Born northern Bihar/ Mithila, c. 11th CE): Considered a student of Śabara and Naropa; and teacher of Atiśa, Marpa¹¹²¹.

¹¹¹³ Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 821-822; Hajime Nakamura, *Indian Buddhism: A Survey with Bibliographical Notes* (Delhi: Motilal Banarsidass, 1999), 281.

¹¹¹⁴ Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 445.

¹¹¹⁵ Keith Dowman, *Buddhist Masters of Enchantment: The Lives and Legends of the Mahasiddhas*, trans. Keith Dowman, illus. Robert Beer (Rochester, VT: Inner Traditions, 1998), 115–19; Keith Dowman, *Masters of Mahāmudrā: Songs and Histories of the Eighty-Four Buddhist Siddhas*, trans. and comm. by Keith Dowman, illus. Hugh R. Downs (Albany: State University of New York Press, 1985), 123–131.

¹¹¹⁶ Fabrizio Torricelli, *Tilopā: A Buddhist Yogin of the Tenth Century* (Dharamsala: Library of Tibetan Works and Archives, 2019).

¹¹¹⁷ Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 914.

¹¹¹⁸ Dowman, *Buddhist Masters of Enchantment*, 93-94; Dowman, *Masters of Mahāmudrā*, 151–155.

¹¹¹⁹ Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 77-78.

¹¹²⁰ Alaka Chattopadhyaya, *Atiśa and Tibet: Life and Works of Dīpaṅkara Śrījñāna in Relation to the History and Religion of Tibet* (Delhi: Motilal Banarsidass, 1981).

¹¹²¹ Mark Tatz, "The Life of the Siddha-Philosopher Maitrīgupta," *Journal of the American Oriental Society* 107, no. 4 (1987): 695–711; Peter Alan Roberts, *Mahamudra and Related Instructions: Core Teachings of the Kagyu Schools*, Library of Tibetan Classics (Boston: Wisdom Publications, 2011), 11–12.

6. Śabara (or Śavaripa, born northern India, c. 10th CE): Travelled to Tibet. Considered to be a teacher of Maitrīpadā, and also one of the eighty-four *mahāsiddhas*¹¹²².

7. Virūpa¹¹²³ (born Bengal, c. 12th CE): An author of some key Vajrayāna texts, who is known to have travelled throughout India and performed miracles; also appears as a *mahāsiddhas* in different non-Buddhist texts, especially of the Nātha sect¹¹²⁴.

2.b From the rest of the Indian subcontinent

1. Aśvagoṣa¹¹²⁵ (c. 80 - 150 CE) Born: Kośalā/ northwest. He played an important role in Kaṇiṣka's First Mahāyānist Council.

2. Nāgārjuna¹¹²⁶ (c. 150 - 250 CE) Born: Vidarbha/ Nāgārjunikoṇḍā. One of the most important and legendary Madhyamaka scholar. He had a dual identity: idealist philosopher and author of *Madhyamakakārika*, and also a magician, alchemist and author of *Rasaratnakāra*¹¹²⁷.

3. Vasubandhu¹¹²⁸ (c. 4th - 5th CE) Born: northwest. His *magnum opus* is *Abhidharmakośa*. He probably converted from the Theravāda tradition by his brother Asaṅga into Mahāyāna¹¹²⁹.

4. Dignāga (c. 480 - 540 CE¹¹³⁰) Born: Kanchipuram. One of the most renowned Indian logician who laid the groundwork of Indian/ Buddhist logic. Considered to have been taught by Vasubandhu¹¹³¹.

¹¹²² Dowman, *Buddhist Masters of Enchantment*, 51-52; Dowman, *Masters of Mahāmudrā*, 60-65.

¹¹²³ Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 980.

¹¹²⁴ Dowman, *Buddhist Masters of Enchantment*, 35-40; Dowman, *Masters of Mahāmudrā*, 43-52.

¹¹²⁵ Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 76.

¹¹²⁶ Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 561-562.

¹¹²⁷ Dowman, *Buddhist Masters of Enchantment*, 73-76; Dowman, *Masters of Mahāmudrā*, 112-22.

¹¹²⁸ Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 961-962.

¹¹²⁹ J. Takakusu, trans., "The Life of Vasubandhu by Paramārtha," *T'oung Pao* 5 (1904): 269-96; Robert Kritzer, "Vasubandhu," *Brill's Encyclopedia of Buddhism Online*, accessed 29 August, 2025, <https://referenceworks.brill.com/display/entries/ENBO/COM-2071.xml?language=en>; Jonathan C. Gold, "Vasubandhu," in *The Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy*, ed. Edward N. Zalta (Stanford, CA: Metaphysics Research Lab, Stanford University, 2015).

¹¹³⁰ Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 259.

¹¹³¹ Vincent Eltschinger, "Dignāga," in *Brill's Encyclopedia of Buddhism*, vol. 2, *Lives*, ed. Jonathan A. Silk (editor-in-chief), Richard Bowring, Vincent Eltschinger, and Michael Radich (Leiden and Boston: Brill, 2019), 179-85.

5. Āryadeva¹¹³² (c. 3rd CE) Born: Sinhala/ Southern India. Author of *Catūśataka*, which exists in Tibetan, and of two classic texts on *Prajñāpāramitā*, whose originals have disappeared¹¹³³.

6. Buddhapālita (c. 470-540 CE¹¹³⁴) Born: Southern India. He was an exponent of the Madhyamaka school, and wrote a commentary on Nāgārjuna's *Mūlamadhyamakakārikā*¹¹³⁵.

7. Bhāviveka/ Bhāvaviveka (c. 500-570 CE) Born: northern India. He was an exponent of the Madhyamaka school, and the author of *Madhyamakahrdayakārikā*, *Madhyamakaratnapradīpa* etc. According to Hsuen Tsang, he was externally a disciple of Kapila (of the Samkhya school), but privately a follower of Madhyamaka¹¹³⁶.

8. Saṃghabhadra (c. 5th CE) Born: Kashmir. He was a near contemporary of Vasubandhu, and according to some sources his disciple. He travelled to Nalanda, and wrote a commentary on his *Abhidharmakośa*¹¹³⁷.

9. Gunamati (c. 5th CE) Born: unknown. Acquired learning at Nalanda¹¹³⁸.

10. Sthiramati (c. 5th CE) Born: unknown. Disciple of Vasubandhu, who acquired learning at Nalanda, and settled in Valabhī, western India¹¹³⁹.

¹¹³² Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 64-65.

¹¹³³ Dowman, *Buddhist Masters of Enchantment*, 69-72; Dowman, *Masters of Mahāmudrā*, 132-137.

¹¹³⁴ Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 154-155.

¹¹³⁵ Jan Westerhoff, *The Golden Age of Indian Buddhist Philosophy* (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2018), 122-23; Buddhapālita," Oxford Reference, accessed August 29, 2025, <https://www.oxfordreference.com/display/10.1093/oi/authority.20110803095533805>.

¹¹³⁶ Malcolm David Eckel, *Bhāviveka and His Buddhist Opponents*, Harvard Oriental Series, vol. 70 (Cambridge, MA: Harvard University Press, 2008); Bhāvaviveka. *Bhāviveka on Sāṃkhya and Vedānta: The Sāṃkhya and Vedānta Chapters of the Madhyamakahrdayakārikā and Tarkajvālā*. Edited by Olle Qvarnström and Per K. Sørensen. Harvard Oriental Series, vol. 78. Cambridge, MA: Harvard University Press, 2015.

¹¹³⁷ K. L. Dhammajoti, "The Contribution of Saṃghabhadra to Our Understanding of Abhidharma Doctrines," in *Text, History, and Philosophy* (Leiden, The Netherlands: Brill, 2016); Chih-chiang Hu, "Self-Cognition? Saṃghabhadra, Armstrong, and Introspective Consciousness," *Philosophy East and West* 68, no. 3 (2018): 702-20; Shuqing Zhang and Jincheng Li, "Saṃghabhadra on Perception of Non-existence," *Philosophy East and West*, published electronically November 8, 2024; Damien Keown, "Saṃghabhadra," in *A Dictionary of Buddhism* (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2004), <https://www.oxfordreference.com/display/10.1093/acref/9780198605607.001.0001/acref-9780198605607-e-1563>, accessed August 29, 2025.

¹¹³⁸ Norisato Aohara, "Gunamati and His Pupil Vasumitra," *Journal of Indian and Buddhist Studies* (Indogaku Bukkyōgaku Kenkyū) 36, no. 2 (1988): 917-919.

¹¹³⁹ William Edelglass, Pierre-Julien Harter, and Sara McClintock, eds., *The Routledge Handbook of Indian Buddhist Philosophy*, 1st ed. (New York: Routledge, 2022), chap. 22, "Sthiramati: A Yogācāra Commentator and Innovator," 376-92; Hidenori Sakuma, "Was There Really Only One Commentator Named Sthiramati?" *Studies in Philosophy* 45 (2020): 212(39)-190(61).

11. Gunaprabha¹¹⁴⁰ (c. 7th CE) Born: unknown. Disciple of Vasubandhu, and considered a pre-eminent authority on the *Vinaya* of the Mūlasarvāstivāda school.

12. Jinaprabha (c. 7th CE) Born: unknown. Name appears in Yijing's record. He perhaps taught the Chinese pilgrim Huen Chao at Nalanda in the seventh century CE.¹¹⁴¹

13. Bhartṛhari¹¹⁴² (c. 5th CE) Born: unknown. According to I-Tsing/ Yijing's record, he was famous throughout the five parts of India. His works on Pāṇini's grammar are considered a seminal text for students of all schools of Sanskrit grammar.

14. Śāntideva¹¹⁴³ (c. 8th CE) Born: Gujarat. Author of *Śikṣāsamuccaya* and *Bodhicaryāvatāra*. He travelled to, and lived in Nalanda and had many adversaries there, and was considered an important philosopher of the Madhyamaka school.

15. Paramārtha (c. 499-569 CE¹¹⁴⁴) Born: Ujjainī. Travelled to China under a provision made by the Gupta king and the emperor of the Liang dynasty, and never returned to India. A large number of his works are included in the Chinese *Tripitaka*, among which, is also, his version of Aśvaghōṣa's *Mahāyānaśraddotpāda*¹¹⁴⁵.

16. Mandāravā¹¹⁴⁶ (c. 8th CE) Born: Bengal or Oḍḍiyāna. Considered a consort of Guru Rinpoche.

17. Padmasambhava or Guru Rinpoche¹¹⁴⁷ (c. 8th CE) Born: Oḍḍiyāna. One of the most influential Indian philosopher and *siddha* who travelled to Tibet, and was an adept in esoteric practices and a proponent of *guru yoga* tradition¹¹⁴⁸.

¹¹⁴⁰ Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 337.

¹¹⁴¹ Ji Yun 紀贇, "Faxian and the Establishment of the Pilgrimage Tradition of Qiufa," *Hualin International Journal of Buddhist Studies* 2, no. 1 (2019): 14.

¹¹⁴² Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 111.

¹¹⁴³ Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 774.

¹¹⁴⁴ Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 622-623.

¹¹⁴⁵ Daniel Boucher, "Paramārtha," in *Encyclopedia of Buddhism*, ed. Robert E. Buswell (New York: Macmillan Reference Library, 2003), 630-31; Diana Paul, "The Life and Time of Paramārtha (499-569)," *Journal of the International Association of Buddhist Studies* 5, no. 1 (1982): 37-69.

¹¹⁴⁶ Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 524-525.

¹¹⁴⁷ Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 608-609.

¹¹⁴⁸ Jamgon Kongtrul, "A Short Biography of Padmasambhava," in *Dakini Teachings*, trans. Erik Pema Kunsang (Rangjung Yeshe Publishing, 1999); Yeshe Tsogyal, *The Life and Liberation of Padmasambhava*,

18. Nāropa (1016-1100 CE¹¹⁴⁹) Born: Bengal/ Punjab. Born into a Brahmanical family of high standing. Considered a student/ brother of Tilopā¹¹⁵⁰.

19. Niguma¹¹⁵¹ (c. 10th/ 11th CE) Literal meaning 'truly secret 'Born: probably Kashmir into a Brahmanical family, and considered the mystic sister or consort of Nāropa.

20. Sukhasiddhi (c. 11th CE) Born: Kashmir. She travelled to Oḍḍiyāna and became a disciple of Virūpa¹¹⁵².

21. Dharmakīrti (c. 600-670 CE¹¹⁵³) Born: Southern India. He was an eminent Buddhist philosopher of the Yogācāra school, who lived and worked in Nalanda, and is the author of *Pramāṇavārttika*¹¹⁵⁴.

22. Dharmapāla of Nalanda¹¹⁵⁵ (530-561 CE) Born: Kanchipuram. A contemporary of Bhartṛhari, he was considered a great philosopher and academic to whom a number of important Mahāyānist works have been ascribed. At a young age, he defeated a *tīrthika* (non- Buddhist) at a deputation organised in Kaushambi.

2.c From Central Asia and Tibet

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¹¹⁴⁹ Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 576.

¹¹⁵⁰ Dowman, *Buddhist Masters of Enchantment*, 89-92; Dowman, *Masters of Mahāmudrā*, 142-147.

¹¹⁵¹ Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 584.

¹¹⁵² Jamgon Kongtrul, *Timeless Rapture: Inspired Verses of the Shangpa Masters* (Ithaca, NY: Snow Lion Publications, 2003), 416; Nicole Riggs, *Like an Illusion: Lives of the Shangpa Kagyu Masters* (Dharma Cloud Press, 2000), 336.

¹¹⁵³ Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 246-247.

¹¹⁵⁴ Tom Tillemans, "Dharmakīrti," *Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy* (2011), <https://plato.stanford.edu/entries/dharmakiirti/>, accessed August 29, 2025; Vincent Eltschinger, "Dharmakīrti," *Brill's Encyclopedia of Buddhism Online*, <https://referenceworks.brill.com/display/db/enbo>, accessed August 29, 2025.

¹¹⁵⁵ Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 250.

1. Rin chen bzang po (958-1055 CE¹¹⁵⁶ Born. Tibet): Student of Atiśa Dīpankara. Credited to have constructed more than hundred monasteries in western Tibet, Ladakh and Himachal Pradesh¹¹⁵⁷.
2. Milarepa (1028/1040-1111/1123 CE¹¹⁵⁸ Born Tibet): Once a criminal, who learnt esoteric magic, and one of the most influential *mahasiddhas* in Tibet. He is considered to be a student of Marpa Lotsāwa¹¹⁵⁹.
3. Marpa Lotsāwa (1012-1097 CE¹¹⁶⁰ Born Tibet): Literally Marpa, the translator. Considered to be a student of Niguma and Maitrīpadā¹¹⁶¹.
4. Dromtön (c. 11th CE Born Tibet): Chief disciple of Atiśa Dīpankara, who is considered to have founded the Reting Monastery¹¹⁶².
5. Chekawa Yeshe Dorje (c. 11th-12th CE Born Tibet): A disciple of Dromtön, who Compiled Atiśa Dīpankara's teachings, and considered an important figure in Kadampa school¹¹⁶³.
6. Kumārajīva (born. China; 344-409/ 413 CE¹¹⁶⁴): He was born to a Kashmiri father in the Kingdom of Kučā, present-day Xinjiang province. Fluent in Sanskrit and Chinese, he translated

¹¹⁵⁶ Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 714.

¹¹⁵⁷ Alexander Gardner, "Rinchen Zangpo," *The Treasury of Lives: Biographies of Himalayan Religious Masters* (July 2011), <https://treasuryoflives.org/biographies/view/Rinchen-Zangpo/10199>, accessed August 29, 2025; Karl E. Ryavec, *A Historical Atlas of Tibet* (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2015), 72–75; Giuseppe Tucci, *Rin-chen-bzan-po and the Renaissance of Buddhism in Tibet Around the Millennium*, first Italian edition 1932; first draft English translation by Nancy Kipp Smith, ed. Lokesh Chandra, under the direction of Thomas J. Pritzker (New Delhi: Aditya Rakashan, 1988).

¹¹⁵⁸ Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 541.

¹¹⁵⁹ Andrew Quintman, *The Yogin and the Madman: Reading the Biographical Corpus of Tibet's Great Saint Milarepa* (New York: Columbia University Press, 2013); *The Life of Milarepa*, trans. Andrew Quintman (London: Penguin Classics, 2010); Andrew Quintman, "Mi la ras pa (Milarepa)," in *Encyclopedia of Buddhism*, ed. Robert E. Buswell (New York: Macmillan, 2004).

¹¹⁶⁰ Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 533-534.

¹¹⁶¹ Nalanda Translation Committee, *The Life of Marpa the Translator* (Boston: Shambhala Publications, Inc., 1982).

¹¹⁶² Alexander Gardner, "Dromton Gyelwa Jungne," *The Treasury of Lives: Biographies of Himalayan Religious Masters* (February 2010), <https://treasuryoflives.org/biographies/view/Dromton-Gyelwa-Jungne/4267>, accessed August 29, 2025.

¹¹⁶³ George Roerich, trans., *The Blue Annals*, 2nd ed. (Delhi: Motilal Banarsidas, 1996), 273; Samten Chhospel, "Chekhawa Yeshe Dorje," *The Treasury of Lives: Biographies of Himalayan Religious Masters* (February 2010), https://treasuryoflives.org/bo/biographies/view/-Chekhawa-Yeshe-Dorje/TBRC_P3447, accessed August 29, 2025.

¹¹⁶⁴ Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 452-453.

important Mahāyānist works from Sanskrit to Chinese. He settled in Chang'an (present-day Xi'an) in later life¹¹⁶⁵.

7. Bodhidharma¹¹⁶⁶ (born. c. 5th/ 6th CE Central Asia/ southern India): Legendary Buddhist monk, who is credited to have introduced Mahāyāna to China. However, *bodhidharma* can also mean Buddhism itself; and the monk Bodhidharma might be a mythic or metaphoric reference.

2.d From China and Korea

1. I-Tsing/ Yijing (635-713 CE¹¹⁶⁷ China): Chinese traveller and student at Nalanda, who translated different Sanskrit and Pāli texts into Chinese. He is considered to be one of the most important Chinese travellers of his period who left a memorable tale-account of fifty-one monks. He returned to China with more than 500 translated texts¹¹⁶⁸.

2. Prajñāvarman (born. 8th CE Korea/ China): Travelled across western and eastern India, and met Yijing at Nalanda¹¹⁶⁹.

3. Prajñādeva (born. c. 7th CE China): He spent initial years in India at Harikela, then travelled to Nalanda and Bodh Gaya, where he met Yijing, and then went back to China¹¹⁷⁰.

APPENDIX 3: VIRTUAL LIBRARY OF BUDDHIST SITES IN SOUTH AND CENTRAL ASIA

¹¹⁶⁵ Shi Huijiao, *The Biographies of Eminent Monks*, trans. Yang Tianshu (Hong Kong: Centre of Buddhist Studies, The University of Hong Kong, 2022), 53–69.

¹¹⁶⁶ Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 132.

¹¹⁶⁷ Buswell Jr. and Lopez Jr., 1028.

¹¹⁶⁸ Tansen Sen, "The Travel Records of Chinese Pilgrims Faxian, Xuanzang, and Yijing," *Education About Asia* 11, no. 3 (2006): 24–33.

¹¹⁶⁹ Johannes Schneider, *Der Lobpreis der Vorzüglichkeit des Buddha* (Bonn: Indica et Tibetica Verlag, 1993), 18.

¹¹⁷⁰ Max Deeg, "Chapter 7 Wailing for Identity: Topical and Poetic Expressions of Cultural Belonging in Chinese Buddhist Literature," in *Buddhist Encounters and Identities Across East Asia* (Leiden, The Netherlands: Brill, 2018), 225–252.

URL link: [https://earth.google.com/earth/d/1rmv_KIJ6gr1pxHANRqqwwJVhq-PEgqSv?usp=share link](https://earth.google.com/earth/d/1rmv_KIJ6gr1pxHANRqqwwJVhq-PEgqSv?usp=share_link)

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